

SYSTEMATICS, DISTRIBUTION, AND ZOOGEOGRAPHY
OF MAMMALS OF TUNISIA

by

BURHAN M. GHARAIBEH, B.S., M.S.

A DISSERTATION

IN

BIOLOGY

Submitted to the Graduate Faculty
of Texas Tech University in
Partial Fulfillment of
the Requirements for
the Degree of

DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY

Approved

Accepted

December, 1997

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Between 1 September 1972 and 30 June 1975, field work was conducted by a team of researchers lead by Dr. E. Lendell Cockrum of the University of Arizona (Tucson) and Dr. Robert Baker of Texas Tech University (Lubbock) to study the mammals of Tunisia. The project was co-sponsored by the Smithsonian Institution (Washington, D.C.) and the Tunisian Association for the Protection of Nature and Environment (TAPNE). This cooperation made use of Public Law 480 funds. Most financial support for the project was provided by that contract. Significant indirect support in the form of supplies, equipment and investigators salaries were provided by the University of Arizona, the United State National Museum and the Natural Science Research Laboratory (NSRL), Museum of Texas Tech University. Part of the collection resulting from this field work was deposited at TAPNE and the other part (nearly 2,500 specimens of small mammals) in the Recent collection of mammals, NSRL. This study was to a large extent an examination of the latter collection.

Drs. E. Lendell Cockrum, Robert Baker, Pamela Vaughan, Thomas Vaughan, Bruce Hayward, Brent Davis, Hedia Baccar, Alya Binous, Robert Jordan, and others have participated in the field work done in Tunisia at different times between 1972-1975. Tom and Pam Vaughan were the two investigators working for Dr. Cockrum who spent most of this period in Tunisia pursuing this project. They were assisted by Mr. Abdul Fatah Ben Ismail and Mr. Dridi Khadhari.

This report could not have been possible without the many pages of unpublished keys, unpublished notes, measurements, photographs of types, literature, maps and other material that Dr. Cockrum agreed to let me use. Further, Dr. Cockrum's discussions on North African mammals and encouragement were

inspiring, motivating, and very informative. I cannot thank him enough for his generosity and kindness. Equally useful were the field catalogs, journals, and photos of habitats, that Pamela and Tom Vaughan have taken during their presence in Tunisia. I would like to acknowledge their efforts and contribution and thank them sincerely.

Three major Tunisian organizations have cooperated with the principal investigators and their crews during their presence in Tunisia and have contributed significantly to the success of this project. The Tunisian Association for the Protection of Nature and Environment, the Faculty of Agronomy at the Tunisian National Institute for Agriculture Research (Institut National Recherche Agricole Tunisien; INRAT), and the Mediterranean Marine Sorting Center (MMSA). The director of Projet des Mammifères, Mr. Zakaria Ben Mustapha was a great help to the American team. His contribution is also acknowledged.

In May-July, 1996, I did further studies of the Tunisian mammalian fauna. This was supported by a grant from the Carnegie Museum of Natural History. I would like to thank Dr. Duane A. Schlitter for helping me obtain those funds. During my stay in Tunisia, I was a guest at the Tunisian Institute for Veterinary Research (Institut de la Recherche Vétérinaire de Tunisie; IRVT). I would like to express my gratitude and appreciation for the help and hospitality of Dr. Khalid El Hicheri and Dr. Saleh Hamami. Mr. Abdullah El Khidri was a faithful assistant for the two months I stayed in Tunisia. Permits to collect in Tunisia have been provided by the Department of Forests (Direction Générale des Forêt; DGF), Ministry of Agriculture via the Tunisian Embassy in Washington, D.C. I wish to thank all those that were involved in particular, Mr. Ben Mahmoud, Mr. Ridha Fekih Salem and Mr. Abdul Hameed Karim.

During my stay at Texas Tech University, I was sponsored in part by Jordan University of Science and Technology, Irbid, Jordan. I would like to extend my appreciation for that. I was also given various teaching assistantships at the Department of Biological Sciences and a research assistantship by NSRL. The help of Drs. John Burns, Clyde Jones, and Richard Strauss are acknowledged. My brother Numan also paid some of my tuition towards the end. Without the above mentioned financial help, this job would have been impossible.

My family in Jordan (mother, father, sisters, brothers and other Gharaibehs) and Mexico (my wife and other Gonzalez's) thought I could do this and always gave me their love, support, encouragement, and sometimes words of wisdom. I honestly do not think I would have finished this job without their support. Further, many friends at TTU had to listen to my ups of downs and I thank them for that: W. Al Gharaibeh, R. Monk, J. Goetze and many others.

Last but not least, I would like to express my deepest appreciation for my graduate committee for all their help. Dr. Robert Baker, my mentor and academic advisor, suggested the project, believed I could do it, and did not spare any resources through his laboratory or through NSRL. Furthermore, he was always grand in the way he dealt with his graduate students and that by itself was a great help during my stay in his laboratory.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	ii
ABSTRACT.....	ix
LIST OF TABLES.....	xi
LIST OF FIGURES.....	xii
CHAPTERS	
I. INTRODUCTION	1
Review of Literature.....	1
Objectives.....	5
II. MATERIALS AND METHODS	7
Methods.....	7
Data Analyses	9
Study Area.....	12
Treatment	21
List of Abbreviations.....	23
III. SPECIES ACCOUNTS.....	25
ORDER INSECTIVORA	25
Family Erinaceidae.....	25
Genus <i>Atelerix</i>	26
Genus <i>Paraechinus</i>	32
Family Soricidae	35
Genus <i>Suncus</i>	36
Genus <i>Crocidura</i>	39
ORDER CHIROPTERA	46
Family Rhinopomatidae.....	47

Genus <i>Rhinopoma</i>	47
Family Rhinolophidae.....	51
Genus <i>Rhinolophus</i>	51
Genus <i>Asellia</i>	69
Family Vespertilionidae	72
Genus <i>Myotis</i>	73
Genus <i>Eptesicus</i>	82
Genus <i>Pipistrellus</i>	84
Genus <i>Otonycteris</i>	95
Genus <i>Plecotus</i>	98
Genus <i>Miniopterus</i>	101
Family Molossidae.....	104
Genus <i>Tadarida</i>	104
ORDER CARNIVORA	108
Family Canidae.....	109
Genus <i>Canis</i>	110
Genus <i>Vulpes</i>	114
Genus <i>Fennecus</i>	119
Family Mustelidae	122
Genus <i>Ictonyx</i>	122
Genus <i>Mustela</i>	125
Genus <i>Lutra</i>	127
Family Viverridae.....	130
Genus <i>Genetta</i>	130
Family Herpestidae	133
Genus <i>Herpestes</i>	133

Family Hyaenidae.....	136
Genus <i>Hyaena</i>	136
Family Felidae.....	139
Genus <i>Felis</i>	141
Genus <i>Panthera</i>	151
Genus <i>Acinonyx</i>	155
ORDER ARTIODACTYLA	159
Family Suidae	159
Genus <i>Sus</i>	159
Family Cervidae.....	163
Genus <i>Cervus</i>	163
Family Bovidae	167
Genus <i>Addax</i>	168
Genus <i>Alcelaphus</i>	171
Genus <i>Oryx</i>	175
Genus <i>Gazella</i>	177
Genus <i>Ammotragus</i>	188
ORDER RODENTIA.....	192
Family Dipodidae	193
Genus <i>Jaculus</i>	193
Family Muridae	204
Genus <i>Gerbillus</i>	205
Genus <i>Pachyuromys</i>	237
Genus <i>Meriones</i>	241
Genus <i>Psammomys</i>	252
Genus <i>Apodemus</i>	261

Genus <i>Lemniscomys</i>	265
Genus <i>Rattus</i>	268
Genus <i>Mus</i>	273
Family Ctenodactylidae	280
Genus <i>Ctenodactylus</i>	281
Family Myoxida.....	285
Genus <i>Eliomys</i>	285
Family Hystricidae.....	289
Genus <i>Hystrix</i>	289
ORDER LAGOMORPHA	293
Family Leporidae	293
Genus <i>Lepus</i>	293
Genus <i>Oryctolagus</i>	298
ORDER MACROSCELIDEA	302
Family Macroscelididae	302
Genus <i>Elephantulus</i>	302
INTRODUCED MAMMALS.....	311
DOMESTICATED MAMMALS	316
MARINE MAMMALS	316
IV. ZOOGEOGRAPHY	318
V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	334
LITERATURE CITED.....	337

ABSTRACT

The taxonomic identity of each species of mammals that occurs in the Republic of Tunisia, North Africa has been determined to the subspecific level. History of names was followed and descriptions of types were studied to better provide opinions on the nomenclature and minimize the confusion existing in the literature concerning the taxonomic identity of many Tunisian species. Keys to distinguish related taxa were constructed and maps depicting the distribution of species within the borders of Tunisia and in the whole North African region were drawn. These maps show original records obtained during this study as well records reported in the literature. Furthermore, the available natural history information on the Tunisian mammal fauna and background information on the vegetation, rainfall, topography, and land forms of the country were presented.

Chromosomal G-band data for *Meriones shawi* from Tunisia, hitherto unavailable, was used to reexamine proposed chromosomal homologies and update the phylogenetic tree of Family Gerbillidae. G-banded chromosomal complement for *Jaculus orientalis* was reported. Notable differences in pelage color were seen between populations of the North African elephant shrew, *Elephantulus rozeti* in northern and southern Tunisia. However, no disjunction was seen in morphometric measurements analyzed using principal components analysis (PCA).

Differences in pelage color between 5 populations of *Gerbillus campestris* are discussed. Two populations of this gerbil, one on the Island of Djerba and the other around Médénine deserve systematic studies using molecular data or multivariate analyses of morphometric measurements. Differences in pelage color, mandibular foramina number, color of foot pad hair and other characters between 2

populations of *Jaculus jaculus* were also noted and further investigation of the taxonomic status recommended.

Zoogeographical analyses of the mammalian faunal elements in Tunisia and the whole area were made. Two groups of bats were recognized. Bat fauna that invaded Tunisia from the north, and one that invaded from the south. Land mammals were in three groups: strictly Mediterranean zone, widely-distributed Mediterranean, and Saharan mammals. Species richness in quadrates 1° latitude X 1° longitude spanning Tunisia was discussed. The species richness provided evidence to areas of high biodiversity. Areas that deserve conservation are Djebel Zaghouan, Ghardimaou, Tamerza-Kasserine, and Dahar-Djeffara plain. Finally, conclusions and recommendations for future mammalian studies in the area were suggested.

LIST OF TABLES

3.1. External measurements for <i>Myotis emarginatus</i>	81
3.2. List of features that separate two groups of <i>Jaculus jaculus</i>	196
3.3. Selected features of four species of hairy-footed gerbils	226
3.4. Reproductive status of elephant shrews (<i>Elephantulus rozeti</i>)	306
3.5. Selected cranial measurements of elephant shrews from Tunisia.....	307
4.1. Geographical distribution of mammalian fauna	328

LIST OF FIGURES

2.1.	Skull of the elephant shrew, <i>Elephantulus</i> showing measurements.....	10
2.2.	Map of the Republic of Tunisia.....	13
2.3.	Geographical regions in Tunisia	14
2.4.	Topography of Tunisia	15
2.5.	Annual average temperatures of Tunisia	17
2.6.	Annual rainfall in Tunisia	18
2.7.	Vegetation of Tunisia	19
2.8.	Typical distribution map.....	22
3.1.	Distribution maps of the Algerian hedgehog, <i>Atelerix algirus</i>	27
3.2.	Distribution maps of the desert hedgehog.....	34
3.3.	Distribution maps of the pygmy shrew, <i>Suncus etruscus</i>	37
3.4.	Distribution maps of the white-toothed shrew, <i>Crocidura russula</i>	41
3.5.	Distribution maps of Whitaker's shrew, <i>Crocidura whitakeri</i>	44
3.6.	Distribution maps of the lesser rat-tailed bat	48
3.7.	Distribution maps of the greater horseshoe bat	54
3.8.	Distribution maps of the lesser horseshoe bat	57
3.9.	Distribution maps of the pack-saddle horseshoe bat	61
3.10.	Drawing of Mehely's horseshoe bat, <i>Rhinolophus mehelyi</i>	63
3.11.	Distribution maps of Mehely's horseshoe bat.....	64
3.12.	Distribution maps of the Mediterranean horseshoe bat	67
3.13.	Distribution maps of the Trident bat, <i>Asellia tridens</i>	70
3.14.	Distribution maps of the lesser mouse-eared bat, <i>Myotis blythi</i>	75
3.15.	Distribution maps of the long-fingered bat, <i>Myotis capaccinii</i>	78
3.16.	Distribution maps of Geoffroy's bat, <i>Myotis emarginatus</i>	80

3.17.	Distribution maps of the Serotine, <i>Eptesicus serotinus</i>	83
3.18.	Distribution maps of Kuhl' s pipistrelle, <i>Pipistrellus kuhli</i>	86
3.19.	Distribution maps of the common pipistrelle.....	92
3.20.	Distribution maps of Savi' s pipistrelle, <i>Pipistrellus savii</i>	94
3.21.	Distribution maps of Hemprich' s long-eared bat	97
3.22.	Distribution maps of the gray long-eared bat	99
3.23.	Distribution maps of the Schreiber' s bat	102
3.24.	Distribution maps of the European free-tailed bat	106
3.25.	Distribution maps of the northern jackal, <i>Canis aureus</i>	111
3.26.	Distribution maps of the red fox, <i>Vulpes vulpes</i>	115
3.27.	Distribution maps of the sand fox, <i>Vulpes rueppelli</i>	118
3.28.	Distribution maps of the fennec, <i>Fennecus zerda</i>	121
3.29.	Distribution maps of the Saharan striped weasel, <i>Ictonyx libyca</i>	124
3.30.	Distribution maps of the weasel, <i>Mustela nivalis</i>	126
3.31.	Distribution maps of the otter, <i>Lutra lutra</i>	128
3.32.	Distribution maps of the genet, <i>Genetta genetta</i>	132
3.33.	Distribution maps of the Egyptian mongoose.....	135
3.34.	Distribution maps of the striped hyena, <i>Hyaena hyaena</i>	137
3.35.	Distribution maps of the wild cat, <i>Felis silvestris</i>	142
3.36.	Distribution maps of the sand cat, <i>Felis margarita</i>	145
3.37.	Distribution maps of the caracal, <i>Felis caracal</i>	147
3.38.	Distribution maps of the serval, <i>Felis serval</i>	149
3.39.	Distribution maps of the leopard, <i>Panthera pardus</i>	152
3.40.	Distribution maps of the lion, <i>Panthera leo</i>	154
3.41.	Distribution maps of the cheetah. <i>Acinonyx jubatus</i>	157
3.42.	Distribution maps of the wild boar, <i>Sus scrofa</i>	161

3.43.	Distribution maps of the red deer, <i>Cervus elaphus</i>	164
3.44.	Distribution maps of the addax, <i>Addax nasomaculatus</i>	170
3.45.	Distribution maps of the hartebeest, <i>Alcelaphus buselaphus</i>	173
3.46.	Distribution maps of the scimitar-horned oryx, <i>Oryx dammah</i>	176
3.47.	Distribution maps of the Dorcas gazelle, <i>Gazella dorcas</i>	180
3.48.	Distribution maps of the sand gazelle, <i>Gazella leptoceros</i>	184
3.49.	Distribution maps of the Edmi gazelle, <i>Gazella cuvieri</i>	186
3.50.	Distribution maps of the aoudad, <i>Ammotragus lervia</i>	189
3.51.	Distribution maps of the lesser Egyptian jerboa, <i>Jaculus jaculus</i>	195
3.52.	Distribution maps of the greater Egyptian jerboa.....	201
3.53.	G-banded chromosomal complement for <i>Jaculus orientalis</i>	202
3.54.	Distribution maps of the large North African gerbil.....	209
3.55.	Distribution maps of Simon's short-tailed gerbil.....	215
3.56.	Distribution maps of the pygmy naked-footed gerbil	218
3.57.	Distribution maps of the small naked-footed gerbil	221
3.58.	Distribution maps of Anderson's hairy-footed gerbil	228
3.59.	Distribution maps of Lataste's hairy footed gerbil.....	230
3.60.	Distribution maps of the large hairy-footed gerbils	233
3.61.	Distribution maps of small hairy-footed gerbil	235
3.62.	Distribution maps of the fat-tailed gerbil, <i>Pachyuromys duprasi</i>	238
3.63.	Distribution maps of the gentle jird, <i>Meriones crassus</i>	243
3.64.	Distribution maps of the Libyan jird, <i>Meriones libycus</i>	245
3.65.	Distribution maps of Shaw's jird, <i>Meriones shawi</i>	248
3.66.	G-banded chromosomal complement of <i>Meriones shawi</i>	249
3.67.	Cladogram showing the distribution of derived chromosomal character states in Gerbillidae.....	250
3.68.	Distribution maps of the fat sand rat, <i>Psammomys obesus</i>	254

3.69.	Distribution maps of pale fat sand rat, <i>Psammomys vexillaris</i>	258
3.70.	Distribution maps of the wood mouse, <i>Apodemus sylvaticus</i>	262
3.71.	Distribution maps of the striped mouse, <i>Lemniscomys barbarus</i>	266
3.72.	Distribution maps of the black rat, <i>Rattus rattus</i>	269
3.73.	Distribution maps of the Norway rat, <i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	272
3.74.	Distribution maps of <i>Mus spretus</i>	276
3.75.	Distribution maps of the house mouse, <i>Mus musculus</i>	278
3.76.	Distribution maps of the garden dormouse, <i>Eliomys melanurus</i>	282
3.77.	Distribution maps of the North African crested porcupine	287
3.78.	Distribution maps of the gundi, <i>Ctenodactylus gundi</i>	291
3.79.	Distribution maps of the brown hare, <i>Lepus capensis</i>	295
3.80.	Distribution maps of the wild rabbit, <i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	299
3.81.	Distribution maps of the elephant shrew, <i>Elephantulus rozeti</i>	304
3.82.	Two-dimensional projection of the first three principal components analysis.....	309
3.83.	Distribution maps of the Mhorr gazelle, <i>Gazella dama</i>	314
4.1.	Superimposed distributions of species of bats that have invaded Tunisia from the north.....	322
4.2.	Superimposed distributions of species of bats that have invaded Tunisia from the south.....	323
4.3.	Superimposed distributions of species of land mammals that are restricted to the Mediterranean zone.....	324
4.4.	Superimposed distributions of widely-distributed Mediterranean species of land mammals.....	325
4.5.	Superimposed distributions of species of Saharan land mammals	327
4.6.	Species richness of mammalian fauna in Tunisia.....	331

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Review of Literature

References to Tunisian mammals, especially to the larger species, can be found in the ancient writings of the Carthaginians and Romans. History books mention the great Carthaginian general Hannibal who crossed the Alps with his army, using horses and elephants, during the Second Punic War (218-201 B.C.). The elephants presumably came, at least in part, from Tunisia. Mosaics in many archeological sites in Tunisia depict not only hunting parties, but also lions, tigers, elephants, and various domesticated animals. Bardo Museum in Tunis has a good collection of such mosaics from many parts of Tunisia. Some of these ancient records of mammals have been reviewed by modern writers, but not, apparently by anyone with special knowledge of mammalian taxonomy and distribution.

Some anthropologists, archeologists and historians have alluded to the presence of various mammals that are now locally extinct. According to Cockrum (in litt.) in 1975 Alya Binous, then of the Department of Zoology of the Tunisian National Institute of Agriculture, was preparing a review of these reports. And H. P. Müller, then of the National Zoological Park, Tunis, was preparing a report on the history of the game animals, with special emphasis on endangered and extinct species. Apparently neither of these reports was ever published.

The pioneer worker making significant contributions to North African mammalian taxonomy, from the modern viewpoint, appears to have been Victor Loche (1858, 1867). Commandant Loche was restricted, by his duties and by other factors, to a first-hand investigation of only a small part of northern Algeria south to about the "high plateau" of the Atlas Mountains. He had no opportunity to

examine critical specimens in British, French, and German museums. His concepts of a species as well as of evolution and zoogeography were, by modern standards, narrow. However, when judged from the viewpoint of the mid-nineteenth century, Commandant Loche was a man ahead of his time. Not only did his writings add significantly to knowledge concerning North African mammals, but he made a collection that was open to the public, in 1860, under the name, Permanent Exposition of Algerian Materials. Therein he deposited all of the specimens (which included birds and mammals) on which he had based the descriptions of his new species as well as examples of all the previously named Algerian species that he could secure. Unfortunately, Loche's "permanent exposition" disappeared shortly after his death. The specimens on which he based species descriptions are apparently no longer in existence. As a result, some of his names are not identifiable with certainty. Fortunately, a few of his specimens were deposited, and still remain, in the collections of the Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle (MNHN) in Paris (see Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska, 1991 for details).

The next major contributor to Algerian and Tunisian mammalogy was Fernand Lataste. Between 1861-1888, Lataste published numerous reports concerning his investigations in the area. Not only did he describe several new species but he also made major contributions in interpreting relations among various groups. Most of his interpretations are still accepted today. His 1887 publication (*Catalogue Critique des Mammifères Appélagiques Sauvages de la Tunisie*) was the first account of the mammals of Tunisia, although it included material from Algeria.

As the result of two trips of six months each made between 1902 and 1904, V. H. de Chaignon compiled several notes on the natural history of Tunisia. He published his observations on mammals as well as other vertebrates (e.g., Chaignon, 1904). Following Chaignon's work, Dr. E. Trouessart (1905)

published an annotated summary of mammals of Algeria, Morocco, and Tunisia. He, apparently, has not been to North Africa and his work presented no new information. Trouessart (1906) also reported on a trip made by Gadeau de Kerville to the Tunisian Khroumirie.

E. Conseil of the Pasteur Institute of Tunis and Chief of Municipal Hygiene Bureau of Tunis, reported on his research concerning plague in Tunisia. In 1908 he examined a total of 713 rodents, mainly house mice. In his report (1928), he published a descriptive resumé of all rodents that he thought occurred in Tunisia. For most he had only records of literature reports. In general, his descriptions were excellent and if the publications were more readily available, it would still be widely used in identifying Tunisian rodents.

A prolific writer on Tunisian mammalogy was Oldfield Thomas (e.g., 1919a) of the British Museum of Natural History. He published several papers that described new taxa from the area and reported on collections brought to the Museum by different expeditions.

Biologists rely upon past publications for facts concerning their area of interest. Information that is never formally published is usually lost to later generations. In Tunisia, one man who undoubtedly had an outstanding knowledge of the local fauna but who never published his findings was Marius Blanc. In one mimeographed report that he produced in 1935, Blanc recorded his first-hand observations from as early as the 1890's. He was a capable naturalist, a taxidermist and apparently a pelt and fur buyer. Chaignon (1904) indicated that Blanc, "naturaliste a Tunis," had helped greatly by accompanying him on his trips and providing much information concerning mammals. Blanc also furnished various specimens to the British Museum (Natural History) and to the Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle in Paris that served as types of two new taxa. His

mimeographed report recorded significant observations concerning the distribution and abundance, population reductions and extinctions of various Tunisian mammals.

One of the first researchers to work on Tunisian mammals after the country achieved its independence from France in 1956 was J. Bernard. He published on the parasites of rodents in North Africa (e.g., 1963b), but subsequently reported on rodents as well. His work on the rodents of Tunisia (1969a) was to be the first volume in a comprehensive report on Tunisian mammalian fauna, but only this volume was ever published. In 1970, he published an annotated key for the identification of rodents.

Baker et al. (1974) have reported karyotypic and morphometric data for eight species of bats from Tunisia. Also, Jordan et al. (1974) reported similar information on five members of the genus *Gerbillus*. Both studies have furnished new information on the mammalian fauna of Tunisia. Cockrum et al. (1976a) described a new species of gerbils (*Gerbillus zakariae*) from Tunisia and Cockrum (1977) reported on the status of other gerbil species, *G. latastei* and the pale sand rat, *Psammomys vexillaris* (Cockrum et al. 1977). Vaughan et al. (1977) reported new records of vespertilionid bats in Tunisia. Other investigators have worked in Tunisia, or at least on specimens from Tunisia, reported on the systematics, ecology, cytogenetics, and other aspects of mammalian biology of one species or a group of species (Aellen and Strinati, 1969; George, 1982; Kahmann and Thoms, 1987; Mason and Macdonald, 1983; Said and Britton-Davidian, 1991; Tranier and Petter, 1978; Vesmanis, 1980).

Tunisia is a relatively complex ecological assemblage. As yet many areas, especially the remote southern parts, have not been surveyed adequately and remain underrepresented in museum collections. Further, the relationship of many species

of Tunisian mammalian fauna to those of neighboring countries are yet to be fully understood. This report will provide the first comprehensive study of all the indigenous mammalian species that occur within the borders of the Republic of Tunisia. This document reports the results of examining a good-sized collection of specimens from Tunisia, and presents information obtained from the field notes that describe a long period of field experience in addition to my own field work there. I hope that it will provide answers to many questions although in many instances (because of the difficulty of the subject) my efforts merely pointed out areas that needed further studies.

Objectives

The purposes of this study are:

1. To provide a comprehensive listing of Tunisian mammals with keys that will facilitate their identification. Specialists and non-specialists concerned with different aspects of conservation, biodiversity, health issues and many other aspects of life are becoming increasingly aware of the need for such inventories of the mammalian fauna and this study is designed to fill this need.
2. To provide full synonymy of each species listing all proposed names and taking into account latest published research. Synonyms hamper proper identification and classification of mammals. Setting the α -taxonomy of the mammalian fauna of Tunisia is a necessary foundation for further biological studies.
3. To outline the distribution range of each Tunisian species of mammals based on actual specimens, field work and literature records from Tunisia and North Africa. Such information will be useful for systematic and zoogeographical studies. Furthermore, decision makers concerned with biodiversity and

conservation issues will be able to extract needed information from the distributional range maps.

4. To consolidate information on the distribution and habitats where mammals exist, along with information on the reproductive biology, parasites, ecology, food, behavior, physiology, and other aspects of the biology of each species.

Investigators of the possible effects of human activities on mammalian populations can utilize such information.

5. To list the faunal regions within Tunisia and compare the historical affinities of the Tunisian mammalian fauna to surrounding areas by outlining routes of dispersal of those mammals. The patterns of distribution of different species when considered with other information on vegetation, physical conditions of habitats, etc., can provide information on biodiversity “hot spots” that are in need of conservation and management. I intend to show those areas of high species richness and evaluate the need for their preservation.

6. Finally, an important objective is to provide a stimulus for more interest in the Tunisian mammalian fauna.

CHAPTER II

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Methods

Field work was conducted in Tunisia between 1972-1975 by Dr. E. L. Cockrum (University of Arizona) and Dr. Robert Baker (Texas Tech University) and their teams and by myself in May and June of 1996. These surveys covered all but the most inaccessible southern sites. Only the edges of sand dunes of Grand Erg Oriental of the Sahara were examined.

Collection Methods

Small mammals were collected with locally built live traps, Museum Special traps, Victor snap traps. Bats were collected using mist nets or by hand nets from roosting sites. Medium-sized animals (particularly carnivores and lagomorphs) were snared or shot. Road kills were salvaged and owl pellets were collected whenever possible. On few occasions, jerboas, gundis and hedgehogs were bought from locals. All collecting was authorized by permits granted by Tunisian authorities.

Processing Methods

Specimens were all prepared in the standard procedures as museum vouchers. The majority of the specimens collected in the 1970s are deposited in the Recent collection of mammals at NSRL. The rest were deposited by Cockrum at TAPNE, which is currently under care of Mohamad El'abrougi.

Mensural, reproductive, and other data were recorded for all specimens. In addition, the majority of specimens collected in the 1970s were karyotyped using

specimens collected in 1996 were karyotyped using tissue culture techniques (Baker and Qumsiyeh, 1988). Ear and lung biopsies were taken under aseptic conditions from most animals and deposited in culture media. These cultures were subsequently used to obtain karyological data. Furthermore, samples of tissues (heart, kidney, liver and muscle) were also taken from those animals collected in the summer of 1996 for the purposes of future studies. These tissues were kept in liquid nitrogen until they were deposited at the vital tissue collection, NSRL.

Laboratory Studies

Lung and ear biopsies stored in culture media were processed at the Cytogenetics Laboratory, Duke University Medical Center. The specimens were grown in fresh media that was incubated at 37 °C for 7-10 days. Cells from successful cultures were harvested and were grown on a cover slip in a small Petri dish or on the bottom of a media flask. After 24 hours, dividing cells were treated with Colcemid (Sigma) to stop the mitotic divisions. Hypotonic solution of 0.8% sodium citrate was added and the cells were incubated for 30 min. These cells were then fixed with 3:1 methanol: acetic acid. Slides were dried and then baked at 65 °C for 3 hours. A number of slides from each individual were evaluated and the best ones were stained with Geimsa stain. Ten spreads were counted, photographed and printed. The standard karyotypes of the animals (diploid number and fundamental number) were determined from these.

G-banding of chromosomes was done following the procedure described by Baker and Qumsiyeh (1988). To determine G-band homologies, at least five spreads were counted and photographed. Chromosomes were cut, and matched first to each other and then to other members of the species. Interspecific

comparisons were made using chromosomes from a single spread (Qumsiyeh, 1986).

Museum Studies

Museum specimens (skins, skulls, skeletons and specimens in fluids) from Tunisia housed at NSRL, Museum of Texas Tech University were examined. Pelage colors, body and cranial measurements were recorded and analyzed for geographic and nongeographic variation within a species and among related taxa. The distributional ranges of each species were drawn on a map of Tunisia. The final outcome also included records by previous studies. Finally, the distributional ranges in North Africa were determined from the literature.

Data Analyses

Morphometric

The following cranial measurements were taken from specimens of the elephant shrew, *Elephantulus rozeti* (to 0.1 mm) using a dial caliper: Greatest length (GL), Condylbasal length (CBL), Basal length (BL), Breadth of braincase (BC), Least interorbital breadth (LIB), Nasal breadth (NB), Zygomatic breadth (ZB), Mastoid breadth (MB), Maxillary tooth row (MTR), and Hind foot length. Figure 2.1 shows the above mentioned measurements.

These measurement were transformed to natural logarithms to linearize the allometric or size component of the data. The data were grouped by region in Tunisia (north, central, and south). A Principal Components Analysis (PCA) of the covariance matrix of the transformed data was used to determine whether cranial measurements of animals from the three regions in Tunisia are different or not. PCA explains the maximum percentage of the matrix variation with a given number

Figure 2.1. Skull of the elephant shrew, *Elephantulus rozeti* showing measurements used in morphometric analyses (upper figure, lateral view; left, dorsal view; right, ventral view). See text for abbreviations.

of components. The first principal component (PC1) was plotted against PC2; and PC2 against PC3 to determine visually if the three populations show any disjunction.

Zoogeographic

Areographic analysis of the distribution ranges of Tunisian mammals was done following the method outlined in Baker and Genoways (1978) and Armstrong et al. (1986). The distributional limits of all mammal species that exist in Tunisia, were superimposed onto one map. This map showed the putative routes of (and barriers to) the dispersal of animals in Tunisia and identified mammalian faunal regions within the area. Subsequently, rodent and bat distributions were superimposed onto separate maps and the faunal groups identified. Furthermore, the country was divided into quadrates $1^{\circ} \times 1^{\circ}$ and the number of species occurring in each quadrate was counted. The preliminary zoogeographic data will provide a start for further zoogeographical and ecological analyses of the mammal fauna of Tunisia. Number of species of Chiroptera, Gerbillidae, Rodentia (with the exception of commensal species), all land mammals, and all mammals (excluding marine and domestic species) were counted in each quadrate and areas of high biodiversity were pointed.

Karyological

Diploid and fundamental numbers of chromosomes for problematic taxa were compared to those for the same and related species occurring inside and outside Tunisia as reported in the literature. G-banded chromosomal complement for one rodent (*Meriones shawi*) was compared to other related taxa to assess homologies. Chromosomal fusions and/or fissions were used as character states and the most

parsimonious phylogenetic tree was drawn for the group containing *Meriones shawi* in Family Gerbillidae.

Study Area

The Republic of Tunisia is a North African country that is 167,000 km² (slightly smaller than Wisconsin; or two thirds the area of United Kingdom). The majority of the surface area is classified as arid land. Tunisia is divided into 23 governorates (Arabic: Wilayat; singular, Wilaya) and each Wilaya is subdivided into delegations. The country is bordered by the Mediterranean to the north and east, Algeria to the west and south, and Libya to the east and south. Tunisia is located between 7° to 12° E longitude and 30° to 38° N latitude (Fig. 2.2).

Topography

Tunisia's topography can be divided into four main landscapes: (1) the mountains which include the Kroumirie and Mogod in the north at the Mediterranean, Tell and Dorsale south of the river Medjerda. Mountains range from 200 to 1500. The highest in the country is Chambi near Kasserine with elevation of 1544 m; (2) the Sahil, the warm and humid coastal plains of the east. This area ranges from 0 to 200 m; (3) the upland and lowland steppes of central Tunisia with the semiarid basins south of the Tell and west of the Sahil. The steppe areas are between 100 to 700 m high; and (4) the dry Sahara desert (Erg) and predesert (Djeffara) regions of southern Tunisia range from 0 to 700 m. Other minor subdivisions were not considered to minimize details. Fig. 2.3 shows the main geographical regions and subregions in Tunisia. Figure 2.4. illustrates the topography of the country using elevation contours.

Figure 2.2. Map of the Republic of Tunisia (large black dots represent major cities, small ones represent towns and villages).

Figure 2.3. Geographical regions in Tunisia (Source: Baedeker Guides).

Figure 2.4. Topography of Tunisia (after Rand McNally Goode's World Atlas).

Climate

Tunisia has two main seasons: a cool, rainy season from mid October to early May, and a warm, dry season from early May to September. Seasonal variation in temperature is more pronounced in the desert parts than the northern parts where the climate is mediated by the sea. The average annual temperatures range from 16 ° to in excess of 21° C (Fig. 2.5).

Average rainfall is much higher in the north than in the south. This gradient is associated with altitude and proximity to the sea. In the northern montane region bordering the Mediterranean, average rainfall can reach 1000 mm, but does not exceed 140 mm in the steppe, 80 mm in the southern parts and 50 mm in the Erg region (Fig. 2.6).

Vegetation

From south to north, the following vegetation zones can be distinguished (P. Vaughan, in litt.; Wickens, 1984):

1. South of Gafsa (around latitude 34° N), and into Fort Saint, is the desert and subdesert vegetation zone. The characteristic landscape consists a) of dunes, among which grow the low bushy joint fir (*Ephedra alata*), the shrub (*Retama raetam*), and the grass (*Aristida pугens*); b) of sebkhat (marshy areas covered by a thin layer of water or salt and fringed with shatls or beaches of saline clay with halophytes); c) vast stretches of with a few plants such as Haloxylon; and oases. In the east, there is the Dahar series of mountains with few plants and esparto grass. Further east, is the Djeffara plain, a subdesert scrub that becomes like steppe near the coast (Fig. 2.7)

2. Between Gafsa ranges and Dorsale lie steppes with light soils poor in humus. Vegetation includes artemisia (*Artemisia*), esparto grass and trees such as

Figure 2.5. Annual average temperatures of Tunisia (after Rand McNally Goode's World Atlas).

Figure 2.6. Annual rainfall in Tunisia (after Rand McNally Goode's World Atlas).

Figure 2.7. Vegetation of Tunisia (composite from different atlases).

Acacia tortilis and *Pistacia atlantica*. The mountains are covered with thin forests of red juniper and Aleppo pines (*Pinus halepensis*). The lower steppe, to the east, consists of jujube lotus and salty vegetation. In the northeast, the hills of the Sahil (the coast) receive more rainfall and the flora is partly Mediterranean.

3. The true Mediterranean vegetation zone begins to the north of Dorsale. There the natural vegetation consists of forest or shrub-like juniper, pine, *Thuja* evergreens, and thin jujuba shrub (*Jujuba*) in dry regions; forests of oak and dense thickets of wild olives and mastic trees on the mountains and better watered regions; and forests of cork oak (*Quercus suber*) on the Kroumerie and Mogod sandstone mountains.

In recent years, the Tunisian Ministry of Agriculture has intensified its efforts to educate farmers on how to best utilize land and water resources. Vast areas of land are being changed by intensive agriculture in the Medjerda Valley and on CapBon. Fields around Lake Ichkeul are densely planted with vineyards, olives, and other fruit trees. Cork oak in Kroumerie and Mogod is harvested and exported to Europe or utilized locally by cork industries. Around Sfax and on the road toward Gabès are vast orchards of olive trees. Tunisian olive oil is a major agricultural export. On the plateau around Kasserine, esparto grass (locally called Halfa) is harvested for use by the cellulose factory. From El Kef southward towards Kasserine and Gafsa, wheat is harvested at the beginning of each summer. On the Cap Bon peninsula, the soil is suitable for the cultivation of citrus fruits and orange groves are a common sight in the vicinity of Grombalia and Nabeul. In the south, date palm groves surround oases like Gabès, Kebili, Tozeur, Nefta and Douz, providing a major source of income for those areas.

Tunisia has a complex mosaic of plant communities at least in the northern region. An understanding of the types of vegetation in each geographical region is

needed for following discussions of mammalian distribution ranges and species richness analyses.

Treatment

The phylogenetic order outlined in Mammal Species of the World (Wilson and Reeder, 1993) was followed in this study except that marine and domestic mammals are listed separately at the end of the other accounts. Within each order of mammals, keys are provided to separate families. Within families additional keys aid in the separation of genera and species. Unfortunately a few taxa are problematic not easy to be identified by merely using the provided keys.

The scheme used in the majority of species accounts is as follows:

- a. The most recent and valid binomial name was used followed by the authority, year and a common name.
- b. Diagnostic features that distinguish the mammals from related taxa were given for most accounts. Measurements and weight, when helpful, were included. General familiar diagnostic features for large artiodactyles and carnivores are not presented (e.g., diagnostic features of the lion).
- c. Distribution of the species in the world, North Africa and Tunisia was estimated from the literature. The reader was then referred to a map that showed the range of the species in North Africa and Tunisia. Range in North Africa was determined from published records from Egypt, Libya, Tunisia, Algeria, and Morocco. The main resources were Osborn and Helmy (1980) and Qumsiyeh (1985) for Egypt; Ranck (1968) and Hufnagl (1972) for Libya; Kowlaski and Rzebik-Kowalska (1991) for Algeria; and Aulagnier (1992) and Aulagnier and Thevenot (1986) for Morocco. The maps in Corbet (1978) were also frequently

consulted. The range in Tunisia was plotted using records obtained in this study as well as records reported in the literature.

In some species where two or more subspecies occur in Tunisia, distributions are shown on map of Tunisia. Subspecies are not shown on the maps of species distribution in North Africa. Figure 2.8 shows a composite map that illustrates the symbols used on the distribution maps.

d. The available data on the natural history of each species were listed. Information on parasites, physiology, ecology, food habits, and behavior were summarized. In many cases, the only reproductive data available was from field notes and museum specimens. Remarks on past distribution for extinct (or nearly extinct) species were listed in this section because it was hard to separate from the information on natural history.

e. Taxonomy included a detailed taxonomic history of the species. The synonymy section starts with a heading that currently is the accepted binomial or trinomial name with the authority and year. The types described were listed with full citation of name, publication, year, type locality, and other remarks. Other usages were listed with authorities and year only, with the citation being given in the Literature Cited.

f. Records of occurrence were listed as specimens examined (which are the original records collected during this study) and literature reports. Spelling of names of cities and/or localities is as written by original authors. I provided the recent equivalent or corrections in brackets (e.g., Borj le Boeuf [= Bordj Bourguiba]). In some records, the localities of collection were not specific (e.g., sud tunisien) or could not be found on recent maps.

Figure 2.8. Typical distribution maps showing all the symbols used.

List of abbreviations

Institutes and Organization

AMNH - American Museum of Natural History.

BM(NH) -British Museum (Natural History).

DGF - Direction Générale des Forêts, Ministère de l'Agriculture, Tunis.

INRAT -Institut National de la Recherche Agricole Tunisien, Tunis.

IRVT -Institut de la Recherche Vétérinaire de Tunisie, Tunis.

MNHS -Musée National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris.

NSRL - Natural Science Research Laboratory, Museum of TTU.

TAPNE -Tunisian Association for the Protection of Nature and the
Environment (French, ATPNE).

TTU - Texas Tech University.

USNM -United States National Museum, Washington, D.C.

Morphological Features

CR - Crown-rump length of embryos (mm).

FA - Forearm length (in bats).

HF - Hind foot length (mm).

M¹ - First upper molar.

Pm² - Second upper premolar.

T - Tail length

General

N Africa - North Africa

E Sfax - East of the city of Sfax.

TD - Tunisian Dinar (currency; almost equivalent to one US dollar).

CHAPTER III
SPECIES ACCOUNTS

In these accounts, nine orders of living mammals are recognized as having representatives in Tunisia. Man is probably the only native member of the Order Primates that has occurred in the area in the past 200 years. The Barbary macaque, *Macaca sylvanus*, occurs in neighboring Algeria but not in Tunisia (Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska, 1991). Marine mammals (including members of the order Cetacea, and the carnivore family Phocidae) and domesticated mammals are only treated superficially. Emphasis is placed on terrestrial species.

ORDER INSECTIVORA

This primitive group of mammals include hedgehogs, shrews and relatives. Two families of this order have representatives in Tunisia: Erinaceidae and Soricidae.

Family Erinaceidae

Hedgehogs

Two species, in two different genera, represent this family in Tunisia.

Key for Family Erinaceidae

1. Median spineless tract narrow; inner digit of hind foot with small nail; hair of venter coarse, sparse; spines smooth; ear less than 40 mm; auditory region not greatly inflated (cavity of bullae barely penetrate pterygoid region)*Atelerix*
- 1'. Median spineless tract wide; inner digit of hind foot with enlarged nail; hair of venter fine, dense (rodent-like); spines papillate; ears more than 40 mm, longer than adjacent spines; auditory region of skull greatly inflated (cavity of bullae extend forward into pterygoid and almost to palate)*Paraechinus*

Genus *Atelerix* Pomel, 1848

Hedgehogs

African hedgehogs most related to *Erinaceus* have variously been grouped with *Erinaceus* or separated as a separate genus, *Aethechinus* (e.g., *A. albiventris*) (Corbet 1971) or *Atelerix* (e.g., *A. algirus*) (Robbins and Stezer, 1985).

According to Corbet (1988), these hedgehogs differ sufficiently from *Erinaceus* to be considered a separate genus. He lists reasons to revive an old name, *Atelerix*, that would refer to all African forms of this group. I follow Corbet (1988) and thus refer to the North African species as *Atelerix algirus*.

Atelerix algirus Lereboullet, 1842

Algerian Hedgehog

Diagnosis. Compared to *Paraechinus aethiopicus*, the auditory region of the skull in the Algerian hedgehogs is inflated slightly. Externally they have smooth spines; sparse, coarse fur on the ventral surface, and short ears that are not as long as the adjacent spines. The ears are 27-37 mm in length. Adults weigh as much as 800 g.

Distribution. These hedgehogs occur in northwest Africa from the western Sahara in southwestern Morocco eastward to Libya and northward to the Mediterranean. Scattered coastal populations, probably introduced, exist in France, Spain, and the Canary Islands (Corbet, 1988; Hutterer, 1983). In Tunisia, they are common, at least locally, in much of the north and central parts of the country and occur around oases as far south as Tatahouine (Fig. 3.1).

Biology. Hedgehogs are nocturnal, spending the daylight hours perhaps in a burrow, under a rock or one of the widespread, introduced cacti (*Opuntia*) or

Figure 3.1. Distribution maps of the Algerian hedgehog, *Aterix algirus* Duvernoy and Lereboullet, 1842. A, *A. algirus algirus* Duvernoy and Lereboullet, 1842; B, *A. algirus girbaensis* Vesmanis, 1981.

agaves (*Agave*). In Tunisia, these plants are used in fencing and separation of cultivated plots. The resulting raised, dense hedges make ideal denning places for hedgehogs as well as providing habitat for their prey.

In cooler weather, hedgehogs are inactive and they probably hibernate as do other related species of hedgehogs (Nowak, 1991). No studies of the food habits of this species were found. Cockrum (in litt.) kept captive individuals for several weeks by feeding them a diet that consisted primarily of canned sardines and milk. They were found to eat grubs, larger tenebrionid beetles, fruit, carrots and other vegetables. No records concerning length of life in nature were found but, in captivity, the related European species has survived up to 10 years (Burton, 1969). Hedgehogs were utilized widely in the past as food throughout Tunisia and North Africa. Live hedgehogs used to be found in the markets of many of the larger villages and towns. Hunters would use trained dogs to catch them at night. However, in recent years the Tunisian Ministry of Agriculture has made it illegal to catch and sell these animals. Some specimens are sold illicitly for folk-medicinal purposes. An old “dog-hunter” was mentioned to me in Mournagia (Ariana governorate) but I was also told he has not practiced in years.

Taxonomy. As mentioned above, Corbet (1988) revived the name *Atelerix* and included members of *Aethechinus* in it. He followed Vesmanis (1979; 1981) in recognizing two subspecies in Tunisia, one on the mainland (*A. a. fallax*) that can be differentiated from the Algerian subspecies, *A. a. algirus*, and one on the Island of Djerba (*A. a. girbaensis*). Djerba subspecies is noticeably lighter in color.

Atelerix algirus fallax (Dobson, 1882)

Erinaceus fallax Dobson, Monogr. Insectivora, 1: 9, 1882, type from Sfax, Tunisia (type in British Museum).

Atelerix algirus Lereboullet, in Duvernoy and Lereboullet, Mem. Soc. Hist. Nat. Strasbourg, 3(2): 14, 1842, type from Algeria (restricted to Oran by Miller. Mammals Western Europe, p. 310, 1912; see Saint Girons, Mammalia, 36: 166, 1972, for use of Lereboullet as author); Lataste, 1887; Anderson, 1895; Trouessart, 1905; Trouessart, 1906; Gadeau de Kerville, 1906; Blanc, 1935; Kahmann and Vesmanis, 1977;

Atelerix algirus algirus, Corbet, 1988.

Erinaceus algirus algirus, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951; Corbet, 1978; Vesmanis, 1979.

Aethechinus algirus algirus, Allen, 1939.

This subspecies occurs in much of northern Tunisia, especially at lower elevations. In central Tunisia, it is restricted to oases and the more humid areas along the coast.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 20, distributed as follows: Vicinity of Sidi Thabet, ca. 20 km NW Tunis (purchased in Tunis market), 5; Vicinity of Medjez-el-Bab (purchased Tunis Market), 1; Tunis (purchased in market), 9; 23.5 km N Pont du Fahs on GP 3 near junction to Menaagha, 1; Tozeur (purchased at "zoo"), 1; 23.5 km NW Médénine on GP 1, 1; Jebel Zaghouan, Jenan Mdena area, 2.

Literature reports: Ain Draham in Khroumerie (Gadeau de Kerville, 1906; Kahmann and Vesmanis, 1977; Kock, 1980b)--probably the same as Ain Draham reported by Colas-Belcouar and Rageau (1951) and repeated by Kahmann and Vesmanis (1977); Bordj Oued Cherchera in Bled Talha S of Jebel Bou Hedma (Heim de Balsac, 1923; Joleaud, 1927; Kahmann and Vesmanis, 1977; Kock, 1980); Between Bou Ficha and Enfidaville (Harrison, 1967; Kock, 1980); El Haouaria, Cap Bon (Vesmanis, 1979); Gabes (Matschie, 1889); Jebel Ouerga,

West of Le Kef (Malec and Storch, 1972; Kahmann and Vesmanis, 1977; Kock, 1980)--probably same as Jebel Ouerga, near Le Kef of Vesmanis (1979); Jebel Ressay (Pavesi, 1884; Hoogstraal, 1955; Kahmann and Vesmanis, 1977; Kock, 1980)--may be the same as Jebel Ressay reported by Colas-Belcour and Rageau (1951); Hoogstraal (1955); and Kahmann and Vesmanis (1977); Khroumerie, NW Tunisia (Trouessart, 1906; Joleaud, 1927; Blanc, 1935; Kahmann and Vesmanis, 1977); Le Kef (Blanc, 1935; Kahmann and Vesmanis, 1977); Mahadia [= Mahdia?] Joyeux (1923); Kahmann and Vesmanis (1977); Matmata (Blanc, 1935; Kahmann and Vesmanis, 1977); 10 km W Sfax (Vesmanis, 1979); Tozem [= Tozzer, = Tozeur in Blad el Djerid] (Lataste, 1885; Lataste, 1887; Joleaud, 1927; Kahmann and Vesmanis, 1977); Tunis (Colas-Belcour and Rageau, 1951; Hoogstraal, 1955; Kahmann and Vesmanis, 1977); Zarzas in Arad (Lataste, 1885; Lataste, 1887; Joleaud, 1927; Kahmann and Vesmanis, 1977).

Atelerix algirus girbaensis (Vesmanis, 1981)

Erinaceus algirus girbaensis Vesmanis, Bonn. Zool. Beitr. 31(3/4): 207, 1981,
type from Etikett, Djerba, Tunisia.

Erinaceus algirus algirus, Corbet, 1971 (part from Djerba).

Erinaceus vagans, Blanc, 1935.

Erinaceus algirus, Vesmanis, 1979.

This subspecies is restricted to the island of Djerba off the eastern Tunisian shore in the Gulf of Gabès.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 28, distributed on the island of Djerba as follows: 2 km W Houmt Souk, 5; 1 km E Cedryen, 9; 1.5 km E Adjim, 1; Guellala, 5; Senouikech, 1; Mahboubine, 1; 2.5 km S Midoun, 1.5 km E of highway, 4; Midoun, 2.

Literature reports: The following, arranged chronologically, reported *Atelerix* from Djerba: Galli Valerio (1911), Kollman (1911), Seurat (1911), Weiss (1911), Joyeux (1921), Joleaud (1927), Blanc (1935), Colas-Belcour and Rageau (1951), Dollfus (1951), Saint Girons (1939), Malec and Starch (1972), Lehmann (1972), Kahmann and Vesmanis (1977), Vesmanis (1979), Kock (1980b).

Blanc (1935) reported that he had sent additional specimens of hedgehogs from Djerba to Thomas and that Thomas had named *Paraechinus deserti blancalis* and had dedicated to Blanc. Apparently Blanc, by 1935, had forgotten what kinds of hedgehogs he had sent to Thomas [both *Atelerix* and *Paraechinus*]. In any case, he discussed at length whether there were two, or only one, white hedgehogs on Djerba. He also speculated as to the possible introduction of hedgehogs from the Balears Islands to Djerba.

Because of these comments, Cockrum and his team (in litt.) were especially interested in securing a topotypical series of *Paraechinus* from Djerba. However, repeated visits to the island failed to reveal any long-eared hedgehogs. Instead they found only white or whitish short-eared hedgehogs (*Atelerix*).

Prior to the collecting activities of Cockrum, Pam and Tom Vaughan in Tunisia (between 1972-1975), only a few specimens had been available from a given locality. As a result, little had been recorded concerning age, sexual and individual variation in this species. Specimens were purchased in markets. The result was a series of 35 from the region of Tunis and 56 from the island of Djerba--probably the largest available from restricted localities.

Kahmann and Vesmanis (1977:1) reported on a large sample (29) of hedgehogs taken from the Mediterranean island of Formentera. They concluded that it is "similar in size to the form from Minorca [in the same island group] known as *A. a. vagans* Thomas, 1901. The color of the hairy parts is different, not the

whiteness' as Thomas (1910) put it. In skull measurements, no difference." They reported that only 17% of the specimens taken in October were adults. Their study included an extensive review of the taxonomic and distributional literature pertaining to *Atelerix algirus*.

In 1980, Vesmanis named the Djerba population as a distinct subspecies. His diagnosis emphasized color--the insular population being very light ("a dirty white") and the mainland populations being dark. He also indicated that the insular form was smaller than the mainland subspecies. However, the apparent size difference might simply be the result of the age of the individuals in the sample available to Vesmanis--younger individuals being from the island.

Thomas (*Erinaceus vagans*, in letter as reported by Blanc, 1935) and Vesmanis (1980) found that the insular population of short-eared hedgehogs on Djerba is distinct from mainland populations in at least the color. My examination of the specimens at NSRL confirm a difference in the shape of the nasal bone and the width of the suture between the nasal and frontal differ in the two populations.

Paraechinus aethiopicus (Ehrenberg, 1833)

Desert Hedgehog

Diagnosis. Desert hedgehogs differ from Algerian hedgehogs in the following characters: ears are longer than the adjacent spines; spines are rough and papillate; venter with dense, soft fur; and the auditory region of the skull is markedly more inflated.

Distribution. They occur in the sub-desert and various oases, south of the Atlas Mountains from Morocco southward in Mauritania and eastward through Algeria, Tunisia, Libya, Sudan, northern Ethiopia to Somalia. Some authors include the Arabian Peninsula populations in this species (Corbet, 1971, 1988).

In Tunisia, this species is much less common than the Algerian hedgehog and may well be extinct in part of its former range (Fig. 3.2). As indicated above, Thomas (1921) described a subspecies from the island of Djerba, based on material taken in 1921. Between 1973-75, on repeated trips to Djerba, Cockrum et al. (in litt.) failed to find any indication that this species was still present.

Biology. During their stay in Tunisia, Cockrum et al. (in litt.) secured only one specimen of the desert hedgehog. It was bought from a farm boy near Médénine. In Tozeur, they attempted buying a specimen at a local zoo. The price asked for *Paraechinus* was 50 times higher than that asked for *Atelerix* which indicates that the animal is very rare.

Taxonomy. Two races are recognized from Tunisia, one on the mainland and one on Djerba.

Paraechinus aethiopicus deserti (Loche, 1859)

Erinaceus deserti Loche, Cat. Mamm. et Oiseaux Algérie, p. 20, 1858, type from "southern Sahara, in oasis of Beni-Mzab, Ouargla, and Tuggurt, Algeria; Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905; Blanc, 1935.

Paraechinus aethiopicus deserti, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

Paraechinus a[ethiopicus]. deserti, Corbet, 1978; Vesmanis, 1979.

Paraechinus deserti deserti, Allen, 1939.

Paraechinus deserti blancalis Thomas, 1921

Paraechinus deserti blancalis Thomas, Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist. 9(8): 570, 1921, type from Island of Djerba, southeastern Tunisia; Allen, 1939; Deleuil, 1956.

Paraechinus a[ethiopicus]. blancalis, Corbet, 1978.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 1, from 23.5 km N Médénine on GP 1.

Figure 3.2. Distribution maps of the desert hedgehog, *Paraechinus aethiopicus* (Ehrenberg, 1833). A, *Paraechinus aethiopicus deserti* (Loche, 1858); B, *Paraechinus aethiopicus blancalis* (Thomas, 1921).

Literature reports: Kock (1980) provided a listing of records for this species. The following localities and authorities are listed: Asam Oasis [= Arram]; Bongrara [= Bou Grara in Arad]; Gafsa (repeated by Joleaud, 1927); Tozem [= Tozeur in Chott El Djerid] (Lataste, 1885). Same localities above in addition to Bir Marabot SE of Gafsa [repeated by Joleaud, 1927] (Lataste, 1887); Gabès (Matschie, 1899); Djerba (Kollman, 1911; Weiss, 1911; Seurat, 1913; 1917; Thomas, 1921; Joyeux, 1923) [by Vesmanis, 1979 under *algirus*]; Matmata (Seurat, 1913).

Family Soricidae

Shrews

This family is distinguished by small size, with a head and body length averaging 40 to 120 mm, and by soft dense pelage, and small ears. The major distinguishing characters for these shrews are the incomplete zygomatic arch, large protruding upper jaw incisors, and two condyles for the condyloid process of the lower jaw. Two genera of shrews are known to occur in Tunisia.

Key for Family Soricidae

- 1. Size tiny (head and body less than 45 mm, hind foot less than 8 mm); four upper unicuspid teeth; condylobasal length less than 14 mm; mandible less than 9 mm*Suncus*
- 1'. Size larger (head and body more than 50 mm; hind foot more than 9 mm); three upper unicuspid teeth; condylobasal length more than 14 mm; mandibular length more than 9 mm*Crocidura*

Genus *Suncus* Ehrenberg, 1833

Both the largest and the smallest soricids are members of this genus. Only a single species of the genus occurs in Tunisia.

Suncus etruscus (Savi, 1822). Pygmy Shrew

Diagnosis. This is may well be the smallest mammalian species in the world, with adults generally weighing only about two grams. Total length ranges up to 80 mm of which the tail comprises 30 mm.

Distribution. Members of this genus occur through much of Europe, Asia and Africa and have been introduced on many of the islands in the Pacific Ocean area. In Tunisia, they have been recorded from the northern region, the central steppe and the Chotts area (Fig. 3.3).

Biology. Although rarely seen or collected the pygmy shrew is at least locally common as indicated by its frequency in owl pellets. The small series taken by Cockrum et al. (in litt.) at Oudna Station were captured in can (pitfall) traps. Müller (1956) reported them as living on plains without rocks or trees, but always in the vicinity of a wadi (dry river valley) where they lived in accumulations of vegetation.

Taxonomy. Whereas so few specimens of this species are available from Africa, no meaningful judgments of relationships to European populations are yet possible. For the time being, I will refer these specimens to the nominate subspecies.

Suncus etruscus etruscus (Savi, 1822)

Sorex etruscus Savi, Nuovo Giorn. de' Letterati, 1: 60, pl. 1, 1822, type from Pisa, Italy.

Suncus etruscus, Allen, 1939; Müller, 1956; Corbet, 1978.

Suncus etruscus etruscus, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951; Heim de Balsac and Meester, 1977.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 11, distributed as follows: Oudna Station, 20 km airline S Tunis, 5; In addition owl pellets containing *Suncus*

Figure 3.3. Distribution maps of the pygmy shrew, *Suncus etruscus* (Savi, 1822).

remains were taken by Cockrum et al. (in litt.) from Djebel Ichkeul; Bulla Regia, near Jendouba (Souk el Arba); and Oudna ruins.

Literature reports: Most of the limited number of specimens from Tunisia were taken by H. P. Müller. Most have been reported more than once, often with conflicting data. The following is a summary:

1. Tunis, 3 crania from owl pellets taken in 1937 (Anon., 1956). The status of this material is unknown.

2. Tunis: City Gardens, found dead in Nov. 1954 by Dr. M. Mathis (Anon., 1955). Belvédère Garden, collected on 30 Nov. 1954 by Dr. Mathis and identified by Heim de Balsac (Arnould, 1956). Also reported by Heim de Balsac (1968), Heim de Balsac and Lamotte (1957), Vesmanis et al. (1980), and Sans-Coma et al. (1981).

3. Roman caves near El Haouaria (owl pellet material), reported by Heim de Balsac et al. (1954), Arnould (1956), and as El Haouaria by Vesmanis et al. (1980).

4. Protville, taken in 1955 by H. P. Müller and identified by Kahmann (Anon., 1956). Also reported by Kahmann and Altner (1956), Vesmanis et al. (1980), and Sans-Coma et al. (1981).

5. Tebourba, a male taken 20 Mar 1955 by Müller (Kahmann and Altner, 1956). Vesmanis et al. (1980) reported this specimen and says it was cited by Heim de Balsac (1968) and Heim de Balsac and Lamotte (1957). Sans-Coma et al. (1981) also list it.

6. Sidi Amor on the banks of the Ariana marsh, four reported as captured by H. P. Müller in May, 1955 (Anon., 1956). What happened to these animals is unknown. Vesmanis et al. (1980) appears to have listed them as from two localities (Sidi Amor and Ariana), crediting the reference to Müller-- a reference that does not

agree with Müller's published report. Sans-Coma et al. (1981) repeat the Vesmanis report.

7. Oued Chaffrou, between Djedeida and St. Cyprien in Aug.- Sept. 1955 by H. P. Müller (Anon., 1956). The disposition of this specimen is unknown.

Vesmanis et al. (1980) and Sans-Coma et al. (1981) list this as St. Cyprien.

8. Oued Chaffrou, near El Bathan 1 taken 15 Oct. 1956, held captive and observed (Müller, 1956). This appears to be the specimen as reported by Kahmann and Altner (1956) and is probably the one listed by Vesmanis et al. (1980). This is also listed by Sans-Coma, et al. (1981).

9. Medjez el Bab [on Oued Chaffrou], taken 16 Oct. 1956 by Müller, (Vesmanis et al., 1980; Sans-Coma et al., 1981).

10. Nefta, reported by Wandeler (1965), Vesmanis et al. (1980), and Sans-Coma et al. (1981).

11. Ain Draham, reported by Vesmanis et al. (1980) as "seen" and repeated by Sans-Coma et al. (1981).

Genus *Crocidura* (Herman, 1780)

The few specimens of white-toothed shrews (genus *Crocidura*) that have been taken in North Africa appear to have been the subject of great confusion as to their taxonomic status. A number of names have been applied in both the specific and the subspecific sense. I follow most recent workers in recognizing two species as occurring in Tunisia.

Key for Genus *Crocidura*

1. Size larger (tail more than 35 mm, total length more 100 mm, weight more than 7 g); color dark (dorsal color dark brown, venter dark gray, dorsal surface of hind foot dark); greatest length of skull more than 19 mm; condylobasal length

more than 17 mm; first and second upper unicuspid more or less equal in size from crown view; M² roughly square in dorsal view; length of rostrum (from anterior end of skull to line connecting posterior extent of molars) long, more than 2.6 mm

.....*Crocidura russula*

1'. Size smaller (tail less than 35 mm, total length less than 100 mm, weight less than 7 g); color lighter (dorsal color pale brownish gray, somewhat dappled, venter white with some gray hairs, dorsal surface of hind foot whitish); greatest length of skull less than 19 mm; condylobasal length less than 17 mm; second unicuspid smaller than third; M² longer than wide; length of rostrum smaller, less than 2.2 mm*Crocidura whitakeri*

Crocidura russula (Hermann, 1780)

White-toothed Shrew

Diagnosis. The white-toothed shrews is much larger than the pygmy shrew. It weighs 6 to 14 g and has a total length of 95 to 140 mm. The hind foot is 11 to 14 mm in length.

Distribution. It is widely distributed in Europe, from Germany and Poland westward to Portugal and along the Mediterranean, the northern Arabian Peninsula and eastward to Japan and northern China. In North Africa, it occurs in Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia and Libya (Fig. 3.4).

Biology. Little information is available on the biology of those animals. In Algeria, Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska (1991) reported them from varying elevations from sea level to around 1700 m. They usually live in humid grassy areas and in the litter of forest habitats where they easily forage on small invertebrates.

Figure 3.4 Distribution maps of the white-toothed shrew, *Crocidura russula* (Herman, 1780).

Taxonomy. Future studies, with more material available, may indicate that two subspecies should be recognized in Tunisia, a darker northern form and a paler southern race. However, for now, I place all in the single subspecies, *Crocidura russula yebalensis*.

The status of the named, *Crocidura anthonyi* Heim de Balsac, is unclear. In his original description, Heim de Balsac (1940) indicated that his new "species" was based on four specimens (2 adults and 2 young, originally preserved in formalin) taken at Gafsa in 1908. However, in 1968, de Balsac expressed doubt that the material actually came from Tunisia. Furthermore, the specimens were not to be found (I. Vesmanis, pers. comm. with E. L. Cockrum, in litt.).

I follow recent usage in applying *yebalensis* as the subspecific name. This is based on the general acceptance of the conclusion that *agilis* and other earlier names are unidentifiable. See Heim de Balsac and Meester (1977) for a summary.

Crocidura russula yebalensis Cabrera, 1913

Crocidura yebalensis Cabrera, Biol. Soc. Esp. Hist. Nat. Madrid, 13: 400, 1913,
type from Tétuan, Morocco.

C[rocidura]. r[ussula]. yebalensis, Corbet, 1978.

Crocidura russula yebalensis, Vesmanis and Vesmanis, 1980.

Crocidura russula, Gadeau de Kerville, 1906; Vesmanis, 1972.

Crocidura russula agilis Allen, 1939; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

C[rocidura]. r[ussula]. agilis, Heim de Balsac and Meester, 1977.

Crocidura russulus Trouessart, 1905.

Crocidura russulus leucodon Trouessart, 1906.

C[rocidura]. araneus Lataste, 1887.

Crocidura anthonyi Heim de Balsac, Bull. Mus. Hist. Nat. Paris, 12: 382, 1940,
type from Gafsa, Tunisia; Heim de Balsac and Meester, 1977.

Crocidura russula anthonyi, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 8, distributed as follows: Ain Oktor, 3 km S Korbous, 1; 15 km SW Port du Fahs on GP4, 1 km E highway, 1; Oudna Station, 20 km airline S Tunis, 3; Djebel Ichkeul (owl pellets, TTU); Bulla Regia near Jendouba (Souk el Arba), (owl pellets, TTU); Maktar (owl pellets, TTU).

Literature reports: (1 = Vesmanis and Vesmanis, 1980; 2 = Vesmanis, 1972). El Haouaria, Djebel Sidi Abiod, Cap Bon (1); Ain Draham region (Gadeau de Kerville, 1906); 7 km S Ain Draham, Strasse nach Feriana (1); Ain Oktor über Soliman, Cap Bon (1); Oued Chafroa (2) [= ? Oued Chaffrou, Djedeida (1)]; St. Germain [= Ez Zahra] near Hammam-Lif (Blanc, 1935); road near Bardo [= near Tunis] (Blanc, 1935); Cartago n. Tunis (1, 2); Bouxiera, Djedeida (1, 2); Galita Archipel, Ile de La Galite (1, 2); NW La Marsa, Tunis (1); Korba (1, 2); Kelibia, Cap Bon (1, 2); Sidi Bou Said, n. Tunis (1, 2); Zaghouan-Gebirge, 40 km S Tunis (1, 2); Djebel Nahli (1); El Bathan, S Tebourba (1); Mansoura (1); Region of the Chotts (Lataste, 1887); Gafsa (Heim de Balsac, 1940, type locality); on road, 1 km from Tatahouine (Blanc, 1935).

Crocidura whitakeri De Winton, 1897

Whitaker's White-toothed Shrew

Diagnosis. This species can be distinguished from pygmy shrews by larger size. It can be discriminated from *Crocidura russula* by lighter fur and, in general, smaller size.

Distribution. *Crocidura whitakeri* is widely distributed from southern Europe eastward through Asia to Korea. It is also found in North Africa (Fig. 3.5).

Figure 3.5. Distribution maps of Whitaker's shrew, *Crocidura whitakeri* De Winton, 1897.

Taxonomy. Two species of *Crocidura* are known to occur in Tunisia. The specific name to be applied to the smaller species has been the subject of some controversy in recent years. Ellerman and Morrison-Scott (1951) referred North African populations to *Crocidura suaveolens whitakeri* De Winton, 1898. Heim de Balsac (1968), Vesmanis (1976), Heim de Balsac and Meester (1977) reported *whitakeri* as specifically distinct from *suaveolens*, a position that tentatively was accepted by Hutterer (1986) in his revision of the *Crocidura* of Morocco.

Lataste (1885) reported this species from an unknown locality in Tunisia, taken in 1883 by Dr. Cossen, leader of the Scientific Exploration of Tunisia team of 1883 (See Lataste, 1887). However, on the advice of Dr. G. E. Dobson (who never actually saw this specimen), Lataste changed the identification in 1887, listing it only as "perhaps only a simple race, a dwarf subspecies." Vesmanis (1977) found this specimen in the collection in Paris, confirmed its identification as *Crocidura whitakeri*, and described it in detail.

Crocidura whitakeri De Winton, 1897

Crocidura whitakeri De Winton, Proc. Zool. Soc. London for 1897: 954, type from Sierzet, Morocco; Heim de Balsac, 1968; Vesmanis, 1976; Vesmanis, 1976; Heim de Balsac and Meester, 1977; Vesmanis, 1977; Vesmanis and Vesmanis, 1980; Hutterer, 1986.

C[rocidura]. s[uaevolens]. whitakeri, Corbet, 1978.

Crocidura suaveolens, Lataste, 1885.

Crocidura russulus suaveolens, Trouessart, 1905.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: Vesmanis (1976a) and Vesmanis and Vesmanis (1980) reported this subspecies from the following localities: Chotts du Sud Tunisien, El Haouaria, Gafsa, and Nefta. Vesmanis (1976b) also reported it from Gafsa.

ORDER CHIROPTERA

Four families of bats have representatives in Tunisia, most of which are known only from the northern half of the country.

Key for Order Chiroptera

1. Muzzle with obvious nose leaf (extremely complex in some); ears separate, without a tragus and independently mobile; tail extends to edge of well developed interfemoral membrane; premaxillae fused medially but widely separated laterally and only fused posteriorly to the maxillae, resulting in a widely separated palatal branchFamily Rhinolophidae

1'. Nose leaf absent (muzzle plain or with only a naked muscular pad surrounding the external nares); ears various (separate or joined at the bases) but immobile and with tragus present; tail various; premaxillae fused laterally and posteriorly to the maxillae and anteriorly they are fused (Molossidae and Rhinopomatidae) or separate (Vespertilionidae)2

2(1'). Small interfemoral membrane with a long tail, almost the length of the head and body; muzzle with naked muscular pad surrounding external nares; ears joined at bases; rostrum with large swelling anterior to the orbits
.....Family Rhinopomatidae

2'. Interfemoral membrane medium or long; tail equal in length to the interfemoral membrane or extending posteriorly no more than half of the length of the head and body; muzzle plain; ears free or joined at the bases; rostrum without large swelling anterior to the orbits3

3(2'). Interfemoral membrane medium (with a stout tail extending posteriorly about half the length of the head and body); ears deeply folded and heavy (depressed) in appearance, usually joined at base, and with a low tragus; premaxillae and maxillae fused into a solid structureFamily Molossidae

3'. Long interfemoral membrane with tail that extends only to (or slightly beyond) its posterior edge; ears usually mouse-like (large, upright, thin) and separate; tragus generally prominent; premaxillary gap present at anterior edge of palate, resulting in gap between upper incisorsFamily Vespertilionidae

Family Rhinopomatidae

Mouse-tailed Bats

This family includes only one genus. It occurs from northern Africa eastward to Burma. Unique features include an excessively long tail that extends far beyond the narrow interfemoral membrane. Two species occurs in North Africa, *Rhinopoma microphyllum* and *R. hardwickei*. Only *R. hardwickei* has been recorded from Tunisia.

Rhinopoma hardwickei Gray, 1831

Mouse-tailed Bat

Diagnosis. This bat has a short interfemoral membrane and a tail that is as long as the head and body. The ears are large, extending beyond the nostrils when laid forward, and are connected at the bases by a band of skin.

Distribution. It is known from scattered localities in northwestern Africa, southward to Niger and, more commonly seen to the east in Egypt and southward to northwestern Kenya. All records are from arid regions. In Tunisia, it is known from Redeyef and Degash near to Chott el Djerid (Fig. 3.6).

Biology. The two specimen that were collected from Tunisia May 26, 1996 were pregnant females. Each had one embryo 22-24 mm crown-rump length. They were obtained from a rock outcropping roost that housed about 10 individuals. Their roost was not deep enough to be well protected from the radiant

Figure 3.6. Distribution maps of lesser rat-tailed bat, *Rhinopoma hardwickei* Gray, 1831.

heat, although there was a tree at the entrance. Nearby was a depression in a rock that had accumulated rain water. Kowlaski and Rzebik-Kowalska (1991) collected a specimen of this species from Roufi, Algeria that roosted in similar situation. Further, they mention the presence of fat deposits in the lower abdominal area. I found the same in the Tunisian specimens. The fat could be seen through the skin in the dorsal and ventral sides.

Taxonomy. Olivier (1909) first reported the mouse-tailed bat in Tunisia when he wrote of one that he caught in a bedroom at Redeyef where “it had been attracted by light.” Apparently the bat was not saved as a voucher specimen. His report gives no features from which a specific identification can be made, but most later authors have contended that it must have been *Rhinopoma hardwickei*, the lesser mouse-tailed bat. See especially Allen and Strinati (1969) who clearly state that *Rhinopoma microphyllum* does not occur in northwestern Africa. Hayman and Hill (1971), however, report *Rhinopoma microphyllum* from Algeria and southwestern Morocco as well as *Rhinopoma hardwickei cystops* from Tunisia and Morocco. Koch-Weser (1984) provided a synopsis of the distribution in North Africa. She listed the material as *R. h. arabium* and *R. h. cystops* from southern Algeria. I suspect that, in general, two subspecies cannot coexist sympatrically and retain different identities. Van Cakenberghe and De Vree (1994) revised the family Rhinopomatidae by studying a large collection of rhinopomatid (including holotype and paratype) specimens from different localities. Using multivariate statistical analyses, they found that a group of *R. hardwickei* from north-central Africa cluster together. They decided to call these specimens from some parts of Egypt, Chad (one specimen was considered “a little to [sic] large”), some parts of Niger, and southeastern Algeria, *R. h. cystops*, whereas the rest of the African (including Tunisian) and Middle Eastern material retained the name *R. h. arabium*. It is worth

mentioning that their statistical analyses did not include specimens from Tunisia. They did examine two Tunisian specimens of *R. hardwickei* which are housed at MNHN and I presume they are the same ones that Olivier (1909) and Laurent (1941) discussed.

Using the keys and illustrations in Van Cakenberghe and De Vree (1994) . I found that the two specimens I have from Tunisia are not typical *R. hardwickei arabium*. Nevertheless, I decided to follow their decision, which is in agreement with Hill (1977), and Koch-Weser (1984). Thus, the following name is provisionally assigned to the specimens from Tunisia.

Rhinopoma hardwickei arabium Thomas, 1913

Rhinopoma cystops arabium Thomas, Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist., [8]12: 89, 1913,
type from Wasil, Yemen.

Rhinopoma hardwickei arabium, Koch-Weser, 1984; Van Cakenberghe and De
Vree, 1994.

Rhinopoma cystops arabium, Laurent, 1941.

Rhinopoma microphyllum, Olivier, 1909.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 2, Mountains near Chott El
Djerid; Dgomous Reserve, Degash delegation, Tozeur governorate.

Literature reports: Between Redeyef and Metlaoui (Laurent, 1941); Redeyef
(Olivier, 1909); Redeyef-Metlaoui and Redeyef (probably the same specimens of
Laurent (1941) Olivier (1909) and Van Cakenberghe and De Vree (1994)).

Family Rhinolophidae

Old World Complex-nosed Bats

Bats of this family are widely distributed in the Old World, especially in the tropics. Two subfamilies (sometimes accorded familial status) generally are recognized. Members of the subfamily Rhinolophinae (horseshoe-nosed bats) have a complex nose leaf that includes a many lobed and folded sella just above the nostrils and a single dorsal triangularly shaped lancet. The hallux has two phalanges, the other fingers have three. Two genera are included only one of which occurs in Africa.

The second subfamily, Hipposiderinae (leaf-nosed bats) has a simpler nose leaf. Each of the toes has only two phalanges. As now interpreted by many taxonomists, the subfamily is divisible into six genera, only one of which (*Asellia*) occurs in Tunisia.

Key for Family Rhinolophidae.

1. Posterior plate of noseleaf triangular and with erect, pointed tip; digits (except hallux) with three phalanges; tail short; three lower incisors on each side (dental formula $\frac{1}{3} \frac{1}{1} \frac{1 \text{ or } 2}{3} \frac{3}{3}$)*Rhinolophus*
- 1'. Posterior plate of nose leaf elliptical; all digits of foot with two phalanges; two lower premolars on each side (dental formula $\frac{1}{1} \frac{1}{1} \frac{2}{2} \frac{3}{3}$)*Asellia*

Genus *Rhinolophus* Lacepède, 1799

Members of this genus occur in Europe, Asia and Australia as well as in Africa. As in many genera of small mammals that contain populations with a relatively large spectrum of morphological variation, the precise number of species is not known.

The identification of a horseshoe bat is not difficult. The large, complex noseleaf that surrounds the nostrils is diagnostic. It is generally devoid of hair and consists of three parts: the horseshoe, so called because of its shape, covers the upper lip and surrounds the nostrils; the lancet, which is attached at its base in the area above the nostrils; and the flattened sella, which is connected at its base in the median line to the base of the lancet and extends anteriorly and dorsally. Between the posterior margin of the sella and median anterior surface of the lancet is usually a thin, membranous connection. The ears of these bats are large and lack a tragus. The interfemoral membrane and tail are short, not extending beyond the feet.

Ellerman and Morrison-Scott (1951) recognized 21 species as occurring in the Palearctic and Indian regions. Others are known from the Malaysian and Australian areas. Hayman and Hill (1971) recognized 19 species as occurring in Africa, only five (or six) of which occurred in the Palearctic region north of the Sahara.

The identification of each species of horseshoe bats within the genus *Rhinolophus* is much more difficult.

Key for Genus *Rhinolophus*

1. Size small; forearm less than 40 mm, weight less than 6 g; greatest length of skull less than 17 mm*Rhinolophus hipposideros*
- 1'. Size larger; forearm more than 44 mm, weight more than 6 g; greatest length of skull more than 17 mm2
- 2(1'). Size large; forearm more than 50 mm, weight more than 14 g; from the side view the portion of the connective at the dorsal edge of the sella low and rounded; greatest length of the skull 19-22 mm*Rhinolophus ferrumequinum*
- 2'. Size medium; forearm less than 50 and more than 44 mm; weight less than 12 g3

3(2'). Second (distal) phalanx of digit IV long (more than twice the length of the first phalanx); margins of sella wedge-shaped; occlusal surface of second and third lower premolars approximately equal; greatly depressed saddle between parietal and occipital, making marked separation of occipital region from the rest of the skull*Rhinolophus blasii*

3'. Second (distal) phalanx of digit IV short (less than twice the length of the first); sides of sella parallel; occlusal surface of second lower premolar markedly less than third; parietal-occipital saddle much less developed4

4(3'). Posterior lance of noseleaf gradually tapered; forearm generally 45-50 mm*Rhinolophus euryale*

4'. Posterior lance of noseleaf with strongly concave borders; forearm generally 48-51 mm*Rhinolophus mehelyi*

Rhinolophus ferrumequinum (Schreber, 1774)

Greater Horseshoe Bat

Diagnosis. The greater horseshoe bat is relatively easy to distinguish from other Tunisian species, primarily because of its larger size. The forearm is generally more than 52 mm in length and the wing expanse reaches 350 mm. Weights of adults are 15 to 17 g.

Distribution. Members of this species occur in Europe, from southern England and Belgium eastward to the Caspian Sea and southward to southern Portugal, Italy and Greece. In Africa, it occurs north of the Atlas Mountains in western Morocco, Algeria and Tunisia. In Tunisia, it occurs in the northern half of the country southward to just south of Tatahouine (Fig. 3.7).

Figure 3.7 Distribution maps of the greater horseshoe bat, *Rhinolophus ferrumequinum* (Schreber, 1774).

Biology. Specimens taken on 26 July at Scarna Mine included one juvenile male. Those taken 29 July in the cave at Djebel Oust included both lactating females and juveniles but no adult males.

Taxonomy. Ellerman and Morrison-Scott (1951) and Corbet (1978) assigned these populations to the nominate race. Gaisler (1983) also is of the opinion that Algerian specimens are not different from Middle European ones and included them in the typical subspecies. The Tunisian material follow this name.

Rhinolophus ferrumequinum ferrumequinum (Schreber, 1774)

Vespertilio ferrum-equinum Schreber, Säugeth, I: Plate 62, upper figs., text page 174, 1774, type from France.

R[hinolophus]. ferrum-equinum, Lataste, 1887.

Rhinolophus ferrumequinum ferrumequinum, Aellen and Strinati, 1969; Aellen and Strinati, 1970; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

Rhinolophus f[errumequinum]. ferrumequinum, Corbet, 1978.

Rhinolophus ferrum-equinum, Trouessart, 1905; Blanc, 1935; Heim de Balsac et al., 1954; Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b.

Rhinolophus ferrum-equinum obscurus, Allen, 1939.

Rhinolophus ferrumequinum obscurus, Aellen and Strinati, 1969.

R[hinolophus]. ferrumequinum obscurus, Hayman and Hill, 1971.

Only this subspecies is currently recognized in Tunisia, thus, its distribution is as described above for the species.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 16, distributed as follows:

Abandoned Kohl mine, 5 km NE Aïn Draham, 1; Djebel Ressay, mine 28 km SSE Tunis, 1; Djebel Zaghouan, cave at Poste Optique, 1; Scarna Mine, 10 km NE Rohia (60 km N Sbeitla), 4 ; Cave, Djebel Oust, 6 km S Oum Djeddour, 28 km E Thala, 4; 4 km S Redeyef on road to Aïoun Ameer, 2; 2 km NW Toujane on MC

104, 45 km S Gabès, 1; 2 km S Tatahouine on GP 19. 1 km E highway at fortification tunnel, 1; Tatahouine, fortification in mountains south of town, 1.

Literature reports: Between El Haouaria and Sidi Daoud (Heim de Balsac et al., 1954; Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b); Djebel Bou Kornine (Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b); Djebel Ressas (Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b); Djebel Zaghouan (Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b); Grotto du Cheval, Zaghouan (Aellen and Strinati, 1970); El Akhouat (= near Gafour; Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b); Feriana (Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905; Blanc, 1935).

Rhinolophus hipposideros (Bechstein, 1800)

Lesser Horseshoe Bat

Diagnosis. This the smallest of the five species of horseshoe bats known from Tunisia. It has a forearm of less than 40 mm, a wingspread of about 210 mm and an adult weight of 4 to 5 g.

Distribution. Lesser horseshoe bat occurs in central and southern Europe easterly into southwestern Asia. In northwestern Africa, it is known from Morocco, Algeria and Tunisia. In northeastern Africa, it is known from Sudan, Ethiopia and Eritrea. A separate population occurs in the Sinai. In Tunisia, this species is known only from a few northern mountain localities (Fig. 3.8).

Biology. No large colonies have been reported in Tunisia. Deleuil and Labbe (1955b) found 4 males (February, 1955) hibernating 30 to 50 meters from the opening of a cave near Poste Optique in Djebel Zaghouan. During their studies in Tunisia, Cockrum et al. (in litt.) took 13 males by placing mist nets over the entrances of two of the caves near Poste Optique. Shortly after dark they trapped the bats in the nets as the bats attempted to leave (or enter, in some cases) the caves. Blanc (1935) recorded nothing other than “taken in rock crevices” concerning his

Figure 3.8 Distribution maps of the lesser horseshoe bat, *Rhinolophus hipposideros* (Bechstein, 1899).

specimens. Gadeau de Kerville (1906) reported it from an ancient tomb known as “Grotte de Kaloi” near Aïn Draham in May or June, 1906. Cockrum et al. (in litt.) did not locate this site in 1974 or 1975.

Taxonomy. The subspecific identification of Tunisian populations is still to be determined. Allen (1939) indicated that *Rhinolophus hipposideros minimus* Heuglin, 1861 (type locality, Kéréen, Eritrea) occurs in the “Mediterranean subregion, south to Sennaar [= in Sudan], east to Eritrea, not known from Egypt.” He also listed, without comment or giving any range other than type locality, two subspecies from Morocco: *Rhinolophus hipposideros escalerae* Andersen, 1918, from Ha-ha, Mogador, and *Rhinolophus hipposideros vespa* Laurent, 1937, from Korifla. Ellerman and Morrison-Scott (1951) essentially followed this arrangement, indicating that *R. h. minimus* occurs along the northern side of the Mediterranean from Portugal to Italy, Malta and Cyprus, Arabia and in Ethiopia and Sudan. Neither author made any specific assignment of Tunisian populations. However, Deleuil and Labbe (1955b) as well as Aellen and Strinati (1969) referred Tunisian material to *R. h. minimus*,--- not to named forms from the western edge of the Atlas Mountains in Morocco.

Panouse (1951) questioned the validity of the two subspecies named from Morocco, in part because of the limited sample available to Andersen and Laurent. The status of these names is further complicated: the type specimen of Laurent’s *R. h. vespa* appears to have been lost (see Hayman and Hill, 1971) and the published description is so incomplete that Panouse (1951) was uncertain that the description even applied to *Rhinolophus hipposideros*. Panouse thought that the description might apply to *Rhinolophus euryale*.

The question of subspecific name to be applied to Tunisian populations will remain until sufficient comparative material is available, especially from Morocco

and Algeria. Because of the absence of any evidence of the occurrence of this species in Libya or Egypt and because of the geographic probability of Tunisian populations being more closely related to the Moroccan populations than to the populations adjacent to the Red Sea in Kérén, Eritrea (the type locality of *R. h. minimus*), I arbitrarily refer Tunisian populations to Andersen's subspecies as follows:

Rhinolophus hipposideros escalerae Andersen, 1918

Rhinolophus hipposideros escalerae Andersen, Ann Mag. Nat. Hist., [9]2:378, 1918, type from Ha-ha, Mogador, Morocco; Allen, 1939.

Rhinolophus hipposideros minimus, Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b.

Rhinolophus hipposideros, Gadeau de Kerville, 1906.

Rhinolophus hipposideros hipposideros, Corbet, 1978.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 7, distributed as follows: Djebel Zaghouan, cave at Poste Optique.

Literature reports: Grotte de Kaloi, Aïn Draham (Gadeau de Kerville, 1906); Djebel Zaghouan (Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b); Mountains near Kasserine (Blanc, 1935).

Rhinolophus blasii Peters, 1866

Pack-saddle Horseshoe Bat

Diagnosis. In general appearance, this bat looks much like *R. ferrumequinum* and *R. hipposideros*; however, this species is intermediate in size and differs in the structure of the horseshoe and cranial details. The forearm ranges from 44 to 48 mm; the weight is about 7-8 g. It differs from the two following species (which are quite similar in size) in the structure of the wing and the noseleaf. In this species, the terminal segment (second phalanx) of the fourth digit is long (more than twice

the length of the first phalanx). In the following two species, this phalanx is less than twice the length of the first phalanx. Further, the sella is wedge-shaped, not parallel sided, and the occlusal surfaces of the second and third lower premolars are almost equal; the area of the first is not less than that of the second lower molar as in the next two species.

Distribution. The pack-saddle horseshoe bat occurs in scattered colonies in Italy, Sicily, coastal Greece, Yugoslavia, eastward into southwestern Asia. In Africa, it has been taken from Zambia, Malawi and eastern Congo northward into Somalia, Ethiopia and Egypt. In northwestern Africa, it has been reported from Morocco, Algeria and Tunisia (Fig. 3.9).

Biology. This bat was obtained from caves in the mountains of north Tunisia. In Algeria, it was mistnetted at the entrances of caves and above water (Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska, 1991). They reported *R. blasii* in mixed colonies with *Myotis emarginatus*, *Miniopterus schreibersi*, and *R. euryale*. They also found torpid individuals in mid May. Based on observations made in Rwanda (Anciaux de Faveaux, 1976), this species goes into hypothermia in dry season when food is scarce. Males of this species obtained from Tunisia showed the following measurements of testes: 3X2-4X2 in mid Jan., 3X2-4X2 in late Feb., 4X2-5X3 in late Apr., 3X1.5-4X3 in May, and 4X2-5X3 in Oct. Females obtained in mid Jan., late Feb., and Oct. showed no signs of reproductive activity.

Taxonomy. According to Ellerman and Morrison-Scott (1951), this species was reported from North Africa by Dobson (1878) but with no details. G. M. Allen (1939) also listed it without further comment. Hayman and Hill (1971) stated that the first authentic record for North Africa was that listed by Aellen (1955) from Morocco. The first record for Tunisia appears to be that of Aellen and Strinati (1969).

Figure 3.9 Distribution maps of the pack-saddle horseshoe bat, *Rhinolophus blasii* Peters, 1866.

Not enough is known about North African forms to make a meaningful judgment as to their taxonomic relationships. For the present, I refer the Tunisian material to the nominate race with the type locality in Italy.

Rhinolophus blasii blasii Peters, 1866

Rhinolophus clivosus Blasius, Säugeth. Deutschlands, p. 33, 1857, from Italy.

Sicily and Austria. (Not of Cretzschmar, 1828).

Rhinolophus blasii Peters, 1866 [new name for *clivosus* Blasius]; Corbet, 1978.

Rhinolophus blasii blasii, Aellen and Strinati, 1969; Aellen and Strinati, 1970.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 26, distributed as follows: Djebel Ressas mine, 28 km SE Tunis, 6; Djebel Zaghouan, mine, 3 km SE Zaghouan on road from Aïn Ayed, 20.

Literature reports: Grotte des Chauves-souris, El Haouaria (Aellen and Strinati, 1970).

Rhinolophus mehelyi Matschie, 1901

Mehely's Horseshoe Bat

Diagnosis. In general appearance, this bat is much like the three preceding species. It is slightly larger and differs somewhat in the structure of the noseleaf and skull. The forearm generally ranges from 47 to 50 mm; the weight is about 12 g. Figure 3.10 shows a typical individual of this species.

Distribution. Mehely's bat is known from scattered records in Europe (Portugal and France eastward, south of the Alps, to the Balkan Peninsula). In northern Africa, it has been recorded from Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia and, possibly, Egypt. In Tunisia, it has been taken in the northern areas (Fig. 3.11).

Biology. Six pregnant females were obtained by Cockrum et al. (in litt.) in May, 1975. All were carrying one embryo (3 embryos were near term). In June, 5

Figure 3.10. Mehely's horseshoe bat, *Rhinolophus mehelyi*. (drawing by Burhan Gharaibeh).

Figure 3. 11. Distribution of Mehely's horseshoe bat, *Rhinolophus mehelyi* Matschie, 1901.

females were found lactating. I found a nursing colony on 21 June, 1996 in Feija National Park HQ. There also were many subadults in that group. It seems that parturition occurs in late May. Specimens collected in October and November were not reproductively active.

The colonies that I saw were mixed *Miniopterus schreibersi*, *Myotis blythi* and *Myotis emarginatus*. One cave occupied by *Rhinolophus mehelyi* in one was extremely humid.

Taxonomy. As has been shown by Cockrum (1976b) the bat originally named as *R. euryale tuneti* by Deleuil and Labbe, is a specimen of this species. Furthermore, Cockrum (1976b) noted that the Tunisian populations differ enough from European populations in many morphometric measurements to warrant subspecific recognition. The Tunisian specimens had longer tails, longer ears, longer metacarpal in digit IV and shorter tibia. I follow Cockrum (1976b) and use the following name.

Rhinolophus mehelyi tuneti (Deleuil and Labbe, 1955)

Rhinolophus euryale tuneti Deleuil and Labbe, Bull. Soc. Sci. Nat. Tunisie, 8: 53, 1955, type from bat cave, El Haouaria, Cap Bon, Tunisia.

Rhinolophus mehelyi, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951; Kahmann, 1958; Aellen and Strinati, 1969; Aellen and Strinati, 1970.

Rhinolophus mehelyi tuneti, Cockrum, 1976. Neotype from 4 km NE El Haouaria, Tunisia (USNM no. 498998).

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 100, distributed as follows: Djebel Ichkeul, 25 km SW Bizerte, 1; 1.5 km NW El Haouaria (Cap Bon) at Roman Grottos, 11; 4 km NE El Haouaria at bat cave, 9; 2 km N El Haouaria, 6; mine at Ras Rajel cemetery, 6 km W Nefza (= 25 km E Tabarka), 11; Abandoned mine no. 7, near El Ouidane (Cap Bon, ca. 60 km E Tunis), 11; El Ouidane, ca. 11

km W on MC 27, 1; 3 km SE Menzel Temime on MC 27 in sand mine, 1; Djebel Ressas, mine 28 km SE Tunis, 1; Djebel Zaghouan, mine 3 km SE Zaghouan on road from Aïn Ayed, 12; Damoos Saïd in Jebel Serdj, Siliana governorate, 1; Ghar Kraiz, Testour delegation, Béja governorate, 5; Feija Park (HQ), Ghardimaou delegation, Jendouba governorate, 30;

Literature reports: Grottes du Djebel Achkeul [= Djebel Ichkeul] (Kahmann, 1958); Djebel Sidi bel Aboid, El Haouaria (Kahmann, 1958); Grotte des Chauve-souris, El Haouaria (Aellen and Strinati, 1970); Djebel Orbata, Gafsa (Kahmann, 1958).

Rhinolophus euryale Blasius, 1853

Mediterranean Horseshoe Bat

Diagnosis. *Rhinolophus euryale* and *R. mehelyi* are similar and both differ from *R. blasii* in the relative length of the second phalange of the fourth digit, the shape of the sides of the sella and the shape of the profile of the cranium, especially in the of parietal-occipital suture. Further, both have similar reductions in the size of the occlusal surface of the second lower premolar.

Compared to *R. mehelyi*, *R. euryale* is smaller, has gradually tapered borders on the posterior lance of the noseleaf (strongly concave in *mehelyi*), a shorter skull and a longer upper tooth row.

Distribution. The Mediterranean horseshoe bat occurs in Europe in the countries bordering the Mediterranean. In Africa, it has been recorded from Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia and Egypt (Fig. 3.12).

Biology. Deleuil and Labbe (1955) found active individuals in caves of El Haouaria and between Testour and El Aroussa in May and September. They also

Figure 3.12. Distribution maps of the Mediterranean horseshoe bat, *Rhinolophus euryale* Blasius, 1853.

found that it becomes rare in November and December and they speculated that it probably migrates during winter.

Taxonomy. There appears to have been confusion in past reports between *R. euryale* and *R. mehelyi* taken from Tunisia (Cockrum et al., in litt.). The descriptions of *R. euryale* seem to apply to *R. mehelyi*. Thus, there is probability that some of *R. euryale* reports actually represent *R. mehelyi*. I mapped all reports together on one map but shaded the questionable ones differently and with question marks.

Rhinolophus euryale barbarus Andersen and Matschie, 1904

[*Rhinolophus*] *Euryalus barbarus* Andersen and Matschie, Sitzb. Ges. Naturf.

Freunde Berlin, p. 79, 1904, type from Tangier, Morocco.

Rhinolophus euryale barbarus, Allen, 1939; Laurent, 1937; Ellerman and

Morrison-Scott, 1951; Aellen and Strinati, 1969; Aellen and Strinati, 1970.

Rhinolophus euryale, Trouessart, 1906; Gadeau de Kerville, 1908.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 4, distributed as follows:
abandoned kohl mine, 5 km NE Aïn Draham, 4.

Literature reports: Grotte near Tebourba (Andersen and Matschie, 1904; Blanc, 1935; Laurent, 1937); Grotte du Djebel Gloub, 10 km W Fernana (Trouessart, 1906; Gadeau de Kerville, 1908).

The following literature records probably refer to some other species--most likely *Rhinolophus mehelyi*. They are plotted on the map with question marks (Fig. 3.12). Djebel Ichkeul, near Mateur (Blanc, 1935; Laurent, 1937); El Haouaria (Deleuil and Labbe, 1955); Djebel Cheid, between Testour and El Aroussa (Deleuil and Labbe, 1955); Djebel Zaghouan (Blanc, 1935); Grotte du Cheval, Zaghouan (Aellen and Strinati, 1970); Gafsa (Blanc, 1935; Laurent, 1937).

Asellia tridens (É. Geoffroy, 1813)

Trident Leaf-nosed Bat

Diagnosis. This bat has large, almost hairless ears, a short interfemoral membrane with the tail extending 5-6 mm beyond its posterior edge, and a unique leafnose consisting of a basal horseshoe portion, central triangular portion and a posterior portion that is deeply emarginate, resulting in three vertical prong-like structures.

Distribution. In Tunisia, this species has been recorded only from the central, semiarid portion of the country (Fig. 3.13).

Biology. The trident bat is locally abundant. A colony observed by Cockrum et al. (in litt.) in the underground aqueduct providing water for the STIL date grove north of Tozeur contained several thousand individuals. These bats left their roost at dusk and flew low to the ground. Their feeding flights were in among bushes that were more than a meter in height. One was captured in a mouse trap that had been set on the ground.

Fourteen of the 16 females taken from a roost near Redeyef on 27 May each contained a single embryo. Crown-rump length ranged from 7 to 16 mm in crown-rump lengths.

Taxonomy. Kock (1969) and Koch-Weser (1984) contend that the named forms from Morocco and Algeria are synonyms of *A. t. murraiana* Anderson 1881, from Western India. They did recognize *A. t. tridens* of É. Geoffroy (type locality in Egypt) as being distinct. They presented the two subspecies as having a widely sympatric distribution in North Africa.

Owen and Qumsiyeh (1987) conducted a multivariate analysis of 153 specimens from many parts of the range of the species. They found that the samples formed two clusters, one including the specimens from the central range of the

Figure 3.13. Distribution maps of the Trident bat, *Asellia tridens* (É. Geoffroy, 1813).

species: Algeria, Tunisia, Chad, Sudan, Yemen and Egypt. The second cluster contained the material from the eastern and western parts of the range. This included material from Mauritania and western Morocco (to the west) and from Palestine, Yemen, Iraq, Iran, Afghanistan and Pakistan to the east. Owen and Qumsiyeh (1987) were critical of past workers because they pooled data from males and females or used univariate statistical analyses. They concluded that the western and eastern populations (group A) were morphologically indistinct and were different from the second, geographically intervening group (group B).

Furthermore, they concluded that *Asellia tridens diluta* Andersen, 1918 was indistinguishable from *Asellia tridens tridens* (É Geoffroy, 1813). An examination of the size, sexual make up and geographic origin of their samples lead me to doubt their conclusion concerning the “western” group of their cluster. Whereas males and females were analyzed separately, the sample sizes are further reduced. The “western” members of group A (Morocco and Mauritania) consist of 41 males (39 from one site in Morocco and 2 from Mauritania) and 1 female (from Mauritania). Can a sample of one [i.e. the “western” female] give a statistically meaningful result, no matter how sophisticated the statistical analysis? There was no explanation for the lack of morphologic difference “homomorphism” between two populations of one subspecies that are at least 4,500 km apart interspersed by the other subspecies. The Tunisian material is assigned the following name until further investigations:

Asellia tridens tridens (É. Geoffroy, 1813)

Asellia tridens tridens É. Geoffroy, Ann. Mus. d’Hist. Nat. Paris, 20: 265. type from Egypt, 1813; ; Allen, 1939; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951; Owen and Qumsiyeh, 1987;

Asellia tridens diluta. Aellen and Strinati, 1969.

Asellia tridens murraiana, Kock, 1969; Koch-Weser, 1984.

P[hyllorhina]. tridens, Lataste, 1887.

Hipposideros tridens, Trouessart, 1905.

Phyllorhina tridens, Lataste, 1885.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 66, distributed as follows: 4 km S Redeyef on road to Aïoun Ameur, 13 ; M'Dilla, abandoned phosphate mine, 20 km S Gafsa, 6; 12 km N Tozeur on GP 3 in underground aqueduct, 46; 12 km N. Tozeur on GP 3 in STIL date grove, 1.

Literature reports: El-Hamma de Gabès, territory of Beni Zid (Lataste, 1887; repeated by Laurent, 1937, as Gabès). Specimens examined by Owen and Qumsiyeh (1987) are from 4 km S Redeyef and 12 km N Tozeur housed at TTU (above).

Family Vespertilionidae

Plain-nosed Bats

In Tunisia, six genera of this family have been recorded.

Key for Family Vespertilionidae

1. In third digit, second phalanx about 3 times length of first; skull high and rounded, with braincase rising abruptly from rostrum*Miniopterus*
- 1'. In third digit, second phalanx subequal to first; brain-case not markedly inflated2
- 2(1'). Ears joined at base, extremely long (almost as long as forearm); five upper and six lower cheek teeth (dental formula $\frac{2}{3} \frac{1}{1} \frac{2}{3} \frac{3}{3}$)*Plecotus*
- 2'. Ears not joined at base, generally short, and never much more than half the length of the forearm; cheek teeth varied in number but never $\frac{5}{6}$ 3

- 3(2'). Ears more than half length of forearm; one upper incisor (dental formula $\frac{1}{3} \frac{1}{1} \frac{1}{2} \frac{3}{3}$) *Otonycteris*
- 3'. Ears less than half the length of forearm; two upper incisors4
- 4(3'). Tragus high and pointed; six upper and six lower cheek teeth (dental formula $\frac{2}{3} \frac{1}{1} \frac{3}{3} \frac{3}{3}$) *Myotis*
- 4'. Tragus short and rounded; fewer than six upper and six lower cheek teeth5
- 5(4'). Length of forearm more than 45 mm; four upper cheek teeth (dental formula $\frac{2}{3} \frac{1}{1} \frac{1}{2} \frac{3}{3}$) *Eptesicus*
- 5'. Length of forearm less than 45 mm; five upper cheek teeth (dental formula $\frac{2}{3} \frac{1}{1} \frac{2}{2} \frac{3}{3}$) *Pipistrellus*

Genus *Myotis* Kaup, 1829

To date three species of this genus have been recorded from Tunisia.

Key for Genus *Myotis*.

1. Size large; forearm more than 53 mm; condylobasal length more than 18.6 mm; upper tooth row more than 8.2 mm *Myotis blythii*
- 1'. Size smaller; forearm less than 52 mm; condylobasal length less than 18.6 mm; upper tooth row less than 8.2 mm2
- 2(1'). Posterior margin of ear with deep, angular emargination; forearm more than 36 mm; condylobasal length more than 14.0 mm *Myotis emarginatus*
- 2'. Posterior margin of ear with shallow, inconspicuous emargination; forearm less than 36 mm; condylobasal length less than 14.0 mm *Myotis capaccinii*

Myotis blythi (Tomes, 1857)

Lesser Mouse-eared Bat

Diagnosis. This is the largest bat in Tunisia. The greater horseshoe bat is the only other bat that approaches this size. The total length is about 125 mm, of which the tail comprised almost 50 mm. The ears are about 25 mm high. Weights range from 18 to 22 g.

Distribution. Lesser mouse-eared bats occur from southern Europe eastward through much of Asia. In Africa, they are only known from Morocco, Algeria and Tunisia. In Tunisia, they are found only in the northern and central regions (Fig. 3.14).

Biology. Cockrum et al. (in litt.) took *Myotis blythi* from caves, mines and cavernous buildings only during the warmer seasons. They found none in hibernation. I collected active bats from day roosts in various caves during May-June, 1996. Seasonal separation of the sexes is common. As early as 1906 Gadeau de Kerville reported that, during May, he captured only males in a cave near Ain Draham, because "the sexes are separate at that time of the year." Cockrum et al. (in litt.) took pregnant females as well as adult males from a warm mine tunnel near Nefza on 11 May 1975. At that time, the single embryo in each of three females ranged from 17 to 21 mm in crown-rump length. Other pregnant females were taken on 4 May, 12 May and on 7 June at El Haouaria. Lactating females and new born young were also present on the latter date.

Taxonomy. As has been pointed out by others (e.g. Hayman and Hill, 1971) the relationships of the North African populations of large *Myotis* are not well understood. They have been variously assigned to *Myotis myotis* and *Myotis blythi*. I follow most recent authors in assigning them to *Myotis blythi*.

Figure 3.14. Distribution maps of the lesser mouse-eared bat, *Myotis blythi* (Tomes, 1857).

Myotis blythi oxygnathus (Monticelli, 1885)

Vespertilio oxygnathus Monticelli. Accad. O. Costa de Aspir. Nar.. Napoli,
1(1):82. 1885, type from Matera, Basilacita, Italy.

Myotis blythi oxygnathus, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951; Aellen and Strinati,
1969; Aellen and Strinati, 1970; Hayman and Hill, 1971; Corbet, 1978.

Vespertilio murinus, Lataste, 1887.

Myotis murinus, Trouessart, 1905; Blanc, 1935.

Myotis myotis murinus, Trouessart, 1906.

Myotis oxygnathus, Allen, 1939.

Myotis myotis oxygnathus, Deleuil and Labbe, 1955; Wandeler, 1965.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 233, distributed as follows:

Cistern at Utica (= Utique), 3; mine tunnel near Sidi Messaoud. Djebel Ichkeul, 25
km SW Bizerte, 1; 1.5 km NW El Haouaria (Cap Bon) at Roman Grottos, 3; 4 km
NE El Haouaria at bat cave, 8; 2 km N El Haouaria, 3; Ras Rajel cemetery. 6 km W
Nefza (25 km E Tabarka, 4; El Ouidiane, abandoned coal mine no. 7, ca 60 km E
Tunis, 2; 3 km SE Menzel Temime of MC 27 in sand mine, 1; Entouna mine, 23.5
km SE Tunis on GP 1, 2 km W highway, 9; Djebel Ressas, cement irrigation pool.
28 km SE Tunis, 1; Djebel Ressas, mine, 28 km SE Tunis, 14; Bulla Regia,
Roman Palais d'Amphitriete, 7 km NNW Jendouba, 6; Bulla Regia, 7 km NNW
Jendouba (formerly Souk el Arba), 1; Roman theater at Chemtou, 17 km W
Jendouba, 3; mine tunnel at Hemam Djedidi, 20 km E Zaghouan, 1; Djebel
Zaghouan, mine 3 km SE Zaghouan on road to Aïn Ayed, 8; Djebel Zaghouan,
mine Sioutayea, 1 km E Zaghouan on MC 133, 1 km S highway, 4; Djebel
Zaghouan, cave at Poste Optique, 2; Scarna mine, 10 km NE Rohia (60 km N
Sbeitla), 5; mine. Djebel Trozza, 50 km WSW Kairouan, 3; pool 4 km NW GP 3

on MC 77, 40 km NE Sbeitla, 7; under large baths at Maktar ruins, 6; 3 km NW Toujane on MC 104, 45 km S Gabès, 9.

Literature reports: (All Deleuil and Labbe, 1955, unless otherwise indicated). Cave in Djebel Aboid in Nefzas (= Nefza); Cistern at Utica ruins; Cave in Djebel Ischkeul (Blanc, 1935); Cave in Djebel Gloub [not found] (Gadeau de Kerville, 1906); Feriana (Lataste, 1887); Cave near Tebourba (Blanc, 1935); El Haouaria Cave; Mine at Djebel Ressas; Kef-el-Agab Cave, 4 km WNW Souk-el-Arba [= Jendouba], (Aellen and Strinati, 1969); Djebel Gattuna near Hammam-el-Lif (Lataste, 1887); cave region of Testour-El Aroussa; caves at Djebel Zaghouan; mine at El Akhouat, near Gafour; la Grotte de Gafsa (Lataste, 1887); Nefta (Wandeler, 1965); Djebel Saikra, near Mednine.

Myotis capaccinii (Bonaparte, 1837)

Long-fingered Bat

Diagnosis. This small version of the mouse-eared bat has a forearm that is 40 to 43 mm in length and weighs 8 to 10 g. The hind foot (13-14 mm) is large in relation to that of the tibia.

Distribution. In Europe, this species occurs from southern Spain, Corsica, Sardinia, eastward to Greece and Cyprus. In Africa, it has been recorded only from Morocco, Algeria and Tunisia. In Tunisia, it has been recorded from only a single locality (Vaughan et al., 1977). Figure 3.15 shows the distribution of this species in Tunisia and North Africa.

Biology. This species was taken three times at a mine in Djebel Ressas. On 7 August 6 males and 11 females were taken; on 23 August 1974, 7 males and 5 females; and on 8 May 1975, 23 males were taken. It appears probable that during May the females had moved to a warmer situation to establish a maternity colony.

Figure 3.15. Distribution maps of the long-fingered bat, *Myotis capaccinii* (Bonaparte, 1837).

Taxonomy. No subspecific name has been assigned for the Maghrebian specimens. Absence of comparative material from Africa and the proximity to Sicily lead me to assign the subspecies to the nominate as below.

Myotis capaccinii capaccinii (Bonaparte, 1837)

Vespertilio capaccinii Bonaparte, Iconogr. Fauna Ital., 1: Mamm., pt. 20 and fig. 2, 1837, type from Sicily, Italy.

Myotis capaccinii, Allen, 1939; Corbet, 1978.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 23, distributed as follows: Djebel Ressay mine, 28 km SE Tunis.

Myotis emarginatus (É. Geoffroy, 1806)

Geoffroy's Bat

Diagnosis. This tiny version of the mouse-eared bat has the distinctive color of reddish-brown. Its forearm is about 38 mm, its weight is about 7.5 g, and its hind foot (11 mm) are short in relation to the length of the tibia. The ears are dark, elongated and markedly emarginated posteriorly. Hind feet digits have golden-brown and dark claws.

Distribution. This species occurs in Europe from Belgium southeastward to Italy and Greece and eastward into Asia. An isolated population has been reported from Portugal. In Africa, it is known from Morocco, Algeria and Tunisia (Fig. 3.16). In Tunisia, it is known only from the specimens taken by Vaughan et al. (1977). Prior to their capture, it was known in Africa from one old record from Algeria (see Lataste, 1885) and a 1956 taking of breeding females in Morocco (Brosset, 1958).

Biology. The specimens obtained June 19, 1996 had a female carrying one embryo (no CR measurements). These were collected from a day roost in the attic

Figure 3.16. Distribution maps of Geoffroy's bat, *Myotis emarginatus* (É. Geoffroy, 1806).

of the a room in the Feija National Park Headquarters. Two to three hundred bats in a mixed nursing colony of *Rhinolophus mehelyi* and *Myotis emarginatus* (the majority were *R. mehelyi*) were roosting and all were active. Both species had many juveniles; some were still attached to their mother's teat. The guano in the attic was more than a foot thick in some areas which means that this roost has been used for a long time.

Table 3.1 lists selected external measurements for *Myotis emarginatus* from 3 different localities in Tunisia, and from Algeria.

Table 3.1. External measurements for *Myotis emarginatus* from different sites in Tunisia (mm). Number of specimens measured in this study =3.

Locality	Total	Tail	Hind Foot	Ear	Forearm	Weight (g)	Resource
Djebel Oust	91(90-91)	41(40-42)	11.3(11-12)	17(17)	39.4(38-40)	7.67(7.0-8.0)	Vaughan et al. (1977)
Djebel Zaghouan	98.8(97-101)	42.8(41-45)	11.0(11)	17.5(17-18)	40.2(39-41)	7.72(7.2-8.0)	Vaughan et al. (1977)
Feija National Park	92.3(90-95)	41.6(40-42)	10(10-10)	13(10-15)	40.0(40-40)	7.7(7.0-11.0)	This study
Algeria:	93.1(88-101)	44.3(42-47)	10.0(9.5-10.5)	16.3(14-18)	41.4(39-43)	9.2(8.0-10.5)	Kowlaski & Rzebik-Kowlaska (1991)
Females	86.2(76-96)	40.5(32-46)	9.6(9-10)	15.9(15-17)	39.3(35.5-41)	5.0(7.0-8.0)	
Males							

Taxonomy. Four subspecies are currently recognized, one in Europe and three in Asia. Lack of adequate comparative materials caused me to provisionally refer the Tunisian material to the European subspecies.

Myotis emarginatus emarginatus

(É. Geoffroy, 1806)

Vespertilio emarginatus É. Geoffroy, Ann. Mus. Hist. Nat., Paris, 8:198, 1806,

type from Charlemont, Givet, Ardennes, France.

Myotis emarginatus, Corbet, 1978.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 12, distributed as follows: Djebel Zaghouan, cave at Poste Optique, 2; Djebel Oust, 6 km S Oum Djeddour, 28 km E Thala (cave), 2; Feija National Park (HQ), Ghardimaou delegation, Jendouba governorate, 8.

Literature reports: Djebel Zaghouan, cave at Poste Optique; Djebel Oust, 6 km S Oum Djeddour, 28 km E Thala, cave (Vaughan et al., 1977).

Genus *Eptesicus* Rafinesque, 1820

Some 15 species of this genus have been recorded from Africa, only one of which has been found in Tunisia.

Eptesicus serotinus (Schreber, 1774). Serotine

Diagnosis. This plain-nosed bat is almost as large as the lesser mouse-eared bat, from which it differs in having much smaller ears and tragi. The tragus is blunt, not sharply pointed as in *Myotis*.

Distribution. In Europe, this species occurs from Portugal and southern England eastward into Russia and southward into the Middle East. In Africa, it occurs in Morocco, Algeria and the central and northern parts of Tunisia (Fig. 3.17).

Biology. The one specimen I collected in May, 1996 was caught in a mist net strung in a clump of *Eucalyptus* trees irrigated by a spring (Oued Cherchera). Several specimens were seen flying among the trees that evening.

Taxonomy. Hayman and Hill (1971) assigned North African serotines to the following subspecies. However, considerable variation in color and size is evident

Figure 3.17. Distribution maps of the serotine, *Eptesicus serotinus* (Schreber, 1774).

in the material with montane samples being much darker and larger than those from low elevations or deserts.

Eptesicus serotinus isabellinus (Temminck, 1840)

Vespertilio isabellinus Temminck, Monogr. de Mammalogie, 2: 205, plate 52, figs. 1 and 2, 1840, type from environs of Tripoli, Libya.

Eptesicus serotinus isabellinus, Allen, 1939; Aellen and Strinati, 1969; Hayman and Hill, 1971; Corbet, 1978.

Vespertilio serotinus isabellinus, Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905.

Eptesicus isabellinus, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951; Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 20, distributed as follows: Bou Hedma National Park, HQ (34° 28' 34" N 09° 39' 01" E), Mazouna delegation, Sidi Bou Zid governorate, 1; Djebel Zaghouan, 4 km W Post Optique (small reservoir), 5; Djebel Ressas, cement irrigation pool, 28 km SE Tunis, 1; Djebel Ressas, mine, 28 km SE Tunis, 1; 4 km NW GP 3 on MC 77, 40 km NE Sbeitla (pool), 7; 4 km S Redeyef on road to Aïoun Ameur, 2; Tatahouine, 3.

Literature reports: Tunis (Lataste, 1887); region of Tozeur (Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b).

Genus *Pipistrellus* Kaup, 1829

Three species of this genus have been taken in Tunisia.

Key for Genus *Pipistrellus*

1. Tragus wide, greatest width equal to half of length of anterior border
.....*Pipistrellus savii*
- 1'. Tragus narrow, greatest width much less than half of length of anterior border2

2(1'). Size larger, forearm greater than 32 mm; wing generally with narrow to wide white posterior border; outer upper incisor less than half of the height of the inner*Pipistrellus kuhli*

2'. Size smaller, forearm less than 30; wing generally without white border; outer upper incisor more than half the height of inner*Pipistrellus pipistrellus*

Pipistrellus kuhli (Natterer, 1817)

Kuhl's Pipistrelle

Diagnosis. Both this species and *P. pipistrellus* have the white-yellowish margin on posterior of wing. However, this species can be distinguished from *P. pipistrellus* by being, generally, larger in size and having lighter fur.

Distribution. In Europe, this species is restricted to the countries bordering the Mediterranean. Its distribution in Africa is documented poorly but it probably occurs throughout most of the continent. In Tunisia, it is common in the northern and central areas (Fig. 3.18).

Biology. Deleuil and Labbe (1955a) reported that 3 of 10 females taken on 21 July 1955 at l'Ecole d'El Hamain were lactating. This is all that has been recorded concerning the natural history of this common, widely distributed species in Tunisia.

During their stay in Tunisia, Cockrum et al. (in litt.) noted repeatedly that this pipistrelle was the first bat to fly during the evening. Routinely, in Khereddine and Le Krem, they became active shortly after sundown. Often several dozen would be in sight at one time, fluttering over and between buildings, obviously feeding on flying insects. Day roost appeared to be under the roof tiles of the buildings. I collected 4 specimens that were roosting between bricks supporting a corrugated tin

Figure 3.18. Distribution maps of Kuhl's pipistrelle, *Pipistrellus kuhli* (Natterer, 1817).

roof in Aïn Jammalah Pépinière Forestière. Temperatures were intolerably high near the ceiling and the crevice they were squeezed in was extremely small.

Pipistrellus kuhli seems to be active during every month of the year. It was not seen active, though, on rainy, cold evenings. It was observed to emerge in mid-afternoon (Cockrum et al., in litt.) on a warm day that was preceded by several days of cold, wet conditions. For example, on 2 March 1975, at Khereddine, several dozen pipistrelles were in flight, obviously feeding at about 3:15 p.m. This feeding flight lasted for about 45 minutes. Although several kinds of birds were also active during this same time, no intraspecific interactions were seen.

Most pipistrelles examined in this study were taken from day roosts: under roof tiles (Tunis, Khereddine; Aïn Jammalah Pépinière, TebourSouk), in crevices in buildings (Oudna, Grombalia, Chemtou, Nefta), and in a bird house (Grombalia). Some were taken in mist nets over water as the bats came to drink. A few were shot as they were on early evening feeding flights.

Deleuil and Labbe (1955a) reported that 65 females and 2 males were taken from under roof tiles of an out building at El Hamain school on 22 May 1955. On 21 July at the same site 10 lactating females were taken. None were present during the winter, between October and April.

Two young per litter and one litter per year appeared to be normal. Young are probably born in late May and early June. Of 15 females taken by Cockrum et al. (in litt.) near Nefta on 25 April 1973, 12 had 2 embryos each and 3 had single embryos. A female taken 28 May contained two near-term embryos. Three females taken 4 June were lactating.

Taxonomy. Morphological variations exist in cranial and morphological features of this species (Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska, 1991; Qumsiyeh, 1985). As early as 1887, Lataste commented that pelage color is very pale in the desert and

dark, even blackish, in the mountains. The wings, he noted, appeared to always be edged with a white band that is narrowest in the dark forms and widest in the pale forms. Thomas (1902) named a new species from the Sahara in Libya as *Pipistrellus deserti*. Still known only from the type, it was described as a "small, buff-colored desert ally of *P. kuhli*." Probably, as suggested by some modern taxonomists, this is a recognizable subspecies of *P. kuhli*.

Heim de Balsac (1936) recorded, from Aszdjers (Djanet, Algeria) a specimen that he reported as the second known record of *Pipistrellus deserti* Thomas. It was described as being much like *P. kuhli*, but lighter in color. Curiously he also described in the same paper, a new subspecies, *Pipistrellus kuhli pallidus*. Its description, minimal, indicates that a lighter color was diagnostic. Unfortunately it was not compared to *P. deserti*.

Deleuil and Labbe (1955a) commented that the local variability in this species was so great, with both light and dark colored individuals in the same area, that separation into subspecies was unwarranted. Equally variable, according to their findings, were the width of the white edging on the wings and forearm length.

Aellen and Strinati (1969), in their review of Tunisian bats, concluded that northern populations were referable to *P. k. kuhli* and that southern populations (from Zarzis, Djerba, Tatahouine, Redeyef and Moularès) were referable to *P. k. pallidus*. They listed *Pipistrellus albolimbatus* Kuster, 1835 from the center and north, as synonymous with *P. kuhli kuhli*. *P. albolimbatus* of authors was considered as synonymous with *P. k. pallidus*.

Examination of 59 specimens at TTU lead me to agree with the views of Deleuil and Labbe (1955a)--variation within a given population is so great that it obscures geographic variability. A sample of 15 females, all adults with embryos, were taken from a maternity colony in the memorial building of Sidi Hassen Ayed

(4.5 km S Nefta) on 25 April 1973 illustrates these findings. Head and body length vary from 45 to 56 mm (average, 49.8); forearm lengths, 31.6 to 34.1 mm (average, 32.2). Colors vary from very light to almost as dark as any taken in northern Tunisia. The width of the white edging of the wing membrane varied, being widest in the lightest colored individuals.

Although some tendency toward lighter color is evident in southern populations, I herein choose to refer all Tunisian material to a single subspecies. The use of a name from Europe is provisional. Future studies, with additional specimens available, will probably show that North African and European populations differ sufficiently to be considered as distinct subspecies. Harrison (1964) argued that gradations (in color, but other features not evaluated) between dark European and light Arabian populations were so gradual that no geographic races could be defined.

Pipistrellus kuhli kuhli (Natterer, 1817)

Vespertilio kuhli Natterer, in Kuhl, Deutschen Fledermausen, Ann. Wetterau. Ges. Naturk., p. 55, 1817, type from Trieste, Italian-Yugoslavian border; Blanc, 1935.

Pipistrellus kuhli, Thomas, 1902a; Vesmanis, 1972; Corbet, 1978; Beaucournu et al., 1983.

Vespertugo kuhli, Dobson, 1878; Lataste, 1887; Anderson, 1892; Olivier, 1896.

Pipistrellus kuhli kuhli, Allen, 1939; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951; Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b; Aellen and Strinati, 1969; Hayman and Hill, 1970.

Vespertilio marginatus, Fitzinger, 1870.

Vespertilio [kuhli] albolimbatus, Blanc, 1935.

Pipistrellus kuhli albolimbatus, Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b.

[*Pipistrellus kuhli*] *pallidus*, Aellen and Strinati, 1969.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 20, distributed as follows:
Tunis, Kherredine, 1; Sidi Mansour, Tunis area, 1; 10 km W Grombalia on MC
34, 1; 1 km SE Oudna Station, 2; Djebel Rerras, cement irrigation pool, 28 km SE
Tunis, 1; Roman theater at Chemtou, 17 km W Jendouba, 2; 4 km NW of GP 3 on
MC 7, 49 km NE Sbeitla, 2; 4 km NW GP3 on MC 7 near Hadjeb el Aioun, 1;
Tamerza oasis, 1; Memorial building of Sidi Hassen Ayed, 4.5 km S Nefta, 7;
Tatahouine, 1.

Literature reports: Ile de Galite (Vesmanis, 1972); “very common at Tunis, in
the suburbs and on the plains near the villages in Medjerdah and the Mornag”
(Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b, but see Aellen and Strinati, 1969); Sidi Daoud [N coast
of Cap Bon] (Deleuil and Labbe, 1955a; Aellen and Strinati, 1969); region of
Massicault [= near Djedeida] (Deleuil and Labbe, 1955a; Aellen and Strinati, 1969);
El Bathan (Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b; Aellen and Strinati, 1969); Tunis (Dobson,
1878; Olivier, 1896; Deleuil and Labbe, 1955a; Aellen and Strinati, 1969;
Vesmanis, 1972); Mégrine [= Tunis] (Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b; Aellen and
Strinati, 1969); Dubosville [= Tunis] (Deleuil and Labbe, 1955a+b; Aellen and
Strinati, 1969); School at El Hamain [region of Medjez el Bab] (Deleuil and Labbe,
1955b; Aellen and Strinati, 1969); Bulla Regia (Deleuil and Labbe, 1955a; Aellen
and Strinati, 1969); Carthago bei Tunis (Vesmanis, 1972); Mornag (Deleuil and
Labbe, 1955a; Aellen and Strinati, 1969); Sousse (Olivier, 1896; Aellen and
Strinati, 1969); Kairouan (Olivier, 1896; Aellen and Strinati, 1969); Region of Aïn
Moularès (Deleuil and Labbe, 1955a; Aellen and Strinati, 1969); Redeyef (Deleuil
and Labbe, 1955a; Aellen and Strinati, 1969); region of the Chotts (Lataste, 1887;
Aellen and Strinati, 1969); El-Hamma de Gabès (Beni Zid) (Lataste, 1887; Aellen
and Strinati, 1969); Gabès (Aellen, 1957; Aellen and Strinati, 1969); Djerba (Blanc,
1935; Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b; Aellen and Strinati, 1969); Zarzis (Blanc, 1935;

Aellen and Strinati, 1969); crevice near Ksar Haddada, NW of Tatahouine (Beaucournu, et al., 1983); Tatahouine (Blanc, 1935; Aellen and Strinati, 1969); Douirat (Anderson, 1892; Aellen and Strinati, 1969); Kebili, S Tunesien (Vesmanis, 1972).

Pipistrellus pipistrellus Schreber, 1774

Common Pipistrelle

Diagnosis. This is the smallest pipistrelle in Tunisia. It is distinguished from *P. kuhli* by its smaller size and darker (dark brown) pelage.

Distribution. This species occurs from Norway, Ireland and Spain eastward into Asia and Asia Minor. It has also been recorded from North Africa (Morocco, Algeria and Tunisia). From Tunisia it has been recorded with certainty only from the Djebel Ressas region (Fig. 3.19).

Biology. Only limited sample from Tunisia is available and thus no significant data on this mammal's biology can be listed at this time.

Taxonomy. Galli-Valerio (1911) reported as *P. pipistrellus*, a bat from Adjim, Djerba in a paper concerned with parasites. As far as can be determined, the bat was never preserved so that its identification cannot be confirmed. Aellen and Strinati (1969) reported that *Pipistrellus pipistrellus* was not known to occur in Tunisia. They thought it highly probable that Galli-Valerio's report was a misidentification.

During their study in Tunisia, Vaughan et al. (1977) took *P. pipistrellus* from one northern site. The status of the Djerba record is still doubtful. It may well be that this species is a northern montane form that does not occur as far south as the island of Djerba.

Figure 3.19. Distribution maps of the common pipistrelle, *Pipistrellus pipistrellus* Schreber, 1774.

The taxonomic relations of North African populations are uncertain. I follow Aellen and Strinati (1969) in applying *P. p. mediterraneus* Cabrera, 1904 to North African populations. Corbet assigned the name *P. p. pipistrellus* for bats from "N. Africa" and believed this subspecies probably included *mediterraneus*.

Pipistrellus pipistrellus mediterraneus Cabrera, 1904

Pipistrellus mediterraneus Cabrera, Esp. Hist. Nat., Madrid, 2:273, 1904, type from Valencia, Spain.

Pipistrellus pipistrellus mediterraneus, Allen and Strinati, 1969.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 3, distributed as follows: Djebel Ressas, mine, 28 km SE Tunis, 1; Djebel Ressas, cement irrigation pool, 28 km SE Tunis, 1.

Literature reports: Adjim, Island of Djerba (Galli-Valerio, 1911); Djebel Ressas, mine, 28 km SE Tunis (Vaughan et al., 1977).

Pipistrellus savii (Bonaparte, 1837)

Savi's Pipistrelle

Diagnosis. This is a relatively robust pipistrelle and is distinguished by the membrane not having a white margin.

Distribution. This species occurs in Europe, Asia, and, in North Africa, from Tunisia to Morocco (Fig. 3.20). In Tunisia, they were reported only from Djebel Zaghouan (Vaughan et al., 1977).

Biology. Three males collected from Djebel Zaghouan were mist-netted over a small pond. No other data is available on this species in Tunisia. Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska (1991) collected this species from high altitudes in Algeria. Selected measurements are listed in Vaughan et al. (1977).

Figure 3.20. Distribution maps of Savi's pipistrelle, *Pipistrellus savii* (Bonaparte, 1837).

Taxonomy. In the absence of adequate records and comparative material, I follow Hill (1964) in referring North African populations to the following subspecies. The three specimens reported by Vaughan et al. (1977) were the first records for the country.

Pipistrellus savii ochromixus (Cabrera, 1904)

Vespertilio ochromixus Cabrera, Mem. Soc. Esp. Hist. Nat., Madrid, 2:267, 1904,

type from Sierra de Guadarrama, Madrid, Spain.

Pipistrellus savii ochromixus, Hill, 1964.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 3, distributed as follows: Djebel Zaghuan, 4 km W Poste Optique.

Genus *Otonycteris* Peters, 1859

This monotypic genus is restricted to semiarid and arid areas from the Middle East westward, across the northern Sahara, to Algeria. It is relatively secretive in its habits and has not been taken in large numbers anywhere.

Otonycteris hemprichii Peters, 1859

Hemprich's Long-eared Bat

Diagnosis. Hemprich's long-eared bat is a relatively large vespertilionid. It is often confused with *Plecotus* (long-eared bats) because of its long prominent ears with rounded tips and long tragus. Unlike those of *Plecotus*, ears of *O. hemprichii* are not joined at the forehead. Furthermore, the tragus in the latter species lacks the nodules at its base (see Gharaibeh and Qumsiyeh, 1995 for other details).

Distribution. *Otonycteris hemprichii* is distributed from Morocco, north Niger, Algeria and Tunisia, east to Iran and northern Pakistan into Uzbekistan, and Tajikistan (Gharaibeh and Qumsiyeh, 1995). It has been taken from three locations

in Tunisia (Fig. 3.21). None were taken during this study. Beaucournu et al. (1983) took one in the twilight portion of a shallow crevice in January or February, 1980.

Biology. Little information is available on the biology of this bat. The available information over its range was summarized by Gharaibeh and Qumsiyeh (1995). Anciaux de Faveaux (1984) listed a parasite reported from *Otonycteris hemprichii* in Tunisia.

Taxonomy. According to Koopman (1993), this is a distinct genus that has no obvious relationship to other vespertilionid species. However, many authors (summarized in Gharaibeh and Qumsiyeh, 1995) presented chromosomal and morphometric data that suggested close relationship to members of the tribe Plecotini (*Plecotus* and *Barbastella*). *Otonycteris* is monotypic.

Otonycteris hemprichi hemprichi Peters, 1859

Otonycteris hemprichii Peters, Monatsb. K. Preuss. Akad. Wiss., Berlin, p. 223.

1859, no locality given but according to Ellerman and Morrison-Scott (1951:180) probably from some part of northeastern Africa; Kock (1969) restricted it to the Nile Valley in southern Egypt-Northern Province, Sudan area, where Hemprich and Ehrenberg collected; Deleuil, 1957.

Otonycteris hemprichi hemprichi, Aellen and Strinati, 1969.

Otonycteris h[emprichi]. hemprichii, Corbet, 1978.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: Redeyef (Deleuil, 1957); Sfax (Fain, 1959); Crevice near Ksar Haddada, NW of Tatahouine (Beaucournu et al., 1983).

Figure 3.21. Distribution maps of Hemprich's long-eared bat, *Otonycteris hemprichi* Peters, 1859.

Genus *Plecotus* Geoffroy, 1818

Only one species of this genus is known from Africa. As mentioned above this bat is similar to *Otonycteris hemprichii* in having noticeably long ears.

Plecotus austriacus (Fischer, 1829)

Gray Long-eared Bat

Diagnosis. This bat was confused for a long time with *Plecotus auritus*, especially where the two species occur together in southern Europe. It has been distinguished, however, by using a suite of morphometric measurements including (Van Bree and Dulic, 1963).

Distribution. This species occurs in Europe, only rarely, in the countries bordering the Mediterranean. In Africa, it has been recorded from Senegal, Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Libya, Egypt, Sudan, Ethiopia and Somalia. It is known from Tunisia from only scattered localities in the central part of the country (Fig. 3.22).

Biology. Cockrum et al. (in litt.) took this species only during the months of May, June, and July. Individuals were taken from mines, a fissure cave and from an abandoned fortification tunnel. All taken in late May (1973 and 1974) were adult males. A recently born young was taken on 5 June from near Tatahouine.

Taxonomy. For years all *Plecotus* of Europe and North Africa were referred to a single species, *P. auritus* (Linnaeus, 1758). It is now generally agreed that two species should be recognized: *P. auritus* (Linnaeus, 1758) in north and central Europe and *P. austriacus* (Fischer, 1829) in central and southern Europe and North Africa eastward into the Middle East. Baker et al. (1974) compared the Tunisian specimens of *Plecotus* to those from Europe using chromosomal data and morphometric measurement comparisons. They follow Aellen and Strinati (1969)

Figure 3.22. Distribution maps of the gray long-eared bat, *Plecotus austriacus* (Fischer, 1829).

and Hayman and Hill (1971) and refer to the Tunisian material as *P. austriacus*. Baker et al. (1974) also recommended further examination of comparative material.

Various authors referred all North African populations to the subspecies *christiei* Gray, 1838, apparently assuming that the earlier name *aegyptius* Fischer, 1829, was not available simply because Fischer used the same subspecific name in two different species. For example, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott (1951) listed as synonym of *Plecotus auritus christiei* Gray, 1838, the following: “1829, *Vespertilio auritus aegyptius* Fischer, Synops. Mamm., p. 117, not *Vespertilio pipistrellus* var. *aegyptius* Fischer, ibid. 105.”

According to the International Rules of Zoological Nomenclature, Fischer's name is available for North African long-eared bats. This conclusion was apparently reached by Aellen and Strinati (1969) as evidenced by their statement that they used the subspecific name *aegyptius* Fischer, 1829, since it antedated *christiei* Gray, 1838. I follow this usage but my assignment to a subspecies having its type locality thousands of kilometers to the east is provisional.

Plecotus austriacus aegyptius (Fischer, 1829)

Vespertilio auritus aegyptius Fischer, Synops. Mamm., p. 117, 1829, type from Egypt. [Based on a description in É. Geoffroy, Desc. de l'Égypte, 2:119, 1818].

Plecotus austriacus aegyptius, Aellen and Strinati, 1969.

Plecotus austriacus christiei, Hayman and Hill, 1971.

Plecotus auritus, Anderson, 1892; Trouessart, 1905; Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b.

Plecotus auritus christiei, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

Plecotus a[uritus]. auritus, Laurent, 1939.

Records. Specimens examined: total, 41, distributed as follows: 4 km S Redeyef on road to Aïoun Aneur, 18; mine Djebel Ank, 30 km SE Gafsa, 7; 3 km

NW Toujane on MC 104, 45 km S Gabès. 11: 2 km S Tatahouine on GP 19. 1 km E highway at French fortification, 5.

Literature reports: Redeyef (Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b); Tatahouine (Laurent, 1939); Douirat (Anderson, 1892).

Genus *Miniopterus* Bonaparte, 1837

Bent-winged Bats

This genus occurs in southern Europe, southern Asia, Australia, and Africa. Eight species are generally recognized, four of which have representatives in Africa. Only one species occurs in Tunisia.

Miniopterus schreibersi (Kuhl, 1819)

Schreiber's Bat

Diagnosis. The diagnostic feature for this bat is its long 3rd finger that folds inward and hence the often-used name bent-winged bat. Its body has long fur but this is denser and shorter in the head and scalp region. Its ears are relatively short.

Distribution. This species primarily borders the Mediterranean in southern Europe. Eastward, it occurs in most of southern Asia. In Africa north of the Sahara, it occurs in Morocco, Algeria and Tunisia. South of the Sahara it occurs from Guinea eastward to Somalia and southward to the Cape. It was the first bat to be recorded from Tunisia (Hartmann, 1868). It is known from several localities north of Chott Djerid (Fig. 3.23).

Biology. During winter months, both males and females were taken in equal numbers at higher elevations. During the summer, females were taken at lower elevations and adult males were taken only at higher elevations. Seven pregnant females, each with a single embryo, were taken by Cockrum et al. (in litt.):

Figure 3.23. Distribution of Schreiber's bat, *Miniopterus schreibersi* (Kuhl, 1819).

3 April, 3 (CR, 5-9 mm); 4 May, 1 (CR, 17 mm); 27 May, 3 (embryo near term). None of the females collected in June, 1996 were pregnant; however, there were many juveniles in the caves that I sampled.

This was one of the most common bats that was encountered during this study (both in the 1970s and in 1996). They were taken during the months of January, March, April, May, June, July, October and November. Almost all were taken in caves or mine tunnels. Few were taken by Cockrum et al. (in litt.) in mist nets over water and none were taken in buildings.

Although this species was first recorded from Tunisia in 1868, it was not again mentioned as being in Tunisia until reported by M. Blanc in 1935. In the intervening years, several cave-dwelling bats had been reported from Tunisia, many from the same places that this species has been found abundant in this report. It is a possibility that Schreiber's bat has become more common in Tunisia in the past 50 years. Perhaps the major shifts in land use and vegetation cover have influenced population levels of this bat.

Taxonomy. I follow most recent authors and refer Tunisian populations of Schreiber's bat to a subspecies described from Europe.

Miniopterus schreibersi schreibersi (Kuhl, 1819)

Vespertilio schreibersii Kuhl, Ann. Wetterau. Ges. Naturk., 4(2):185, 1819, type from Kulmbazey Cave, mountains of southern Bannat, Hungary.

Miniopterus schreibersi, Hartmann, 1868; Blanc, 1935; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951; Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b.

Minniopterus[sic] schreibersi schreibersi, Aellen and Strinati, 1969; Aellen and Strinati, 1970; Hayman and Hill, 1971.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 73, distributed as follows: Ain Dhab in Jebel Serdj, Siliana Sud Delegation, Siliana Governorate, 4; 4 km NE El

Haouaria at bat cave, 7; Entouna mine, 23.5 km SE Tunis on GP 1, 2 km W highway, 2; Ghar Kraiz (26° 26' 10" N 09° 23' 08" E), Testour delegation, Béja governorate, 3; Mine, W edge Ras Rajel cemetery, 6 km W Nefza, 1; abandoned Kohl mine, 5 km NE Aïn Draham, 3; Base of cliff at Chemtou quarry, 17 km W Jendouba, 1; Djebel Rassas, mine 28 km SE Tunis, 6; Djebel Zaghouan, cave at Poste Optique, 2; Djebel Zaghouan, 4 km W Poste Optique, 1; Djebel Zaghouan, mines 3 km SW Zaghouan on road to Aïn Ayed, 20; Scarna mine, 10 km NE Rohia (60 km N Sbeitla), 18; 4 km W GP 3 on ME 77, 49 km NE Sbeitla, 1; 4 km W Redeyef on road to Aïoun Ameer, 4.

Literature reports: Cave at Djebel Ischkeul (Blanc, 1935; Aellen and Strinati, 1969); ruins at Utique (Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b; Aellen and Strinati, 1969); El Haouaria (N-Tunisien) (Vesmanis, 1972); cave at El Haouaria (Cap Bon) (Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b; Aellen and Strinati, 1969); cave at Tebourba (Blanc, 1935; Aellen and Strinati, 1969); region of Ghardimaou (Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b; Aellen and Strinati, 1969); region of Souk el Arba [= Jendouba] (Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b; Aellen and Strinati, 1969); Bulla Regia (Deleuil and Labbe, 1955b; Aellen and Strinati, 1969); cave at Gafsa (Blanc, 1935; Aellen and Strinati, 1969).

Family Molossidae

Free-tailed Bats

Only one genus of this family occurs in the Palaearctic region including the Mediterranean area and North Africa.

Genus *Tadarida* Rafinesque, 1814

Only one species of this genus has been recorded in Tunisia and that only recently.

Tadarida teniotis (Rafinesque, 1814)

European Free-tailed Bat

Diagnosis. As the name implies, these bats are characterized by a free, thick tail. They are also known by their wrinkled upper lips and the fold of skin connecting the two ears. *Tadarida teniotis* is distinguished from *Tadarida aegyptiaca* by larger size and an extra pair of lower incisors (Qumsiyeh, 1985). But, as mentioned before, only the former species occurs in Tunisia.

Distribution. This species is known from southern Europe eastward to China and Japan. It is known from a few localities in North Africa. It does not appear to be common anywhere in its range and no large populations have been recorded. Aellen (1966) summarized the known distribution (from literature and museum specimens). Most records are based on single occurrences (Fig. 3.24).

Biology. Two specimens are known from Tunisia. Beaucournu et al. (1983) reported one captured in a rock crevice in January in Ksar Haddada, south-central Tunisia. Kock and Nader (1984) recorded another from Gorge of Seldja, northeast of Hamma el Djerid, Chotts area. Neither Beaucournu et al. nor Kock and Nader reported any natural history data.

Kowlaski and Rzebik-Kowalska (1991) caught 3 lactating females over a stream in Aures Mountains in Algeria in August. Anciaux de Faveaux (1984) listed the parasites associated with *T. teniotis rueppelli* from Egypt and Sudan.

Taxonomy. Aellen (1966) made a comprehensive review of *Tadarida teniotis*. He recognized 3 subspecies: *T. teniotis teniotis* (Rafinesque, 1814) distributed in the European Mediterranean; *T. teniotis rueppelli* (Temminck, 1826) from North Africa, the Middle East and *T. teniotis insignis* (Blyth, 1861) from the Far East and northwest India. Kock and Nader (1984) recognized two subspecies only. *T. t. teniotis* in the western part of the Mediterranean including Europe, North Africa

Figure 3.24. Distribution maps of the European free-tailed bat, *Tadarida teniotis* (Rafinesque, 1814).

eastward into Egypt. According to Qumsiyeh (1985), there is a probability that *rueppelli* is consubspecific with *teniotis*. The following name applies to the Tunisian material.

Tadarida teniotis teniotis (Rafinesque, 1814)

Cephalotes teniotis Rafinesque, Précis Découv. som. zool. bot., Palermo: 12;
Sicily, Italy.

Tadarida teniotis teniotis, Kock and Nader, 1984.

Mops rüppellii, Allen, 1939.

Tadarida teniotis rüppelli, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

Tadarida teniotis rueppelli, Aellen, 1966.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: Near Ksar Haddada, NW of Tatahouine (Beaucourmu et al., 1983); Gorge of Seldja, 34° 21' N 08° 19' E, NE of El Hamma el Djerid (Kock and Nader, 1984)

ORDER CARNIVORA

Six different families of carnivores have occurred in Tunisia in historic times.

Key for Order Carnivora

1. Mane present on back, forelimbs longer than hind limbs; coarse, stripped fur; heavy, rugose skull with prominent, keel-like sagittal crest; total number of teeth 34 ($\frac{3}{3} \frac{1}{1} \frac{4}{3} \frac{1}{1}$)Family Hyaenidae

- 1'. No mane; hind limbs equal to or larger than forelimbs; silky fur; skull not as rugose; total number of teeth more or less than 34 (except Mustelidae: *Ictonyx*, which has greatest length much less than 80 mm)2
- 2(1'). Ears large (over 80 mm) and erect; digits $\frac{5}{5}$, inside toe on forefoot high; limbs long, adapted for running; tooth row more than half the length of the skull; 7 lower cheek teethCanidae

- 2'. Ears short (less than 70 mm); five digits on hind feet; legs not particularly adapted for running; tooth row less than half the length of the skull; fewer than 7 lower cheek teeth3
- 3(2'). Toes $\frac{4}{5}$ with retractile claws; width of braincase less than 75% of zygomatic breadth; three lower cheek teeth; upper carnassial (P⁴) dominant upper cheek tooth, first upper molar (M¹) tiny and may be lostFelidae

- 3'. Toes $\frac{5}{4}$ with non-retractile claws; width of braincase more than 75% of zygomatic breadth; generally more than three lower cheek teeth (if three, then tail less than 66% of head and body); at least one well developed functional upper molar4

- 4(3'). Tail less than 66% of head and body (except *Lutra* which has webbed toes); pelage not as above; non-retractile claws; short rostrum; slightly inflated bullae; 1 upper molarMustelidae

- 4'. Tail more than 66% of head and body; pelage either spotted or coarse and grizzled; semi-retractile claws, two upper molars5
- 5(4') Pelage spotted, tail ringedViverridae
- 5'. Pelage not spotted but coarse and grizzledHerpestidae

Family Canidae

Jackal and Foxes

The following will aid in the identification of the members of this family that occur in Tunisia.

1. Size small (head and body less than 400 mm); ears large (more than 150 mm); greatest length of skull less than 90 mm; rostrum narrow; bullae large, about equal to combined lengths of P³, P⁴, M¹ and M²*Fennecus zerda*

1'. Size large (head and body more than 400 mm), ears relatively small (usually less than 150 mm) length of skull more than 90 mm; bullae less than combined length of M¹-M²2

2(1'). Tail length less than half of head and body; greatest length of skull more than 150 mm; frontals elevated; postorbital processes convex above
.....*Canis aureus*

2'. Tail length more than half of head and body; greatest length of skull usually less than 150 mm; frontals flat; postorbital processes concave above
.....3 (*Vulpes*)

3 (2'). Hind foot 100-150 mm; back of ears black or dark brown, contrasting with color of head and nape; bullae not bulbous; mastoid process reaches ventral part of bullae*Vulpes vulpes*

3'. Hind foot 90-115 mm; back of ears same color as head and nape; bullae bulbous; mastoid process weak, extending about halfway down bulla

.....*Vulpes rueppelli*

Canis aureus Linnaeus, 1758. Northern Jackal

Diagnosis. The jackal is about the shape of a typical dog. Large adults reach 1300 mm in total length, of which the tail comprises 230 to 260 mm and weigh from 10 to 15 kg. The pelage is a grizzled grayish color, often with much black. The shoulders, especially, often have reddish hair. The tip of the tail is black. The undersides are white.

Distribution. Jackals are essentially Asiatic and African in distribution with only a few populations known in southeastern Europe. In Africa, it occurs from Morocco to Egypt southward to Sudan, Ethiopia, Somalia and Kenya. In Tunisia, it commonly occurs throughout the northern and central part of Tunisia and rarely in the south (Fig. 3.25).

Biology. At present *Canis aureus* seem to be much less abundant than formerly. Lataste (1887) stated "certainly common throughout Tunisia" but added that they were not found much south of the high plateau. Sir Harry Johnston reported (1898) that jackals were "abundantly met with. I have seen wild ones running across my garden at Marsa, twelve miles from Tunis." Blanc (1935) reported them to be common throughout the northern part of the country but less so in the south. During his years of dealings as a fur-buyer, he received an "extremely large" number of jackal pelts.

Chaignon (1904) wrote that of the mammals that he had been able to obtain or observe, the jackal occupied the first place. He found them to be extremely

Figure 3.25. Distribution maps of the northern jackal, *Canis aureus* Linnaeus, 1758. A, *C. a. algirensis* Wagner, 1841; B, *C. a. tripolitanus* Wagner, 1841.

abundant in a large forest to the west of Bir M'Cherga and in Djebel Maouine. He reported hearing their plaintive barking almost every evening.

By 1960 the jackal populations of most of Tunisia had been so reduced that Schomber and Kock (1960: 148) commented: "Today one is extremely fortunate if, in a stay of some weeks in the distant parts of the country, one sees a single jackal."

Nowadays, it seems that their numbers are increasing because of hunt regulations by the Department of Forests (DGF) and probably because of the increase in the abundance of wild boar, especially in the northern region. About an hour after sunset in Feija National Park, near Ghardimaou, I was able to hear their cry in June, 1996. DGF regulations allow for hunting jackals if they destroy property. In Kebili, one official told me that sheep grazers complain frequently about jackals attacking sheep and newborn camels. It seems that they attack camels during parturition. There was an eradication campaign for jackals in a valley west of Sfax when I was collecting in that area. In Bou Hedma National Park, jackals almost ended the ostrich (*Struthio camelus*) reintroduction program. Apparently they killed several ostriches by attacking them at night. The ostrich's long neck is most vulnerable when they are asleep on the ground. Rangers there shoot jackals on sight.

While at the Veterinary Research Institute in Tunis, I was able to observe and photograph 2 adult jackals and 3 cubs. They were kept in cages for the purpose of experimentation with rabies vaccine. I was told by researchers there that jackals were obtained by paying locals (through the DGF) about TD 30 per individual. Most of the IRVT specimens came from the Chotts area.

Taxonomy. Blanc (1935) commented on the great variation in size and color of Tunisian jackals. Those from the south were lighter and brighter in pelage color.

Several different names have been variously applied to jackals in Tunisia. I did not have adequate material to properly evaluate the differences but suspect that no more than two subspecies can be adequately distinguished. The applicable names may be:

Canis aureus algirensis Wagner, 1841

Canis aureus algirensis Wagner, Schreb. Säugeth. Suppl. 2:384, 1841, type from Algeria; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

C[anis]. a[ureus] algirensis, Coetzee, 1971.

Thos aureus algirensis, Allen, 1939.

Canis lupaster grayi Hilzheimer, Zool. Beobachter, 47: 367, 1906, type from Morocco and Tunis.

Thos adustus grayi, Allen, 1939.

Canis studeri Hilzheimer, Zool. Beobachter, 47: 368, 1906, type from Tunis.

C[anis]. aureus, Lataste, 1887.

Canis aureus. Chaignon, 1904; Blanc, 1935.

Canis lupaster, Trouessart, 1905.

This subspecies formerly occurred throughout northern Tunisia, southward to the desert edge.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 1, distributed as follows: Oued Zarga, 18 km airline W Medjez el Bab, 1.

Literature reports: Forests west of Bir M'Cherga and Djebel Maouine (Chaignon, 1904); "Common in Tunisia but not in the south." (Lataste, 1887); "Tunisia" (Trouessart, 1905).

Canis aureus tripolitanus Wagner, 1841

Canis aureus tripolitanus Wagner, Schreb. Säugeth. Suppl. 2:384. 1841. type locality not indicated but “Tripoli, Tunis implied” according to Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

Canis anthus, Gray, 1868; Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905.

This subspecies was formerly uncommon and now rare in the southern desert parts of Tunisia.

Records. Specimens examined: none. Photographed in cages of IRVT. Localities of collection was the “Chotts area” but no definite sites were given.

Literature reports: “Algeria and Tunisia” (Trouessart, 1905).

Vulpes vulpes (Linnaeus, 1758). Red Fox

Diagnosis. The red fox is smaller than the jackal, has a longer tail, longer ears and a much more pointed snout. Adults reach lengths of just over 1000 mm of which about 400 mm is the tail. The hind foot is about 160 mm, the ears about 100 mm. Adults weigh from 4 to 5 kg. The fur is long and dense. A middorsal stripe of reddish brown extends from the shoulders to the base of the tail. The backs of the ears are black, the inner surfaces, white.

Distribution. Red foxes are Holarctic in distribution. African populations were restricted to areas along the Mediterranean Sea (Fig. 3.26). Although not as common as in the past, they are still found in much of northern and central Tunisia.

Biology. Lataste (1887) reported the presence of red foxes but made no comment concerning their numbers. Johnston (1898) wrote that “a fox, scarcely distinguishable from the English form [= red fox] is found in the wooded country [of northern Tunisia].” Chaignon (1904) reported that red foxes were more common in northern Tunisia than jackals and that M. Blanc received its furs daily.

Figure 3.26. Distribution maps of the red fox, *Vulpes vulpes* (Linnaeus, 1758)

Blanc (1935) considered them to be “very common.” Like the jackals, red foxes are considered pests in some areas and the Tunisian DGF issues permits to combat them.

In recent years, the Tunisian Ministry of Agriculture has been experimenting with cactus as an emergency cattle feed in case of severe droughts. Large plots of Barbary fig (*Opuntia*; in Arabic: El Hindi) cactus have been planted (e.g., El Nasr artificial forest, Bou Hajla, Kairouan Governorate). Such areas provided shelter for both foxes and their prey. The numbers of the red fox are on the increase and the DGF authorizes their capture and killing. One method used to capture foxes is “flooding-out” by pouring large amounts of water (100-200 liters) into its den while two or three workers hold heavy canvas sacks over the exits. I was told that this was an effective way to catch them alive and that several individuals were caught this way.

Taxonomy. Most early workers considered the North African red foxes to be specifically different from those of Europe and Asia. Lataste (1887) with only a few specimens available to him, attempted to find some morphological difference that would separate the two. He discussed the problem at length and listed dental and cranial characters that distinguished the North African from the European form. Today they are considered to be conspecific.

Some differences between northern and southern Tunisian populations have been reported. Blanc (1935) found those from the north to be more robust and have darker pelage. Those from the south had a more uniform, paler color and softer pelage that he “could immediately tell if the specimens were from the north or from the south” [Blanc, 1935: 8; translated by Burhan Gharaibeh]. The red fox populations in Tunisia need further study using skull morphometry and molecular biology. At the moment, I have no comparative material on which to make a

meaningful judgment and all the Tunisian material are listed as members of a single subspecies as follows:

Vulpes vulpes atlantica (Wagner, 1841).

Canis vulpes var. *atlantica* A. Wagner, in M. Wagner, *Reisen in d. Regenschaft Algier*, 3: 31, 62, pl. 3, 1841, type from Mitiyá, Atlas Mountains, Algeria.

Vulpes vulpes atlantica, Trouessart, 1905; Allen, 1939; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

V[ulpes]. v[ulpes]. atlantica, Coetzee, 1971.

C[anis]. niloticus, Lataste, 1887.

Vulpes niloticus, Blanc, 1935.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 3, distributed as follows: 62 km S Sfax on GP1, 1; Bir Bou Hamed, 26 km ESE Médénine on GP 1, 2 ; Seldja vicinity, 40 km airline WSW Gafsa, 1; Oudna, 20 km S Tunis, 1.

Literature reports: Gafsa (Lataste, 1887; Blanc, 1935); Metameur in Arad (Lataste, 1887); Moularès (Blanc, 1935); Mélaoui (Blanc, 1935); Maknassy (Blanc, 1935); Tamerza (Blanc, 1935); Kebili (Blanc, 1935); “throughout Tunisia” (Blanc, 1935) Oued Miliane (Chaignon, 1904).

Vulpes rueppelli (Schinz, 1825). Sand Fox

Diagnosis. The sand foxes are smaller, lighter colored, and more lightly built than red foxes. Total lengths rarely exceed 890 mm of which the tail is about 390 mm. The hind foot is about 130 mm, the ear, 120 mm.

Distribution. These foxes are inhabitants of desert and subdesert areas from southern Algeria to Afghanistan. In Tunisia, they have been recorded as far north as Gafsa (Fig. 3.27).

Figure 3.27. Distribution maps of the sand fox, *Vulpes rueppelli* (Schinz, 1825).

Biology. During the collections of Cockrum and his co-workers (in litt.), foxes, perhaps of this species, were reported from just north of Fort Saint. None were seen or taken. Blanc (1936) reported that they were not common. Others made no reference to numbers.

Taxonomy. One subspecies has been named from southern Algeria and another from Libya. On geographic grounds it appears probable that Tunisian populations would be referable to the Libyan race. However, I examined no specimens, therefore I am unable to offer any opinion as to relationships.

Vulpes rueppelli cyrenaica Festa, 1921

Vulpes cyrenaica Festa, Boll. Mus. Zool. Anat. Comp., Univ. Torino, 36(740):3, 1921, type from near Benghazi, Cyrenaica Prov., Libya.

Vulpes rüppelli cyrenaica, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

V[ulpes]. r[ueppelli]., Coetzee, 1971.

Vulpes pallida cyrenaica, Allen, 1939

Vulpes famelicus, Trouessart, 1905; Blanc, 1935;

Records. Specimens examined: none. Photographed only: Sidi Toui Reserve (museum building), Ben Gardane, 1 skull.

Literature reports: Gafsa, Mévlaoui, Tozeur, Redeyef, Kébili, Tatahouine (all from Blanc, 1935).

Fennecus zerda (Zimmermann, 1780). Fennec Fox

Diagnosis. Fennecs are the smallest of all known foxes, being slightly smaller than a typical house cat. Total length rarely exceed 700 mm of which the tail makes up about 300 mm. Hind foot length is about 100 mm, the ears, large for the small size of these foxes are about the same length as the hind foot. The long, soft pelage

is a creamy tan to light brownish in color. The head, flanks, limbs and underparts are almost pure white. The short, bushy tail has a blackish brown tip.

Distribution. In Tunisia, fennecs are only known from the southern desert (Fig. 3.28).

Biology. Saint-Girons (1962) and Petter (1967) summarized information on the fennec's reproduction based on captive specimens from Beni Abbès, Algeria. Gestation period is 50-51 days. One to three cubs are born altricial with closed eyes, small ears, and soft short fur. Parturition under natural conditions takes place in March or April (Rosevear, 1974).

Diploid number is 64, FN= 70. The fennec has 2 pairs of metacentric and submetacentric chromosomes and 29 pairs of acrocentrics (Chiarelli, 1975).

Vulpes vulpes and *V. ruppelli* have 2N= 34-38 and 2N= 40, respectively, and the majority of their chromosomes are metacentric.

Taxonomy. Wozencraft (1993) placed the genus *Fennecus* in *Vulpes*, whereas Stains (1975) recognizes *Fennecus* as a separate genus. The chromosomal complement of *Fennecus zerda* was found most similar to that of the gray fox, *Urocyon cinereoargenteus* (Chiarelli, 1975). Wayne and O'Brien (1987) studied allozyme divergence within the Canidae and found that *Vulpes*, *Fennecus* and *Alopex* form a distinct phenetic group. Further, they speculated that they diverged from other canids ca. 9 million years ago. The Tunisian material is best given the following name:

Fennecus zerda (Zimmermann, 1780)

Canis zerda Zimmermann, Geogr. Ges. 2:247, 1780, type from "Sahara, and other parts of North Africa behind the Atlas, and in Tripoli."

Fennecus zerda, Allen, 1939; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951; Coetzee, 1971.

Vulpes zerda, Trouessart, 1905; Blanc, 1935.

Figure 3.28. Distribution maps of the fennec, *Fennecus zerda* (Zimmermann, 1780).

Fennecus brucei Desmarest, Encyclop. Méthodique, Mammalogie. p. 235. 1820,
type from Libya, Tunis, Algeria and Sennaar.

Records. Specimens examined: none. Photographed in Tozeur Zoo.

Literature reports: Tozeur (Blanc, 1935); Tozzer [= Tozeur] (Lataste, 1887);
Ghadamès (Lataste, 1887); Metlaoui (Blanc, 1935); Redeyef (Blanc, 1935); Kebili
(Blanc, 1935); Tatahouine (Blanc, 1935); Déhibat (Blanc, 1935); Bir Djenein
(Blanc, 1935).

Family Mustelidae

Weasels and Otters

Three species of mustelids are known from Tunisia; the otter, the weasel, and
the striped weasel.

Key for Family Mustelidae

1. Tail long, thickened and fleshy at base; fur short; feet clearly webbed; M¹
much enlarged and more or less square; 5 upper cheek teeth*Lutra lutra*
- 1'. Tail not thickened at base; fur long; feet not webbed; M¹ smaller than
carnassial; 4 or fewer upper cheek teeth2
- 2(1'). Fur on head and body never of two contrasting colors; antorbital
foramen larger than greatest diameter of canine*Mustela nivalis*
- 2'. Fur pattern striped (blackish and whitish); antorbital foramen smaller than
greatest diameter of canine*Ictonyx libyca*

Ictonyx libyca (Hemprich and Ehrenberg, 1833)

Striped Weasel

Diagnosis. Striped weasels are black, with much white on the dorsal surface.
The white is generally arranged in various bands and spots. The tail is bushy and

generally white but may be darker toward the tip. Measurements include: total length, 450 mm, tail 150-160 mm, hind foot, 40 mm, weight, 1 kg.

Distribution. Striped weasels are restricted to northern Africa (Fig. 3.29). None were seen by Cockrum et al. during their study (in litt.) nor by me in 1996. Chaignon (1904) reported that near Tunis striped weasels were more common than mongooses.

Biology. Blanc (1935) reported it from a number of localities but made no comment about numbers. Coetzee (1971) reported that its favored habitats are fringes of cultivated fields on the edges of desert areas. There appears to be no information on the biology of this animal in Tunisia. Hufnagl (1972) reported that its food is mainly insects with a preference for maggot of the May beetle. It is strictly nocturnal and predated on snakes, rats and no birds (Coetzee, 1971).

Gestation period for captive animals was 37 days, breeding season is Feb.-May and litter size is 1-3 and young are born. Young are born altricial with closed eyes and white hair that changes into dark after 3 weeks (Petter, 1959)

Taxonomy. This species has been placed in the genus *Poecilictis* by many authorities. Rosevear (1974) discussed the differences between *Poecilictis* and *Ictonyx* and concluded that the differences in the skull measurements does not “justify a genus or a subgenus” but used the name *Poecilictis libycus* (Hemprich and Ehrenberg). Corbet (1978) listed it as *Poecilictis libyca* but suggested that *Poecilictis* should be reunited with *Ictonyx*. Wozencraft (1993) listed this species as *Ictonyx libyca* (Hemprich and Ehrenberg, 1833) and discussed evidence that *Poecilictis* Thomas and Hinton, 1920 is congeneric with *Ictonyx* Kaup, 1835. I have no opinion on this issue and to avoid further confusion of the literature, I follow the last view.

Figure 3.29. Distribution maps of the striped weasel, *Ictonyx libyca* (Hemprich and Ehrenberg, 1833).

Ictonyx libyca vaillanti (Loche, 1856)

Zorilla vaillantii Loche, Rev. et Mag. de Zool., [2] 8: 497, plate 22. 1856, type
from Algeria.

Ictonyx libyca, Wozencraft, 1993.

Poecilictis libyca vaillanti, Allen, 1939; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott. 1951;
Coetzee, 1971.

Z[orilla]. libyca, Lataste, 1887.

Zorilla libyca, Chaignon, 1904; Trouessart, 1905; Blanc, 1935.

Poecilictis libyca, Hufnagl, 1972.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: Marsa (Blanc, 1935); Ariana (Blanc, 1935); Le Mornag
(Blanc, 1935); Hamamet (Blanc, 1935); Cap Bon (Blanc, 1935); Kalaat-es-Senam
(Blanc, 1935); Slata (Blanc, 1935); Pavillier [not found](Blanc, 1935); Sfax
(Blanc, 1935); Zarzis (Blanc, 1935); Tatahouine (Blanc, 1935); Redeyef (Blanc,
1935); "southern Tunisia" (Lataste, 1887); Tunis (Chaignon, 1904); southwest of
Sebkha Sedjoui (Chaignon, 1904); Bir M'Cherga (Chaignon, 1904); "Tunisian
border" (Loche, 1867); Tozeur (Hufnagl, 1972).

Mustela nivalis Linnaeus, 1776. Least Weasel

Diagnosis. This weasel is one of the smallest carnivores (weight of 25-250 g).
It is distinguished from other mustelids in Tunisia by a uniform coloration that lacks
spots. Its pelage is usually golden-brown on the dorsum and whitish on the
ventrum.

Distribution. This weasel is Holarctic in distribution. In Africa, it is restricted
to the Atlas Mountains (Fig. 3.30). Blanc (1935) stated that it was never found in
southern Tunisia.

Figure 3.30. Distribution maps of the weasel, *Mustela nivalis* Linnaeus, 1776.

Biology. Few authors have observed it in Tunisia and then without comment concerning numbers. None were seen by Cockrum et al. (in litt.) during 1972-1975 study.

Taxonomy. Ellerman and Morrison-Scott (1951) commented: "Both Miller and G. Allen (1939) give this large form specific status."

Mustela nivalis numidica (Pucheran, 1855)

Putorius numidicus Pucheran, Rev. et Mag. de Zool., 7:393, 1855, type from Morocco and Algeria (type locality fixed at Tangier by Cabrera, Bol. Soc. Real Esp. Hist. Nat., Madrid, 13:428, 1913).

Mustela nivalis numidica, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951; Coetzee, 1971.

Mustela numidica, Miller, 1912; Allen, 1939.

Putorius nivalis numidicus, Trouessart, 1905; Blanc, 1935.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: Béja; Ebba-Ksour; Sidi El Aouane; Ber Bou Rekba; Tébourba; outskirts of Tunis (all from Blanc, 1935); "Tunisia, saharan region" (Trouessart, 1905).

Lutra lutra (Linnaeus, 1758). Otter

Diagnosis. These are semi-aquatic mammals that live in riverine habitats, fresh water ponds, deltas and estuaries. Its webbed feet are the main distinguishing character.

Distribution. River otters were formerly essentially Palearctic in distribution. In North Africa, they occurred in the larger streams in Morocco, Algeria and Tunisia. Now they are rare throughout most of their former range and are extinct in much of the area. They occur in the northern part of Tunisia (Fig. 3.31) but they are rarely seen.

Figure 3. 31. Distribution maps of the otter, *Lutra lutra* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Biology. Macdonald and Mason (1983) examined 75 localities in Medjerda River Valley in Tunisia and found that 71% of those were positive for otter spraints (a term used specifically when referring to otter scats; Mason and Macdonald, 1983: 14). Lake Ichkeul catchment area seems to be important for the existence of the species in northern Tunisia. The availability of oleander (*Nerium oleander*) which is a poisonous bush that is not grazed by sheep and goats, on the river banks provides cover for the otter. According to Mason and Macdonald (1983) the Medjerda River tributaries have healthy populations of *Lutra lutra*.

The investigation by Mason and Macdonald (1986) points to the fact that otter distribution was inversely related to human population density and agricultural activities. The amount of pollution in rivers found negative was high. This makes this species a good indicator species of the health of fresh water bodies in North Africa.

Lataste (1887) reported observing 6 captive pets that had been taken from Oued el Kebir near Aïn-Draham. Blanc (1935) reported them to be fairly common in the principal rivers and streams of northern Tunisia and that he had received one that weighed more than 8 kg. One specimen in the Department of Zoology, INAT, was collected in 1964 (Cockrum et al., in litt.) and Lehmann (1972) reported seeing one in northwestern Tunisia.

Taxonomy. The name to be applied to African populations of river otters is unclear, as indicated by Coetzee (1971) and others. Van Bree (1968) pointed out that Lataste, in his original description, compared the skull of an adult from Algeria with the skull of an immature from France. Until a meaningful sample of African material is compared with a similar sample from the type locality of *Lutra lutra* -- Upsala, Sweden--and material from intermediate geographic localities are evaluated, the taxonomic status of African populations will remain in doubt. For the time

being, I follow Ellerman and Morrison-Scott (1951) in listing Lataste's name as "available for the North African Otter if it proves racially separable."

Lutra lutra angustifrons Lataste, 1885

Lutra angustifrons Lataste, Actes Soc. Linn. de Bordeaux, 39:168. 237. 1885.
from Bone, Algeria.

Lutra lutra angustifrons, Allen, 1939; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

Lutra lutra, Trouessart, 1905; Blanc, 1935; Lehmann, 1972; Coetzee, 1971.

L[utra]. lutra, Lataste, 1885.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: (Blanc, 1935, unless otherwise indicated). Oued El Kebir (Trouessart, 1905); Khroumirie; valley of Medjerda river; oued near Tabarka; Sedjenane; Thala; Pont-de-Trajean; Djedeida; Hourareb [= Aóuareb] near Kairouan; Deer reserve near Feidja (Lehmann, 1972); Kairouan; Oued Medjerda and tributaries; Oued El Abiod, Cap Bon; Lake Ichkeul area; Sedjenane, and other areas spot-mapped by Macdonald and Mason (1983) and Mason and Macdonald (1986).

Family Viverridae

Genets and Relatives

This family is distributed in the tropics of the Palearctic region. It is represented in Africa by the genera *Ichneuma*, *Herpestes*, and *Genetta* (Corbet, 1978).

Genus *Genetta* G. Cuvier, 1816

One species extends into North Africa and occurs in Tunisia.

Genetta genetta (Linnaeus, 1758). Genet

Diagnosis. This species can be discriminated from other carnivores in Tunisia by its unique spotted pelage, its ringed-tail, and its relatively long snout. From other species of genets it can be distinguished by its medium-sized spots and white tip on its tail.

Distribution. Genets are widely distributed in Africa south of the Sahara. North of the Sahara they occur from Morocco to Libya. In Europe, they occur from southwestern France southward through Spain and Portugal. Tunisian records are from the northern and central regions (Fig. 3.32).

Biology. Genets were not common anywhere in Tunisia during the period of this study (Cockrum, et al., in litt.). They may have been more common in the past. Although Lataste (1887) did not collect genets in Tunisia, he reported that it was common in northern Algeria. Chaignon (1904) made no mention of this species. Blanc (1935) reported them common, even in the outskirts of Tunis and that every winter he received many from northern and central regions. He also indicated that genets were unknown from southern Tunisia.

Taxonomy. Genets are highly variable, even in a single region. Various past authors have ascribed as many as three different subspecies to Tunisia. Gadeau de Kerville (1906), for example, reported two different subspecies from the same locality (the Ain Draham region). Blanc (1935) reported that great variability in color patterns in most of the pelts seen by him from throughout northern and central Tunisia. Until more detailed studies are available, I include all Tunisian material in a single subspecies.

Coetzee (1971) and Crawford-Cabral (1981) have arranged North African names as synonymous with the mainland form, *genetta*.

Figure 3.32. Distribution maps of the genet, *Genetta genetta* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Genetta genetta (Linnaeus, 1758)

Viverra genetta Linnaeus, Syst. Nat., 10th ed., 1: 45, 1758, type from Spain.

G[enetta]. genetta, Lataste, 1887.

G[enetta]. g[enetta] genetta Coetzee, 1971.

Genetta afra F. Cuvier, in Cuvier and Geoffroy, Hist. Nat. Mamm., pt. 52, pl. 195
and pt. 51, text, 1825, type from "Barbary" [= coast of North Africa].

Genetta genetta afra, Schwarz, 1930; Allen, 1939; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott,
1951.

Genetta afra barbara, Trouessart, 1905; Gadeau de Kerville, 1906; Blanc, 1935.

Genetta afra bonapartei, Gadeau de Kerville, 1906.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: Gabès (Trouessart, 1905); throughout northern and central
Tunisia (Blanc, 1935); Aïn-Draham region [7 as *G. a. bonapartei* and 3 as *G. a.*
barbara] (Gadeau de Kerville, 1906).

Family Herpestidae

Mongoose

Recent views (Wozencraft, 1993) have shown evidence to separate the
subfamily Herpestinae from Viverridae and raise it to a family level. I will adopt
this view here to be consistent with recent literature.

One genus is listed from Tunisia.

Genus *Herpestes* Illiger, 1811

In Tunisia, one species represent this family.

Herpestes ichneumon (Linnaeus, 1758). Mongoose

Diagnosis. The mongoose is a small mustelid (ca. 850 mm total length, tail ca. 350 mm) with long dark gray fur. Its limbs are short and both hind and forelimbs are almost equal in length.

Distribution. Mongooses are essentially restricted to Africa where it occurs in all but the most arid parts of the continent. Some occur in southern Spain and Portugal and scattered populations occur elsewhere, probably as the result of introduction by man. In Tunisia, they occur in northern and central areas (Fig. 3.33).

Biology. Mongooses appear to be abundant locally. Chaignon (1904) reported that they were “not rare” in northern Tunisia. Blanc (1935) reported them from a number of localities. Cockrum et al. (in litt.) reported seeing one in midday in May, 1975, as it was crossing the highway a few kilometers east of Tabarka.

Taxonomy. Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska (1991) noted that some authorities (e.g., Lataste, 1887) debate if there is enough difference between the Egyptian specimens which were used by Linnaeus, 1758 to name *Viverra ichneumon* and Cuvier’s specimen from Algeria that he named *Ichneumon numidicus*. I decided to follow this name for the Tunisian material.

Herpestes ichneumon numidicus (F. Cuvier, 1834)

Ichneumon numidicus F. Cuvier, Hist. Nat. Mamm., pt. 68, pl. 191, and text, 1834, type from Algeria.

Herpestes ichneumon numidicus, Cabrera, 1932; Allen, 1939; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

H[erpestes]. i[chneumon]. numidicus Coetzee, 1971.

Herpestes ichneumon, Chaignon, 1904; Trouessart, 1905; Gadeau de Kerville, 1906; Blanc, 1935; Hufnagl, 1972.

Figure 3.33. Distribution maps of the Egyptian mongoose, *Herpestes ichneumon* (Linnaeus, 1758).

H[erpestes]. ichneumon, Lataste, 1887.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: (Blanc, 1935, unless otherwise indicated): "Tunisia" (Trouessart, 1905); Khroumirie (Gadeau de Kerville, 1906; Blanc, 1935); Valley of Medjerda river; Mateur; Soliman; Béja; Ghardimaou; Le Kef; Tabarka; Djebel Maouine (Chignon, 1904); El Kef (Hufnagl, 1972).

Family Hyaenidae

Hyaenas

This family of carnivores, specialized in feeding on carrion, is restricted to Africa and southwestern Asia.

Hyaena hyaena (Linnaeus, 1758). Striped Hyaena

Diagnosis. These are large carnivores, the size of a large dog. The main distinguishing characters are striped body, a mane (crest) on its neck, shoulders, and back. Their forefeet are noticeably longer than their hindfeet.

Distribution. Striped hyaena formerly occurred from northern India and southwestern Russia westward into Africa. In Africa, they occurred from Egypt to Morocco southward to Kenya. Hyaena's former range included most of Tunisia, being most common in the central and northern parts (Fig. 3.34).

Biology. Today hyaenas are extremely rare throughout Tunisia. During their survey, Cockrum et al. (in litt.) learned of one killed in the summer of 1972 at Bir Amir. They purchased the skin of this individual on 4 June 1973 from a herdsman 30 km S Tatahouine on GP 19.

Lataste (1877) reported that he had observed hyaena droppings at several localities in southern Tunisia (of the Chotts). In 1880 Johnston (1898)

Figure 3.34. Distribution maps of the striped hyena, *Hyaena hyaena* (Linnaeus, 1758).

photographed a hyaena that had been shot in northwestern Tunisia. By 1898, he reported: “sparsely distributed all over the Regency and right down into the Sahara, though of course it is never found now near any of the big towns. Yet I can remember a hyaena being killed in the suburbs of Tunis in 1880.”

Chaignon (1904) reported that hyaenas were rare at Djebel Mouine, not as residents but as transients moving through the area. Blanc (1935) reported them as “very common” at certain localities in central and northern Tunisia but few in number in the south. Schomber and Kock (1960) stated “one is extremely fortunate if, in a stay of some weeks in the distant parts of the country, one sees a single hyaena.”

The rangers in Chambi National Park, near Kasserine, observe them occasionally during their night patrols (pers. comm. with Gharaibeh). The hyaena is protected by the hunt regulations and DGF pamphlets claim that its numbers in the montane parts of Tunisia are increasing.

Taxonomy. Most authors have applied a single name to North African populations of hyaenas. However, Blanc (1935) reported that hyaenas of the south were paler and had less fur.

Filippi (1853) obtained a striped hyaena from a traveling animal show in Italy and described it as a new species (*Hyaena suilla*). He wrote that the animal had come from some unknown locality in Africa and suggested that it may have come from the Cape of Good Hope region--now known to be far outside the range of the striped hyaena. Trouessart (1905) reported seeing a specimen from Gabès, Tunisia, in the Musée Gênes. The label on this specimen led Trouessart to conclude that it was the type of Filippi's *Hyaena suilla*. Trouessart then assumed Gabès to be the type locality and referred southern Tunisian material to this taxon. Cockrum et al. (in litt.) are of the opinion that the specimen seen by Trouessart was

not Filippi's type but rather, a specimen from Gabès identified as *Hyaena suilla*. The difference between southern and northern populations (sensu Blanc, 1935) remains to be investigated when sufficient number of skin and skulls becomes available. The Tunisian material is follows the name below.

Hyaena hyaena barbara Blainville, 1844

Hyaena vulgaris barbara Blainville, Ostéographie, Mamm., 2: les Hyènes, pp. 6, 81 and pls. 2 and 6, 1844, type from Oran, Algeria.

Hyaena hyaena barbara, Allen, 1939; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

H[yaena]. h[yaena]. barbara Coetzee, 1971.

Hyaena suilla Filippi, Mem. R. Accad. Torino, 13, 2: 131, 1953, from unknown locality [Trouessart, 1905: 382 thought it was Gabès, Tunisia]; Trouessart, 1905.

H[yaena]. hyaena, Lataste, 1887.

Hyaena hyaena, Blanc, 1935.

Hyaena striata, Chaignon, 1904.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: (Blanc, 1935, unless otherwise indicated): Tunis region (Lataste, 1887); many localities in southern Tunisia [= Chott region] (Lataste, 1887); Tatahouine; Tamerza; Metlaoui; Kasserine; Hadjeb-el-Aïoun; Thala; Tébourouk; Le Kef; Bou-Chebka; Béja; Tabarka; Djebel Maouine (Chaignon, 1904); Gabès (Trouessart, 1905).

Family Felidae

Cats

Seven species are known to occur or have occurred in Tunisia.

Key for Family Felidae

1. Legs long; body with solid black spots and a black line from the inner corner of the eye down side of nose to upper lip; claws when retracted not covered by sheaths; face short; skull arched (in profile short and high), skull length 146-203 mm; hyoidean apparatus unspecialized*Acinonyx jubatus*
- 1'. Legs short; body not with solid black spots (if black, then no black line from eye to lip); retracted claws covered by sheaths; skull not greatly arched2
- 2(1'). Size large; skull length in adults more than 170 mm; hyoidean apparatus modified with median part of suspensor a long elastic tendon3
- 2'. Size small; skull length in adults less than 160 mm; hyoidean apparatus normal4
- 3(2). Body unicolored, not spotted; tip of tail with tuft; males with well developed mane; greatest length of skull of adults usually more than 250 mm; sagittal crest and mastoid process well developed*Panthera leo*
- 3'. Body color with rosettes of dark color; tip of tail without tuft; no mane in males; greatest length of skull of adults usually less than 250 mm; sagittal crest and mastoid process little developed*Panthera pardus*
- 4 (2'). Hind foot more than 140 mm; weight more than 15 kg; greatest length of skull more than 120 mm5
- 4'. Hind foot less than 140 mm; weight less than 15 kg; greatest length of skull less than 115 mm6
- 5 (4). Ears elongated with triangular tips, black posterior surfaces and tufts of elongated black hairs; dorsal color with indistinct markings or unicolor*Felis caracal*
- 5'. Ears short and the tip is rounded, with no black on posterior surface and no tufts; dorsal color with distinct bars or spots*Felis serval*

6(4'). Fur long, lax and pale colored; soles of feet covered with long (20 mm) hairs; hind foot less than 110 mm; greatest length of skull 90 mm; auditory bullae inflated more than 25% of condylobasal length)*Felis margarita*

6'. Fur short and dark colored; soles of feet with short (5-6 mm) hairs and bare areas; hind foot more than 110 mm; greatest length of skull more than 90 mm; auditory bullae less than 22% of condylobasal length*Felis silvestris*

Felis silvestris Schreber, 1777. African Wild Cat

Diagnosis. This mammal is the size and shape of a house cat. Its tail is ringed and has a dark tip. Its pelage is short and dark gray with faint bars.

Distribution. This species formerly occurred from central Asia westward through southern Europe and southward into Africa where it occurs in most parts of the continent. Currently these cats are rare, but not extinct, in most of Tunisia (Fig. 3.35).

Biology. Lataste (1887) reported these cats to be common in the south-central parts of Tunisia. Johnston (1898) reported: "the Arabs constantly speak of a wild cat which from their accounts would seem to be *Felis maniculata* [= *Felis silvestris*]." Curiously, Chaignon (1904) made no mention of any members of the family Felidae. Blanc (1935) indicated that a few wild cats were to be found throughout the country, in the south, as well as in the north.

Taxonomy. Corbet (1978) provided a summary of the status of various "species" names. I follow his usage of *Felis silvestris*.

In Tunisia, considerable variation exists in pelage color, even in one population as discussed by Blanc (1935). Populations in the south of Tunisia are typically lighter than those from northern localities. Further studies may demonstrate that

Figure 3.35. Distribution maps of the wild cat, *Felis silvestris* Schreber, 1777.

should be recognized from the area. However, I refer all to a single subspecies, as follows:

Felis silvestris libyca Forster, 1780

Felis lybica [sic] Forster, in Buffon's Naturgesch. d. Vierfüß. Thiere, 6: 313, 1780, from Gafsa, Tunisia.

F[elis]. s[ilvestris]. libyca, Corbet, Mammals Palaeartic, 1978.

Felis libyca libyca, Allen, 1939; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

F[elis]. libyca, Lataste, 1887.

F[elis]. l[ibyca]. libyca, Smithers, 1975.

Felis cristata Lataste, Actes Soc. Linn. Bordeaux, (4) 39: 229, 1885, type from Haïdra, Tunisia.

Felis ocreata, Trouessart, 1905; Blanc, 1935.

Felis ocreata libyca, Gadeau de Kerville, 1906.

Felis maniculata, Johnston, 1898.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: (Blanc, 1935, unless otherwise indicated): Gafsa (Lataste, 1887); Gabès (Lataste, 1887); Zarzis (Lataste, 1887); Tozzeur, (Lataste, 1887); Haïdra (Lataste, 1887); Zaghouan; Gafour; Ghardimaou; Béja; Tébourouk; Tebarka; Cap Bon; Medjerda Valley; Gabès; Medenine; Tatahouine; Sidi Thabet region (Bernard, 1967).

Felis margarita Loche 1858. Sand Cat

Diagnosis. This cat has long, lax, pale-colored fur. It differs from *Felis silvestris* in its light, long pelage and broader ears. Weights can reach 2.5 kg and total length between 700-900 mm.

Distribution. Sand cats inhabit the deserts of the Middle East and North Africa. They are nowhere common in their range. In Tunisia, they are known only from the southern-most regions (Fig. 3.36). Lataste (1887) reported sand cats from Metameur and Matmata. Blanc (1935) reported only one, an individual from Tatahouine. During their study, Cockrum et al. (in litt.) saw nothing that they could ascribe to this species.

Felis margarita margarita Loche, 1858

Felis margarita Loche, Rev. et Mag. de Zool., [2] 10:49, pl. 1, 1858, type from near Négonça, Algeria.

[*Felis margarita*] var. *margarita*, Lataste, 1887.

Felis margarita margarita, Allen, 1939; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

Felis ocreata marguerittei Trouessart, Causéries Sci. Soc. Zool. de France, p. 275, 1: 386, 1905 [emendation of *margarita* to conform to Général Margueritte for whom the species was named].

F[elis]. m[argarita]. margarita, Smithers, 1975.

F[elis]. l[ibyca] libyca, Smithers, 1975.

Felis cristata Lataste, Actes Soc. Linn. Bordeaux, (4) 9:229, 1885, type from Haïdra, Tunisia.

Felis ocreata, Trouessart, 1905.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: Metameur (Lataste, 1887); Matmata (Lataste, 1887); Tatahouine (Blanc, 1935).

Figure 3.36. Distribution maps of the sand cat, *Felis margarita* Loche, 1858.

Felis caracal Schreber, 1776. Caracal Lynx

Diagnosis. This elegant cat can easily be distinguished by the large ears that end with long tufts of black hair. Its dorsal color is sandy and does not have any spots or bars.

Distribution. Caracal lynxes were formerly inhabitants of desert and subdesert regions from northern India westward through Arabia into Africa. In Africa, they occurred from Egypt to Morocco and, in eastern Africa, south to the Cape of Good Hope. The caracal has been recorded from northern and central Tunisia (Fig. 3.37).

Biology. During their study in Tunisia, Cockrum et al. (in litt.) found no evidence of these cats. Lataste (1887) reported a caracal from just west Tunisia in Algeria so close to the border that it could cross the border in one of its hunts. He thought that it certainly occurred in Tunisia. Johnston (1898) reported: "occasionally met with in the extreme south of Tunisia, to the south of the salt lakes of the Jerid." Blanc (1935) reported that it was "not rare" in forests of central and northern Tunisia.

Taxonomy. This species is listed in Wilson and Reeder (1993) as *Caracal caracal*. It seems that Wozencraft (1993) is convinced with the evidence that placed *caracal* in the monotypic genus *Caracal*. However, he mentions that recent literature shows closeness to *Felis*. I follow the more traditional scheme concerning this issue.

Felis caracal algira Wagner, 1841

Felis caracal var. *algira* A. Wagner, in W. Wagner, Reisen in der Regenschaft Alger. 3:76, p. 4. 1841, type from Algeria.

Felis caracal algira, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

Caracal caracal algirus, Allen, 1939.

Figure 3.37. Distribution maps of the caracal, *Felis caracal* Schreber, 1776.

F[elis]. c[aracal]. algirus, Smithers, 1975.

F[elis]. caracal, Lataste, 1887.

Felis (Caracal) berberorum spatzi Matschie, Sitzb. Ges. Naturf. Freunde, Berlin, p. 61, 1912, type from between Feriana and Tebessa, Tunisia.

C[aracal]. berberorum medjerdae Matschie, Sitzb. Ges. Naturf. Freunde, Berlin, p. 62, 1912, type from Tunis.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: (Blanc, 1935, unless otherwise indicated): Oued Medjerda, (Matschie, 1912); Aïn Bou Dries (Matschie, 1912); between Aïn Bou Dries and Bir Bou Haya (Matschie, 1912); between Feriana and Tébessa (Matschie, 1912); between Haïdra and Tébessa at Algerian border (Lataste, 1887) and (Matschie, 1912); Khroumirie; Feriana; Bou Chebika; Cap Bon; Kef; Thala; Testour; mountains of Matmata.

Felis serval Schreber, 1776. Serval

Diagnosis. The serval has long slender legs like a caracal but its fur is spotted and its tail is short and ringed. Another distinctive character for this cat is its large, oval ears.

Distribution. Servals occur or formerly occurred in all of Africa except the most arid parts of the Sahara. It formerly occurred in the northern parts of Tunisia (Fig. 3.38).

Lataste (1887) saw a skin in Tunis of an animal that had been taken in the region and two living animals in Aïn Draham that had been taken nearby. Johnston (1898) reported that “the Pardine Lynx is found in the wooded mountains” of Tunisia. Trouessart’s report that servals occurred in the vicinity of Tunis and Aïn

Figure 3.38. Distribution maps of the serval, *Felis serval* Schreber, 1776.

Draham, is probably based on Lataste's reports. Blanc (1935) reported them from a number of northern localities.

Biology. No specific information is available for Tunisian specimens. Kacem et al. (1994) reported that the gestation period is 72-74 days and the litter size is 2-5 young. Parturition takes place April-November. Animal reaches maturity at age 2-3 years. They usually live in pairs.

Kacem et al. (1994) mentioned that there are plans to reintroduce this cat into Feija National Park. Three servals brought from the Munich Zoo (1 male, 2 females) are being acclimated in Dar Chichou, Cap Bon before they are transferred to Feija.

Taxonomy. Some authorities place this species in a separate genus by raising the subgenus *Leptailurus* to generic level. Thus the name appears as *Leptailurus serval* (Wozencraft, 1993). I have not seen the evidence on which this decision was based. The following applies to the Tunisian material.

Felis serval constantina Forster, 1780

Felis constantina Forster, in Buffon's Naturgesch. d. Vierfüss. Thiere, 6: 313, 1780, type from vicinity of Constantine, Algeria.

Felis serval constantina, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

F[elis]. s[erval]. constantina, Smithers, 1975.

Felis serval, Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905; Blanc, 1935.

Felis libyca constantina, Allen, 1939.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: (Blanc, 1935, unless otherwise indicated): Tunis (Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905); Aïn-Draham (Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905); La Khroumirie; Ghardimaou; Tabarka; Aïn Draham; Tamerza; Béja; Mateur; Gafour; Cap Bon.

Panthera pardus (Linnaeus, 1758). Leopard

Distribution. Leopards probably formerly had the greatest distribution of any member of the family. They occurred throughout almost all of Asia and Africa, including all of Tunisia (Fig. 3.39). Today they are exterminated from most of this range.

Biology. Leopards, most probably now extinct in Tunisia, appear to have been fairly common within the past century. Lataste (1887) reported that leopards (also known as Barbary lions) were more common than lions throughout North Africa. He reported that Algerian officials paid bounties on 1214 leopards killed in Algeria in an 11-year period including 112 in 1880; 71 in 1881; and 48 in 1882.

In 1880, Johnston photographed a leopard shot in northwestern Tunisia and wrote (1898) that they were “still to be found in the wilder parts of Northern and Western Tunisia.” Trouessart (1905) reported them as less common than the lion in North Africa and “very rare” in Tunisia. Blanc (1935) reported that two or three had been taken 10 years previously along the Algerian border near El-Feija and that he had received panthers from the live oak forest of Khroumirie, two in 1900 and one each in 1908, 1909, 1914, and 1934.

Schomber and Kock (1960) found no evidence that leopards still occurred in Tunisia even though they heard occasional reports of its existence in the forests between Bizerte and Tabarka and in the mountains near Tamerza. The only specific record they had was from near Babouch in 1900.

Taxonomy. I have followed Smithers (1975) in using the generic name *Panthera* Oken, 1816, although according to Cockrum et al. (in litt.) doubt exists under the strict interpretation of the International Rules of Zoological Nomenclature as to the availability of Oken names .

Figure 3.39. Distribution maps of the leopard, *Panthera pardus* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Panthera pardus panthera (Schreber, 1777)

Felis panthera Schreber, Säugthiere, 3: 384, 587, 1777, pl. 99, 1776, type from Algeria, based on a copy of Buffon's plate of a female from that country.

Panthera pardus panthera, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

P[anthera]. p[ardus]. panthera, Smithers, 1975.

Felis pardus panthera, Allen, 1939.

F[elis] pardus, Lataste, 1887.

Felis pardus antiquorum, Trouessart, 1905; Blanc, 1935.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: Between Feriana and Medjerda plain (Lataste, 1887); El-Feidja region (Blanc, 1935); oak forests of Khroumirie (Blanc, 1935); near Babouch, (Schomber and Kock, 1960).

Panthera leo (Linnaeus, 1758). Lion

Distribution. Lions formerly occurred from India westward through the Middle East into Africa. In Africa, they once occurred throughout the continent. In Tunisia, they were once in most of the country but more common in central and northern areas (Fig. 3.40).

Biology. Lataste (1887) speculated that lions must have been common in North Africa in the Roman Era, as evidenced by the large numbers used in circus games. By the 1880's they were rare throughout Tunisia and Algeria. He reported that in the 11 years between 1 January 1893 and 24 December 1884 a total of 202 lions were presented for bounty in Algeria (16 in 1880, 6 in 1881, and 4 in 1882).

Johnston photographed a lioness killed in northwestern Tunisia in 1880 and reported three other kills in the region in a six-week period. By the end of the nineteenth century, Johnston (1898: 351) reported that "the lion is practically extinct

Figure 3.40. Distribution maps of the lion, *Panthera leo* (Linnaeus, 1758).

in Tunisia.” Blanc (1935) made no mention of them. Ellerman and Morrison-Scott (1951) thought that the lion had been extinct in Algeria and Tunisia since about 1891 and in Morocco since the 1920’s. Schomber and Kock (1960:277) reported that the “genuine Barbary [sic] Lion is not even to be found in zoological gardens . . . the last Tunisian Lion was killed near Babouch to the south of Tabarka in 1891.”

Taxonomy. According to Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska (1991) the place of origin of the type according to Linnaeus is “Africa.” Allen (1924; see below) fixed the type locality as Algeria. The North African specimens would follow the nominative subspecies.

Panthera leo leo (Linnaeus, 1758)

Felis leo Linnaeus, Syst. Nat., 10th ed., 1:41, 1758, from “Africa,” fixed as

Constantine, Algeria (see J. A. Allen, Bull. Amer. Mus. Nat. Hist., 47: 222, 1924); Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905.

Panthera leo leo, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

Panthera leo, Smithers, 1975.

Felis leo leo, Allen, 1939.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: forests of Ghardimaou (Lataste, 1887); forests between Feriana and Medjerda (Lataste, 1887); forests between Ghardimaou and Souk-Harras (Lataste, 1887); near Babouch south of Tabarka (Schomber and Kock, 1960).

Acinonyx jubatus (Schreber, 1776). Cheetah

Distribution. Cheetahs formerly occurred in sub-desert and desert regions from India westward through the Middle East and in Africa to Morocco and Rio de

Oro and southward in eastern Africa to South Africa. They formerly occurred in most of southern Tunisia (Fig. 3.41).

Biology. Cockrum et al. (in litt.) could not obtain any evidence concerning the occurrence of cheetahs in Tunisia during their study. Lataste (1887) reported the skin of one that had been killed in the Nefzaoua, south of the Chotts and recounted hearing of one killed at Douz. He thought that they were to be found throughout the Sahara. Johnston (1898) reported that they were “occasionally met with in the extreme south of Tunisia, to the south of the salt lakes of the Jerid.” Blanc (1935) reported that 25 to 30 years earlier, he had received these animals from the region of Tatahouine and from Kebili but that by 1935 they had become extremely rare in the southern part of Tunisia. Schomber and Kock (1960: 278) indicated that the “sandy regions south of the Chott el Djerid and the desert wastes south of Fom Tatahouine were once the home of the Cheetah.” They suggested that some were still to be found in the Grand Erg Occidental and that decreases in numbers were primarily due to “the fact that the Dorcas Gazelle, its principal prey, has been totally exterminated.”

Taxonomy. Rosevear (1974) reported that there is no more than one species in *Acinonyx*. The following subspecies have been named from Northwestern Africa: *Acinonyx jubatus jubatus* (Schreber, 1776) from sub-Saharan Africa, *A. jubatus venaticus* (Griffith, 1821) from India and extending into North Africa and *A. jubatus hecki* Hilzheimer, 1821 from southern Mauritania (Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska, 1991). The population of cheetah that existed in Tunisia is followed to this name.

Acinonyx jubatus venaticus (Griffith, 1821)

Felis venatica Griffith, Vert. Anim. Carnivora, 2: 93, 1821, type from India.

Acinonyx jubatus venaticus, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

Figure 3.41. Distribution maps of the cheetah, *Acinonyx jubatus* (Schreber, 1776).

A[cinonyx]. j[ubatus]. venaticus, Smithers, 1975.

C[ynailurus]. guttatus, Lataste, 1887.

Cynailurus jubatus guttatus, Trouessart, 1905.

Cynailurus guttatus, Blanc, 1935.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: (Blanc, 1935, unless otherwise indicated): South of the Chotts (Trouessart, 1905); Nefzaoua (Lataste, 1887); Merazig [= Sidi Merzoug] (Lataste, 1887); Kebili; Tatahouine; Dehibat; Bir-Kecira [= 150 km SW Tatahouine]; Ghadames.

ORDER ARTIODACTYLA

Evidence for the presence of a wide variety of indigenous even-toed mammals in the Maghreb, and in particular, Tunisia, can be found in paleontological sites (Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska, 1991) and the records of naturalist working in the area (e.g., Johnston, 1898). However, due to overkill by humans, climatological change, disappearance and fragmentation of suitable habitats, or a combination of the above led to the decimation of several species. Efforts are now focused on re-introduction programs for artiodactyles like Scimitar oryx, addax, Barbary stag, Mhorr gazelle and others.

Three families of artiodactyles including are present in Tunisia.

Family Suidae

Pigs

This family contains 5 genera that, as natives, are distributed throughout Africa, Asia and the adjacent islands. Only one genus occurs in Tunisia.

Genus *Sus* Linnaeus, 1758

Genus *Sus* includes 4 species that occur in Eurasia. One species, *Sus scrofa*, the ancestor of the domestic pig, has been introduced in many other parts of the world including some oceanic islands.

Sus scrofa Linnaeus, 1758. Wild Boar

Distribution. In Europe, the wild boar formerly occurred from northern France, Holland and Finland southward throughout most of Europe. Now it has a greatly limited distribution as a result of man's activities. Its occurrence in Africa ranged from Morocco eastward through Egypt but is almost extinct in most of the

region. It is still present in most of the northern hilly areas, the central steppe, and southern parts of Tunisia in some of the wadis around the oases (Fig. 3.42).

Biology. Records of the presence of the animal from travelers and naturalists are listed under this section because they sometimes provide information on habits and habitats, and possible causes of extinction of the taxon.

Ansell (1971) reported that *Sus scrofa* disappeared from Egypt in 1902 and from Libya by 1954. In Tunisia, it formerly occurred throughout the wooded parts. Lataste (1887) reported wild boar as abounding throughout North Africa, wherever water and woodlands occurred. Johnston (1898) wrote that, "in 1880, a number of wild boar were shot in northwestern Tunisia during a single hunt." Blanc (1935) indicated that they were to be found in northern, but not southern, Tunisia. Schomber and Kock (1960) reported:

At the beginning of this century the Barbary wild pig in Tunisia still reached southwards as far as Chott el Djerid and Gabès. In the course of time, it has completely vanished from there, although this could not be attributed to widespread hunting, for only Europeans hunt the wild pig . . . As the Barbary wild pig has its habitat in areas of thick undergrowth within easy reach of water, just as do its European counterparts and all pigs in general, one can trace its disappearance to the increasing desiccation of southern Tunisia. (p. 278)

This recent "desiccation" has been the result of overgrazing and other land use practices and not from any decrease in rainfall (Cockrum et al., in litt.).

In recent years, numbers of wild boar are on the increase. Now, the animal is considered a serious pest in some parts of Tunisia. According to some officials in Tunisia, it comes from Algeria through the wadis of Atlas mountains in north and central Tunisia. It can be heard feeding after sunset in Feija National Park. According to Schomber and Kock (1960) wild boar favors arum tubers (*Arum*: Araceae) and they dig for them in the leaf litter. The area grazed by wild boar can

Figure 3.42. Distribution maps of the wild boar, *Sus scrofa* Linnaeus, 1758.

easily be recognized by typical digging marks and boar tracks. I photographed wild caught individuals in Tozeur and Tunis zoos.

In Aïn Draham (and the governorate of Jendouba in general), wild boar hunts are a substantial business for hotels and tour companies. Tourism hunt is regulated by the regulation of the DGF (Anon. 1995: chapter 2). Tourists pay TD 100 to secure a license (permit), and are allowed to export the meat to their countries for an extra TD 100 per kill (Anon. 1995: chapter 2: article 18).

Taxonomy. A single subspecies of the wild boar occurs in this area.

Sus scrofa barbarus Sclater, 1860

Sus scrofa var. *barbarus* Sclater, Proc. Zool. Soc. London, 1860: 443, type from North Africa. Allen, Bull. Mus. Comp. Zool., 83:464, 1939, lists this as a nomen nudum and uses Loche's *algira* as the available name. Latter authors disagreed.

Sus scrofa barbarus, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951; Corbet, 1978.

S[us]. s[crofa]. barbarus, Ansell, 1971.

Sus scrofa, Trouessart, 1905; Blanc, 1935.

Porcus scrofa, Lataste, 1887.

Sus scrofa var. *algira* Loche, Exploration Sci. de l'Algérie, Zool., Mammifer., p. 59, 1867, from Country of Beni Sliman, Algeria.

Records. Specimens examined: none. Photographed in Tozeur and Tunis zoos.

Literature reports: (Lataste, 1887 and Trouessart, 1905 unless otherwise indicated): Aïn-Draham--common; Ouchteta [near Jebel Sidi Abiod]--frequent; Oued Zesa; Oum Mezessar; Khroumirie (Blanc, 1935); Ghardimaou (Blanc, 1935); Le Kef (Blanc, 1935); Bou Chebka (Blanc, 1935); Cap bon (Blanc, 1935); Feidja (Lehmann, 1972).

Family Cervidae

Deer

This family contains 16 genera (see Grubb, 1993 for details). One genus is native to the Atlas Mountains of northwest Africa.

Genus *Cervus* Linnaeus, 1758

This genus includes about 15 species that are found in the Palearctic and Oriental regions. One species occurs in Tunisia.

Cervus elaphus Linnaeus, 1758. Red Deer

Diagnosis. Red deer in Tunisia can easily be distinguished from other artiodactyles by branching antlers in males of the species.

Distribution. This species formerly occurred throughout Europe and most of Asia as well as in North Africa from Morocco to Tunisia. Some taxonomists include North American elk in this species. These deer have been eliminated from most of their former range. Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska (1991) reported fossils from the Pleistocene and Holocene in North Africa from Morocco to Tunisia. At present, in Tunisia, it is restricted to the northwest part of the country in Kroumerie and Mogod mountains (Fig. 3.43).

Biology. In Africa, Loche (1867) reported these deer to be rare in Algeria, with only a few being present on the Tunisian border. Lataste (1887) summarized an 1848 report by Gervais on the status of the species. At that time, red deer were common near Bône, Algeria, near La Calle and near Tebessa. In each region, they were so common that their harvest furnished an export trade of some importance. Lataste also reported that Letourneux rated deer as common from Bizerte to La Calle

Figure 3.43. Distribution maps of the red deer, *Cervus elaphus* Linnaeus, 1758.

[= El Kala], as shown by antlers which were still (1870) to be found in the forest soils. However, by 1887, Lataste found red deer only in a small area northwest Tunisia, at the Algerian border and in the south, near the Libyan border. The latter was a region without trees, a fact that surprised Lataste. However he was convinced that a herd existed on the plains in the region of Douiret and saw two, one at Tozeur and one at Gafsa, that had been taken from this herd.

Johnston (1898:351) reported having photographed, in 1880, a stag that had been shot in northwestern Tunisia and that "The Barbary Stag is found in some abundance in the well-wooded mountains of the West, along the Algerian border. It is now carefully protected by the French and has begun to revive in numbers, having once been nearly extinct."

Blanc (1935) reported that he had received antlers almost every year but thought that most came from Algeria. He stated that "several years ago" the Barbary Stag was not rare in the large forest of western Tunisia along the Algerian border.

Allen (1939: 39) listed them as "local, and now rare in parts of Tunis, and Algeria." Ellerman and Morrison-Scott (1951: 368) reported: "now confined to a strip of forest country on the Algerian-Tunisian border."

Schomber and Kock (1960: 278) reported that by 1960 they were restricted to a small area in northeastern Algeria and northwestern Tunisia in the "fighting zone of the present Algerian War. This is having a catastrophical effect on the survival of the species." Apparently poaching was rampant. Lehmann (1972) reported that in 1965, as the result of a cooperative project among Tunisia, Germany and Austria, a concerted effort was made to save the species in Tunisia. A deer-proof fence was constructed around 460 hectares near Feija on the Algerian border. All the red deer that could still be found in Tunisia were rounded up and confined to the

pen. Only about 35 were found. This may have been the majority of this species left in all of North Africa. By 1971, under strict protection, the population in the pen had grown to 65 or 70.

Recent reports (Kacem et al., 1994) show that populations of this animal in enclosures (M'hèbes, Aïn Baccouche, Feija) are about 820 heads. However, the reporters believe that there is a wild population of the Barbary stag of about 2000 animals. It seems that accidental release due to wild boar damage to enclosure fences allowed escapees and the establishment of a feral population. The area is favored by red deer because of its typical maquis, cork oak (*Quercus suber*) and *Quercus fagina* plant associations.

Gestation period is ca. 8 months, fawns are born between April and June. The newborn are able to walk within hours (Kacem et al., 1994).

Taxonomy. Probably all Tunisian populations of red deer that occurred in historic times were referable to the following subspecies. However, the taxonomic status of the population reported by Lataste (1887) from southeastern Tunisia is obscure. Lataste commented "All that I can say is that the deer that I have seen living at Tozzer and Gafsa [taken from the herd mentioned] struck me with their spotted coats which resembled that of the fallow deer and of fawns, although judging from the development of their antlers, they were definitely adults."

Cervus elaphus barbarus Bennett, 1848

Cervus barbarus Bennett, in Fraser, Zool. Typica, pl. 13, 1848, type from Tunisia.

(Bennett, List Anim. Gardens Zool. Soc. London, 1833:48, nomen nudum).

Cervus elaphus barbarus, Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905; Blanc, 1935; Allen, 1939; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951; Lehmann, 1972.

C[ervus]. e[laphus]. barbarus, Ansell, 1971.

Cervus elaphus, Schomber and Kock, 1960; Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska, 1991.

Records. Specimens examined: none. Animal photographed in Feija National Park, June, 1996.

Literature reports: Near La Calle [= El Kala] (Lataste, 1887). Reports from Blanc (1935): Ghardimaou; Kef; Bou Chebka; and north of Fériana. Tunisian-Algerian northern border (mapped by Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska, 1991); near Babouch, S Tabarka (Schomber and Kock, 1961).

Family Bovidae

Cows, Sheep, Antelopes and Relatives

According to Corbet (1978), this family includes about 45 genera and 120 species. Six genera are found in North Africa, 5 of which occur in Tunisia.

Key for Family Bovidae

1. Legs thin; neck slender; horns small (less than 400 mm); tail short (less than 200 mm); preorbital fossa (depression or lacrimal pit in front of orbit) present; greatest length of skull less than 280 mm; length of upper molariform tooth row less than 85 mm; length of lower jaw less than 240 mm*Gazella*

1'. Legs not notably thin; neck thick; horns more than 400 mm; tail more than 200 mm; preorbital fossae absent (except in *Alcelaphus*); greatest length of skull more than 280 mm; length of upper molariform tooth row more than 85 mm; length of lower jaw more than 240 mm2

2(1'). Mantle of long hairs on throat and forelimbs of both sexes; distance between bases of horns about 50 mm; length of upper molariform tooth row less than 95 mm*Ammotragus*

2'. No mantle; distance between bases of horns more than 150 mm; length of upper molariform tooth row more than 95 mm3

3(2'). Size large (head and body more than 1800 mm); tail long (more than 400 mm); greatest length of skull more than 450 mm; length of mandible more than 300 mm*Alcelaphus*

3'. Size smaller; tail shorter; greatest length of skull less than 450 mm; length of mandible less than 330 mm4

4(3'). Circular mop of black hair between horns; conspicuous band of white below eyes; strong, ridged, spiraled horns; greatest length of skull less than 320 mm; hooves low, flat, broadly rounded in front*Addax*

4'. No mop of hair; no white band below eye; horns long, thin, ringed; hooves pointed in front; greatest length of skull more than 320 mm*Oryx*

Genus *Addax* Rafinesque, 1815

This genus, with a single species, appears to have been restricted to the Sahara desert and sub-desert. In ancient times, it occurred from Morocco eastward into Egypt. It is depicted in ancient Egyptian tomb frescos and may have been domesticated. It is now extinct in most of its former range including Tunisia. Those now present are recent reintroductions from European and North American zoos.

Addax nasomaculatus (Blainville, 1816). *Addax*

Diagnosis. This large bovid has corkscrew-like spiral horns in both sexes. The hooves are low, flat, and broadly rounded in front. It has the general appearance of a heavily built antelope that is about the size of a small calf (weight 70-150 kg).

Distribution. The addax originally occurred in semidesert and desert situations from Rio de Oro [= Western Sahara] eastward to Egypt but is now extinct in Egypt (since 1900 according to Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951), Tunisia and Rio de Oro and probably so in Libya (Ansell, 1971). At present, in Tunisia, a re-introduced herd is in Bou Hedma National Park (Fig. 3.44).

Biology. Lataste (1887) had no direct evidence of its occurrence at that time but reported that Mayet, in 1885, had seen a skin in Tozeur from the Chott Djerid region. It was reported as still being common in southern Algeria. Johnston (1898) wrote that the addax

is still a Tunisian animal, though it is rarely heard of north of the limits of the real sandy desert. In my recent journey into the Tunisian Sahara I saw a freshly-killed head . . . and found the horns and skins abundant and cheap as articles of purchase (p. 352).

Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska (1991) cited Hartert (1913; not seen) who reported that the addax was “not rare” in Grand Erg Oriental between Bir Beresof (near the Tunisian-Algerian border) and Ghadamès.

Blanc (1935) reported having seen horns during his first trip (in 1890) to Fom Tatahouine that had been taken near Dehibat and Bir Djenein. He thought that the species was no longer to be found in Tunisia in 1935.

Schomber and Kock (1960: 281) thought that formerly the addax occurred in the subdesert region as far north as the Chott Djerid but was then only to be found in the “dune region of the distant south,” but they had no observations to substantiate this view. Kock (pers. comm.) reported that addax probably survived in the south in Bir Kisra until 1902 and that a few were present between Dehibat and Nalut as late as 1912. Hufnagl (1972) cited reports that there were only 50 addax in all of Algeria by 1966.

It seems possible that the addax was extinct in Tunisia by 1930s. As previously mentioned, the Tunisian government recently re-introduced it into Bou

Figure 3.44. Distribution maps of the addax, *Addax nasomaculatus* (Blainville, 1816).

Hedma National Park. A group of 14 animals from captive groups in zoological gardens (4 females from Germany, 6 females and 4 males from the USA) were released in an enclosure and they seem to be doing well (Kacem et al. . 1994).

Taxonomy. Genus *Addax* is monotypic and according to Ansell (1971) and Kowlaski and Rzebik-Kowalska (1991), *Addax nasomaculatus* is also monotypic with no subspecies.

Addax nasomaculatus (Blainville, 1816)

Cerophorus (Gazella) nasomaculata Blainville, Bull. des Sci. Soc. Philomatique, Paris, p. 75, 1816, type probably from Senegambia, West Africa. Ellerman and Morrison-Scott (1951) doubt that the type came from Senegal/Gambia. *Addax nasomaculatus*, Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905; Blanc, 1935; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951; Ansell, 1971.

Addax naso-maculatus, Johnston, 1898.

Addax nasomaculatus nasomaculatus, Allen, 1939.

Records. Specimens examined: none. Reintroduced individuals were photographed in Bou Hedma National Park.

Literature reports: Dar-el-Bey at Tozzer; south Nefzaoua (in Sobria); and the Djerid (Lataste, 1887); Dehibat and Bir Djenein (Blanc, 1935); Bir Beresof [near the Tunisian-Algerian border in the Grand Erg Oriental] (mapped by Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska, 1991). The following are from Schomber and Kock (1960): Bir Keura [= Bir Ksira]; between Dehibat and Nalut [in Libya]; and Remada.

Genus *Alcelaphus* de Blainville, 1816

This genus formerly occurred from Morocco eastward through North Africa and southward in East Africa into the south African region. It is now extinct in

North Africa as well as in several other parts of its former range. Two species are recognized, only one of which occurred in Tunisia.

Alcelaphus buselaphus (Pallas, 1766). Hartebeest

Diagnosis. This animal is distinguished by a disproportionately long face and horns are that curved posteriorly and upwardly forming a U-shape when viewed from the front.

Distribution. Formerly this antelope ranged through most of North Africa from Morocco to Egypt (Fig. 3. 45). It may have survived in parts of Morocco and Algeria through the 1930s (Cabrera, 1932) and in Tunisia until the 1900s (Lavauden, 1924, not seen, cited in Kacem et al., 1994). It is now probably extinct north of the Sahara (Corbet, 1978).

Biology. As mentioned above, the hartebeest has been extinct in Tunisia for many years. At the time of the Romans it may have been common. Certainly it is a prevalent representation in Roman mosaics. Depictions of hartebeest were also found in many ancient Egyptian tombs and temples.

Lataste (1887) did not mention it. Johnston (1898) reported that it “is now quite extinct” in Tunisia, but reported that it still occurred in southern Algeria and Libya. Trouessart (1905), however, reported that it was “rare” in Tunisia. Blanc (1935) made no mention of the hartebeest. Schomber and Kock (1960) reported that the last hartebeest was killed at Bir Keura [possibly, Bir Ksira] prior to 1902 and that a few were present between Dehibat and Nalut as late as 1912. However, Kock (pers. comm. with Gharaibeh) informed me that these records are erroneous as they were taken from Bedouins who mentioned to him the presence of “Bagr el Ouash” [Arabic= wild cows] which he understood as hartebeest when it meant addax. I have seen this colloquial name referring both to addax and hartebeest in

Figure 3.45. Records of occurrence of the hartebeest, *Alcelaphus buselaphus* (Pallas, 1766).

Egypt (Osborn and Helmy, 1980). Dr. Kock believes the reference was to *Addax nasomaculatus*. Lavauden (1926) reported that this antelope was abundant until 1870 in the mountains of the south; on the Algerian border; in the Hammada; and between Bir-Aouïn and Ghadamès (Fig. 3.45).

A reintroduction of the hartebeests into Tunisia is planned and will probably involve importing animals from Senegal or Burkina Faso. Bou Hedma, Sidi Toui, and Chambi National Parks are prospective sites for this project (Kacem et al., 1994).

Taxonomy. Allen (1939) listed as a synonym of *Alcelaphus buselaphus major* (Blyth), *A. bubalis* var. *tunisianus* Gray, 1852 collected from “Tunis.” However, for the range of *A. b. major*, Allen (1939) listed Tunisia with a query.

Ansell (1971) reported that *major* possibly includes *tunisianus* but cited Ruxton and Schwarz (1929; not seen) as listing *tunisianus* under *major* with a query and seems to doubt the record from “Tunis.” *Alcelaphus buselaphus* occurring north of the Sahara has been assigned the nominate subspecies (Ansell, 1971).

Alcelaphus buselaphus buselaphus (Pallas, 1776)

Antelope buselaphus Pallas, Misc. Zool., p. 7, 1766, type probably from Morocco.

Alcelaphus buselaphus buselaphus, Allen, 1939.

Alcelaphus buselaphus, Schomber and Kock, 1960.

A[lcelaphus]. b[uselaphus]. buselaphus, Ansell, 1971.

Bubalis buselaphus, Johnston, 1898; Trouessart, 1905.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: The following sites are from Lavauden (1924; cited in Kacem et al., 1994): “mountains of the Tunisian south; on the Algerian border; in the Hammada; and between Bir-Aouïn and Ghadamès.”

Genus *Oryx* de Blainville, 1816

This genus, with three species, formerly occurred from the Arabian peninsula westward into Africa. There it occurred through much of the continent. Only a single species occurred in Tunisia until it was exterminated early this century. Individuals found in Tunisia at present are the result of reintroductions.

Oryx dammah Cretzschmar, 1826

Scimitar-horned Oryx

Diagnosis. This large, heavy antelope stands about 1200 mm high at the shoulders and has a total length of about 2200 mm of which the busy tail makes up about 450 mm. Long, recurved, saber-shaped horns reach length of up to 1000 mm and occur in both sexes.

Distribution. This species formerly occurred in semidesert areas both north and south of the Sahara from Rio de Oro and Morocco eastward to Egypt. It is probably now extinct north of the Sahara (Ansell, 1971) (Fig. 3.46).

Lataste (1887) made no mention of this species. Johnston (1898) wrote "In the Tunisian Sahara the Arabs report the existence of a true Oryx--seemingly *Oryx leucoryx*. A small specimen of the Antelope (immature) is to be seen --stuffed-- in the Bey's Natural History Collection at the Marsa near Tunis."

Trouessart (1905) thought that oryx in North Africa was not documented by any specimens. Blanc (1935) did not mention it. Schomber and Kock (1960: 281) reported that it "disappeared from Tunisia decades ago" and that (*op cit.* : 146) "this large antelope of the Sahara desert disappeared from North Africa so long ago that only a very few Europeans ever encountered it. Arabs were still reporting its existence in the Tunisian Sahara at the end of the 19th century and, according to

Figure 3.46. Records of occurrence of the scimitar-horned oryx, *Oryx dammah* Cretzschmar, 1826.

F. Sommer, the last white oryx in Tunisia was killed prior to 1906.” Kacem et al. (1994) cite Lavauden (1924; not seen) as mentioning the last 2 or 3 kills by 1912.

Biology. Reintroduction into Tunisia was begun in 1985 when 5 males and 5 females were imported from the London Zoo. The animals seem to be adapting well and their numbers are on the increase. Future reintroductions into southern Tunisia from this herd are planned (Kacem et al., 1994).

Taxonomy. This is a monotypic species according to Ellerman and Morrison-Scott (1951). Ansell (1971) did not list any subspecies.

Oryx dammah (Cretzschmar, 1826)

Antilope dammah Cretzschmar, Atlas zu Rüppell's Reise im Nördl. Afrika,

Säugeth., p. 22, 1826, probably from Kordofan [= Haraza, eastern Sudan].

Oryx dammah, Ansell, 1971.

Oryx tao, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951; Schomber and Kock, 1960

Aegoryx algazel dammah, Allen, 1939.

Records. Specimens examined: none. Reintroduced individuals were observed and photographed in Bou Hedma National Park.

Literature reports: “Tunisian Sahara” (Schomber and Kock, 1960).

Genus *Gazella* de Blainville, 1816

Gazelles formerly occurred in the desert and subdesert regions of Asia and North Africa from Chinese Turkestan westward to Morocco. In East Africa, this range extended as far south as Tanzania. Some ten or twelve different species are recognized. The combination of large individual and geographic variations and small sample sizes have resulted in great difficulties for taxonomists to establish relationships. Three species occur or have occurred in Tunisia. A fourth, *Gazella*

dama may have reached southern Tunisia but no records from exist. I treat this species as introduced (see page 312).

Key for Genus *Gazella*

1. Size larger (head and body more than 1250 mm); height at shoulders more than 900 mm; tail short (less than 400 mm); no dark band on flanks; large area around base of tail, anus, much of legs, flanks and face white; horns deeply ringed, lyrate, and points directed forward; greatest length of skull more than 210; small preorbital fossa*Gazella dama*

1'. Size smaller (head and body less than 1250 mm); height at shoulders less than 900 mm; tail longer (more than 400 mm); band on flanks; restricted white area around anus does not enclose brown base of tail; skull of adult less than 220 mm; larger preorbital fossa2

2(1'). Fur thick and grayish brown; reddish brown facial markings; dark nasal spot; dark eye strip; large preorbital fossa; greatest length of skull more than 190 mm; length of upper molariform teeth more than 60 mm; length of mandible more than 150 mm*Gazella cuvieri*

2'. Fur not so thick nor so brownish; greatest length of skull less than 190 mm; length of upper molariform teeth less than 60 mm; length of mandible less than 150 mm3

3(2'). About 700 mm high at shoulder; color pale; line on flanks and from eye to nostril pale; horns long; small preorbital fossa*Gazella leptoceros*

3'. About 600 mm high at shoulder; color darker (pale sandy fawn with reddish band on lower flank; tail and face with dark markings; rump patch and venter are white); small dark line from eye to nostril; horns shorter (to 380 mm); large preorbital fossa*Gazella dorcas*

Gazella dorcas (Linnaeus, 1758). Dorcas gazelle

Diagnosis. This small gazelle, about 600 mm at the shoulder; weighs, 12 to 15 kg in free-living individuals. Large adults in captivity may reach 25 kg. The horns, larger in the males than the females, may reach 380 mm.

Distribution. Most widely distributed of all species of *Gazella*. Dorcas gazelles formerly occurred throughout northern Africa south of Atlas Mountains, southward to Mauritania and eastward to coastal Somalia. It also occurred in the Sinai and much of the Arabian Peninsula. In Tunisia, it was in the central and southern parts (Fig. 3.47).

Lataste (1887) reported that Dorcas gazelles as common he went in southern Tunisia and that, at that time, in Algeria a live young gazelle cost 75 centimes to 2 francs and that all of the military posts in the region had a troupe of gazelles. By 1935 Blanc (1935) reported that Dorcas gazelles were becoming rare in most of Tunisia. Schomber and Kock (1960: 281) reported that it was only rarely seen in central Tunisia but thought it more common south of the Chott Djerid and on the western plains near the Algerian border. They reported that "in Erg el Mitt, herds of from 100 to 150 are said to exist today." Allen (1939) reported this gazelle as occurring in the "mountainous districts of Morocco, Algeria and Tunisia."

Biology. Dorcas gazelles have been used as a meat source throughout their range for generations. However, excessive hunting pressure and heavy grazing by domestic animals have resulted in the modern low populations with restricted distributions. Game laws had been enacted in an effort to restore populations to a level that hunting might again be permitted.

I found no information concerning the biology of this species in Tunisia. However, data are available from other areas. Gestation period is about 6 months. Calving in Chad and Air (Niger) was in late October to December. Females usually

Figure 3.47. Distribution maps of the Dorcas gazelle, *Gazella dorcas* (Linnaeus, 1758). A, *G. d. dorcas* (Linnaeus, 1758); B, *G. d. neglecta* Lavauden, 1926.

give birth to single fawn; however, twins have recorded in Algerian populations. Dams have their first fawn when they are 2 years old, but captive animals are known to mature much earlier (Yom-Tov et al., 1995).

Taxonomy. Gentry (1971) thought that the great individual and local variations of Dorcas gazelles obscure their relationships. Published reports provided (and usually conflicting) interpretations as to relationships in differing Sahara population of *Gazella dorcas*. Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska (1991) provided a good summary for these studies in North Africa and Algeria in particular. Lavauden (1926) listed two subspecies in the region based on differences in the shape of horns (*G. dorcas neglecta* with inward sharply-curved horns and *G. d. dorcas* with regularly-curved horns) and other characters. A recent study (Groves, 1981) listed one subspecies from Libya and Tunisia, *Gazella dorcas dorcas* (Linnaeus, 1758), from Douz, Gabès, and “Tunis.” From reading the pertinent literature, it seems that there are two morphs in Tunisia: a bright phase with well-marked flank bands (extending from the north central Tunisia eastward to Libya, Chad, and Egypt, and a pale phase that does not show well-marked flank bands. The two do not occur in the same area. *Gazella dorcas neglecta* is distributed in the Plateaus of central and western Sahara reaching into the Erg in southern Tunisia.

Alados (1987) provided a statistical analysis for cranial variation within *Gazella dorcas* using principal component method. He also provided cladistical treatment for the relationship among different subspecies. Dorcas gazelle populations from the north, center, and southeastern Sahara into Sudan were similar to each other and all clustered in a group Alados classified as *G. d. dorcas*. The relatedness among populations that are separated by vast distances was explained by the occurrence of three corridors for faunal dispersal across the Sahara during the Pleistocene. The

northern region is connected to the center and southeastern regions by one of these corridors. The following names are available for the Tunisian material.

Gazella dorcas dorcas (Linnaeus, 1758)

Capra dorcas Linnaeus, Syst. Nat., 10th ed., 1: 69, 1758, type from lower Egypt according to Blaine (see Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951: 391).

G[azella]. dorcas, Lataste, 1887.

Gazella dorcas, Johnston, 1898; Trouessart, 1905; Blanc, 1935.

Gazella dorcas dorcas, Lavauden, 1926; Allen, 1939; Groves, 1981; Alados, 1987.

G[azella]. d[orcas]. dorcas, Gentry, 1975.

Gazella kevella, Lataste, 1887 (probably Tunisia).

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: Kairouan (Blanc, 1935); Kasserine, (Blanc, 1935); Feriana (Blanc, 1935); Redeyef (Blanc, 1935); Tamerza (Blanc, 1935); Metlaoui (Blanc, 1935); Maknassy (Lavauden, 1926; Blanc, 1935); Gafsa (Lataste, 1887; Blanc, 1935; Trouessart, 1905); Tozeur (Blanc, 1935); near Douz (Schomber and Kock, 1960; Groves, 1981); Ghomrassen (Lataste, 1887); Nefzaoua (Lataste, 1887); Blad-el-Djerid (Lataste, 1887); Plain of Arad (Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905); Tatahouine (Blanc, 1935); mountains of Matmata (Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905); Médénine (Blanc, 1935); Ben-Gardane (Blanc, 1935); Gabès (Groves, 1981); "Tunis" (Groves, 1981).

Gazella dorcas neglecta Lavauden, 1926

Gazella dorcas neglecta Lavauden, Bull. Soc. Nat. Hist. Arfrique du Nord, 17: 16, 1926, type from Plateau de Tadmeit, central Sahara, Algeria; Allen, 1939; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

Gazella dorcas osiris, Groves, 1969; Corbet, 1978.

G[azella]. d[orcas]. neglecta, Gentry, 1971.

Records.

Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: Plains S Oued Abdallah (Schomber and Kock, 1960); Erg el Mitt (Schomber and Kock, 1960); “Sud tunisien” (Lavauden, 1926).

Gazella leptoceros (F. Cuvier, 1842)

Slender-horned Gazelle

Diagnosis. This medium-sized, extremely pale gazelle is sometimes called the sand gazelle. It stands about 700 mm high at the shoulders and horns that are notably slender, almost straight--with only a slight posterior curving. Adults weigh as much as 27 kg.

Distribution. This gazelle formerly occurred in the Sahara from Algeria eastward to Egypt and southward to northern Chad and Arabia. Many years ago it was recorded from the extreme south of Tunisia (Fig. 3.48). Lataste (1887) made no mention of this species. Johnston (1898) reported that he had observed it in Tunisia. Trouessart (1905) without indication of specimens or localities, reported it of the country. Schomber and Kock (1960) reported it as present in the region south of Douz southward to Fort Saint.

During their presence in Tunisia, Cockrum and co-workers (in litt.) found no evidence of the slender-horned gazelle in Tunisia.

Taxonomy. I follow Gentry (1971: 89) in his suggestion that there is not enough “difference between the ‘subspecies’ to justify the use of trinomial names” in this species.

Figure 3.48. Distribution maps of the sand gazelle, *Gazella leptoceros* (F. Cuvier, 1842).

Gazella leptoceros (F. Cuvier, 1842)

Antilope leptoceros F. Cuvier, in Geoffroy and Cuvier, Nat. Hist. Mamm., 4:72, 1842, type from “Sennaar” (but probably desert between Giza and Wadi Natron, Egypt--see Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951: 393).

Gazella leptoceros, Johnston, 1898; Trouessart, 1905; Blanc, 1935; Gentry, 1971.

Gazella leptoceros leptoceros, Allen, 1939.

Gazella leptoceros loderi, Schomber and Kock, 1960.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: “extends into Tunisia” (Trouessart, 1905); Déhibat (Blanc, 1935); South of Douz; Bir Aouïn region; 100 km S Dehibat; and “along track to Fort Saint” (Schomber and Kock, 1960).

Gazella cuvieri (Ogilby, 1841). Mountain Gazelle

Diagnosis. Also known as the Idmi (Arabic: Edm) gazelle, this species is the largest of the North African gazelles. The pelage is of the typical gazelle pattern but the dorsal colors are darker. Since the venter and rump patch are white, the contrast is even more striking.

Distribution. This gazelle formerly occurred in the Atlas and Anti-Atlas mountains and adjacent hills and high plateaus to the south and east, including much of northern and central Tunisia (Fig. 3.49).

Lataste (1887) had no records but thought that this species must occur in Tunisia. Johnston (1898) reported seeing it and having seen one killed during a hunt in 1880 in the northwestern part of the country. Blanc (1935) reported it from the high mountains and adjacent desert edge where populations had diminished but not to the point that he would consider it as rare.

Figure 3.49. Distribution maps of the Emdi gazelle, *Gazella curvieri* (Ogilby, 1841).

Schomber and Kock (1960) reported that the former wide distribution had been restricted to a few populations between Fériana and Thala. Lehmann (1972) reported 30 individuals from Djebel Kechem el Kalb near Kasserine. During their studies, Cockrum et al. (in litt.) saw no individuals.

Biology. Schomber and Kock (1961) reported that the species lives in montane habitats in Tunisia and that this might allow it to survive. In Algeria, it inhabits the mountain forests of pine (*Pinus halepensis*) and thicket of oak. It is also reported where there is esparto grass (*Stipa tenacissima*) (Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska, 1991).

This gazelle lives in small herds of 3-5 (usually one male and few females) but solitary individuals and pairs have been observed. The rut takes place in winter and 1-2 young are born in the summer (Gentry, 1971; Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska, 1991).

Taxonomy. I follow Gentry (1971) who maintained that the Emdi gazelle is a species distinct from the so-called mountain gazelle, *Gazella gazella*. The latter was apparently restricted to the Middle East and never occurred in Africa.

Gazella cuvieri (Ogilby, 1841)

[*Antelope*] *cuvieri* Ogilby, Proc. Zool. Soc. London for 1840, p. 35, 1841, type from Mogador, Morocco.

Gazella cuvieri, Johnston, 1898; Trouessart, 1905; Blanc, 1935; Allen, 1939.

Gentry, 1971.

Gazella gazella cuvieri, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951; Schomber and Kock, 1960; Lehmann, 1972.

G[azella]. kevella, Lataste, 1887.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: Blanc, 1935, unless otherwise indicated). Gafour; Le Kef; Thala, TébourSouk, El-Aouane, near Kairouan; Thélepte; Kasserine; Hadjeb-el-Aïoun; Bou Chebka; Djebel Reças; Haut-Mornag; Djebel Chambi, 7 miles from Kasserine (Schomber and Kock, 1960); between Feriana and Thala (Schomber and Kock, 1960); Djebel Kechem el Kalb near Kasserine (Lehmann, 1972); Djebel Bou-Kormine; Djebel Tebaga (Lavauden, 1926).

Genus *Ammotragus* Linnaeus 1758

Ammotragus Blyth, 1840 is given a generic status by some authorities (Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951; Corbet and Hill, 1991; Grubb, 1993) while others argue that it is a subgenus of *Capra* Linnaeus, 1758 (Corbet, 1978; Ansell, 1971). I follow Grubb (1993) the most recent review, and use the name *Ammotragus lervia*. This will hopefully minimize confusion in the literature.

Ammotragus lervia (Pallas, 1777). Barbary Goat

Diagnosis. This species, which has many sheep-like features, has been called the Barbary sheep and Audad as well as the Barbary goat. It is sandy colored above and lighter below. Large adult males reach shoulder heights of about 1000 mm, 1850 mm in total length and weights in excess of 130 kg.

Distribution. These goats formerly occurred throughout central and southern Tunisia but are now restricted to remote regions (Fig. 3.50).

Biology. Lataste (1887) reported them from several localities in the south. Johnston (1898) found them to be common in the mountains of southern Tunisia. Blanc (1935) reported them as present in the higher mountains of central and southern Tunisia. He found them occasionally in the market at Gafsa where the

Figure 3.50. Distribution maps of the aoudad, *Ammotragus lervia* (Pallas, 1777).
 A, *A. l. lervia* (Pallas, 1777); B, *A. l. fassini* (Lepri, 1930)

meat was sold, often as beef or mutton. By that 1935 the Barbary goats were becoming rare and their hunting was strictly prohibited by the government.

Schomber and Kock (1960) reported that the populations north of the Chott Djerid were almost extinct. They thought the species to be more abundant south of the Chott, because of less hunting, and they probably had a better chance of survival. Gray and Simpson (1980) provided a detailed review of different aspects of biology of the Barbary goat over its wide range.

Taxonomy. Two subspecies are present in Tunisia as follows.

Ammotragus lervia lervia (Pallas, 1777)

Antilope lervia Pallas, Spicil. zool., 12: 12, 1777, type from “Mauritania” but restricted by Harper (1940: 327) to Oran, Algeria (see Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951: 409).

Ammotragus lervia lervia, Allen, 1939; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

C[apra]. l[ervia]. lervia, Ansell, 1971.

Ammotragus lervia, Trouessart, 1905; Blanc, 1935; Schomber and Kock, 1960; Corbet and Hill, 1980.

Aires tragelaphus, Lataste, 1887.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: mountains of Matmata (Lataste, 1887); Ghomrassen (Lataste, 1887); Nefzaoua (Lataste, 1887); Tozzer (Blad-el-Djerid) (Lataste, 1887); Djebel el Guettar (Blanc, 1935); southeast of Gafsa (Blanc, 1935); Djebel Ain Tfel [not mapped] (Blanc, 1935); mountains of Kasserine (Blanc, 1935); region of Redeyef (Blanc, 1935); Métlaoui (Blanc, 1935); Djebel bou Hedna, at Foug el Khanga near Tamerza (Schomber and Kock, 1960); mountains north of Chott Fedjady (Schomber and Kock, 1960).

Ammotragus lervia fassini (Lepri, 1930)

Ammotragus lervia fassini Lepri, Att. Pont. Accad. Sci. Nuovi Lincei, Roma, 83: 271, 1930, type from Garian, Libya; Allen, 1939; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1939.

C[apra]. l[ervia]. fassini, Ansell, 1971.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: Djebel Kambout, 10 km S Remada (Schomber and Kock, 1960); Djebel Segdel, S Remada (Schomber and Kock, 1960); Merbah Safsaf [not mapped] (Schomber and Kock, 1960); between Remada and Bordj Bourguiba (Schomber and Kock, 1960).

ORDER RODENTIA

Five families of rodents known to occur in Tunisia.

Key for Order Rodentia

1. Head and body covered with elongate circular spines; size large, length of head and body more than 500 mm; greatest length of skull more than 100 mm
.....Hystriidae
- 1'. Pelage of soft fur or short flattened spines; size smaller, length of head and body less than 500 mm; greatest length of skull less than 100 mm2
- 2(1'). Extreme saltatorial modifications, hind feet and legs greatly elongated, fore feet and legs reduced, tail elongated; skull with auditory bullae extremely enlarged; zygomatic arch sharply angledDipodidae
- 2'. No or few saltatorial modifications; skull with auditory bullae various but never extremely enlarged; zygomatic never sharply angled3
- 3(2'). Guinea pig-like appearance; digits of hind foot with fringe of stiff bristles; infraorbital canal larger than the foramen magnum
.....Ctenodactylidae
- 3'. Shape not guinea pig-like; no fringe of bristles on digits of hind foot; infraorbital canal smaller than the foramen magnum4
- 4(3'). Tail bushy, with long, dense hairs throughout its length; four lower cheek teeth on each sideMyoxidae
- 4'. Tail not bushy (terminal tuft often present); three lower cheek teeth on each sideMuridae

Family Dipodidae

Jumping Mice and Rats

This family contains the most highly specialized saltatorial rodents. Hindlimbs are elongated and animals move by jumps in the form of leaps that are kangaroo like. The family contains 10 genera and 27 species that are distributed in North Africa, Arabia, Turkey east to northeast China deserts.

Only a single genus is represents this family in Tunisia.

Genus *Jaculus* Erxleben, 1777

Four species are found in this genus. They are found in North Africa south into Somalia, the Middle East eastward into western Pakistan and north into Turkmenistan and central Uzbekistan (eastern Caspian Sea area).

There is disagreement as to the number of jerboas occurring in Tunisia. The larger species (*Jaculus orientalis*) has been collected from many parts of north and central Tunisia. A smaller jerboa also occur in the central and southern parts of Tunisia, *Jaculus jaculus*. Ranck (1968) divided *Jaculus jaculus* in Libya into two species: *Jaculus jaculus* and *Jaculus deserti*. Some authorities have included all the smaller ones in a single species *Jaculus jaculus* (Corbet, 1978; Harrison, 1978).

Key for Genus *Jaculus*

1. Size large; weight more than 100 g; hind foot more than 70 mm; total length more than 340 mm; greatest length of skull more than 36 mm; glans has two long spiny processes*Jaculus orientalis*
- 1'. Size smaller. weight less than 90 g; hind foot less than 70; total length less than 340 mm; greatest length of skull less than 36 mm; glans lacks spiny processes; mastoid portion of tympanic bullae more inflated *Jaculus jaculus*

Jaculus jaculus (Linnaeus, 1758). Lesser Egyptian

Jerboa

Diagnosis. The main characters that distinguish *Jaculus jaculus* from *Jaculus orientalis* is the smaller size and the absence of two prominent spines on the glans.

Distribution. As generally reported in the recent literature, this jerboa ranges from the Atlantic eastward through the Sahara into the Arabian Peninsula (Corbet, 1978; Osborn and Helmy, 1980; Honacki et al., 1982). However, a distinct possibility exists that two sympatric species occur in part of the area. Fig. 3.51 shows the distribution of the species in Tunisia and North Africa.

Biology. One *Jaculus jaculus* female was found lactating in mid February, one in mid January, and one in late May. One female was found with a swollen vagina in late March. Males had enlarged scrotal testes in January, March, and May. The highest measurements of testes length X width were attained in February with an average for 3 males (that all had scrotal testes) of 13 X 5.5 mm. Average for March (4 males, 2 of which had inguinal testes) was 12.25 X 6.6 mm. Average in May (5 males, 2 of which had inguinal testes) was 11.6 X 6.6 mm.

Specimens of *Jaculus jaculus* I kept did not survive well in lab cages. They became thin and weak. When the temperatures increased, they seem to go into estivation.

Taxonomy. Material from Tunisia, at least, appears to be assignable to two distinct groups, based on color and other characters. One group has pale orangish dorsum with roots of hair gray mixed with white while the other has dark dorsum (or generally suffused with dark hairs) and roots of hair gray. The angular process on the mandible is pierced by a single foramen versus two foramina in the second group. Other characters the distinguish the two groups are summarized in Table (3.2).

Figure 3.51. Distribution maps of the lesser Egyptian jerboa, *Jaculus jaculus* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Table 3.2 . List of features that separate two groups of *Jaculus jaculus*.
The terms “light” and “dark” are used to distinguish the two.

Feature	dark	light
Hind foot sole hair	dark brown to black	white
Longest vibrissae	black, some with white tips	white
Mandible angular	2 foramina (22 out of 26)	1 foramen (27 out of 31)
Habitat	pebble/ hard clay	sand dunes/ soft clay
Karyotype: 2N(FN)	Not available from Tunisian material. 48(92) from Saudi Arabia (Al Saleh and Khan, 1984)	

Conseil (1909) applies the name *Jaculus hirtipes* (Lichtenstein, 1823) to “*jaculus*” and *Jaculus darricarrei* (Lataste, 1883) to “*deserti*.” He emphasized that “*hirtipes*” had vibrissae that are entirely white, white hairs on the soles of the feet and a mandible pierced by a single foramen. Blanc (1935) recognized *Jaculus orientalis*, *Jaculus jaculus*, and, from the “south but not the extreme south” [southern Tunisia], *Jaculus daricarreri*. Concerning the last species he speculated “is it not possibly a ‘very distant cross’ between the two preceding species.” Petter (1961) reported a grayish form with partially pigmented hairs on the sole of the feet living on pebbly soils at Beni Abbès, Algeria.

Bernard (1969) found jerboas in the depression that extends from the base of Djebel Bou Hedma, to be the size of *Jaculus jaculus*, but with the pelage, especially the sole of the foot, like that of *Jaculus orientalis*. He cited Blanc’s speculation concerning hybrids but reported that a study of the material from Djebel Bou Hedma showed the penis to be similar to that of *Jaculus jaculus*, and unlike *Jaculus orientalis*. He also cited Petter’s report of a dark-footed form at Beni Abbès. Some

of Bernard's specimens had "partially pigmented" soles but other had the soles "plainly black."

Ranck (1968) recognized the two groups as distinct species, based on the characters listed in Table 3.1. He recognized 4 Libyan subspecies of *Jaculus deserti*, and 5 Libyan subspecies of *Jaculus jaculus*.

Corbet (1978) summarized Ranck's position but concluded that Harrison's (1972) conclusion that such a separation was not evident in Arabia, and Ranck's maps showing only one case of sympatry (and only one specimen of each from this site--near the Libyan coast), helped influence Corbet to conclude that the two are conspecific. Furthermore, in Egypt and Arabia, traits of color and mandibular foramina were "quite uncorrelated."

When Cockrum (in litt.) examined the type specimens of the *deserti/jaculus* group in the British Museum and in the United States National Museum, the color (dorsum, sides and sole of hind feet) and the number of mandibular foramina do not always coincide. In a few topotypes, the left ramus of the mandible differs from the right ramus as to the number of foramina. In the Tunisian material at TTU, a small group had a difference between left and right rami. Also few specimens (about 15%) showed lack of correlation between pelage color and number of foramina but the majority had one foramen on both angular processes correlating with pale-orange color. Based on the apparent difference in pelage, I am of the opinion that there are two different populations of *Jaculus jaculus* but further studies involving molecular techniques may well prove that they are two separate subspecies. For the time being, I assign the Tunisian material to the following.

Jaculus jaculus jaculus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Mus jaculus Linnaeus, Syst. Nat., 10th ed., 1:62, 1758, type from Giza, Egypt;

"in Arabia, Calmukia."

Jaculus jaculus jaculus, Allen, 1939; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

Jaculus jaculus, Bernard, 1969; Vesmanis, 1984b (in part); Wassilieff, 1932.

Dipus hirtipes, Lataste, 1887.

Jaculus hirtipes, Conseil, 1909.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 57, distributed as follows: 6 km SW Tozeur, slope above Chott Djerid, 2; 6 km N Tozeur on GP 3, 1; 3 km N Tozeur on GP 3, 5; ca. 10 km E Nefta, 2; IBP site, 31 km SE Médénine on GP 1. 9; 9 km NW Redeyef on MC 201 in river valley, 2; 5 km N Douz, 4; 39 km NE Ft. Saint (Derder), 1; 16 km S Médénine on GP 19, 1 km E highway, 1; Well 39 km NE Fort Saint on pipeline between markers km 300 and km 310, 2; Mechiguig, 2; 40 km NW Gabès on GP 15 (kept in captivity), 1; 29.5 km SE Médénine on GP 1, 1; 108 km S Tatahouine on GP 19, 34 km SW highway on rd to El Borma, 1; El Borma, ca. 200 km airline SSW Tatahouine, 1; Oued Abdallah, 110 km S Tatahouine on GP 19, 1; 20 km NNE Tozeur near oued, 2; El Hamma, 9 km N. Tozeur, 1; 2 km E. Kriz on Chott Djerid, 17 km NE Tozeur, 1; 12 km S Gabès on MC 107, W highway, 1; Aïn el Ouchika, 2.5 km NE Tamerza, slope above oued, 2; 10 km S Gabès, 1; 15 km S Tatahouine on GP 19, E highway, 4; 10 km W Gafsa on MC 201, 2; Oued Abdallah, 110 km S Tatahouine on GP 19, 1.

Literature reports: (Vesmanis, 1984b): Tozem [= Tozeur] (Lataste, 1885; Lataste, 1887; Vesmanis, 1984b), Tozeur (Trouessart, 1905; Wassilieff, 1932; Bernard, 1969; Bernard, 1970; Vesmanis, 1984b); Nefta (Wassilieff, 1932; Wandeler, 1965; Vesmanis, 1984b); El Rhitan (Wandeler, 1965; Vesmanis, 1984b); Djebel Bou Hedma (Bernard, 1969; Bernard, 1970; Vesmanis, 1984b); Menzel Hédi Chaker (Bernard, 1969; Bernard, 1970; Vesmanis, 1984b); Gabès (Bernard, 1969; Bernard, 1970; Vesmanis, 1984b); 15 km W Gabès (Vesmanis, 1984b); 3 km N Tadjerouine (Vesmanis, 1984b); Thala (Vesmanis, 1984b); Zarzis

(Bernard, 1969; Bernard, 1970; Vesmanis, 1984b); Ben Gardane (Bernard, 1969; Bernard, 1970; Vesmanis, 1984b); SW of Kasserine (Lehmann, 1972; Vesmanis, 1984b); 23 km S Djorf (Vesmanis, 1984b); Fériana (Vesmanis, 1984b); Redeyef (13 specimens at MNHN; collected by Choumowitch and reported by Vesmanis, 1984b); Djebel Orbata (BM; collected by W. P. Lowe and reported by Vesmanis, 1984b); El Hamma du Djerid (Vesmanis, 1984b); 21 km S Fériana (Vesmanis, 1984b); Djeneien (Wassilieff, 1932; Vesmanis, 1984b); Bir Pister (Wassilieff, 1932; Vesmanis, 1984b); Fort Saint (Wassilieff, 1932; Vesmanis, 1984b); Djerid (Lataste, 1885; Lataste, 1887; Vesmanis, 1984b); Oued Mtaleghmine near Chott Fedjej [= Fedjadj] (Lataste, 1885; Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905; Vesmanis, 1984b); S Djebel Dahir [= Tebaga] (Matschie, 1889; Vesmanis, 1984b); between Kebili and Douz (Matschie, 1889; Vesmanis, 1984b); Sidi Aïch near Gafsa (Matschie, 1889; Vesmanis, 1984b); Gafsa (Chaignon, 1904; Wassilieff, 1932; Bodemeyer, 1933; Blanc, 1935; Vesmanis, 1984b); Tatahouine (BM; collected by Blanc and reported by Vesmanis, 1984b); Tatahouine (Blanc, 1935; Vesmanis, 1984b); Djerba (Blanc, 1935; Vesmanis, 1984b); Metlaoui (Blanc, 1935; Vesmanis, 1984b); Tozzer (Lataste, 1887); Oued Metaleghmin (Lataste, 1887); Chotts (Lataste, 1887)

The two groups appear to occur sympatrically in southern Tunisia, although they occur in different microhabitats (pebbly hammada vs. sandy). Published records are for *Jaculus jaculus* in general, and no specific information on habitats are included. Detailed information on different aspects of the biology and ecology of each population to show if they do occupy different habitats and utilize different resources.

Jaculus orientalis Erxleben, 1777

Greater Egyptian Jerboa

Diagnosis. This jerboa is distinguished from the previous species by its large size, long tail and a glans with two spines.

Distribution. In North Africa, this species occurs north of the Sahara from Morocco eastward through Egypt. In Tunisia, it is restricted to the northern parts of the country (Fig. 3.52).

Biology. Apparently no food is stored by this rodent and seasonal inactivity includes, in cold weather, almost hibernation-like reactions. Food apparently is made up mainly of soft, moist materials such as plant stems, roots, bulbs and tubers as well as various grubs and insects. I have kept specimens (June, 1996) in a cage for about 3 weeks before I sacrificed them. They seem to adapt well to the cage and would feed on the barley and wheat that was made available to them. They were docile and did not attempt to bite but when I handled them by their hind feet to examine the number of claws and color of foot pad, they kicked and caused cuts with their claws. On a couple of occasions, when the temperature got high in the closed vehicle, they went into deep estivation. On one occasion, I mistakenly thought they were dead.

Diploid number is 48 and FN is 90. G-banding of the chromosomal complement for this species is provided herein for the first time (Fig. 3.53). Al Saleh and Khan (1984) reported a diploid number of 48 and FN of 92 for *J. jaculus* from Saudi Arabia.

Taxonomy. Details of taxonomic relations remain to be worked out. As discussed in the account of *Jaculus jaculus*, some earlier authors thought that hybridization occurred between the two species (*Jaculus jaculus* and *Jaculus orientalis*) and Conseil (1909) and others thought that two species were present in

Figure 3.52. Distribution maps of the greater Egyptian jerboa, *Jaculus orientalis* Erxleben, 1777.

Figure 3.53. G-banded chromosomal complement for *Jaculus orientalis* Erxleben, 1777.

“*orientalis*” in Tunisia. They were reputed to greatly resemble each other with one being slightly larger, darker, and having black hairs on the hind feet. I refer all Tunisian material to a single subspecies, as follows:

Jaculus orientalis mauritanicus (Duvernoy, 1841)

Dipus mauritanicus Duvernoy, L’Institut, 9: 400, 1841, type from Oran, Algeria.

Jaculus orientalis mauritanicus, Ellerman, 1940.

Dipus gerboa, Chaignon, 1904.

Jaculus orientalis orientalis, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

Jaculus orientalis, Conseil, 1909; Wassilieff, 1932; Blanc, 1935; Bernard and Gannoun, 1965; Bernard, 1969; Bernard, 1970; Vesmanis, 1984a+b

Dipus aegypticus, Duvernoy and Lereboullet, 1840; Lataste, 1887.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 10, distributed as follows: Aïn Er Rahma, 85 km S Tunis on GP1, 2 km W highway, 1; 4 km S Gabès on MC 107, 1; 10 km S Gabès near MC 107, 2; 12 km S Gabès near MC 107, W of highway, 2; jct. MC 201 and 122, ca. 33 km W Gafsa, 1; 33 km NE Sbeitla on GP3, 1; 12 km N Sbeitla on MC 71, 1; 11 km N Souassi on MC 96, 80 km NNW Sfax, 1; 15 km S Tatahouine on GP 19, E of highway, 1; Gar’at El Mekky, Gabès governorate, 2; El Nasr artificial forest, Bou Hajla, Kairouan governorate, 1.

Literature reports: Djebel Tamesmida between Fériana and Tébessa (Lataste, 1885; Lataste, 1887; Vesmanis, 1984b); Seggi (Matschie, 1889; Vesmanis, 1984b); Gafsa (Matschie, 1889; Vesmanis, 1984b); Medjerda-Tal (Chaignon, 1904; Vesmanis, 1984b); Bir M’Cherga (Chaignon, 1904; Vesmanis, 1984b); near Medjez El Bab (Chaignon, 1904; Bernard, 1969; Vesmanis, 1984b); Tozeur (Trouessart, 1905; Vesmanis, 1984b); Oued Mtaleghmine near Chott Fedjej (Trouessart, 1905; Vesmanis, 1984b); Cap Bon (Wassilieff, 1932; Bernard, 1969; Vesmanis, 1984b); region of Bizerte (Wassilieff, 1932; Bernard, 1969; Vesmanis,

1984b); Kairouan (Wassilieff, 1932 reported from Bede, as did Bernard, 1969; Vesmanis, 1984b); S Hammamet [as *Jaculus* sp.] (Harrison, 1967; Vesmanis, 1984b); near Gabès (Bernard, 1969; Vesmanis, 1984b); Gabès (Bernard, 1969; Vesmanis, 1984b); Le Kef (Bernard, 1969; Vesmanis, 1984b); Maktar (Bernard, 1969; Vesmanis, 1984b); 10 km S Maktar (Vesmanis, 1984b); Menzel H. Chaker (Bernard, 1969); Fériana (Vesmanis, 1984b); 30 km SW Sfax (Vesmanis, 1984b); 35 km N Sbeitla (Vesmanis, 1984b); Hadjeb Abd el Djebar, Djebel Mrhila, N Sbeitla (Vesmanis, 1984b); 7 km NW Gafsa (Vesmanis, 1984b); road Sfax-Sbeitla, 65 km from Sbeitla, Oued Faid (Vesmanis, 1984b); Djebel Ech Cherichera, SW Kairouan (Vesmanis, 1984b); between Gabès and El Hamma (Vesmanis, 1984b).

Family Muridae

Rats and Mice

Two subfamilies of murid rodents have representatives in Tunisia.

Key for Family Muridae

- 1. Tail densely haired, obscuring the scales and often penicillate; internal cheek pouches present; cusps of upper cheek teeth either in two rows or semiprismaticGerbillinae
- 1'. Tail naked or with scattered hairs not hiding scales; cusps of upper cheek teeth in three rowsMurinae

Subfamily Gerbillinae

Gerbils, Jirds and Relatives

Four genera of this subfamily occur in Tunisia.

Key for Subfamily Gerbillinae

1. Tail short (much less than 50% of head and body), greatly thickened; auditory bullae and mastoid greatly inflated (more than 40% of the length of the skull)*Pachyuromys*
- 1'. Tail more than 50% of head and body; auditory bullae and mastoid not so inflated (less than 40% of length of the head and body)2
- 2(1'). Tail less than 80% of head and body; foot more than 25 mm; upper incisors not grooved*Psammomys*
- 2'. Tail various; generally terete (if less than 80% of head and body, then hind foot less than 25 mm); grooves on upper incisors3
- 3(2'). Hind foot with anterior half of sole hairy and posterior half naked; tail with well developed black terminal tuft; total length of adults more than 230 mm; cheek teeth prismatic throughout life*Meriones*
- 3'. Sole of hind foot entirely naked or entirely haired; tail with slight dark (not black) terminal tuft; total length less than 230 mm; cheek teeth with two rows of cusps, separate transverse laminae in unworn, wearing into elliptical shape (in extreme wear, prismatic pattern)*Gerbillus*

Genus *Gerbillus* Desmarest, 1804

Gerbils can be distinguished from their rodent relatives only by a combination of features, as indicated in the above keys. Grooved upper incisors distinguish them from most. In Tunisia, however, the jirds (*Meriones*) and the fat-tailed sand rats (*Pachyuromys*) also have grooved upper incisors.

Members of this genus occur from western India westward through the Middle East into Africa. In Africa, they occur throughout the northern region and southward into the Sahara and East Africa.

Specific relationships among the various populations are still obscure. In recent years, as many as 35 different species have been recognized. Even the generic status of some of these has been the subject of controversy.

I follow Wassif et al. (1969) and recognize three subgenera within the genus. The details of the considerations upon which this decision was based is to be presented in a paper currently in preparation by Gharaibeh and Cockrum (in litt.).

Key for Genus *Gerbillus*

1. Plantar surface of hind feet hairy; forefeet with some plantar hairs; greatest length of the skull more than 28 mm; lateral inflation of auditory bullae visible from dorsal view of skullsubgenus *Gerbillus*

1'. Plantar surface of hind feet naked; forefeet with some hair; greatest length of skull generally less than 28 mm (if more than 26 mm, then bullae not visible in dorsal view); bullae variously inflated2

2(1'). Size large (head and body more than 90 mm, hind foot more than 25 mm); greatest length of skull more than 28 mmsubgenus *Dipodillus* (part)

2'. Size medium to small (head and body less than 90 mm, hind foot less than 25 mm); greatest length of skull less than 28 mm3

3(2'). Tail short (about equal to or less than length of head and body); auditory bullae little inflated (not extending posterior to level of occipital condyles); cheek teeth with cusps alternatesubgenus *Dipodillus* (part)

3'. Tail long (more than 110 % of head and body); auditory bullae greatly inflated (extending markedly posterior to occipital condyle); cheek teeth with cusps oppositesubgenus *Hendecapleura*

Subgenus *Dipodillus* Lataste, 1881

Primitive Naked-footed Gerbils

This subgenus ranges from Western India westward through the Middle East into North Africa. In Africa, these gerbils occur in the northern Sahara, from Egypt to Morocco and, in the eastern part of their range, southward into Sudan.

Members of this subgenus have naked feet, primitive teeth and auditory bullae that are moderately inflated. Three species are known to occur in Tunisia.

Key for Subgenus *Dipodillus*

1. Size large (head and body more than 90 mm, hind foot more than 25 mm); tail longer than the head and body; greatest length of skull more than 28 mm
.....*Gerbillus campestris*
- 1'. Size smaller (head and body less than 90 mm, hind foot less than 25 mm); tail about the length of or shorter than the head and body; greatest length of skull less than 28 mm2
- 2(1'). Tail less than 80 mm; length of skull less than 25 mm *Gerbillus simoni*
- 2'. Tail more than 80 mm; greatest length of skull more than 25 mm
.....*Gerbillus zakariai*

Gerbillus campestris Loche, 1867

Large Naked-footed Gerbil

Diagnosis. These are the largest of the naked-footed gerbils. Adults have a head and body length of about 100 mm, a long black-tufted tail about 120 mm in length and weights of up to 40 g.

Distribution. They occur only in North Africa, from the Atlantic Coast of Morocco eastward to Egypt and southward from the Mediterranean into the Sahara

(Fig. 3.54). In Tunisia, they occur in all but the most sandy southern portions of the country.

Biology. Eventhough this species is widely distributed, trap night success points to population variation from area to area and from year to year in the same area (Cockrum et al., in litt.). In the spring of 1975 this species was extremely common along the coastal edge of an ungrazed eucalyptus forest sand stabilization area of the Sebkhet Ariana, northwest of Gammarth. Tracks were everywhere and trap success was high. In contrast, in the same period of time, populations were low in the heavily grazed coastal region near Bordj Cedria, only some 25-30 km to the southwest.

During the course of their survey, Cockrum et al. (in litt.) examined a total of 103 females, only three of which were pregnant (one in January, with five embryos; two in November, one with three and one with four embryos). Lactating females were taken in January (1), March (1), April (3), May (1), and November (2). A total of 149 males were examined. Reduced testes size in adult males occurred in November and December (3 X 2 - 8 X 4 mm; average 5.5 X 3 mm). Enlarged testes were most evident in March and April (10 X 4 - 15 X 10 mm; average 12 X 7 mm). Juvenile and subadults were taken most commonly in January through April. These results agree with those of Bernard (1969) who found most reproduction to occur between March and July, with most being observed in March. He recorded 3 to 8 embryos per litter, with 5.3 being average, and was unable to successfully breed the species in the laboratory. I obtained one pregnant female from Ariana governorate (June 13) that had 7 embryos (6 right, 1 left; crown-rump length 4 mm). Apparently, wild-caught gerbils do well in captivity on a diet of barley. The few specimens I kept adapted to the cage conditions quickly.

Figure 3.54. Distribution maps of the large North African gerbil, *Gerbillus campestris* Loche, 1867. A, *G. c. campestris* Loche, 1867; B, *G. c. rozsikae* (Thomas, 1908); C, population C; D, population D; E, *G. c. dodsoni* (Thomas, 1902).

Taxonomy. Considerable geographic variation existed in the material examined in this study. There is a cline in pelage color, from dark in the humid north to light in the south. For example, individuals from Tabarka, when compared with those from Mechiguig, are strikingly different. In the past, three names have been variously applied (as distinct species or as subspecies) to specimens taken in Tunisia: *Gerbillus campestris*, *Gerbillus dodsoni*, and *Gerbillus jamesi*. The variations are best expressed by the recognition of 3 different subspecies in Tunisia. There is a possibility that two more subspecies that had not been previously described exist in Tunisia, one on the island of Djerba (population C in Fig. 3.54) and the other around Médénine (population D in Fig. 3.54). Statistical analyses of morphometric measurements and molecular data are needed in order to make a taxonomic decision concerning these two populations.

Gerbillus campestris campestris Loche, 1867

Gerbillus campestris Loche, Atlas Expl. Sci. Algeria, Zool., Mamm., p. 106, 1867, type from Philippeville, Algeria; Conseil, 1909; Blanc, 1935; Bernard and Gannoun, 1965; Harrison, 1967; Bernard, 1970.

G[erbillus]. campestris, Lataste, 1887.

Gerbillus c[ampestris]. campestris, Bernard, 1969.

Gerbillus campestris campestris, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

Dipodillus campestris, Wassilieff, 1932.

Gerbillus dodsoni, Thomas and Trouessart, Bull. Soc. Zool. France, [5] 25:173, 1903 (part from Bargou, 1380 m. [= Djebel Maouine, 323 m]--see Chaignon, 1904:45 for correction of locality); Chaignon, 1904; Trouessart, 1905; Counsel, 1909; Blanc, 1935.

Dipodillus dodsoni, Chaignon, 1904.

Gerbillus jamesi Harrison, Mammalia, 32(3): 383, 1967, type from Between Bou Ficha and Enfidaville, Tunisia.

Remarks: *Gerbillus campestris campestris* appears to be restricted to the more moist, coastal and mountainous areas of northern Tunisia (A in Fig. 3.54).

The authorship of the name *Gerbillus campestris* has been attributed to Levaillant at various dates ranging from 1850 to 1857. As Cockrum and Setzer (1976) have shown, all have referred to a single drawing (figure 2, plate V) prepared by Levaillant and made available for Loche around 1858. Loche published it with the description in 1867. Loche's 1867 textual description and use of the name therefore has page priority over Levaillant's plate. Loche's early use of the name *Gerbillus campestris* (1858) appears to be an nomen nudum.

The inclusion of *Gerbillus jamesi* Harrison, 1967, as a pure synonym of this subspecies is somewhat subjective. In any case, an examination by Cockrum et al. (in litt.) of the type and only known specimen shows that *G. jamesi* is a juvenile *Gerbillus campestris*. Efforts to capture topotypes is somewhat complicated by the fact that Harrison did not precisely identify the type locality. Cockrum and his co-workers (in litt.) failed to secure *Gerbillus* of any sort from this region. In nearby coastal regions they did secure one *Gerbillus latastei* and two *Gerbillus campestris* (12 km S Bou Ficha on GP1, 1 km E highway). The *G. campestris* were somewhat atypical of *G. c. campestris*. Future studies may show that specimens from coastal and adjacent areas of east-central Tunisia may well warrant subspecific recognition. If so, then the name *Gerbillus campestris jamesi* Harrison, 1967, should be applied.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 87, distributed as follows: Sebkhet Ariana, near coastal dunes, ca. 6 km NW Gammarth, 15 km airline NE Tunis, 21; 2 km NW Gammarth at lookout point eucalyptus forest, 4; 3.5 km S

Korbous (Cap Bon) 1; 3.5 km SW Korbous, 2 km off road (on STEG dirt road).
 1; 5.5 km S Korbous (Cap Bon) 3; ca. 6 km airline N Korbous, off MC 26, 2;
 Djebel Zaghouan, 3 km SE Zaghouan, on road from Ain Ayed, 1; 15 km SW Pont
 du Fahs on GP 4, 2 km E highway, 6; Stabilized dunes 2 km NE Bordj Cedria (23
 km SE Tunis), 2; Djebel Oust, 6 km S Oum Djeddour, 28 km airline E. Thala, 1;
 31 km NE Le Kef on GP 5, 4 km S highway near Oued Tessa, 2; Touiref, near
 mines, ca. 27 km airline SW Jendouba, 1; 31 km NW Grombalia on MC 34, 2 km
 N highway, 1; West base of Djebel Ichkeul, 10 km W GP 11, 1; 11 km N Tunis on
 GP 8, 1; 12 km S Bou Fichta on GP1, 1 km E highway, 2; 8 km W Sedjenane on
 GP 7, 1 km S of highway, 3; 3 km E Tabarka, 16; 10 km W Carthage on GP 10, 2;
 10 km NW Hadjeb El Aïoun on MC 77, ca. 35 km airline NE Sbeitla, 3; Scarna
 mine, 10 km airline NE Rohia (60 km airline N Sbeitla), 2; 38 km NE Sbeitla on
 GP 7 (W of Hadjeb El Aïoun), 2; 28 km NW Sbeitla on MC 84, 1; 16 km N Sbeitla
 on MC 71, 1; 20 km N Sbeitla on MC 71, E of highway, 1; 38 km NE Sbeitla on
 GP 3, 1; Oued Thibar, 9 km SW Bou Salem, 3.

Gerbillus campestris rozsikai (Thomas, 1908)

Dipodillus campestris rozsikai [sic] Thomas, Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist, [8] 2: 374,
 1908, type from Biskra, Algeria.

Dipodillus campestris rozsikai. Thomas, 1913 (correction of typographical error).

Dipodillus campestris, Bernard, 1969 (part).

Gerbillus dodsoni, Wassilieff, 1932 (part).

Gerbillus campestris, Wassilieff, 1932 (part).

This race occurs in central Tunisia, north of the Chott Djerid and south of the
 Atlas foothills (see B in Fig. 3.56).

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 16, distributed as follows: jct.
 MC 201 and MC 122, ca. 33 km airline W Gafsa, 1; 4 km W Redeyef on road to

Aïoun Aneur, 6; 10 km W Gafsa on MC 201, 7; 12 km N Tozeur, near STIL date grove, 2; 3 km S Nefta, 1.

Literature reports: (Wassilieff, 1932), unless otherwise indicated: Tozeur; el-Lala [= Lalla], near Gafsa; Sidi Bou Zid; Chorfa [not found]; Nefta; Kasserine (Bernard, 1969); Maknassy (Bernard, 1969).

Gerbillus campestris population C

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): all from Island of Djerba, total, 1, distributed as follows: 10.5 km NE Elkantara on RVE 941, 1 (type); 1 km S las Tourgereness, 1 (TTU 72658).

Literature reports: Île d’Djerba (Bernard, 1969 and 1970).

Gerbillus campestris population D

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 18, distributed as follows: 27 km NW Médénine on MC 104, 2; Oued el Fera, 10 km SE Matmata on MC 104, 1; 26 km SE Matmata on MC 104, 11; 28 km W Beni Kheddache on MC 114 (55 km airline W Médénine), 1; 9 km W Bir Amir (55 km airline SW Tatahouine), 3;

Literature reports: Tamezret, in the mountains of Matmata (Lataste, 1887).

Gerbillus campestris dodsoni (Thomas, 1902)

Dipodillus dodsoni Thomas, Proc. Zool. Soc. London, 2(1):7, 1902, type from

Ain Hammen, Libya; Wassilieff, 1932 (part from Bir Pistor).

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 16, distributed as follows: 5 km NE Dehabit near MC 203, 1; 19 km N Bir Zar, 2; Mechiguig, 13.

Literature reports: Bir Pistor (Wassilieff, 1932).

Gerbillus simoni Lataste, 1881

Simon's Short-tailed Gerbil

Diagnosis. This is a medium-sized naked-footed gerbil with a short, unicolored, non-tufted tail. Generally the tail is slightly longer than the head and body length. Total length is about 160 mm, of which the tail is about 85 mm. Adults weigh about 21 g.

Distribution. They occur in the coastal portions of western Egypt, westward through Libya into central Tunisia, thence across the high plateau of Algeria into eastern Morocco (A in Fig. 3.55).

Biology. In Libya, Ranck (1968) found these gerbils in two contrasting habitats-- (a) in non-sandy situations on the narrow coastal plains and adjacent lowlands and (b) in the upper reaches of narrow, grassy valleys at the highest elevations of Jebel Nefusa. In Tunisia, it was taken along the coast and at higher elevations.

Based on evidence from the remains of skulls in owl pellets, this gerbil is much more common in Tunisia than trapping results indicated. One female taken on 12 March contained 5 embryos.

Taxonomy. Ellerman and Morrison-Scott (1951) listed *simoni* as a subspecies of *Gerbillus dasyurus* (Wagner, 1842), a species that does not occur west of the Nile. Cockrum et al (1976a) summarized the known distribution and morphological variation of this species. Only a single subspecies occurs in Tunisia.

Gerbillus simoni simoni Lataste, 1881

G[erbillus]. simoni Lataste, Le Naturaliste, Paris, 3(63), p. 497, 1881, from Oued Magra, between M'sila and Barika, Algeria.

Gerbillus simoni, Harrison, 1967; Bernard, 1970.

Dipodillus simoni, Bernard, 1969.

Figure 3.55. Distribution maps of Simon's short-tailed gerbil, *Gerbillus simoni* Lataste, 1881 (A), and *G. zakariai* Cockrum, Vaughan and Vaughan, 1976 (B).

Remarks. Blanc (1935) recorded: "... a very small species with naked feet that only inhabits the southern sandy region. It is very pale. I have taken it at Kébili and Gafsa. It was identified by Dr. Trouessart a few years ago" (translated by Cockrum, in litt.). This probably was not *simoni*. The brief description of the animal and of the habitat leads one to suspect that Blanc was referring to *Gerbillus nanus*.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 23, distributed as follows: 10 km NW Hadjeb el Aïoun on MC 77, ca 35 km airline NE Sbeitla, 6; 38 km NE Sbeitla on GP 3, 2; 21 km N Sbeitla on MG 71, E of highway, 1;

Literature reports: Near [= a few km S] Hammamet (Harrison, 1967).

Gerbillus zakariai Cockrum, Vaughan and Vaughan, 1976

Zakaria's Gerbil

Diagnosis. This island species is related to the mainland species, *Gerbillus simoni*, but differs in being larger and lighter colored and having long, narrow skull. Detailed comparison between *G. simoni* and *G. zakariai* are provided by Cockrum et al. (1976a).

Distribution. *G. zakariai* inhabits only the Kerkenna Islands, just off Sfax. Almost nothing is known of its abundance or habits (see B in Fig. 3.55).

Biology. The only known specimens were taken during the night of 21 May 1975 in a field 0.5 km E Kellabine. Two of the three females taken were pregnant. One had four embryos, and the other five.

Gerbillus zakariai Cockrum, Vaughan and Vaughan, 1976

Dipodillus zakariai Cockrum, Vaughan and Vaughan, Mammalia, 40:320, 1976,

type from 0.5 km E Kellabine, Kerkenna Islands, Tunisia.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 4, distributed as follows: 0.5 km E Kellabine, Kerkenna Islands, 4.

Subgenus *Hendecapleura* Lataste, 1884

Specialized Naked-footed Gerbils

Diagnosis. This subgenus includes only those members of the genus *Gerbillus* that have naked feet and inflated auditory bullae. Two species in this subgenus are known to occur in Tunisia.

Key for Subgenus *Hendecapleura*

1. Size tiny (head and body less than 75 mm; hind foot less than 21 mm);
greatest length of skull less than 23 mm*Gerbillus henleyi*
- 1'. Size medium (head and body more than 75 mm, hind foot more than 21
mm); greatest length of skull more than 24 mm*Gerbillus nanus*

Gerbillus henleyi (De Winton, 1903)

Pygmy Naked-footed Gerbil

Diagnosis. This is the smallest of the Tunisian gerbils. Adults reach length of only 150 to 170 mm of which the tail makes up 85 to 100 mm. Weights are 7 to 9 g.

Distribution. In the past, this species has been reported from the coastal parts of eastern Libya and northern Egypt and the high plateau of central Algeria, but not from Tunisia.

Biology. Ranck (1968) reported that in Libya this species was confined to the coastal plain and littoral deserts. In Tunisia, Cockrum et al. (in litt.) took it in a variety of situations -- all in the subdesert and desert edge (Fig. 3.56). These tiny gerbils are probably much more common than the trapping activities would show.

Figure 3.56. Distribution maps of the pygmy naked-footed gerbil, *Gerbillus henleyi* (De Winton, 1903).

According to Cockrum et al. (in litt.), the traps used in the 1972-1975 study were probably not sensitive enough to respond to the small weight of one of these rodents. One pregnant female taken 5 June carried 4 embryos.

Taxonomy. Kowlaski and Rzebik-Kowalska (1991) are of the opinion that molars of *Gerbillus henleyi* are typical for *Gerbillus* and different from *Dipodillus*. Corbet (1978) listed *jordani*, the subspecies known from Algeria with the nominate subspecies described from Wadi Natron, Egypt. Petter (1975) recognized *G. henleyi jordani* from Central Plateau, Algeria.

Gerbillus henleyi jordani (Thomas, 1918)

Dipodillus jordani Thomas, Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist., [9] 2:60, 1918, from Guelt-el-Stel, Algeria.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 9, distributed as follows: 10 km NW Hadjeb el Aïoun on MC 77, ca 35 km airline NE Sbeitla, 1; 38 km NE Sbeitla on GP 3, 1; Oued Sbeitla, 5 km SE Sbeitla, 1; 10 km W Gafsa, 1; Edge of STIL. date grove, 12 km N Tozeur, 1; 20 km N Gabès, 2 km E GP 1, 1; 30 km SE Médénine on GP 1, near IBP site, 2; 10 km N Tatahouine on GP 19, 1.

Literature reports: none.

Gerbillus nanus Blanford, 1875. Southern Naked-footed Gerbil

Diagnosis. This gerbil is intermediate in size between *Gerbillus campestris* and *Gerbillus henleyi*. It is only slightly smaller, in weight, than *Gerbillus simoni*. Measurements of adults include total length, about 195 mm; tail, about 110 mm; and weight about 18 g.

Distribution. This species occurs from southern Morocco and northern Mauritania, south of the Atlas Mountains, eastward in the northern Sahara into the

Middle East. In Tunisia, it occurs in the central and southern portions of the country (Fig. 3.57).

Biology. Populations of this gerbil apparently vary greatly from year to year in central Tunisia. For example, 24 were taken by Cockrum and his team (in litt.) in 50 traps in one night at Kebili and 31 in 50 traps during another just south of Nefta. A year later, trapping in the same areas yielded only one animal of this species. One female taken on 17 March from 6 km southwest Tozeur contained 7 embryos; one from 10 km east Nefta on 14 February contained 6 embryos; and one taken May 26 near El Rahmat, Kebili contained 5 embryos. Males in the latter area had testes ranging from 4X2 to 6X4 mm.

Taxonomy. Ellerman and Morrison-Scott (1951) listed *Gerbillus nanus arabium* as a subspecies of *Gerbillus nanus* Blanford, 1875. The type locality of the nominate species is in Baluchistan. An analysis of additional specimens may well demonstrate that populations in North Africa are not conspecific with the Arabian species. Further, it appears that two (or more) subspecies of this species should be recognized from Tunisia. However, pending further studies, I include all Tunisian material in a single subspecies as follows:

Gerbillus nanus garamantis Lataste, 1881

Gerbillus garamantis Lataste, Le Naturaliste, Third year (whole number 64):507, 1881, type from Sidi Roueld (Ouargla), Algeria.

Gerbillus nanus garamantis, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

Gerbillus nanus, Bernard, 1970; Jordan et al., 1974.

Dipodillus nanus, Bernard, 1969.

Gerbillus simoni, Blanc, 1935.

Dipodillus garamantis, Choumowitch, 1954.

Figure 3.57. Distribution maps of the small naked-footed gerbil, *Gerbillus nanus* Blanford, 1875.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 52, distributed as follows: 10 km W Gafsa on MC 201, 5; Oum el Khir, 6 km NW Chebika, ca. 53 km airline NWW Tozeur, 3; edge of STIL. date grove, 12 km N Tozeur, 11; 6 km SW Tozeur, slope above Chott Djerid, 2; 10 km E Nefta, 1; 3 km S Nefta, 15; Kebili, sand beside oasis, 13; 2 km S Tatahouine on GP 19, 1; Bordj el Khadra, formerly Fort Saint, 1.

Literature reports: Kébili and Gafsa, (Blanc, 1935, as *G. simoni*).

Subgenus *Gerbillus* Desmarest, 1804

Hairy-footed Gerbils

Members of this subgenus have well-haired hind feet and inflated auditory bullae.

Great confusion has existed concerning the taxonomy and distribution of hairy-footed gerbils in Tunisia. Most workers have failed to recognize that four species occur in the area. As a result, they have often grouped two or more into a single species. Some appear to have used only size as the primary criterion of taxonomy. *G. pyramidum* Geoffroy, 1825 (type from Egypt) and *G. gerbillus* (Olivier, 1801; type also from Egypt) were the two most commonly “recognized.” Heim de Balsac (1936) wrote that “to him, it seemed that *G. latastei* was a separate species.”

The confusion was further confounded when Ellerman (1941) and Ellerman and Morrison-Scott (1951) considered *G. latastei* Thomas and Trouessart to be a subspecies of *G. gerbillus* (Olivier, 1800) and *G. hirtipes* Lataste to be a subspecies of *G. pyramidum* Geoffroy, 1825. As shown by Cockrum (1976a) and Cockrum (1977), the former is a distinct species that includes *G. aureus* (sensu Ranck, 1968) and the latter is a subspecies of *G. gerbillus* (Olivier, 1800).

The four species recognized here appear to represent a graded series of morphological adaptations for living in large areas of loose sand. *G. andersoni* appears to be least modified, with dark colors shortest hind foot, and shortest tail. *G. latastei* and *G. tarabuli* are larger, lighter in color, and have longer hind feet. *G. gerbillus* is small in body size, but has a relatively long tail and large hind feet. The toes of the hind foot are elongated and both the toes and the foot are fringed with stiff hairs. Colors of all are usually pale.

Gerbillus andersoni occurs in coastal situations from Tunisia eastward to Palestine (see Cockrum et al., 1976b). The existence of an “*andersoni*-like” form west of eastern Libya was not recognized although Ranck (1968) reported similar gerbils (*G. eatoni*). *Gerbillus eatoni* is a hairy-footed gerbil, slightly larger than *G. gerbillus* that was described from a coastal sand habitat in central Libya by Thomas (1902a). In his description, he indicated that the new species was related to *G. andersoni* De Winton, 1902.

Ranck (1968) recognized, as *G. eatoni*, coastal populations from central and eastern Libya as a distinct species. Ranck apparently had no specimen of *G. andersoni* available for comparison and was misled by the assignment of “*andersoni*” as a subspecies of *G. gerbillus* by Ellerman and Morrison-Scott (1951) and others.

Chaignon (1904) reported that Blanc had taken some hairy-footed gerbils at Saint Germain [= Ez Zahra], on the outskirts of Tunis. These specimens were sent along others from Kebili to Dr. Trouessart at the Museum National d'Histotire Naturelle. Kebili gerbils were identified as a new species, *Gerbillus latastei* by Thomas and Trouessart (1903) and Saint Germain specimens were thought to be juveniles was included within *latastei*. Thomas and Trouessart (1903) indicated that the new species was related to the Libyan species, *Gerbillus eatoni* Thomas.

When Cockrum et al. (in litt.) visited the same locality in Ez Zahra, they discovered that in the intervening 75 years, the area had been markedly changed by human activities. Their searches along the coast in the general region of Ez Zahra revealed an area of stabilized sand dunes to the south that was being grazed by domestic animals (mainly cattle and sheep but some goats and a few camels used for “camel rides” at nearby tourist hotels also forage in the area). Traps in the area revealed a low density of rodents. Some 1000 trap nights captured only 17 rodents, of which 14 were small, dark hairy-footed gerbils. These had a karyotype with a diploid number of 40, consisting of all bi-armed elements. At the time, the karyotype of *G. eatoni* had not been published. However, a similar (possibly identical) karyotype had been reported for both Egyptian (as *G. andersoni* by Wassif et al., 1969) and Palestinian (as *G. allenbyi* by Wahrman and Zahavi, 1955) coastal populations of smaller hairy-footed gerbils. A later examination by Cockrum et al. (in litt.) of types of *G. andersoni* De Winton 1902, *G. eatoni* Thomas 1902, and *G. allenbyi* Thomas, 1918 in the British Museum (Natural History) led them to conclude that the Tunisian material as well as the three types were all members of a single species. The difference seen in the Tunisian material were considered to merit subspecific rank. Cockrum et al. (1976b) described a new subspecies, *Gerbillus andersoni blanci*, from the coastal region of Bordj Cedria.

Some of the confusion as to what species the name “*latastei*” should be applied has already been discussed (Cockrum, 1977). The type was of one species, *G. latastei*, and part of the type series was a second species, *G. andersoni*. Studies of that large hairy-footed gerbils showed two distinct groups (“*pyramidum*” and “*aureus*”) based on differences in karyotypes and other features. As detailed by Cockrum (1977), the examination of the type in the British Museum (Natural History), in an effort to determine applicable subspecific names for the *G. gerbillus*

in the region, revealed that *G. latastei* Thomas and Trouessart was conspecific with *G. aureus* Setzer, 1956 (sensu Ranck, 1968).

The use of *G. tarabuli* Thomas, 1902, as the specific name for the third species appears to be new in this work. However, Lay et al. (1975) may well have earlier arrived at similar conclusions is indicated by their referral of a Moroccan gerbil to *Gerbillus* sp. (?= *tarabulli* [sic]).

Most previous workers have considered the large Saharan hairy-footed gerbils to be subspecies of *Gerbillus pyramidum* (Geoffroy, 1803), type from Giza, Egypt. Even Thomas (1902a) described *tarabuli* as a subspecies: *Gerbillus pyramidum tarabuli*.

Ranck (1968) was aware of the large hiatus that existed in the distribution of “*pyramidum*-like” gerbils in eastern Libya and western Egypt. He postulated that the eastern Libyan populations would prove to be linked to the Egyptian populations through northern Chad and west-central Sudan. It is now evident that the Tunisian, Algerian, and Moroccan populations have a uniform karyotype that differs significantly from that of the Egyptian populations (see Lay et al., 1975).

Selected morphological features of these three hair-footed gerbils and of *Gerbillus gerbillus* are given in Table 3.3.

Key for Subgenus *Gerbillus*

1. Tip of tail with well-developed terminal tuft; dorsal color light or bright, uniform across dorsum from lateral line to lateral line; auditory bullae so inflated posteriorly as to project posterior to the occipital condyle2
- 1'. Tip of tail with weakly or undeveloped terminal tuft; dorsal color generally dark, with darker middorsal area and lighter sides; auditory bullae not projecting posterior to the occipital condyles3

Table 3.3. Selected features of four species of hairy-footed gerbils from Tunisia (2N= diploid number; FN= fundamental number; HB= head and body; T= tail; HF= hind foot).

Feature	<i>G. andersoni</i>	<i>G. latastei</i>	<i>G. tarabuli</i>	<i>G. gerbillus</i>
Karyotype:				
2N	40	74	40	Males 43 Females 42
FN	76	91-100	74	72
Sample size	7 Females	10 Females	10 Females	6 Males
External measurements (mm)				
HB	94.0±3.1 (88-99)	96.2±2.2 (91-110)	103.7±3.2 (92-110)	94.5±4.4 (85-99)
T	111±6.2 (98-122)	125.3±3.8 (118-132)	138.3±4.2(131-154)	126.2±7.9 (117-139)
HF	26.1±0.3 (26-27)	29.6±0.4 (28-31)	29.7±0.8 (27-31)	

2(1). Size smaller (head and body about 95 mm) but hind feet (about 30 mm) large in relation to head and body (34 % of head and body); toes long (middle toe more than 10 mm) and generally heavily fringed with long, stiff hairs; greatest length of skull less than 30 mm*Gerbillus gerbillus*

2'. Size larger (head and body about 104 mm) but hind foot (about 30 mm) smaller in relation to head and body (29 % of head and body); toes shorter (middle toe less than 10 mm) and little or no fringe; greatest length of skull more than 30 mm*Gerbillus tarabuli*

3(1'). Size smaller (head and body about 95 mm, hind foot about 26 mm); tail with no terminal tuft; greatest length of skull less than 29 mm*Gerbillus andersoni*

3'. Size larger (head and body about 100 mm, hind foot about 29 mm; tail generally with slight terminal tuft; greatest length of skull more than 29 mm
.....*Gerbillus latastei*

Gerbillus andersoni De Winton, 1902. Anderson's

Gerbil

Diagnosis. Tunisian members of this species have hairy feet and inflated bullae (subgeneric traits) as well as a tail with no or only a slight trace of a terminal tuft and, a dark middorsal area with lighter sides. In the latter two features *andersoni* resembles *Gerbillus latastei*. From the latter it differs by a smaller size as well as karyotype (2N= 40 compared to 74 in *latastei*).

Distribution. *Gerbillus andersoni* exists in coastal situations from Tunisia eastward to Palestine (see Cockrum et al., 1976b). Cockrum suspects that some coastal populations of hairy-footed gerbils of western Morocco may be closely related to this species. In northern Tunisia, *andersoni* was collected in areas of stabilized sand dunes (Fig. 3.58). Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska (1991) made no mention of the species in coastal Algeria.

Biology. In Tunisia, this gerbil is known only from two isolated areas of coastal sand dunes in Tunis and Sousse regions and probably occurs in similar coastal sand dune areas in other parts of Tunisia. During 1972-1975 study, this species was uncommon in all coastal dune areas that Cockrum et al. (in litt.) sampled and appeared to be absent in two areas where it had formerly been found in (Ez Zahra and Raouad Chott).

Taxonomy. Some authorities (e.g., Ranck, 1968) list as separate species: *Gerbillus eatoni*. Cockrum et al. (1976b) reviewed this species and included all the following in it: *Gerbillus andersoni allenbyi* Thomas in Israel, *G. a. andersoni* De Winton in Egypt, *G. a. eatoni* Thomas, *G. a. versicolor* Ranck, and *G. a. inflatus* Ranck in Libya, and *G. a. blanci* Cockrum, Vaughan and Vaughan in Tunisia.

Figure 3.58. Distribution maps of Anderson's hairy-footed gerbil *Gerbillus andersoni* De Winton, 1902.

Gerbillus andersoni blanci Cockrum, Vaughan and
Vaughan, 1976

Gerbillus andersoni blanci Cockrum, Vaughan and Vaughan, Mammalia, 40(3):
470, 1976, type from 2 km NE Bordj Cedria, 23 km SE Tunis, Tunisia.

Gerbillus latastei, Thomas and Trouessart, 1903 (part); Chaignon, 1904.

Record. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 8, distributed as follows:

Stabilized sand dunes, 2 km NE Bordj Cedria, 23 km SE Tunis, 6; 13 km NNW
Sousse, on coast near dunes, 2.

Literature reports: Saint-Germain [= Ez Zahra], Chaignon, 1904.

Gerbillus latastei Thomas and Trouessart, 1903

Lataste's Gerbil

Diagnosis. This large-sized hairy-footed gerbil has a poorly developed tuft on the tail. It is slightly smaller than *G. tarabuli* Thomas 1902. It is generally lighter in color than *G. andersoni*, with the dorsal dark area not so wide but darker in color than either *G. tarabuli* or *G. gerbillus*. Adults reach about 245 mm in length of which the tail makes up about 135 mm. Weights of large adult males reach 50 g. Females are somewhat smaller with an average weight of 37 g.

Distribution. This species is known from northwestern Libya and central Tunisia. Probably it occurs to the west, on the high plateau immediately south of the Atlas, through Algeria and Morocco (Fig. 3.59). In Tunisia, it occurs in the coastal lowlands north of Sousse southwestward to the Chotts region and south to Bir Amir.

Biology. These gerbils apparently undergo marked multi-annual fluctuations in abundance. As indicated by the lists of specimens examined by Cockrum et al. (in litt.), they were found at times to be locally abundant. Of the 157 females taken

Figure 3.59. Distribution maps of Lataste's hairy-footed gerbil *Gerbillus latastei* Thomas and Trouessart, 1903.

during 1972-1975 study, only 7 were pregnant (1 in Mar. 6 in April). Embryo counts average 5.6 (range 4-7). Lactating females were observed in June. July and December.

Because of the confusion of names outlined above, I find it impossible to realistically assign many of the various past reports of gerbils of this complex from Tunisia to appropriate synonymies. Considerable variation, especially in color, exists among various populations in Tunisia. For example, those from near the Chott Djerid (e.g., Kebili and Tozeur) are all quite pale. In all probability, two or three subspecies will eventually be recognized. For the present, I refer all to a single subspecies as follows.

Gerbillus latastei latastei Thomas and Trouessart, 1903

Gerbillus latastei Thomas and Trouessart, Bull. Soc. Zool. France, [5] 28:172, 1903, type from Kébili, Tunisia; Chaignon, 1904 (part from Kebili); Trouessart, 1905; Conseil, 1909; Blanc, 1935.

Gerbillus aureus, Jordan et al., 1974.

Gerbillus gerbillus latastei, Ellerman, 1941; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

Gerbillus latoni [sic], Choumowitch, 1954.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 205, distributed as follows: 5 km N Bou Fichta on GP 1, 1 km E highway, 1 ; 13 km NNW Sousse on coast near dunes, 1 ; 10 km NW Hadjeb el Aïoun on MC 77, ca. 35 km airline NE Sbeitla, 10; Oued Sbeitla, 5 km SE Sbeitla, 14; jct. MC 201 and 122, ca. 33 km airline W Gafsa, 12; 9-10 km NW Redeyef on MC 201 in river valley, 13; 2 km N Redeyef on MC 201, 1 km N highway, 8; 26 km NNE Tozeur on GP 3, 1; 20 km NNE Tozeur, near oued, 1; 40 km NW Gabès on GP 15 , 4; 20 km N Gabès, 2 km E GP 1, 1; 3 km S Nefta, 14; 6 km SW Tozeur, slope above Chott Djerid. 1; 21 km NW Kebili, dunes W Oum Semaâ, 10; Kebili, 1; 28 km W Beni Kheddache on MC

114 (55 km airline W Médénine), 4; 16 km S Médénine on GP 19, 1 km E highway, 13; 30-31.5 km SE Médénine on GP 1, near IBP site, 63; 10 km N Tatahouine on GP 19, 1; Jarjar, 13 km S Tatahouine on GP 19, 8; 14-15 km S Tatahouine on GP 19, 15; 12 km N Sidi Toui at jct. to Ben Morra (40 km S Ben Gardane) on MC 203, 3; 38 km S Tatahouine on GP 19, 1 km W highway on Oued Darshene, 4; 9 km W Bir Amir (55 km airline SW Tatahouine), 1.

Gerbillus tarabuli Thomas, 1902

Large Hairy-footed Gerbil

Diagnosis. See section on *G. latastei*.

Distribution. This species is restricted to the Sahara, from central Libya westward to southern Morocco. In Tunisia, it is restricted to sandy deserts of the south (Fig. 3.60).

Biology. Most of the specimens collected by Cockrum and his team (in litt.) were taken in sandy areas, often near large, moving sand drifts. The species is often locally common. Pregnant females were taken in March, April, May and August. Of fifty one females taken, 8 were pregnant. Embryo counts averaged 4.5 and ranged from 2 to 8.

Taxonomy. Corbet (1978) included *G. tarabuli* from Libya under *G. pyramidum*. Lay (1983) listed this species as *G. tarabuli* and Lay et al. (1975) commented on certain chromosomal and morphological differences that distinguish *pyramidum* from *tarabuli*. The following name applies to the Tunisian material.

Gerbillus tarabuli hamadensis Ranck, 1965

Gerbillus pyramidum hamadensis Ranck, U. S. Nat. Mus. Bull. 275:118, 1968,
from 5 km E Derg, Tripolitania, Libya.

Figure 3.60. Distribution maps of the large hairy-footed gerbils: A. *Gerbillus tarabuli* Thomas, 1902; B. *G. pyramidum* I. Geoffroy, 1825.

Record. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 64. distributed as follows: Oum El Khir, 6 km NW Chebika, ca 53 km airline NW Tozeur, 3; 20 km NNE Tozeur. near Oued, 2 ; 12 km N Tozeur on GP 3, near STIL. date grove. 19; 11 km N Tozeur on GP 3, 1.5 km E highway, 3; 5 km SW Tozeur. 2; 6 km SW Tozeur, slope above Chott Djerid, 8; dune 3 km S Nefta, 17; sand beside oasis, Kebili. 1; 108 km S Tatahouine on GP 19, 1; 19 km N Bir Zar, 1; El Borma, ca 200 km airline S Tatahouine, 2; well, 38 km NE Fort Saint on pipeline between markers 300 km and 310 km, 4; Bordj El Khadra (formerly Fort Saint), 1.

Literature reports: It is certain that past authors have reported this species from Tunisia. However, the confusion of species identifications and the absence of voucher specimens make it impossible to prepare a meaningful synonymy of name usages or literature records of occurrence.

Gerbillus gerbillus (Olivier, 1801)

Lesser Egyptian Hairy-footed Gerbil

Diagnosis. This is the smallest of the four species of hairy-footed gerbils native to Tunisia. The hind feet, and especially the toes, are unusually elongated, especially as the animal has small body size. The toes and hind feet are edged with long stiff hairs.

Distribution. The species is widely distributed in sandy desert situations through the Sahara in North Africa and eastward into the Middle East. In Tunisia, it occurs in the southern part of the country (Fig. 3.61).

Biology. Six of the 42 females taken by Cockrum et al. (in litt.) were pregnant. Three taken in January had 4 embryos each, while three taken in April had 6 embryos each.

Figure 3.61. Distribution maps of small hairy-footed gerbil, *Gerbillus gerbillus* (Olivier, 1801).

Taxonomy. As indicated above, Ranck (1968) referred the *G. gerbillus* of western Libya to *G. g. latastei*, a taxon now considered to be specifically distinct. I do not have samples from Algeria to properly evaluate the relations of Tunisian populations of this species. On the grounds of geographic probability, I refer all Tunisian to a single subspecies as follows:

Gerbillus gerbillus hirtipes Lataste, 1882

Gerbillus hirtipes Lataste, Le Naturaliste, 3rd year (whole number 64): 506, 1881, type locality not specified, and Le Naturaliste, 4th year, (no. 3): 21, 1882, type from Bemendile, Ouargla, Algeria.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 57 , distributed as follows: 16 km S Médénine on GP 19, 1 km E highway, 17; 28 km W Beni Kheddache on MC 114 (55 km airline W Médénine), 3; 10 km N Tatahouine on GP 19, 1; 12 km N Sidi Toui at jct. to Ben Morra (40 km S Ben Gardane) on MC 203, 4; 14 km S Tatahouine on GP 19, 4; 38 km S Tatahouine on GP 19, 1 km W highway, on Oued Darshene, 4; 2 km E Saniat Lebbada near MC 203 (90 km S Ben Gardane), 3; 10 km NW Remada, 1 km S jct. MC 112 and GP 19 on GP 19, 1; 108 km S Tatahouine on GP 19, 34 km SW highway on road to El Borma, 2; Oued Abdallah, 110 km S Tatahouine on GP 19, 2; 19 km N Bir Zar, 4; El Borma, ca 200 km airline SSW Tatahouine, 2; Mechiguig, 11; Tiaret, 3; 20 km S Tiaret on pipeline, 4 km N marker 350, 2; well, 39 km NE Fort Saint on pipeline between markers km 300 and km 310,5.

Literature reports: none.

Genus *Pachyuromys* Lataste, 1880

This monotypic genus is known only from North Africa, from Egypt westward through Libya, Tunisia, Algeria, southern Morocco and southward into northern Mauritania.

Pachyuromys duprasi Lataste, 1880

Fat-tailed Gerbil

Diagnosis. Fat-tailed gerbils have short tails and greatly inflated bullae. The limbs and feet are extremely short in relation to body size. The short, almost naked, tail is often fat. The pelage is soft, fluffy and ranges from light yellowish gray to deep buff in color. The ventral surface, legs and feet are white. The total length may reach 170 mm of which the tail comprises about 60 mm. Weights reach about 40 g.

Distribution. This species is an inhabitant of sparsely vegetated deserts and subdeserts. Setzer (1957) thought that, in Libya, it was restricted to rock-shingle deserts. Ranck (1968) reported it from areas of sparse vegetation, on flat, rock-strewn hamadas and at the margins of shallow, dry, water courses. Osborn and Helmy (1980) reported that in Egypt it occurred in “transitional deserts” with scattered vegetation. They had one that was “dug from barren gravel.” In Tunisia, it occurs in the subdesert and desert parts of central and southeast Tunisia (Fig. 3.62).

Biology. As a result of their short limbs, fat-tailed gerbils have a non-gerbil-like locomotion. Most gerbils, especially when startled, move by leaps and bounds. Fat-tailed gerbils trot, somewhat like the walk of a hedgehog. Mermod (1970) reported that, in Algeria, two of six transplanted individuals returned to their burrows after having been released at a distance of 2 km. One return occurred in

Figure 3.62. Distribution maps of the fat-tailed gerbil, *Pachyuromys duprasi* Lataste, 1880.

less than 8.5 hours, the other in 14.5 hours. A two thousand meter trip for an animal with a small body size and atypical short legs is indeed an achievement. Lataste's (1881) description of the species was based on a female and its litter of three young obtained in May. These animals, taken to Paris, gave rise to a number of descendants born in captivity. Lataste (1888) reported the gestation as 19 to 22 (usually 20 or 21) days and the litter size as 3 to 6 (average 3.4). Choumowitch (1954) reported that 5 to 6 young were common. Bernard (1969) reported that in the London Zoo litters of 1 to 9 (average 5) had been recorded. The single pregnant female taken by us contained 7 embryos.

Almost no observations of behavior and food habits in nature are available. Petter (1961) indicated that they remain inactive, in their underground burrow, for several days at a time. He thought such behavior was routine when high winds caused prolonged sand storms. In captivity he reported that, at low temperatures, these gerbils remained completely immobile for days at a time--apparently undergoing some degree of hibernation.

Setzer (1957) suggested that, in nature, they may feed on land snails. Petter (1961) thought that crickets make up at least a part of their natural food. In captivity Choumowitch (1954) maintained them on a diet of green vegetation, grain, and bread. Petter (1961) raised many generations on a diet of only ground meat and lettuce. Harry Norman (personal communication with Cockrum, in litt.) maintained an individual in captivity in Arizona on a diet of laboratory rat food and lettuce. The captured individual made no attempt to hoard food, but in times of food abundance became extremely fat, as was especially evident in the greatly enlarged tail. Most of the individuals taken by Cockrum et al. (in litt.) in nature had the tails that were little-enlarged. In just a few days in captivity, with food ad libitum, the tail became fat and "club-shaped."

Bernard (1969) reported that, although usually rare, this gerbil is occasionally common. He recounted Blanc's (1935) statement that 30 were taken in one 8-day period and Petter's (1961) report of finding the highest populations to occur when many crickets had undergone occlusion. Bernard captured 14 in two days on steppes near Ben Gardane at a time that much of the vegetation was covered by large caterpillars of Sphingid moths. These observations leads to a hypothesis that individuals move into places of food availability from surrounding areas. Much remains to be learned of their habits.

Taxonomy. Considerable age and geographic variation exists in the few specimens examined. For the time being I refer all Tunisian populations to a single subspecies.

Pachyuromys duprasi duprasi Lataste, 1880

Pachyuromys duprasi Lataste, Le Naturaliste, Paris, 1:314, 1880, type from

Laghouat, Algeria; Lataste, Le Naturaliste, 10th year, 2nd series (34):181-3); Trouessart, 1902; Blanc, 1935; Choumowitch, 1954; Petter, 1961; Bernard, 1969; Bernard, 1970; Petter, 1975; Corbet, 1978.

Pachyuromys duprasi duprasi, Ellerman, 1941; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 6, distributed as follows: 6 km SW Tozeur, slope above Chott Djerid, 1; 12.5 km S Gabès on MC 107, 1.5 km W highway, 1; 14 km S Tatahouine on GP 19, 1; 15 km S Tatahouine on GP 129, east of highway, 1; 12 km N Sidi Toui at jct. of Ben Morra (40 km S Ben Gardane) on MC 203, 2.

Literature reports: Mountains N of Gafsa (Blanc, 1935); Gafsa (Bernard, 1969); Djebel Bou Hedma (Bernard, 1969); Metlaoui (Bernard, 1969); Matmata

(Blanc, 1935; Bernard, 1969); Ben Gardane (Bernard, 1969); Tatahouine (Blanc, 1935; Bernard, 1969).

Genus *Meriones* Illiger, 1811. Jirds

Species in this genus range from Mongolia and northern China westward through Russia, India and other Asian countries, through Arabia and into northern Africa. In Africa, they are confined to areas north of the Sahara proper. Authorities are still not in agreement as to how many species should be recognized. Musser and Carleton (1993) listed 16 species. I recognize three species of this genus as occurring in Tunisia. The following will aid in their separation.

1. Size small (tail less than 125 mm, hind foot less than 32 mm); claws pale, soles of hind feet covered with white hair; pelage long, comparatively lax and “silky”; tail short and with short conspicuous tuft; body shape “chunky” (short, stout); bullae inflated (more than one third of occipitonasal length) extending markedly posterior to occiput; suprimeatal triangle large and not enclosed posteriorly by temporal and supraoccipital processes*Meriones crassus*

1'. Size larger (tail more than 125 mm, hind foot more than 32 mm); claws dark basally and dark to pale distally; soles of hind feet partly covered with white hair; tail with tuft varied; bullae less than one third of occipitonasal length and not extending markedly posterior to occiput; suprimeatal triangle small and enclosed posteriorly by temporal and supraoccipital processes2

2(1'). Short tail (125-143 mm) with short, brownish tuft; claws dark throughout length; base of tail gray; auditory bullae less inflated, with suprimeatal triangle spherical in shape and with posterior processes incompletely closed, lateral meatal process of auditory bullae only slightly expanded and clearly distinct from squamosal part of temporal bone; in general, habitat more mesic ..*Meriones shawi*

2'. Long tail (130-175 mm) with long, black tuft; nails dark brown to black basally, paler distally; base of tail reddish; auditory bullae more inflated ventrally and laterally, with suprameatal triangle elliptical in shape and with posterior processes completely closed; lateral meatal process of auditory bulgy markedly expanded and applied to squamosal part of temporal bone; habitat, from plains into desert*Meriones libycus*

Meriones crassus Sundevall, 1842. Gentle Jird

Diagnosis. This jird is discriminated by the presence of white hair on soles of hind feet and by proportionately large bullae.

Distribution. This species ranges from central Asia westward through the Middle East into Africa, westward to the Atlantic coast. It is more desert adapted than other Tunisian jirds and is restricted to the south (Fig. 3.63).

Biology. Koffler (1972) summarized the available information on the reproductive biology, behavior, ecology and other natural history aspects of *M. crassus* over its range. *Meriones crassus* is strictly nocturnal and is well adapted to dry conditions. In Beni Abbès, Algeria, Petter (1961) found that it lives in “dayas” which are small depressions in the hamada pebbly sahara where fine sand accumulates and vegetation grows. It constructs a burrow with a variable number of openings interconnected by a group of galleries leading to chambers. Chambers can be deep. Very often scorpions and tenebrionid beetles are found in *M. crassus* burrows.

This species has exceptional homing capabilities (Petter, 1961). One individual successfully found its way home after being dropped 6 km away. Gestation period is 21 days and the young reach full dimensions after 2 weeks and leave the nest after one month.

Figure 3.63. Distribution maps of the gentle jird, *Meriones crassus* Sundevall, 1842.

Taxonomy. The species was originally described from Sinai. Ellerman and Morrison-Scott (1951) and Petter (1975) regarded subspecies from Sudan (*Meriones crassus pallidus*), Libya (*M. c. tripolius*), northern and eastern Arabia as synonym to the nominate subspecies. I follow those authorities and refer the Tunisian specimens to the nominate race.

Meriones crassus crassus (Sundevall, 1842)

Meriones crassus crassus Sundevall, K. Sv. Akad. Handl. Stockholm, 233. 1842, type from Fons Moses (Ain Musa), Sinai.

Meriones shousboei [sic], Blanc, 1935.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 4, distributed as follows: 5 km NE Dehabit near MC 203, 1; 19 km N Bir Zar, 2; well, 39 km N Fort Saint on pipeline between markers km 300 and km 310, 1.

Literature reports: Ben Gardane (Bernard, 1969); Metlaoui (Choumowitch, 1954); Médénine and Tatahouine (Blanc, 1935)

Meriones libycus Lichtenstein, 1823. Libyan Jird

Diagnosis. This jird can easily be confused with *M. shawi* can be distinguished by its pale claws and less hypertrophied tympanic bullae.

Distribution. As currently recognized, this species occurs from the western edge of the Gobi Desert in Mongolia, westward through the deserts and subdeserts of the Middle East, into Africa where it occurs through most of the Sahara (Fig. 3.64).

Taxonomy. Probably Tunisian populations of this jird are referable to one of the named forms from Algeria, perhaps *Gerbillus guyoni* Loche, 1867. However, I did not have the opportunity to examine the comparative material necessary to adequately judge the relationships of the various named forms. Apparently all of

Figure 3.64. Distribution maps of the Libyan jird, *Meriones libycus* Lichtenstein, 1823.

Loche's type specimens have been lost and Cockrum (in litt.) has been unable to locate topotypical material. In several cases, confusion between *Meriones shawi* and this species has occurred. In captivity, hybrids have been produced from crosses between *M. shawi* and *M. libycus* (see Lay and Nadler, 1969). I refer Tunisian material to the nominate species.

Meriones libycus libycus Lichtenstein, 1823

Meriones libycus Lichtenstein, Verz. Doubl. Zool. Mus. Berlin, p. 5, 1823, from "E deserto libyco" but restricted to near Alexandria, Egypt by Allen, 1939 and Chaworth-Musters and Ellerman, 1947.

Gerbillus guyonii Loche, 1867.

Gerbillus schousboeii Loche, 1867.

Meriones shousboei Trouessart, 1905.

Gerbillus renaultii Loche, 1867.

Meriones erythrurus. Lataste, 1887.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 56, distributed as follows: 10 km W Gafsa on MC 201, 1; Oum El Khir, 6 km NW Chebika, ca. 53 km airline NW Tozeur, 1; 20 km NNE Tozeur, near oued, 1; 12 km N Tozeur of GP 3 near STIL. date grove, 1; 11 km N Tozeur on GP 3, 1.5 km E highway, 1; 6 km SW Tozeur, slope above Chott Djerid, 1; 3 km S Nefta, 1; 4 km S Nefta, dunes W Sidi Hassen Ayed, 1; 21 km NW Kebili, dunes W Oum Sema, 2; 15 km S Tatahouine on GP 19, east of highway, 1; 9 km W Bir Amir (55 km SW Tatahouine), 31; 38 km S Tatahouine on GP 19, 1 km W highway on Oued Darshene, 2; 5 km NE Dehibat near MC 203, 6; Oued Abdallah, 110 km S Tatahouine on GP 19, 1; 19 km N Bir Zar, 1; Mechiguig, 1; Well, 39 km NE Fort Saint on pipeline between markers km 300 and km 310, 4.

Literature reports: Metlaoui (Bernard, 1969); Maknassy (Bernard, 1969), Hama, near Medenine (Bernard, 1969); Remada (1969); Ben Gardane (Bernard, 1969); Medenine and Tatahouine (others mapped by Bernard, 1969), south of Gafsa (Lataste, 1887)

Meriones shawi (Duvernoy, 1842). Shaw's Jird

Diagnosis. This species can be distinguished from *M. libycus* with certainty only by examining the skull. The posterior processes enclose the suprameatal triangle as previously noted. There are also 3 derived chromosomal characters that differentiate *Meriones libycus* from *M. shawi* (see below for more details).

Distribution. This species is restricted to the Atlas Mountains of Morocco and Algeria and coastal North Africa from Egypt to southwestern Morocco (Fig. 3.65).

Biology. G-banded chromosomal complement of *Meriones shawi* from Tunisia was used with other chromosomal data for *Meriones* to reassess the phylogenetic relationships between gerbillids of the genus *Meriones* and related genera (Fig. 3.66). The following symbols are used in Fig. 3.66 and Fig. 3.67: FU, centric fusion; FI, centric fission; E+, euchromatic addition; E- euchromatic deletion; PEI, pericentric inversion; d, distal; p, proximal; slash, chromosomes joined by fusion; comma, chromosomes separate; parentheses; alteration from the primitive condition by an inversion. Numbers are taken from the standard numbering system of gerbillid chromosomes by Qumsiyeh (1986). A critical centric fusion in *Meriones* is fusion of chromosomes 5 and 33. This fusion was present in *Meriones shawi* examined in this study and other species of the genus *Meriones* (*M. unguiculatus*, *M. persicus*, *M. libycus* from Jordan and Iran). *Meriones* is a monophyletic group the common ancestor of which has three derived fusions (see Fig. 3.67). The cladogram in Fig. 3.67 represents the revised

Figure 3.65. Distribution maps of Shaw's jird *Meriones shawi* (Duvernoy, 1842).

Figure 3.66. G-banded chromosomal complement of *Meriones shawi* (see text for explanation of numbering system).

Figure 3.67. Cladogram showing the distribution of derived chromosomal character states in Gerbillidae (see text for explanation of abbreviations).

distribution of derived chromosomal character states in the Gerbillidae. Sections of the cladogram are taken from Qumsiyeh and Chesser (1987), Qumsiyeh and Baker (1988) and Qumsiyeh et al. (1987; 1991).

Three derived conditions in *Meriones libycus* distinguish it from *Meriones shawi*, centric fission of chromosome 1 and the distal portion of chromosome 2, centric fusion of chromosomes 9 and 31, and an acrocentric X (*Meriones shawi* has a metacentric X chromosome). This lead to reassessment of the phylogenetic tree of the this group of gerbillids (Fig. 3.67).

Taxonomy. Relationships among the various populations of *Meriones shawi*-like populations of jirds remains obscure. As listed by Cockrum and Setzer (1976), 12 to 14 named forms exist. Many are currently considered as synonyms of *Meriones shawi* (Duvernoy, 1842) and at least one (*Meriones grandis* Cabrera, 1907) is thought to be a distinct species.

Examination of the material housed at TTU indicates that Tunisian populations from the north (e.g., Sebkhet Ariana) have noticeably darker pelage than populations from other parts of the country. Furthermore, there is variation in the shape and size of suprameatal triangle and tympanic bullae. Morphological analysis of a large series of *Meriones shawi* from its range is needed before any taxonomic decisions are made on the Tunisian populations. In the meantime, I refer all Tunisian material to a single taxon.

Meriones shawi shawi (Duvernoy, 1842)

Gerbillus shawii Duvernoy, Mém. Soc. Mus. H. N. Strasbourg, 3, 2: 22, 1842,
type from Oran, Algeria.

(*Meriones shawi*) var. *longiceps*, Lataste, 1885

M[eriones]. shawi, Lataste, 1887.

Meriones shawi, Ellerman, 1941.

Meriones shawi shawi, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott. 1951.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 35, distributed as follows:
Sebkhet Ariana, ca. 6 km NW Gammarth, near coastal sand dune, 6; 10 km NW Hadjeb el Aïoun on MC 77, ca. 35 km airline NE Sbeitla, 1; 47 km W Sfax on GP 14, 1; jct. MC 201 and MC 122, ca. 33 km airline W Gafsa, 7; 72 km N Gabès on GP 2, 1; 2-10 km NW Redeyef on MC 201, 3; 40 km NW Gabès on GP 15, 1; 20 km N Gabès, 20 km E GP 1, 2; 13 km W Zarzis, 1; 30 km SE Médénine on GP 1, near IBP site, 3; 31 km SE Médénine on GP 1, near IBP site, 4; 21 km S Ben Gardane on MC 203, 1; 10 km N Tatahouine on GP 19, 2; 6-15 km S Tatahouine on GP 19, 1; 12 km N Sidi Toui at jct. to Ben Morra (40 km S Ben Gardane on MC 203), 1.

Literature reports: “All the north of the country south to the line between Gabès and Gamouda passing Maknassy” (Bernard, 1969), Djerba and Zarzis (Bernard, 1969); Between Gafsa and Mahares, South of Sfax, and El Hamma de Gabès, (Wassilieff, 1932), Sidi-Bougrara, in l’Arad [= near Médénine], and Nefzaoua (Lataste, 1887), Metameur (Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905), Gafsa (Trouessart, 1905), Kebili (Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905), Taferma (entre Tozzer [sic] et Gafsa, Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905); Tamesmida (near Feriana; Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905).

Genus *Psammomys* Cretzschmar, 1828

These large gerbillids occur from Palestine and Arabia westward through northern Egypt, Libya, central and southern Tunisia, central Algeria, southern Morocco and into northern Mauritania. Similar in size and general appearance to the jirds (genus *Meriones*), they differ in being primarily diurnal, and in having smooth (not grooved) upper incisors and short ears. Some confusion has existed as to the

identity of sand rats. Cockrum et al. (1977) showed that there are two species in the genus, both of which occur in Tunisia. Many earlier workers grouped the two as a single species.

Key for Genus *Psammomys*

1. Dorsal color pale; dorsal surface of hind feet white; head and body less than 133 mm; hind foot less than 34 mm; temporal ridges reduced; supraorbital bead absent; molar row relatively longer*Psammomys vexillaris*

1'. Dorsal color darker; dorsal surface of hind feet buff; head and body more than 133 mm; hind foot more than 34 mm; temporal ridges well developed; supraorbital bead present; molar row relatively short *Psammomys obesus*

Psammomys obesus Cretzschmar, 1828

Fat Sand Rat

Diagnosis. *Psammomys* can be distinguished from *Meriones* by its smooth (non-grooved) incisors and its pelage that has a greenish tinge. This species can be distinguished from *Psammomys vexillaris* by its larger size and darker color.

Distribution. This species is distributed in North Africa from the Atlantic eastward into the Red Sea, the eastern Mediterranean and south into parts of the Arabian Peninsula. In Tunisia, it was collected from north, center, and south (except for the extreme sandy southwest; Fig. 3.68).

Biology. This species is essentially diurnal. In the cooler months, a peak of activity is reached about 1400 h and by sundown, little activity is observed. In the hottest part of the year, above ground activity is concentrated in the early mornings and late afternoons. Usually this species occurs in areas where clumps of vegetation (often salt bush, *Salicornia*) exist on small mounds or earth. The lower intervening spaces are often devoid of vegetation, especially during dry seasons.

Figure 3.68. Distribution maps of the fat sand rat, *Psammomys obesus* Cretzschmar, 1828.

A main burrow, consisting of a complex series of tunnels, is constructed among and under the plant roots. Alternate burrows, generally much simpler in construction, are under nearby clumps of vegetation. I have observed *Psammomys obesus* in Sidi Toui Reserve, southeastern Tunisia, feeding on the plants its nesting under while sitting at the rim of its burrow. Occasionally it would go in and later emerge from another hole and feed there too. Home range has been estimated to be about 190 m for males, and 76 m for females (Daly and Daly, 1975).

Psammomys obesus is a Saharn herbivore. Daly and Daly (1973) investigated the feeding ecology of this species in the Algerian Sahara. He found that *P.obesus* specialized in feeding on the succulent salty leaves and stems of plants of the family Chenopodiaceae. Daly (1975) reported that this species starts feeding on solid foods earlier than other granivorous gerbils. This is an adaptation to low-energy diet that demand little search time but prolonged ingestion time.

Adults are solitary but often males visit burrows of females. Interactions are infrequent and most were between dominant males. Gestation period is 23-25 days. Postpartum copulation was observed and delayed implantation probably caused by lactation is suspected (Daly and Daly, 1975).

Taxonomy. The few specimens available from southern Tunisia may well represent a distinct, unnamed subspecies because of their lighter pelage. For the time being, I refer all Tunisian specimens to a single subspecies.

Psammomys obesus roudairei Lataste, 1881

Psammomys roudairei Lataste, Le Naturaliste, Paris, (3rd year) whole number 62:492, 1881, from the Chotts [= near Chott Djerid], Tunisia; Thomas, 1906; Conseil, 1909; Thomas, 1919a; Thomas, 1925a; Wassilieff, 1932; Blanc, 1935.

Psammomys obesus roudairei Ellerman, 1941.

Psammomys algiricus, Thomas and Trouessart, 1903; Chaignon, 1904;

Trouessart, 1905; Conseil, 1909.

Psammomys algirus [sic], Blanc, 1935.

Psammomys obesus obesus, Allen, 1939; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951 (part from Tunisia).

Psammomys obesus, Bernard, 1969; Bernard, 1970; Vesmanis, 1978.

Ps. [= *Psammomys*] *tripoli*, Thomas, 1902b.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 33, distributed as follows: 113 km N Gabès on G P 1, 1; 3 km S Maharès on G P 1, 1; 72 km N Gabès on G P 1, 11; Jct. MC 201 and MC 122, ca. 33 km W Gafsa, 8; 11 km NW Redeyef on MC 201, in river valley, 1; 10 km W Gafsa on MC 201, 3; 12-16 km SW Gafsa on GP3, 5; 41 km N Gabès on GP1, 1; 20-26 km NNE Tozeur on GP3, 2; 13 km NNW Tozeur, Chott el Rharsa, 1; Nefta Oasis, Beidh el Hmam, 3; El Borma, ca. 200 km SSW Tatahouine, 1.

Literature reports. The possibility exists that at least some of these references include *Psammomys vexillaris*: Kairouan (Blanc, 1935), Souassi (Bernard, 1970), Sbeitla (Blanc, 1935), Feriana (Blanc, 1935), Gafsa (Lataste, 1887; Chaignon, 1904; Trouessart, 1905; Conseil, 1909; Thomas, 1925; Blanc, 1935), Metlaoui (Bernard, 1970), Tamerza (Bernard, 1970), Tozzer (Bab-el-Djerid) [= Tozeur] (Lataste, 1887), Nefta (Wassilieff, 1932), Region of the Chotts (Lataste, 1887; Thomas, 1919a), Kebili (Thomas and Trouessart, 1903; Trouessart, 1905; Conseil, 1909; Blanc, 1935), Maknassy (Wassilieff, 1932; Blanc, 1935; Bernard, 1970), Bou Hedma (Bernard, 1970), Zarzis (Bernard, 1970), Ben Gardane (Bernard, 1970), Remada (Bernard, 1970), Michiguig (Wassilieff, 1932), Fort Saint (Wassilieff, 1932); Bir-Pistor [= ca. 30 NE Ghadamès](Wassilieff, 1932); Djeneine [= ca. 50 km S Bordj Bourguiba] (Wassilieff, 1932).

Psammomys vexillaris Thomas, 1925. Pale Sand

Rat

Diagnosis. This species differs from *P. obesus* by being smaller, having a shorter, less penicillate tail, grayish (not blackish) ears, white (not strongly buff colored) dorsal surfaces of the hind feet and a paler color of the dorsum. Total length reaches 260 mm of which the tail comprises about 110 mm. Cockrum et al. (1977) documented these and other differences between the two species of *Psammomys* in Tunisia.

Distribution. Pale sand rat occurs in Libya, southern Tunisia and southern Algeria (Fig. 3.69). It ranges as far westward as Marbouma Oasis, Beni Abbès, Algeria.

Biology. *Psammomys* are diurnal, and occur in significant numbers in areas such as described above. Throughout this investigation (in 1970s and in 1996), significant numbers were never captured, even when traps were set in front of burrows into which the rat just disappeared. Most of the traps Cockrum et al. (in litt.) used were baited with various mixtures of grains and oils. A common mixture that was highly successful in capturing *Gerbillus*, *Apodemus*, and other rodents was a mixture of crushed oats and peanut butter. I baited traps with tomato and cucumber slices and oats but no sand rat were caught using this bait, even when the trap was so set that the individual had to make special efforts to avoid the trap as it exited from the burrow. Daly and Daly (1974; 1975) successfully used leaves of succulent plants of the family Chenopodiaceae as bait for *Psammomys obesus*.

Vesmanis (personal communication with Cockrum, in litt.) took a total of 29 *P. vexillaris* from 20 km E Nefta on 7 and 8 March, 1972. These were secured by flooding large volumes (100 to 150 liters) of water into the entrance of active

Figure 3.69. Distribution maps of pale fat sand rat, *Psammomys vexillaris* Thomas, 1925. A. *P. vexillaris edusa*; B. *P. v. vexillaris*.

burrow systems and “drowning-out” the occupants. As the rodents emerged, they were chased down and captured. He obtained up to 3 individuals from a single burrow. I used the same method to catch *P. obesus* in Jordan. I covered exit holes with a fish gill net. Sand rats and other species abandoned the burrows and usually got entangled in the net and were captured alive.

The *Psammomys* I took in Jordan were kept in the lab on a diet of salt bushes gathered from the vicinity of their burrows. In some parts of Jordan, *Psammomys* is a reservoir host for cutaneous leishmaniasis (Qumsiyeh, 1996).

Ranck (1968) reported that, in Libya, traps were “surprisingly ineffective” in capturing sand rats. His few specimens were obtained by digging them from burrows. Cockrum et al. (in litt.) used other methods to collect most of their specimens. One series (14) was taken 72 km N Gafsa by following a tractor pulled plow that was turning over previously uncultivated habitat. Several specimens were obtained with a shot gun.

Taxonomy. Ranck (1968) traced the history of confusion involving the status of this species (essentially several workers chose to place *P. vexillaris* as a member of the species *P. obesus*) and documented many of the differences between the two. Two subspecies of pale sand rats can be recognized in Tunisia as follows:

Psammomys vexillaris edusa Thomas, 1925

Psammomys vexillaris edusa Thomas, Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist., 16(9) : 199, 1925,
type from Mal Mahases, Chegga, just south of Biskra, Algeria; Cockrum et al., 1977.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 2 , distributed as follows: 4.5 km N Tozeur on GP 3, 1; Ain el Ouchika, 2.5 km NE Tamerza, slope above oued, 1.

Literature reports: 4.5 km N Tozeur on GP3; Ain el Ouchika, 2.5 km NE Tamerza, slope above oued (both records by Cockrum et al., 1977).

Psammomys vexillaris vexillaris Thomas, 1925

Psammomys vexillaris Thomas, Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist., 16(9): 197, 1925, type from Bonjem [= Bu Ngem], Libya; Cockrum et al., 1977.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 1, distributed as follows: 19 km N Bir Zar.

Literature reports: 19 km N Bir Zar (Cockrum et al., 1977).

Subfamily Murinae

Typical Rats and Mice

Members of this subfamily, with about 71 different genera, occur widely in Europe, Asia, Africa, and Australia. Most are relatively small and have a characteristic mouse- or rat-like appearance. Six genera occur in North Africa, one of which (*Rattus*) appears to have been introduced by human activity.

Key for Subfamily Murinae

1. Size large, head and body more than 105 mm; hind foot more than 30 mm; length of maxillary tooth row more than 6 mm*Rattus*
- 1'. Size smaller, head and body less than 105 mm; hind foot less than 30 mm; length of maxillary tooth row less than 6 mm2
- 2 (1'). Lines or stripes on back; supraorbital ridges on skull; rostrum short, not more than 28% of skull length; greatest length of skull more than 28 mm*Lemniscomys*
- 2'. No lines or stripes on back; greatest length of skull less than 28 mm3
- 3 (2'). Tail scantily haired; hind foot generally 21 mm or less; M¹ with three roots; M³ small, only half the length and width of the M²*Mus*

3'. Tail obviously haired; hind foot generally 21 mm or more; M¹ with four or five roots; M³ more than half the length and width of the M²; pelage dark with middorsal wide band*Apodemus*

Genus *Apodemus* Kaup, 1829

Members of this genus are widely distributed in Eurasia, primarily in forested or shrub situations. Taxonomic relations among these are still not clearly defined. Ellerman and Morrison-Scott (1951) arranged the 125 named forms to 5 species, but suggested that future studies might prove their arrangement to be too conservative. Corbet (1978) listed about 148 names in 12 species. In recent years, comparative studies invoking molecular and chromosomal data lead to the identification of several new species and distinction among others. Twenty-one species of *Apodemus* were recognized by Musser and Carleton (1993).

All North African wood mice appear to be referable to a single species.

Apodemus sylvaticus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Wood Mouse

Diagnosis. Small individuals of this species can be mistaken for *Mus musculus*. However, the pelage of *Apodemus* is darker especially in middorsal band and the tail is proportionately longer. Further, close examination of the molars shows the characteristic M¹ with four or five root, whereas M¹ in *Mus* has three roots.

Distribution. This species is widely distributed in Europe and Asia but according to Missone (1971) in Northwest Africa, it is “not common in Morocco, Algeria, and Tunisia” (Fig. 3.70). In Tunisia, Conseil (1928) reported *A. sylvaticus* from fields, where it caused great damage to grain crops. Specifically he

Figure 3.70. Distribution maps of the wood mouse, *Apodemus sylvaticus* (Linnaeus, 1758).

reported it in the region of Khangnet-Gromabalia, as being part of a rodent “invasion.” Bernard (1969, 1970) reported similar large populations as destructive to agricultural crops. The only place where dense populations were encountered by Cockrum et al. (in litt.) during their collection (1972-1975) was a small region in the coastal sand dunes around the Morjane Hotel, 3 km E Tabarka. There its tracks and feeding signs were extremely common in areas of loose sand around the bases of the coastal vegetation. Inland, only a kilometer to the south where no drifting sand existed, few wood mice were taken. In June, 1996, I took 3 from a line of 20 traps set in an oak (*Quercus fagina*) forest in Ain Bou Lehia, Jendouba. The locals told me that “wild mice” sometimes invade their houses. I took others from a *Juniperus-Pinus* forest in Djebel Bou Kormine Reserve.

Biology. The diet of this animal is 75-80% seeds. The remainder is vegetation and some insects (Bernard, 1969). Norman (1977) provided information on non-geographic variation in *Apodemus sylvaticus* from Morocco. *Apodemus* is sexually dimorphic, at least for some characters. Using analysis of variance, Norman (1977) found that males of this species were significantly larger in foot length and body weight and were narrower in palate width. Adults reached maximum adult size in many parameters by age group four and five. Norman (1977) concluded that only adults of age four and five combined should be used in population comparisons.

Taxonomy. The specimens available to me at TTU are assigned as follows.

Apodemus sylvaticus algirus (Pomel, 1857)

Mus algirus Pomel, C. R. Acad. Sci. Paris, 42:654, 1857, type from Oran Province, Algeria.

Apodemus sylvaticus algirus, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951; Harrison, 1967.

Mus sylvaticus, Lataste, 1887; Chaignon, 1904;

Mus sylvaticus algira, Gadeau de Kerville, 1908.

Mus sylvaticus algirus, Conseil, 1909; Blanc, 1935.

Apodemus sylvaticus, Chaignon, 1904; Heim de Balsac et al., 1954; Bernard, 1969; Bernard, 1970.

Apodemus sylvaticus hayi, Saint Girons and Van Bree, 1962; Harrison, 1967; Lehmann, 1972; Vesmanis, 1979b; Kock and Felten, 1980.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 82, distributed as follows: 3 km E Tabarka on GP 7, 10; 28 km NW Sbeitla on MC 84, 4; 15 km SW Pont du Fahs, on GP 4, 2 km E highway, 2; 15 km SW Pont du Fahs on GP4, 1 km E highway, 5; 5.5 km SW Korbous, off MC 26, 10; 6 km SW Korbous, off MC 26, 1; 3.5 km SW Korbous, Cap Bon, 18; 3.5 Korbous, 2 km up dirt road, 14; 31 km NW Grombalia on MC 34, 2 km N highway, 1; Djebel Zaghouan, 3 km SE Zaghouan on road from Aïn Ayed, 10; Stabilized sand dunes, 2 km NE Bordj Cedria (23 km SE Tunis), 1; Bou Kornine National Reserve, Ben 'Arous Governorate, 2; Aïn Bou Lehia near Aïn Draham, Jendouba Governorate, 4.

Literature reports: Maktar (Bernard, 1969); Oued Mornag (Bernard, 1969; Kock and Felten, 1980); Medjerda (Bernard, 1969; Kock and Felten, 1980); Djebel Sidi Abiod, El Haouaria, Cap Bon (Vesmanis, 1979b; Kock and Felten, 1980); El Haouaria (Heim de Balsac et al., 1954); Wadi Zriba, SE of Zaghouan (Harrison, 1967); Aïn Draham, Khroumirie (Gadeau de Kerville, 1908; Kock and Felten, 1980); Sidi Tahar, Djebel Ouergha, W of Le Kef (Kock and Felten, 1980); Bir M'Cherga, NE Zaghouan (Chaignon, 1904; Kock and Felten, 1980); "northern Tunisia" (Saint Girons and Van Bree, 1962).

Genus *Lemniscomys* Trouessart, 1881

Members of this genus occur only in grasslands and savannas of Africa. They are diurnal but, in the hotter periods, are most active in early morning and later afternoon hours. Only a single species is known in North Africa. Some authorities (e.g., Corbet, 1978) suggest that the striped mice are not generically distinct from the grass rats, genus *Arvicanthis* Lesson, 1842. The latter name has priority. However, Musser and Carleton (1993) continue to recognize the two as separate. They recognize 10 species in *Lemniscomys*. The Tunisian striped mice will be referred to follows.

Lemniscomys barbarus (Linnaeus, 1767)

Striped Mouse

Diagnosis. These mice are slightly larger than *Apodemus sylvaticus*. Large adults reach lengths of 250 mm of which the tail comprises 150 mm. The hind foot is about 29 mm and large adults weigh about 60 g. Their dorsal color is a series of stripes (or dots arranged in antero-posterior rows) of light to dark buff on a background of dark grayish that is often tinged with buff.

Distribution. This species occurs in Africa, north of the Sahara from Morocco to Tunisia and south of the Sahara from Sudan and Kenya westward to Gambia. In Tunisia, it is restricted to grassy areas in the northern part of the country (Fig. 3.71)

Biology. Bernard (1969) captured pregnant females in May, June, and September. Number of embryos ranged from 3-11 with an average of 7.5. I obtained one individual from Bal'oum area, in tall thick grass, next to a ravine, wheat fields, and some cactus fences. Filippucci et al. (1986) reported the G- and C-banded chromosomal complement of this animal from Algeria. Diploid number was found to be 54 chromosomes with the majority of chromosomes acrocentric.

Figure 3.71. Distribution maps of the striped mouse, *Lemniscomys barbarus* (Linnaeus, 1767).

Taxonomy. I refer the Tunisian specimens as follows.

Lemniscomys barbarus barbarus (Linnaeus, 1767)

Mus barbarus Linnaeus, Syst. Nat. , 12th ed., 1(2), at end of volume. unpagged.

1767, type from “Barbara” [= Morocco]; Lataste, 1887; Chaignon, 1904:

Conseil, 1909;

Lemniscomys barbarus barbarus, Allen, 1939; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

Lemniscomys barbarus, Bernard and Gannoun, 1965; Harrison, 1967; Bernard,

1969; Bernard, 1970.

Arvicanthis barbarus, Wassilieff, 1932; Blanc, 1935.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 9, distributed as follows:

Stabilized dunes, 2 km SE Bordj Cedria, 23 km SE Tunis, 1; 4.5 km N Korbous, off MC 26, 1; 10 km N Tunis on GP 8, 1; 8 km W Sedjenane on GP 7, 1 km E highway, 2; 38 km NE Sbeitla on GP 3, 1; 15 km SW Pont du Fahs on GP4, 1 km E highway, 1; 6 km N Korbous of MC 26, 1; Sebket Ariana, near coastal dunes, ca. 5 km NW Gammarth, 1; Sebket El Kalbiah, Bal’oum, Sousse Governorate, 1.

Literature reports: Haffouz (Bernard, 1969), Ain Draham (Wassilieff, 1932; Blanc, 1935), Tabarka (Wassilieff, 1932; Blanc, 1935; Bernard, 1970); Sedjenane (Wassilieff, 1932; Blanc, 1935), Carthage (Wassilieff, 1932), Cap Bon (Wassilieff, 1932), Tunis suburb (Blanc, 1935; Bernard, 1970), Khroumirie (Blanc, 1935); Bizerte (Bernard, 1970); Djebel Maouine (Chaignon, 1904); Hajeb El Ayoun (Olivier, 1896; Bernard, 1969); Ousselatia (Bernard, 1969; Bernard, 1970); El Bathan, Medjerda valley (Bernard, 1965; Bernard, 1969); El Habibia, Medjerda valley (Bernard, 1965; Bernard, 1969); Medjez el Bab (Bernard, 1970); Nabeul (Bernard, 1970); Haffouz (Bernard, 1970); Mansour, Medjerda Valley (Bernard, 1965); Djedeida (Bernard, 1969); between Bou Ficha and Enfidaville (Harrison, 1967).

Genus *Rattus* Fischer, 1803

As a native wild animal, members of this genus appear to have occurred in India, southeastern Asia, and adjacent islands to the south (Eisenberg, 1981). Two species, especially, have a long history as commensals with man, as a result, are almost worldwide in their distribution. These two are the only members of the genus known to occur in Africa. Both occur in Tunisia.

Key for genus *Rattus* Fischer, 1803

1. Tail about as long as head and body (90 to 105%); greatest distance between the almost parallel temporal ridges on skull about equal to length of lateral edge of parietals; first labial cusp of M¹ and posterior labial cusp of M² obscure
.....*Rattus norvegicus*

1'. Tail longer than head and body (over 105%); greatest distance between the widely curved temporal ridges greater than length of lateral edge of parietals; first labial cusp of first upper molar and posterior labial cusp of second upper molar well developed*Rattus rattus*

Rattus rattus (Linnaeus, 1758). Black Rat

Diagnosis. This animal can readily be distinguished from other rodents that occur in Tunisia by its distinctive scaly tail that is almost devoid of hair. From its congener (*Rattus norvegicus*), it can be distinguished by a tail that is longer than head and body. Distinguishing the two species of *Rattus* with certainty can only be done by investigating the temporal ridges and labial cusps of M¹ and M² according to the key above.

Distribution. In Tunisia, this species has become established, not only in the coastal towns but also in some of the remote oases in the central and southern parts of the country (Fig. 3.72).

Figure 3.72. Distribution maps of the black rat, *Rattus rattus* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Biology. Lataste (1887) reported that this species is sometimes called the palm rat and that he shot it from the tops of palm trees in two different oases in southeastern Tunisia. Trouessart (1905) indicated that this species has been introduced into North Africa in ancient times, thus become much more widespread than *Rattus norvegicus*. Bernard (1969) published extensively concerning the economic importance and its role in human diseases, including the plague.

Taxonomy. This species was first introduced into Tunisia, perhaps 3-4,000 years ago. Undoubtedly it has been reintroduced, from many different parts of the world from many different genetic pools, on many occasions. The result is a population or series of populations with so many genetic origins that the identification as to subspecies is almost impossible. For simplicity, I follow several recent workers in referring all Tunisian populations to a single population as follows:

Rattus rattus alexandrinus (Geoffroy, 1803)

Mus alexandrinus Geoffroy, Cat. Mamm., Nat. Hist., Paris, p. 192, 1803, type from Alexandria, Egypt; Conseil, 1909; Blanc, 1935.

Rattus rattus alexandrinus, Allen, 1939; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951; Bernard and Gannoun, 1965.

Mus rattus alexandrinus, Lataste, 1887.

Mus rattus alexandrinus, Trouessart, 1905; Gadeau de Kerville, 1908.

Rattus rattus, Bernard, 1969; Bernard and Gannoun, 1970; Misonne, 1971; Vesmanis, 1972.

Epimys rattus alexandrinus, Wassilieff, 1932.

Mus rattus, Conseil, 1909.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 8 . distributed as follows: 5.5 km S Korbous, Cap Bon, 1; Salambo, 16 km NE Tunis. 5; Carthage, Punic Ports, 1; Jct. MC 201 and MC 122, about 33 km W Gafsa, 1.

Literature reports: Île de La Galite (Vesmanis, 1972); Mansourah Oasis (Nefzaoua) (Lataste, 1887); Nefta (Blad el Djerid) (Lataste, 1887); Zarzis (Lataste, 1887); region of the Chotts (Lataste, 1887); Aïn Draham (Gadeau de Kerville, 1906); St. Germain (Blanc, 1935); Pontiville (Blanc, 1935); Marsa (Blanc, 1935); Gafsa (Blanc, 1935); Medjerda Valley (Bernard, 1965); Tunis (Wassilieff, 1932).

Rattus norvegicus (Berkenhout, 1769). Norway Rat

Diagnosis. The species can easily be mistaken for the black rat, but can be discriminated by parallel temporal ridges and by obscure labial cusp on M¹ and posterior labial cusp of M². Temporal ridges in *Rattus rattus* are curved and labial cusps are well developed.

Distribution. This species is found only in coastal cities or towns that have or have had some marine shipping activities and adjacent islands in the Tunisian area (Fig. 3.73).

Biology. Bernard (1969) provided a lengthy section on this rat's biology. Most of the information, however, was not obtained from Tunisian specimens.

Taxonomy. I follow several authorities in referring all to the nominate species as follows.

Rattus norvegicus norvegicus (Berkenhout, 1769)

Mus norvegicus Berkenhout, Outline Nat. Hist. Gr. Britain and Ireland, 1:5, 1769, type from Great Britain.

Rattus norvegicus, Bernard and Gannoun, 1969; Bernard, 1969; Misonne, 1971.

Figure 3.73. Distribution maps of the Norway rat, *Rattus norvegicus* (Berkenhout, 1769).

Mus decumanus, Lataste, 1887; Conseil, 1909; Blanc, 1935.

Mus norvegicus [sic], Trouessart, 1905.

Epimys norvegicus norvegicus, Wassilieff, 1932.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: Djebel Khanguet (Bernard, 1969); La Goulette, Tunis (Lataste, 1887); “ports on the Coast” (Trouessart, 1905); “seaside villages” (Blanc, 1935).

Genus *Mus* Linnaeus, 1758. Mice

Taxonomic relations in the genus *Mus* are still poorly understood.

Polymorphic populations, the probability of multiple introductions from diverse sources with varying inbreeding abilities (Said and Britton-Davidian, 1991), inadequate knowledge concerning the chronology and origin of introductions, inadequate sampling of past and present populations, lack of adequate documentation concerning the microhabitats of individuals that are available as samples-- all help to make confusion widespread (Cockrum et al., in litt.). Corbet (1978) considered all forms in the Palaearctic to be members of the single species, *Mus musculus*. Further, although he recognized variations, some of which have been used by others to distinguish separate subspecies and distinct species, Corbet (1978) arranged all but two as synonyms of *Mus musculus musculus*. See his discussion for the basis of his arrangement.

Joe Marshall has identified all of the *Mus* that Cockrum et al. (in litt.) collected in Tunisia. He (pers. comm. with Cockrum in litt.) presented a strong case for the recognition of two species in Tunisia. Part of his arguments are based on the application to North African specimens of findings concerning populations in southern Europe. In southern France, two “sympatric subspecies” have long been

recognized. Other workers (e.g., Britton and Thaler, 1978; Darviche and Orsini, 1982) have shown that the two species of *Mus* have different origins. *Mus spretus* in southwestern Europe is probably of North African origin, according to genetic data (Michaux et al., 1990). Darviche and Orsini (1982) compiled twelve morphological traits that, when used together, distinguish the two species. Orsini et al. (1983), in their report on populations in central and eastern Europe, discussed subspecific relations within *Mus musculus*.

In brief, as interpreted by Marshall (pers. comm. with Cockrum in litt.), the two Tunisian species are *Mus musculus* and *Mus spretus*.

Key for Genus *Mus*

1. Tail index (length of tail/ length of head and body X 100) about 65 (60-80); tail slender and with narrow dorsal dark stripe; tail with slight covering of hair; dorsal color rust brown, often with tufts of white behind ears; pelage of venter white tips and gray bases; zygomatic ratio (width of dorsal ramus of zygomatic plate/width of anterior end of zygomatic arch) about 0.79 (the two are closer to the same size); notch in upper incisors (when viewed from lateral plane) absent or poorly developed*Mus spretus*

1'. Tail index about 90 (75-105); tail larger in diameter, usually uniform color above and below and with few hairs so scaly surface evident; pelage of venter varied, generally non-white but may be white or buff with gray base or, in some "wild" populations, white to the base; zygomatic ratio about 0.50 (the dorsal ramus about half the width of the zygomatic arch); notch in upper incisors (when viewed from lateral plane) usually present and often pronounced, musky "mouse" smell*Mus musculus*

Mus spretus Lataste, 1883. Wild Mouse

Diagnosis. Members of the genus *Mus* have the typical “mouse” color and shape. Two species (*M. musculus* and *M. spretus*) can be confused for one another. *M. spretus* is distinguished from *M. musculus* by the lack of a notch in the upper incisors. Other morphometric characters are also used (see key) .

Distribution. Auffray and Darviche (in litt.) used multivariate analyses to determine the identity of *Mus* paleontological material obtained from Doukkala II site in Morocco. They reported the fossils (40,000 - 10,000 years old) to be for *Mus spretus* lineage and found no evidence that *Mus musculus domesticus* has occurred in that site at that time. *Mus spretus* inhabited North Africa before *M. musculus* was introduced. Michaux et al. (1990) believe both species may have entered Europe at the same time (Plio-Pleistocene) but through different routes (strait of Gibraltar vs. Tunisia-Sicily bridge). Figure 3.74 shows the distribution of *Mus spretus* in the area.

There is evidence also for the presence of this species along with *Mus musculus* in Portugal, the Atlantic islands off the coast of Northwest Africa (Mathias and Mira, 1992), southern France, Spain and several Mediterranean islands (Michaux et al., 1990).

Biology. The information available from Tunisia on this species probably includes information on *Mus musculus*. Bernard (1969) and Bernard and Gannoun (1965) studied extensively commensal pest rodents in Medjerda valley. He reported *Mus* is a host for pathogens like *Salmonella* and *Rickettsia* and cestodes like *Hymenolepis nana* and *H. diminuta* which are infectious to humans.

Bernard and Gannoun (1965) described *M. spretus* as rural as compared to the urban *M. musculus*. In the south, *Mus spretus*, seems to prefer the oasis whereas *M. musculus* was found more in the steppe (Bernard, 1969).

Figure 3.74. Distribution maps of the wild mouse, *Mus spretus* Lataste, 1883.

Taxonomy. The following name is applied to the Tunisian specimens of this species.

Mus spretus spretus Lataste, 1883

Mus spretus Lataste, Act. Linn. Soc. Bordeaux, 7, 4:27, 1883, type from Oued Magra, north of Hodna, Algeria; Conseil, 1909.

Mus musculus spretus, Wassilieff, 1932; Blanc, 1935; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951; Bernard and Gannoun, 1965; Bernard, 1969; Bernard, 1970.

Mus bactrianus, Conseil, 1909.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 23, Ben Kornine National Reserve, Ben 'Arous governorate, 1; Sebkheth El Kalbiah Reserve, Bal'oum, Sousse governorate, 1; Ain El Matouia Forest, El Matouia, Gabès governorate, 1; 4 km W La Goulette, 2; 10 km W Carthage on GP 10, 3; 3.5 km SW Korbous (Cap Bon), 1; 5.5 km SW Korbous (Cap Bon), 1; 1 km SW La Goulette on Lake Tunis Causeway, 7; 12 km S Bou Fichta on GP 1, 1 km E highway; 3; Sebkheth Er Riana near coastal dunes, ca. 6 km NW Gamarth, 15 km airline NE Tunis, 3.

Literature reports: "countryside" (Blanc, 1935); St. Germain (Blanc, 1935); Hammam-Lif (Blanc, 1935), Potinville (Blanc, 1935), Sedjenane (Khroumirie) (Blanc, 1935); "Oases of the south" (Bernard, 1969).

Mus musculus Linnaeus, 1758. House Mouse

Diagnosis. This species can be diagnosed by the presence of a pronounced notch in the upper incisors. Dorsal ramus of zygomatic plate is about half the width of the zygomatic arch. The house mouse has the distinctive musky smell.

Distribution. This species is a commensal that lives wherever there is human habitation. Its distribution is world-wide save the north and south poles. In Tunisia, it has been collected from almost every part of the country (Fig. 3.75).

Figure 3.75. Distribution maps of the house mouse, *Mus musculus* Linnaeus, 1758.

Biology. Three chromosomal races exist in Tunisia. In northern Tunisia (Medjerda Valley), populations with chromosomal complement all acrocentric and $2N= 40$ are found. In central Tunisia (Monastir, Sousse, and Kairouan areas), there are Robertsonian populations with $2N= 22$. Mixed polymorphic from $2N= 21$ to $2N= 40$ are found at the city limits of major cities of central Tunisia (Said and Britton-Davidian, 1991).

Bernard (1969, 1970) compared morphometric measurements of specimens of *Mus* from Tunis, Medjerda valley, oasis, and steppe of the south. Further, he provided information on distribution, reproduction, diet, and the impact on agriculture. Bernard (e.g., 1963) investigated the role of rodents as reservoirs for parasites and pathogenic microbes that might impact domestic animals and humans. Pathogens like *Salmonella*, *Rickettsia*, cestodes like *Hymenolepis nanus* and Nematodes like *Syphacia obvelata* and *Trichuris muris* were recorded in *Mus* species.

Taxonomy. The following name is applied to the Tunisian specimens of domestic mouse.

Mus musculus praetextus Linnaeus, 1758

Mus musculus Linnaeus, Syst. Nat. 10th ed., 1: 62, 1758, type from Upsala, Sweden; Lataste, 1887; Thomas and Trouessart, 1903; Trouessart, 1905; Gadeau e Kerville, 1906; Conseil, 1909; Blanc, 1935; Bernard, 1969; Bernard and Gannoun, 1969; Bernard, 1970; Corbet, 1978.

Mus domesticus praetextus, Marshall, 1981.

Mus musculus praetextus, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951; Marshall, 1986.

Mus musculus genitilis, Wassilieff, 1932 (in part); Blanc, 1935.

Mus musculus azoricus, Wassilieff, 1932 (in part).

Mus musculus praetextus, Vesmanis, 1972.

Mus musculus musculus, Bernard and Gannoun, 1965.

Mus musculus domesticus, Bonhomme, 1986

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 23, distributed as follows:

Bizerte governorate, Jebel Ichkeul National Reserve, 1; Sousse governorate, Kal'ah Al Kubra, Sebket El Kalbiah, 7; Sfax governorate, 'Agarib, Algunah forest, 3; Gabès, El Matouia, Ain El Matouia Forest, 4; Sidi Bou Zid governorate, Mazouna, Bou Hedma National Park, 3; Kairouan governorate, Bou Hajla, El Nasr Forest, 3; Ariana governorate, Gal'al Al Andalous, Shatt Gal'at Al Andalous, 2.

Literature reports: Île de La Galite (Vesmanis, 1972); Following are the sites reported by Said and Britton-Davidian (1991): Tebourba, Tunis, Grombalia, Kairouan city, Kairouan periphery, Sidi Bouzid, Enfida Ville, Sidi Bou Ali, Sousse, Zaouiet Sousse, M'Saken city, Sahline, Maatmer, Monastir city, Monastir Gr, Monastir Out, Khenis, Ksibet, Lamta, Ksar Hellal, Bembla, Menzel Ennour, Djemmal, Smiret, Bou Merdes, Teboulba, Mahdia. "cities and habitations of the countryside" (Blance, 1935); "intensive agriculture zones" (Bernard, 1969); Ain Draham (Gadeau de Kerville, 1906).

Family Ctenodactylidae

Gundis

This family, with only four living genera, is restricted to a small part of northwestern Africa, from Morocco southward to Senegal, eastward to Libya and southward into Somalia. All members of this family are compact, thick-set rodents that somewhat resemble the New World guinea pigs. Digits have a series of stiff bristles that form a comb-like structure on the two inner digits of the hind feet used in preening the fur. A single genus is known from Tunisia.

Genus *Ctenodactylus* Gray, 1830. Gundis

This is a monospecific genus that is found from the Western Sahara into northwestern Libya. *Ctenodactylus* contains two species with a single occurring in Tunisia.

Ctenodactylus gundi (Rothmann, 1776). Gundi

Diagnosis. A guinea-pig like rodent with short stocky body, short ears and proportionately short tail. The gundi's unique feet pads and stiff bristles around the claws make it readily distinguishable.

Distribution. This species is restricted to the northern edge of the Sahara, from Morocco eastward to Libya. In Tunisia, it is known only from rocky habitats in the central part of the country (Fig. 3.76). Lataste (1887) indicated that it was abundant in southern Tunisia, both on mountains and in Roman ruins.

Biology. I presume that *Ctenodactylus gundi* has increased its distribution in recent years due to human activities. Arid, grazed mountains (in Gabès area, for example) that had little rocky tali and outcroppings to provide dens for gundis, nowadays have sizable populations of this ctenodactylid. These hilly areas have been treated against soil erosion by series of contour terraces. Those horizontal rocky walls furnish ample nesting sites for gundis. Further, they detain the eroded soil and support dense vegetation for gundis.

This is a meek rodent that lives in rocky areas. I have seen it in colonies basking in the morning in Jebel Ank (Gafsa) near Chenini (Tatahouine) and in Bou Hedma National Park. When approached, it scurries to its shelters between rocks. Grenot (1973) believes it is better adapted to diurnal desert life than other rodents. It is adapted to high temperatures and it can feed on dry food as well as succulent

Figure 3.76. Distribution maps of the gundi, *Ctenodactylus gundi* (Rothmann, 1776).

halophytes. Seguignes (1983) showed that *Ctenodactylus gundi* occurs in Tunisia in regions where the annual rainfall ranges from 50 to 300 mm and mean low temperatures are between 2° and 7° C. Annual average temperatures in the gundi nesting sites ranges from 27° to 35° C.

The main plant association with gundis in south Tunisia are subdesert species found with *Stipa tenacissima*. North of the Chotts area, its *Rosmarinus officinalis* and wild parsley (*Pituranthos scoparius*). Further north, *Ctenodactylus gundi* occurs in areas that has *Pinus halepensis* and *Juniperus phoenicea* (Seguignes, 1983).

Locals catch gundis with spring traps, snares or by spooking it to shallow shelters where they dig for it. They also mentioned to me the use of a “date palm branch” the tip of which is made into a crude brush. Once the gundi is cornered under a rock, the branch is inserted and probed until it touches the heavy fur of the animal. It then is twisted and pulled quickly bringing the gundi out.

The animal was found with young in March and date of birth time was estimated to be January, February and March (George, 1978). Number of young per litter ranged from 1 to 3 and gundis were described as “opportunistic breeders.” Grenot (1973) was successful in breeding it in captivity and reported that it can be used as an experimental animal for studies on toxoplasmosis.

Bernard and Ben Rachid (1969) made a detailed study of the internal parasites of the gundi. They dissected 134 gundis obtained from different areas of Tunisia and reported high (71.6%) infection rate with helminth worms. *Ctenodactylus gundi* was parasitized by four species of nematodes and by cestodes at the adult and larval stages. Gundi males and females were found to be infected at the same rate.

Taxonomy. Allen (1939) listed three species of *Ctenodactylus* (*C. gundi*, *C. vali* and *C. joleaudi*) from North Africa. Ellerman and Morrison-Scott (1951)

recognized only *Ctenodactylus gundi* with three subspecies (*C. g. gundi*, *C. g. vali* and *C. g. joleaudi*). A recent study (George, 1982) suggested that there are only two species of *Ctenodactylus* in North Africa (*C. gundi* and *C. vali*). Only *C. gundi* occurs in Tunisia. I refer the Tunisian populations to the nominate subspecies.

Ctenodactylus gundi gundi (Rothmann, 1776)

Mus gundi Rothmann, in Schlözer's Briefwechsel, 1: 339, 1776, from Gharian, 80 km S Tripoli, Libya.

Ctenodactylus gundi, Lataste, 1887; Olivier, 1896; Trouessart, 1905; Wassilieff, 1932; Blanc, 1935; Choumowitch, 1954; Bernard, 1969; Bernard, 1970.

Ctenodactylus gundi [sic], Conseil, 1909.

Ctenodactylus gundi gundi, Ellerman, 1940; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 17, distributed as follows: 27 km NW Médénine on MC 104, 2; 2 km N Matmata on MC 104, 7; 9 km W Bir Amir (55 km SW Tatahouine), 1; jct. MC 201 and MC 122, ca. 33 km W Gafsa, 1; 60 km NW Tozeur on GP 16 (8 km NW Chebika), 1; Jebel Ank mine, El Guettar, Gafsa Governorate, 3.

Literature reports: Maktar (Bernard, 1969); Tozeur (Bernard, 1969); Djebel Bou Hedma (Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905; Bernard, 1969); Matmata (Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905; Bernard, 1969); Tatahouine (Bernard, 1969); Bordj Bourguiba (Bernard, 1969); Remada (Bernard, 1969); Kairouan (Wassilieff, 1932; Olivier, 1896); Fondouk-el- Auerb [= Aouareb] (Olivier, 1896); near Ksar Haddada, NW of Tatahouine (Beaucornu et al, 1983); Taoudjout (Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905); Tamezrert (Lataste, 1887); Hadjeb near Matmata (Lataste, 1887); Matmata (Trouessart, 1905); Koutin ruins near Ksar-el-Metameur (Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905); Taferma Pass between Tozzer and Gafsa (Lataste, 1887;

Trouessart, 1905); Thelepe ruins and nearby mountains at Feriana (Lataste, 1887); Tamesmida ruins (Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905); Pass at Khanget-es-Slougui (Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905); Guela'at-es-Snam between Feriana and Tebessa (Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905); El-Ouidian near Sedda (Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905); Djebil et d'El Gara de Tembain (33° N 9° E), south Tunisia (Seguignes and Vernet, 1996); (Grenot, 1973); "Tunisia" (George, 1978).

Family Myoxidae

Dormice

Holden (1993) used the name Myoxidae to refer to this family on the basis that Gliridae, with the type genus *Glis* Brisson, 1762, is based on an unavailable name because Brisson's name is not Linnaean or binomial. According to Hutterer (1996), some still argue that the valid name is Gliridae. The family contains about 26 species arranged in 8 genera. Only a single genus occurs in North Africa, north of the Sahara, and dormice appear to be absent in the typical desert.

Genus *Eliomys* Wagner, 1840. Dormice

In North Africa, members of this genus are known from eastern Libya westward to the Atlantic coast. I follow Holden (1993) and refer all north African and eastern Mediterranean forms to a single species.

Eliomys melanurus (Wagner, 1839). Garden

Dormouse

Diagnosis. These dormice have a soft pelage that is generally grayish or brown above and whitish below. The tail is fluffy, almost bushy and has a black end with a white tip. Total length reaches 250 mm of which the tail makes up to about 115 mm. Weights reach about 80 g.

Distribution. Southern Turkey, east Mediterranean countries, south to the Arabian Peninsula, westward through Sinai and into Morocco. In Tunisia, it is distributed in most of the country except the dry south and southeast (Fig. 3.77).

Biology. Wassilieff (1932) reported that this species inhabited the cacti south of Kairouan and fed on its “juicy leaves.” Chaignon (1904) and Kahmann and Thoms (1987) wrote that it fed on the Barbary fig (*Opuntia* cacti). Conseil (1908) reported that it inhabited rock crevices but immediately on the maturation of dates, they climb the palms to feed on the fruit. In Kebili, I was told of a “rat” that jumps to palm tops to eat the new growth but the description of the rodent by one local was vague. The name he mentioned in the vernacular Arabic was “Guntseyah.” It may be *E. melanurus*.

Kahmann and Thoms (1987) discussed the variability of adult pelage, and listed measurements of body and skull. They also provided data on reproduction, development and foraging in a study of a group of *Eliomys quercinus* in Cap Bon.

Taxonomy. Using allozyme data, Filippucci et al. (1988a) found that populations from Morocco (3 females, 1 male) and specimens (2) from Israel formed a monophyletic group using UPGMA analysis of the genetic distance. They suggested that the Middle Eastern and North African myoxids form one lineage on the phenogram, *Eliomys melanurus*, whereas the European ones form another, *Eliomys quercinus*.

However, Filippucci et al. (1988b) also reported that the specimens from Israel have a diploid number of 48, whereas those from Morocco, Algeria, and Tunisia (using data from Tranier and Petter, 1978) had a diploid number of 46. According to Filippucci et al. (1988b), the ancestral form had a karyotype of $2N=48$ and had come probably from east Mediterranean and took two routes: northwest to the Balkans and southwest to North Africa. Chromosomal polymorphism in both

Figure 3.77. Distribution maps of the garden dormouse, *Eliomys melanurus* (Wagner, 1839).

lineages is extensive. They conjectured that the two allopatric karyotypes are probably the result of active speciation (*status nascendi*).

Filippucci et al. (1988b) concluded that there is no correlation between morphotypes and karyotypes in the genus *Eliomys* and tail color should not be used to assess phylogenetic relationships among individuals with different karyotypes.

I follow Holden (1993) in recognizing *Eliomys melanurus tunetae* as being a distinct subspecies. The material from Tunisia is assigned the following status:

Eliomys melanurus tunetae Thomas, 1903

Eliomys lerotinus tunetae Thomas, Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist., 7(9):495, 1903, type

from Karouana [= Kairouan ?], Tunisia; Thomas and Trouessart, 1903.

Eliomys munbianus tunetae, Trouessart, 1905; Conseil, 1909; Wassilieff, 1932;

Blanc, 1935; Ellerman, 1940.

Fliomys [sic] *quercinus*, Bernard, 1969.

E[liomys]. quercinus, Lataste, 1886; Lataste, 1887.

Eliomys quercinus, Bernard and Gannoun, 1970; Corbet, 1978.

Myoxus munbyanus, Chaignon, 1904.

Eliomys quercinus munbanus, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

Eliomys quercinus tunetae, Niethammer, 1959; Kahmann and Thoms, 1987.

Eliomys tunetae, Tranier and Petter, 1978.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 5, distributed as follows: 15 km SW Pont du Fahs on GP 4, 2 km E highway, 2; 15 km SW Pont du Fahs on GP4, 1 km E highway, 1; Stabilized dunes, 2 km NE Bordj Cedria (23 km SE Tunis), 1; 28 km NW Sbeitla on MC 84, 1.

Literature reports: Bou Kornine, near Tunis (Bernard, 1969); Dar Chichou (Bernard, 1969); Cap Bon (Bernard, 1969); near Tabarka (Blanc, 1935); near Mornag (Blanc, 1935); Khroumirie (Blanc, 1935); Sedjenane (Blanc, 1935):

Kasserine (Blanc, 1935); Matmata (Blanc, 1935); Tatahouine (Blanc, 1935); Karouana (Trouessart, 1905); Bargou (Trouessart, 1905); Chorfa, 50 km S Kairouan (Wassilieff, 1932); Tozeur (Wassilieff, 1932); Nefta (Wassilieff, 1932); Fort Saint (Wassilieff, 1932); Metameur in the Arad (Lataste, 1886); near Bir M'Cherga (Chaignon, 1904). The following localities are from Kahmann and Thoms (1987): Dj. Si Abiod; Ras ed Drek; El Haouaria; Sahab el Djebel; Tazhohrane; Umgebung v. Kelibia; Kelibia; Dar Chichou (Reservat); Dj Bou Korbous; Hammam Lif; Grobalia [sic]; Hammamed [= Hammamet]; Tunis; Dj. bou Kornine; Testour; Maktar; Kairouan; Kasserine; Chorfa; around Sfax; Gafsa; Tozeur; Kelibi [sic]; around Gabès; Djerba; Metameur; Foum Tatahouine .

Family Hystricidae

Old World Porcupines

This family is restricted to the Old World. It occurs from southern Europe eastward through Asia to the Philippines. In Africa, it occurs in the Atlas Mountains, in the Nile Basin, and, south of the Sahara, through the rest of the continent. Only a single genus occurs in North Africa.

Genus *Hystrix* Linnaeus, 1758. Old World

Porcupines

This genus contains 8 species that are distributed in Africa, the Middle East eastward into south Asia. Only a single species occurs in Tunisia.

Hystrix cristata Linnaeus, 1758. North African

Crested Porcupine

Diagnosis. Porcupines are the largest rodents of Africa, with adults reaching weights of 15 kg or even more. The total length is up to 800 mm, of which the tail makes up about 1500 mm. The long (to 400 mm), stout quills on the back, sides, and tails make mammal readily identifiable on sight.

Distribution. Crested porcupines occur in southern Italy and Greece and, in Africa, north of the Sahara from Morocco to Libya and from southern Egypt southward to the tropics and eastward to Senegal (see Fig. 3.78). Cockrum et al. (in litt.) secured no specimens of the porcupine and neither did I in summer of 1996. Apparently they have been rare in the region for some time. Blanc (1935) reported them as rare. Ranck (1968), in Libya, found no evidence of their presence although some earlier reports were available from coastal mountainous regions. Bernard (1970), however, reported that they were widespread in the mountains of northern, central (Kasserine), and southern (Djebel Tebaga), Tunisia.

Biology. This large rodent is a nocturnal herbivore. It forages mainly in hilly vegetated areas. According to Bernard (1969), it is rare and most of his reports were from hunters. It seems that its meat is valued by locals in North Africa (Bernard, 1969; Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska, 1991).

The reproductive biology of the animal in Tunisia is not known and requires further research. Hufnagl (1972) reported a gestation period of 110 days for *Hystrix cristata* from Libya. One to four young are born once a year.

Taxonomy. Inadequate samples make a determination of relations between European and African populations difficult. As pointed out by Corbet (1978), the possibility exists that populations in Europe (southern Italy, Sicily and Greece)

Figure 3.78. Distribution maps of the North African crested porcupine, *Hystrix cristata* Linnaeus, 1758.

are the results of past introductions by humans. I follow Corbet (1978) and others in referring Tunisian material to the nominate race.

Hystrix cristata cristata Linnaeus, 1758

Hystrix cristata Linnaeus, Syst. Nat. 10th ed., 1:56, 1758, type from near Rome, Italy; Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905; Conseil, 1909; Wassilieff, 1932; Blanc, 1935; Bernard, 1970.

Hystrix cristata cristata, Ellerman, 1940; Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951.

Histrix [sic] *cristata*, Bernard, 1969.

Records. Specimens examined: none. Quills (only) were collected from the following localities: mine, Djebel Ressas, 28 km SE Tunis; Grottes Taboda, 5 km SE El Haouaria, Nabeul Governorate .

Literature reports: Feriana (Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905); Kasserine (Bernard, 1970); Dejebl Tebaga (Wassilieff, 1932; Blanc, 1935); Djebel Ressas, near Tunis (quills seen, Lataste, 1887); Trouessart, 1905; Blanc, 1935); Bédé (Wassilieff, 1932); Gafsa (Wassilieff, 1932); Montagne de Plomb [= Djebel Ressas] (Wassilieff, 1932); Bou-Kornine (Wassilieff, 1932); Smindja (Wassilieff, 1932); Djouggar (Wassilieff, 1932); Zaghouan (Wassilieff, 1932); Djebel Zaghouan (Blanc, 1935); Chaouach (Bernard, 1969).

ORDER LAGOMORPHA

Lagomorphs are distributed throughout the world either as native or introduced species. This order is characterized by the presence of small, peg-like teeth immediately behind the incisors. One family represents this order of mammals in the Africa.

Family Leporidae

Rabbits and Hares

Two genera of this family occur in Tunisia.

Key for Family Leporidae

1. Hind foot less than 100 mm; inside of ear brown at tip; well-defined interparietal bone evident; mesopterygoid space narrow (60 to 80% of length of palatine bridge)*Oryctolagus*
- 1'. Hind foot more than 100 mm; inside of ear black at tip; interparietal and supraoccipital fused into single element; mesopterygoid space wide (more than length of palatine bridge)*Lepus*

Genus *Lepus* Linnaeus, 1758. Hares

Relationships among African hares are obscure. Most workers recognize five species on the continent, only one of which occurs in Tunisia.

Lepus capensis Linnaeus, 1758. Brown Hare

Diagnosis. The Brown (or Cape) hare can be distinguished from the wild rabbit *Oryctolagus*, the only other leporid that occurs in Tunisia, by its larger size and longer extremities. In general, *Lepus capensis* is more probable to be running in open range than to burrowing (Corbet, 1983).

Distribution. This species occurs in Europe from southern Sweden and Finland eastward through most of Asia. In Africa, it occurs throughout the continent (Fig. 3.79).

Biology. During the three years of field work (1972-1975), Cockrum et al. (in litt.) did not see more than 20 individuals of *Lepus capensis*. At that time, hares appeared to be almost extinct in Tunisia. Most were either in northern mountain situations or in brush along the seacoast. In contrast, Lataste (1887) reported that the hare was “common” in Tunisia. Blanc (1935) reported it as common throughout Tunisia, especially on certain large estates on the outskirts of Tunis. He commented that one would be certain to see many on any short trip to the region. Olivier (1896) reported that this rabbit was common in all of Tunisia.

In recent years, hunting of rabbits and hares (called wild rabbits) has been regulated. Open season is 15 October through 26 November and the hunters bag limit is two and “flushing” by groups of hunters is prohibited (Anon., 1995). While in Tunisia in May and June, 1996, I saw two individuals in El Madfoun area near Sousse and noticed abundant “leporid” pellets in the same site. One road kill was noted near Chambi National Park near Kasserine. According to Angermann et al. (1990), the Cape hare status is considered “locally common” over its range.

Taxonomy. The taxonomy of African hares is confusing, primarily because adequate samples are unavailable. To date, no large sample from a single locality in North Africa has been accumulated. Therefore the limits of variation associated with age and sex can not be ascertained.

In the past, 14 separate species of hares have been described from the area: five in Morocco, three in Egypt, two in Algeria, two in Libya, and one in Tunisia. Eleven of these were described before 1910. Most were described on the basis of one or two examples. Petter (1971) contended that all are members of *Lepus*

Figure 3.79. Distribution of the brown hare, *Lepus capensis* Linnaeus, 1785. A, *Lepus capensis kabylicus* De Winton, 1898; B, *L. c. pallidior* Barrett-Hamilton, 1898.

capensis. Furthermore, he reported that this is the only hare that occurs in Africa north of the Sahara. As he points out, hares occurring in the desert are the smallest and palest. Angermann (1983) believes the hares of the montane northern Morocco, Algeria and Tunisia are “closer to or identical with *granatensis*”, a form related to *L. europaeus*. Typical desert dwelling *L. capensis*, according to Angermann occurs in the more desertish, southern parts of these countries and exhibits pronounced differences in “skin characters.”

I am not certain that the following assignments of Tunisian *Lepus* are correct, even at the specific level. From the limited material available and from the literature (especially Blanc, 1935) I conclude that hares from northern Tunisian populations are larger and darker than those from southern populations. I judge these to be subspecifically distinct.

Lepus capensis kabylicus De Winton, 1898

Lepus kabylicus De Winton, Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist., [7] 1:155, 1898, type from Algiers, Algeria; Conseil, 1908; Blanc, 1935.

L[epus]. c[apensis]. kabylicus, Petter, 1971.

Lepus aegyptius, Olivier, 1896.

Lepus tunetae De Winton, Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist. [7]1:157, 1898, type from Tunis [see discussion below]; Trouessart, 1905; Allen, 1939.

Lepus capensis tunetae, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951; Petter, 1971.

Remarks. In 1898 De Winton named both *Lepus kabylicus* (from Algiers, Algeria) and *Lepus tunetae* (from Tunis). “Tunis” at that time usually meant “Tunisia, the country” and De Winton may have been implying that he thought the specimen had come from the region (and not necessarily the city) when he reported “The specific name is the genitive of Tuneta, the earlier form of Tunis.” De Winton (1898: 158) also reported that “There are two specimens of this hare in the British

Museum, presented by the same collector as the type specimen, labeled 'Island of Kerkenna, off Tunis.' ” Obviously, in this usage, “Tunis” is “Tunisia.” Whether the type of De Winton’s *Lepus tunetae* is from the island or not, I do not know. Certainly his original description says not. However, Cabrera (1914) and others have been misled and report the type locality as Kerkennah Island [sic].

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 2, distributed as follows: 10 km NW Tunis on GP 9, 1; 12 km SW Pont du Fahs on GP 4, 1.

Literature reports: “Tunis” (type of *L. tunetae*); Island of Kerkenna, off Tunis (De Winton, 1898).

Lepus capensis pallidior Barrett-Hamilton, 1898

Lepus pallidior Barrett-Hamilton, Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist., [7]2:422, 1898, type from Aures mountains, near Biskra, Algeria; Wassilieff, 1932; Blanc, 1935; Allen, 1939.

Lepus tunetae, Blanc, 1935.

Lepus aegyptium, Lataste, 1887.

Remarks. Barrett-Hamilton (1898), in describing this taxon, stated that “in its size and form and in the peculiar narrowness of its skull this hare is very similar to *Lepus kabylicus* De Winton, but it is remarkably different in its conspicuously lighter coloration; it appears to be a desert form of *Lepus kabylicus*, in which all the rich cinnamon tints of that species are replaced by pale gray or yellowish buff.” The description did not include cranial or external measurements; not even an indication of the sex of the type.

Blanc (1935) reported that this hare was common on the plains and sandy coasts of southern Tunisia and that some years previous to 1935 they had occurred rarely on the island of Djerba.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: Aram [= Arram] (Lataste, 1887); Bougrara [= Bou Ghrara] (Lataste, 1887); Bordj-Le-Boeuf (Wassilieff, 1932); Djenneen (Wassilieff, 1932); Gafsa (Blanc, 1935); Khanget-es-Slougui (Lataste, 1887); Matmata, mountains of (Lataste, 1887); Metameur in the plain of Arad (Lataste, 1887); Mezzouna (Wassilieff, 1932); Tozzer in Blab-el-Djerid (Lataste, 1887).

Genus *Oryctolagus* Lilljeborg, 1873. Rabbits

A single species is recognized in the genus. Its distribution is essentially restricted to Europe. This species is the original stock of various breeds of domestic rabbits. As the result of deliberate introductions and from the escape of captives, the species is now widely distributed on many islands, and in localized populations North Africa.

Oryctolagus cuniculus (Linnaeus, 1758). Wild

Rabbit

Diagnosis. The rabbit can be distinguished from the hare based on size and habits, as mentioned in the previous section. *Oryctolagus cuniculus* has more rounded head and the tips of its ears are never black.

Distribution. In North Africa, populations are known from coastal regions of Morocco and Algeria and from insular populations off the coast of Tunisia (Fig. 3.80). While these populations appear to have been present for many years, perhaps several centuries, their origins are unknown. Probably they are descendants of introductions from Europe.

Lataste (1887) indicated that the wild rabbit did not occur on the mainland but was abundant on several adjacent islands. Blanc (1935) reported it as absent on the mainland and rare on all islands and that, while formerly quite abundant on the two

Figure 3.80. Distribution maps of the wild rabbit, *Oryctolagus cuniculus* (Linnaeus, 1758).

islets of Krait, the construction of a lighthouse has caused reduction of its numbers to the point that he thought it might become extinct within the year.

Biology. At the present, not only are many introduced populations present but many of the domesticated varieties have been accidentally or deliberately released into the areas. Resultantly, even though the species may exist in more or less pre-domesticated form, deliberate or accidental matings with domesticated varieties have occurred throughout North Africa. The Tunisian Department of Forests allows farmers to shoot “feral rabbits” if they are proven a danger to their crops (Anon. 1995).

Deleuil (1954) reported that trails made by wild rabbits were common over all of the island of Zembra but that burrows were found only under trees that were confined to one part of the island. He commented that *Oryctolagus cuniculus algirus* Loche had been described as being small, grayish blue, and with the nape of the neck reddish. However the rabbits taken by him on Zembra were large and very reddish on the upper side.

Taxonomy. The taxonomic status of the wild rabbit in North Africa is uncertain. Along coastal areas of Morocco and western Algeria, mainland populations have been named as taxonomically distinct from European populations. Even the origin of the wild rabbit is uncertain. Corbet (1978: 74) speculated that the “original range [was] probably confined to NW Africa and Iberia.” He indicated that introductions to adjacent areas occurred as early as the twelfth century.

Subspecific assignment seems improper since the rabbits occurring in the Tunisian mainland are introduced populations and limited number of specimens is available from the islands.

Oryctolagus cuniculus (Linnaeus, 1858)

Lepus cuniculus Linnaeus, Syst. Nat., 10th ed. , 1:58, 1758, type from “Europa australi.” ; Lataste, 1887.

Oryctolagus cuniculus, Trouessart, 1905; Conseil, 1909; Blanc, 1935.

Cuniculus algirus Loche, 1858, type from Algeria.

O[ryctolagus]. cuniculus habetensis Cabrera, 1923, type from Dar Amezuk, Morocco.

Oryctolagus cuniculus oreas Cabrera, Bol. Soc. Española Hist. Nat., Madrid, 22: 112, 1922, type from Xauen, Morocco.

Oryctolagus cuniculus algirus, Deleuil, 1954.

Records. Specimen examined: none.

Literature reports: Islands of La Galita (Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905); off Tabarka (Blanc, 1935); Djezeïret-Djamour [= Zembra and Zembretta] (Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905); Zambra [= Zembra], island at entrance of the Gulf of Tunis (Blanc, 1935); Zembra (Deleuil, 1954); Conigliera [not found] (Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905); Krait, opposite Monastir (Blanc, 1935).

ORDER MACROSCELIDEA

This unique order, related to the Order Insectivora, is known only from Africa and the adjacent island of Zanzibar. Members are characterized by hind legs modified for hopping; an elongated snout; somewhat extensile tongue; and some unique cranial features. The latter include a comparatively large brain case, strong zygomatic arches, well developed auditory bullae and orbit surrounded by bone. The digestive system has a well developed cecum, a structure that is absent in the Order Insectivora.

Family Macroscelididae

Elephant Shrews

About 15 species, grouped in five genera, are recognized in the single family of living elephant shrews. Most occur south of the Sahara. One genus occurs in North Africa (including Tunisia).

Elephantulus Thomas and Schwann, 1906

This genus includes 10 species but only a single species occurs in the area.

Elephantulus rozeti (Duvernoy, 1830)

North African Elephant Shrew

Diagnosis. Elephant shrews are mouse-like mammals that are distinguished by their distinctive long, tubular and flexible snout (trunk), long ears, long hind legs, and unique dental formula. The pelage is soft and silky. Eyes are large relative to the size of the head. *E. rozeti* is distinguished from other elephantules in Africa by the lack of pectoral gland and by certain cranial and dental characters.

Distribution. This species is known only from north of the Sahara, from southwestern Morocco eastward into western Libya. In Tunisia, it is known from scattered localities in the central and southern parts of the country (Fig. 3.81).

Biology. Elephant shrews are locally abundant, usually in rocks and along rocky ledges. Cockrum et al. (in litt.) took this species in areas of sparsely vegetated, rock strewn hillsides near Matmata, southern Tunisia. I have taken one individual in a limestone rocky mountain side among bushes of oak, pine, and other Mediterranean maquis association near Ousselatia, E Jebel Serdj.

Elephant shrews are generally diurnal. In Ousselatia one individual (possibly the same one caught there) was observed active at about 5 p.m. on a cloudy, cold day (June, 1996). During the hot summer months, they are crepuscular. Rarely are they active on bright moonlight nights. They usually live in small colonies and, in captivity, reportedly prefer to be with another of the same species.

Choumowitch (1954) reported that captive animals fed on bits of hard boiled egg, soft bread, and the seeds of the Barbary fig (*Opuntia*), as well as milk. He contended that, in nature, insects made up very little of the food; the main diet being the spiny seeds of mountain clover (*Medicago arabica*). He reported observations (at some unspecified locality and date, presumably in southern Tunisia) that hulls of such seeds were found by the thousands around the entrances to elephant shrew burrows. These burrow entrances were often under boulders. He excavated some burrows that were filled with these seeds. Blanc (1935) indicated that elephant shrews were hard to keep alive and that he fed them meal worms (of which they were afraid) and bits of meat from birds that he was skinning.

Choumowitch (op. cit.) also reported that when the temperature dropped below 5° C, captive animals became torpid and, when warmed by the sun, became active again. Blanc (1935) reported that they became torpid easily and, during the winter,

Figure 3.81. Distribution maps of the elephant shrew, *Elephantulus rozeti* (Duvernoy, 1830).

did not leave their burrows except during periods of mild temperature. Cockrum et al. (in litt.) took an elephant shrew southeast of Matmata in a live trap during the night of 11 December. The low temperature that night was 5° C. During the night of 20 February, west of Bir Amir, when the low temperature reached 0° C, one was taken in a live trap and three in steel traps. Obviously elephant shrews can be active at low temperatures.

Reproduction in this species is poorly documented. Records kept by Cockrum et al. (in litt.) indicate that a litter consists of one, or generally two young. At birth, the young are well developed, fully-haired and have their eyes open. Table 3.4 summarizes observations concerning reproductive status of the material taken during this study.

Taxonomy. Material from Tunisia has notable geographic variability in pelage color. The area seems to contain three different morphotypes of elephant shrews. The first one occurs in the Mediterranean montane habitats in northern Tunisia is characterized by dark pelage. The second has lighter fur and inhabits the central parts of the country north of Chott El Djerid and Chott El Fedjadj. The last comes from the mountains south of the Chotts region is distinguished by light coats that are almost sandy colored.

It is worth mentioning that elephant shrews have rather specific microhabitat requirements, being closely associated with rocky terrain and rocky ledges. Such habitats are not continuous; thus various degrees of geographic and genetic isolation are expected. Interpopulation differences in color, however, were not correlated by difference in morphometric measurements.

Preliminary statistical analyses of selected cranial measurements and hind foot length for the Tunisian material showed that morphometrically, at least, the three groups do not show great disjunction. Principal component analysis (PCA) was

performed on 10 log-transformed morphometric measurements (Table 3.5) taken from 17 specimens. Skull characters were measured to 0.1 mm using a dial caliper. Analysis was conducted using Matlab software (The Mathworks, Inc.).

Table 3.4. Reproductive status of elephant shrews (*Elephantulus rozeti*) from Tunisia. (M= Male; F= Female).

Date	Locality	Sex	No.	Observation
21-24 Feb.	Pont du Fahs	M	1	testes enlarged
=	=	F	5	no signs
20 Feb.	Bir Amir	M	1	testes medium size
=	=	F	2	no signs
24 Feb.	Beni Kheddache	M	1	no data
26 Feb.	Djebel Zaghouan	M	2	testes enlarged
=	=	F	1	1 embryo
1 Mar.	Sbeitla	F	1	no signs
13 Mar.	=	M	2	testes enlarged
=	=	F	1	2 embryos X 11 mm
28 May	Toujane	M	3	testes enlarged
=	=	F	1	2 embryos X 38 mm
12 Dec.	Matmata	M	1	testes minute
13 Jun.	near Ousselatia	M	1	testes 4 X 7 mm

Table 3.5. Selected cranial measurements of elephant shrews from Tunisia.
(Abbreviations as in Fig. 2.1 and page 21). All measurements are in mm.

GL	CBL	BL	BC	LIB	NB	ZB	MB	MTR	HF	Sex	Area
33.3	31.1	28.5	14.9	6.8	3.4	19.4	12.6	7.2	32.0	male	south
32.5	30.4	28.0	14.5	6.7	3.5	19.3	12.5	7.2	35.0	female	south
33.8	31.8	29.1	15.1	6.6	3.4	19.9	12.5	7.4	35.0	male	south
32.8	30.5	28.6	14.5	6.8	3.3	19.1	12.5	7.6	33.0	female	south
33.0	30.6	28.0	14.9	6.8	3.3	19.0	12.1	7.5	32.0	male	south
33.8	31.8	28.7	15.2	6.8	3.4	19.8	12.4	7.4	36.0	male	south
33.7	31.4	28.7	15.0	6.8	3.5	19.4	12.6	7.5	35.0	male	south
32.5	30.6	27.6	14.8	6.8	3.4	19.4	12.5	7.3	33.0	male	south
32.9	31.0	28.5	14.8	6.7	3.0	19.5	12.5	7.4	34.0	female	south
32.3	30.1	27.8	14.9	7.0	3.7	19.0	11.9	7.5	33.0	male	south
33.2	30.7	28.0	14.7	6.6	3.1	19.4	12.5	7.3	34.0	male	central
32.3	30.5	27.5	14.7	6.5	3.0	19.0	12.3	7.4	33.0	female	central
33.6	31.5	29.0	14.6	6.5	3.3	19.5	12.1	7.1	37.0	male	north
33.0	30.7	29.0	14.9	6.3	3.4	19.0	12.1	7.2	36.0	male	north
33.0	30.8	28.5	14.9	7.0	3.8	19.5	13.3	7.4	34.0	male	north
32.8	30.0	27.7	14.5	6.3	3.5	18.9	12.3	7.5	32.0	female	north
31.1	28.5	26.1	14.9	6.2	3.5	18.3	12.4	6.7	33.0	male	north

Based on variance-covariance matrix, principal component 1 through 3 accounted for 48.6, 29.0, and 10.5 percent of the variation, respectively. When plotting PC2 versus PC3 scores, the two specimens from central Tunisia grouped closely with the northern population. With the exception of one specimen, the northern and central populations were non-overlapping, with the southern population well outside of the convex hull of the southern population (Fig. 3.82). The differences in the color exhibited by populations of elephant shrews might be a response to selective pressures. Caution is warranted here, given the small sample size from the central part of Tunisia and the fact that only one age group was prevalent in the examined material. More adults and juveniles from each area need to be measured and genetic indices need to be provided before a final decision is

made on the status of the three populations. In the meanwhile, the Tunisian material seem to best assigned to a single taxon.

Elephantulus rozeti deserti (Thomas, 1901)

Macroscelides rozeti deserti Thomas, Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist., [7]8:155, Aug. 1901.

type from near Djebel Bourzel, Biskra, Algeria.

Elephantulus rozeti deserti, Allen, 1939.

M[acroscelides]. Rozeti, Lataste, 1887.

Macroscellides [sic] *Rozeti*, Chaignon, 1904.

Macroscelides rozeti, Trouessart, 1905; Blanc, 1935.

Macroscelides rozeti deserti, Trouessart, 1905.

Records. Specimens examined (TTU): total, 15, distributed as follows: 15 km SW Pont du Fahs on GP 4, 1 km E highway, 3; 33 km NE Sbeitla, 2; Aïn el Ouchika, 2.5 km NE Tamerza, 1; Oued el Fera, 10 km SE Matmata on MC 104, 1; 28 km W Beni Kheddache (55 km W Médénine) 1; 26 km SE Matmata on MC 104, 1 ; 3 km NW Toujane on MC 104, 45 km S Gabès, 4; 9 km W Bir Amir (55 km SW Tatahouine), 2;

Literature reports: Oued Nebana near Zaghouan (Vesmanis, 1979; Kock, 1980); Maktar (Vesmanis, 1979; Kock, 1980); Djebel Ech Cherichera, W of Kairouan (Vesmanis, 1979; Kock, 1980); Kasserine (Blanc, 1935; Kock, 1980); Feriana (Lataste, 1887; Joleaud, 1927; Kock, 1980); Djebel Sidi Aich (Kock, 1980); El Aquareb [= Agarab, W Sfax] (Kock, 1980); Mountains N Gafsa (Blanc, 1935; Kock, 1980); Gafsa (Chaignon, 1904; Heim de Balsac, 1936; Kock, 1980); Djebel Bou Hedma (Trouessart, 1905; Kock, 1980); “region of the Chotts” (Lataste, 1887; Trouessart, 1905; Kock, 1980); Chebika (Vesmanis, 1979; Kock, 1980); Degache, Chott el Djerid (Vesmanis, 1979; Kock, 1980); Matmata (Seurat,

Fig. 3.82. Two-dimensional projection of the first three principal components. (A, PC1 plotted against PC 2; B, PC 2 against PC 3; n= northern Tunisia; c= central; s= southern).

1913; Thomas, 1913; Joleaud, 1927; Joyeux and Baer, 1928; Blanc, 1935;
Vesmanis, 1979; Kock, 1980); Djebel Feijeije, 3 km W Beni Kheddache (Anon.,
1955); Foug Tatahouine (Blanc, 1935; Vesmanis, 1979; Kock, 1980); Chenini, W
Tatahouine (Vesmanis, 1979; Kock, 1980); Sedgel [= Djebel Segdel, S Remada]
(Vesmanis, 1979; Kock, 1980); Oued Nachla (Kock, 1980).

INTRODUCED MAMMALS

Bubalus bubalis Linnaeus, 1758. Water Buffalo

Diagnosis. This is a huge bovid (600-1000 kg). Adults are black and both sexes have horns curved posteriorly and laterally.

Distribution. In Tunisia, this animal is known from Djebel Ichkeul (between Bizerte and Mateur) National Park where it lives on the lake shores and swamps.

The status of the water buffalo as a native mammal of Tunisia is obscure. Lavauden (1924) apparently considered the herd at Lake Ischkeul, near Mateur to be a remnant indigenous population that had survived from the Pleistocene. The view was also assumed by Allen (1939). Haltenorth and Diller (1980: 132) reported that "very probably established since Roman times as a wild-living herd." Zeuner (1963: 245) thought that "contrary to widely held belief, northwest Africa never had indigenous buffaloes of the genus *Bubalus*."

Lataste (1887), Trouessart (1905) and Blanc (1935) made no mention of this species in their reports. Johnston (1898) reported that:

. . . in the district of Mateur in northern Tunis there is a rather remarkable herd of Buffaloes--about fifty in number. They are said to be descended from a few domestic Buffaloes of the Indian species presented forty years ago or more by a King of Naples to the Bey of Tunis. They were placed on a property of the Bey's where there was a large swampy lake, in the middle of which rises a mountainous island. Here they have resumed the feral state, and, judging from the several heads that I have seen, are developing much longer horns than those of the domestic buffalo of Italy. These creatures are now strictly preserved by the Bey, and it is useless to ask for permission to shoot them, as it is always withheld. (p. 352)

Kacem et al. (1994) mention that the animals were a present from a Sicilian princess to Sidi Mohamed es-Sadok Bey in 1859. Schomber and Kock (1961) wrote:

. . . remnants of a herd of buffalo, concerning whose origin no information was available, lived in the district at that time [1924]. Robin contended that it was connected with the Carthaginian herd,

whereas Johnston was of the opinion that they had descended from domesticated Indian buffaloes which the King of Naples had presented to the then Bey of Tunis in 1850. (p. 141)

Schomber and Kock further reported that they could find no evidence of the herd in 1960 when they visited the area. Müller (1970: 224) wrote “On the grounds of historical resources it can be assumed that water buffaloes existed in Tunisia already at the time of the Romans, approximately 2000 years ago.” Lever (1985) quoted Haltenorth and Diller (1980) who also share this view.

Ansell (1971: 17) summarized several papers related to this herd. He concluded that these animals “were feral descendants of imported stock, though they were evidently there for a long time and their origin remains obscure.”

Müller (1970) reported that all but a few calves in the herd at Lake Ischkeul were killed by 1957. Three cows but no bulls were found on farms in 1960. These, plus a bull imported from Italy, were the nucleus of a herd established at a Tunisian Forest station on Cap Bon. By 1969, the herd had increased to 13 males and 14 females and in 1996 contained more than 30 individuals.

Gazella dama (Pallas, 1766). Mhorr Gazelle

Diagnosis. From other species of *Gazella*, the mhorr gazelle is distinguished by its long slender legs. Its weight is between 40 to 70 kg in adult males. Females are about 10% smaller than males. It is more brightly colored than other gazelles. It is reddish brown at the dorsum, sides, part of the neck, and lateral sides of legs. Its belly, ventral side of the neck, and most of the legs is white.

Distribution. The former distribution of this gazelle encompassed a large area of Saharan and Sahelian Africa, from southern Morocco to Senegal, eastward into northern Sudan including southern Tunisia and Libya. It probably vanished from southern Tunisia between the 17th and 19th centuries (Kacem et al., 1994). Figure

3.83 shows the area in Tunisia where it probably was distributed and the region of North Africa where it was recorded. The species is now introduced into Bou Hedma National Park in central Tunisia. Abaigar et al. (1997) considers the importation of dama gazelle into Bou Hedma an introduction not a reintroduction according to IUCN rules.

Biology. The mhorra gazelle was reintroduced into Tunisia from zoos in Munich, Frankfurt, Berlin, and the Center for Arid Zones Studies, Almeria [South Spain]. It is believed that the world population of this animal possibly came from 4 males and 6 females that were kept at the Center for Arid Zones Studies. I found no record for *Gazella dama* in Lataste (1887) and Blanc (1935).

Using G-banded karyotypes of *Gazella dama mhorra*, Nombela et al. (1990) reported the sex-determining mechanism in this subspecies. Males have $X_1X_2Y_1Y_2$ and females have $X_1X_1X_2X_2$. Further, the subspecies had two variants in diploid number ($2N= 38$ and 39). They also discussed chromosomal sex-determining mechanism in *Gazella dama*.

The common name comes from Arabic “Mohor” (or Mhorra) which means “colt or foal” referring to long legs of this gazelle.

Taxonomy. Nombela et al. (1990) discussed the relationships between two subspecies of this *Gazella dama dama* and *G. d. mhorra* using G-banded chromosomal data and outlined the relationship among these two subspecies and other gazelles within the subgenus *Nanger*. Female karyotypes ($2N= 38$) are similar in *G. d. dama* and *G. d. mhorra*. Males, however, were different ($2N= 39$ in *dama* with small acrocentric Y_1 versus $2N= 38$ in *mhorra* with long submetacentric Y_1 in *mhorra*).

According to Gentry (1971), populations of *G. dama* were separated by taxonomists using color differences. The subspecies occurring in Morocco (*G.*

Figure 3.83. Distribution maps of the mhorh gazelle, *Gazella dama* (Pallas, 1766).

dama mhor) having more red-brown on its body than the one in Senegal eastward to Chad (*G. dama dama*). The subspecies occurring in Sudan (*G. dama ruficollis*) has no more red than in the neck region. Gentry (1971) believes a rigorous study of skins (if at all possible now) is needed to establish the validity of those names. In the meanwhile, the Tunisian material seems to be best assigned as follows.

Gazella dama mhor (Bennett, 1833)

Antelope mhor Bennett, Proc. Zool. Soc. London, p. 1, 17 May 1833; Trans.

Zool. Soc. London, 1: 7, pl. 1, 14 Aug. 1833. Type from Wednun, near Tafilat, Mogador, southern Morocco Pallas, 1766.

Gazella dama mhor, Allen, 1939; Gentry, 1971;

Gazella dama, Ellerman and Morrison-Scott, 1951; Corbet, 1978.

Records. Specimens examined: none.

Literature reports: Lavauden (1926) reported it from Grand Erg Oriental.

DOMESTICATED MAMMALS

The following species are domesticated mammals that humans have brought into Tunisia. The previous section on the water buffalo is a special case since the animal may have been in Tunisia for nearly 2000 years.

Felis catus Schreber 1777. Domestic cat.

Canis familiaris Linnaeus, 1758. Domestic dog.

Equus caballus Linnaeus, 1758. Horse.

Equus asinus Linnaeus, 1758. Donkey.

Camelis dromedarius Linnaeus, 1758. Arabian camel.

Bos taurus Linnaeus, 1758. Cattle.

Ovis aries Linnaeus, 1758. Domestic sheep.

Capra hircus Linnaeus, 1758. Domestic goats.

MARINE MAMMALS

Following is a list of marine mammals that possibly occur in the Mediterranean in or near the Tunisian shores. I compiled the list from the following resources: Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska (1991), Jefferson et al. (1994), and Mead and Brownell, Jr. (1993). I relied on their distribution maps and not on actual records from the Tunisian coastline.

ORDER CETACEA

Family Balaenidae

Eubalaena glacialis (Müller, 1776). Northern right whale.

Family Balaenopteridae

Balaenoptera physalus (Linnaeus, 1758). Fin whale.

Family Delphinidae

Delphinus delphis Linnaeus, 1758. Common dolphin.

Globicephala melas(Traill, 1809). Long-finned pilot whale.

Grampus griseus (G. Cuvier, 1812). Risso's dolphin.

Steno bredanensis (Lesson, 1828). Rough-toothed dolphin.

Stenella coeruleoalba (Meyen, 1833). Striped dolphin.

Orcinus orca (Linnaeus, 1758). Killer whale.

Tursiops truncatus (Montagu, 1821). Bottlenose dolphin.

Pseudorca crassidens (Owen, 1846). False killer whale.

Family Phocoenidae

Phocoena phocoena (Linnaeus, 1758). Harbour porpoise.

Family Physteridae

Physeter macrocephalus Linnaeus, 1758 (= *Physeter catodon* Linnaeus, 1758).

Sperm whale.

Family Ziphiidae

Mesoplodon densirostris (de Blainvill, 1817). Blainville's beaked whale.

Ziphius cavirostris G. Cuvier, 1823. Cuvier's beaked whale.

ORDER CARNIVORA

Family Phocidae

Monachus monachus (Hermann, 1779). Mediterranean monk seal.

CHAPTER IV

ZOOGEOGRAPHY

Some works, with varying degrees of details, are available on the zoogeography of North African mammals. Heim de Balsac (1936) provided a good discussion of biogeography of North African birds and mammals. He divided the area into two regions: the Barbarian Region, including the Mediterranean zones of Morocco, Algeria and Tunisia, and the Saharan Region which encompasses the whole desert section of North Africa and Arabia.

Ranck (1968) noted a high the degree of endemism among the mammalian fauna of North Africa, the Middle East, Iran, Afghanistan and eastward into the former Soviet republics east of the Caspian Sea. He suggested that this arid belt of steppe and deserts be considered a distinct subregion of the Palaearctic realm. He named this faunal region the Saharo-Sindien Faunal Region. Furthermore, Ranck (1968) divided Libya into 3 primary faunal areas based on the distribution of the rodents: Mediterranean, Saharan steppe, and Saharan desert. According to Ranck's map (1968: 27), the first two regions (with subdivisions) extend into Tunisia.

Schlitter (1976) suggested 3 basic patterns of distribution of North African endemic rodents: species that are ubiquitous throughout the Sahara, northern edge species which occur in the coastal desert zone and barely advance towards the Sahara, and Sahel-Savanna species which occur in the southern border of the Sahara.

Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska (1991) followed Heim de Balsac (1936) and divided the Algerian mammal fauna into two main groups: the Barbarian Region,

which extends from the Mediterranean coast south to the edge of the Sahara, and the Saharan Region, which includes the desert regions of south Algeria.

Qumsiyeh (1985) studied the zoogeography of mammalian species in areas of southwestern Palaearctic including North African countries. Using Unweighted Pair-Group Matrix Analysis (UPGMA; following Rohlf et al., 1974) of similarity indices between areas, he presented phenograms that showed that north Tunisian bats (south not included in the analysis) clustered with Algerian and Moroccan bats. The Maghreb bats were most similar to the bat fauna from southern Spain. The same results were obtained by Aulagnier (1992). Furthermore, the clustering results showed the Maghrebian bats separated from those from Europe. This led Aulagnier to report that there is a distinct Maghrebian bat fauna characterized by “high representation of Palaearctic and Mediterranean species.”

Qumsiyeh (1985) also reported that north Tunisian land mammals were most similar to those from Algeria and Morocco and grouped with land mammals from Spain, although, the similarity values were low. Qumsiyeh believes the anomalies between the clustering of land mammals and bat fauna is due to the fact that many Palearctic bats are widespread but land mammals are not. Another possible cause for the anomaly is that the majority of land mammals in North Africa are gerbillid rodents that occur only in the Saharo-Sindian region. Aulagnier (1992) showed that Moroccan, Algerian, Tunisian and Libyan mammals clustered together and those, as a group, clustered with mammals from Egypt. Mammal fauna from Spain clustered with those from Italy as one branch.

Aulagnier (1992) examined the Rodentia and its subdivisions in North Africa. Rodents from Tunisia were more similar to Morocco and Algeria than to Libya. Tunisian murids were more similar to Algeria than Morocco, and gerbillids were more similar to Algeria-Libya than to Moroccan. I presume the reason why rodents

from Algeria clustered with rodents from Libya in the latter case is the large number of Saharan gerbillids these two countries have in common. The two countries have large surface areas (much larger than Tunisia) and share a long border line. If the coastal and subdesert gerbillid species are tested alone, the results might be similar to that of murids relationship.

Areography of Tunisia

Armstrong et al. (1986: 1) define areography as “the study of geographical ranges of species” and consider this form of biogeography as a bridge between descriptive and historical biogeography. I attempt in this section to provide information on the origins of Tunisian mammal fauna using areography.

Baker and Genoways (1978) studied the faunal origins of Antillean bats by superimposing the distribution maps of the species occurring in the area. The “superimposed distributions” map showed a possible origin for groups of species, dispersal routes or barriers to those routes. They used the term “invaders” and described the bat fauna as invaders from west and invaders from the south, etc.

I followed on the study by Baker and Genoways and superimposed the distributional ranges of Tunisian bats. Both the range in Tunisia as well as North Africa were considered. The following groups could be discerned from this analysis:

1. Invaders from the north and these are divided into two groups: (a) a group that is restricted to the Mediterranean zone. They are associated with habitats that have relatively high precipitation like Mediterranean forests and maquis in the north and Medjerda valley. These are: *Pipistrellus savii*, *P. pipistrellus*, *Myotis emarginatus*, *M. capaccinii*, *Rhinolophus mehelyi*, *R. blasii*, *R. euryale*, *R. hipposideros* ; (b) a group that are not strictly Mediterranean and thus they reach

farther south into the steppe and subdesert habitats: *Rhinolophus euryale*, *R. ferrumequinum*, *Myotis blythi*, *Miniopterus schreibersi*, *Eptesicus serotinus*, and *Tadarida teniotis*. The majority of those species are Palearctic in origin and are widely distributed in Europe and Asia (Fig. 4.1).

2. Invaders from the south: *Rhinopoma hardwickei*, *Asellia tridens*, *Otonycteris hemprichii* and *Plecotus austriacus*. These species have entered Tunisia from the south (the Sahara) but they occur in deserts of Asia, the Middle East as well as the Sahara (Fig. 4.2).

I also plotted the rodents as a group (with the exception of the commensal species of *Mus musculus*, *Rattus rattus* and *R. norvegicus*) and all mammals (as a group) with the exception of extinct species because of the limited or ambiguous records of occurrence, and from those maps the following mammalian faunal groups in Tunisia could be discerned

1. Species that are restricted to the Mediterranean zone: *Apodemus sylvaticus*, *Lemniscomys barbarus*, *Mus spretus*, *Mustela nivalis*, *Lutra lutra*, *Herpestes ichneumon*, *Cervus elaphus* and *Gazella cuvieri*. These species are associated with mesic habitats of the forest of the Atlas mountains and steppe and maquis in Medjerda valley (Fig. 4.3).

2. Species that are distributed in the north but are not strictly Mediterranean thus they reach farther south into the steppe and subdesert habitats: *Atelerix algirus*, *Crocidura whitakeri*, *C. russula*, *Jaculus orientalis*, *Eliomys melanurus*, *Meriones shawi*, *Hystrix cristata*, *Vulpes vulpes*, *Felis caracal*, *Ictonyx libyca*, *Genetta genetta*, *Sus scrofa*., and *Elephantulus rozeti*. (Fig. 4.4).

3. Species that are distributed in narrow coastal zones: *Gerbillus andersoni*.. Also *Rattus norvegicus* and to some extent *Mus spretus*, but *M. spretus* might have dispersed elsewhere following human activity.

Figure 4.1. Superimposed distributions of species of bats that have invaded Tunisia from the north.

Figure 4.2. Superimposed distributions of species of bats that have invaded Tunisia from the south.

Figure 4.3. Superimposed distributions of species of land mammals that are restricted to the Mediterranean zone.

Figure 4.4. Superimposed distributions of widely-distributed Mediterranean species of land mammals.

4. Species that occur in the southern portions of the country and the Grand Erg Oriental . These species seem to be tolerant of aridity: *Paraechinus aethiopicus*, *Gerbillus campestris*, *G. gerbillus*, *G. tarabuli*, *G. simoni*, *G. henleyi*, *G. nanus*, *G. latastei*, *Pachyuromys duprasi*, *Meriones crassus*, *M. libycus*, *Jaculus jaculus*, *Psammomys obesus*, *Psammomys vexillaris*, *Ctenodactylus gundi* *Gazella dorcas*, *Vulpes ruppelli*, *Fennecus zerda*, *Felis margarita*, *G. leptoceros* (Fig. 4.5).

In Tunisia, the following species and subspecies are endemic: *Gerbillus zakariae*, *Atelerix algirus girbaensis*, *Paraechinus aethiopicus blancalis*. Species that are endemic to North Africa (including Tunisia): *Crocidura whitakeri*, *Gazella cuvieri*, *Gerbillus simoni* and *Elephantulus rozeti*. Other species are endemic to North Africa but extend into some parts of the Arabian Peninsula: *Gerbillus henleyi*, *Meriones shawi*, *Jaculus orientalis* and *Ctenodactylus gundi*.

Following is a summary of the species of mammals and where they occur in Tunisia (Table 4.1). This will provide a more comprehensive listing of Tunisian mammals for comparisons to lists from Algeria (Kowalski and Rzebik-Kowalska, 1991) and from Morocco (Aulagnier, 1992).

Fig. 4.5. Superimposed distributions of species of Saharan land mammals.

Table. 4.1. Geographical distribution of mammalian fauna in Tunisia.

Species	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
<i>Atelerix algirus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
<i>Paraechinus aethiopicus</i>	-	-	-	-	+		+	+	+	-	+
<i>Crocidura whitakeri</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-
<i>Crocidura russula</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Suncus etruscus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	-
<i>Elephantulus rozeti</i>	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-
<i>Rhinopoma hardwickei</i>	-	-		-	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Rhinolophus ferrumequinum</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	-
<i>Rhinolophus hipposideros</i>	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Rhinolophus euryale</i>	+	+	?	?	?	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Rhinolophus mehelyi</i>	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Rhinolophus blasii</i>	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Asellia tridens</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Myotis emarginatus</i>	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Myotis blythi</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Myotis capaccinii</i>	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Pipistrellus pipistrellus</i>	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Pipistrellus kuhli</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Pipistrellus savii</i>	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Eptesicus serotinus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	-
<i>Otonycteris hemprichi</i>	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Plecotus austriacus</i>	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Miniopterus schreibersi</i>	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Tadarida teniotis</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Lepus capensis</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Oryctolagus cuniculus</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
<i>Gerbillus campestris</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Gerbillus henleyi</i>	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Gerbillus gerbillus</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Gerbillus andersoni</i>	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Gerbillus nanus</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Gerbillus tarabuli</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	-
<i>Gerbillus latastei</i>	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Gerbillus simoni</i>	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	-
<i>Gerbillus zakariae</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
<i>Pachyuromys duprasi</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Meriones shawi</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	+
<i>Meriones libycus</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Meriones crassus</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Psammomys obesus</i>	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Psammomys vexillaris</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Apodemus sylvaticus</i>	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Lemniscomys barbarus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-

Table 4.1. Continued

Species	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
<i>Rattus rattus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Rattus norvegicus</i>	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Mus spretus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Mus musculus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Eliomys melanurus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
<i>Jaculus jaculus</i>	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Jaculus orientalis</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Hystrix cristata</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-
<i>Ctenodactylus gundi</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Canis aureus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Vulpes rueppelli</i>	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Fennecus zerda</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-
<i>Mustela nivalis</i>	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Ictonyx libyca</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Lutra lutra</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Gennetta genetta</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Herpestes ichneumon</i>	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Hyaena hyaena</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Felis silvestris</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Felis margarita</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Felis caracal</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Felis serval</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Panthera pardus</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Panthera leo</i>	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Acinonyx jubatus</i>	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Sus scrofa</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
<i>Cervus elaphus</i>	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Addax nasomaculatus</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Gazella dorcas</i>	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Gazella dama</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
<i>Gazella cuvieri</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Gazella leptoceros</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	-
<i>Ammotragus lervia</i>	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	-
<i>Alcelaphus buselaphus</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
<i>Oryx dammah</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-

Key to Table 4.1. 1- Kroumerie and Mogod mountains, 2- Medjerda valley, 3- Cap Bon, 4- Tell and Atlas Dorsale, 5- Upland and Lowland Steppe, 6- Coastal Steppe (Sahil), 7- Chotts and Nefzaoua, 8- Dahar mountains, 9- Djeffara, 10- Grand Erg Oriental, 11- One of the Tunisian Islands (Djerba, Kerkenna, Zembra, Zembretta, and Krait; see text or distribution maps for specific information).

Table 4.1. Continued

Plus sign (+) indicates a species is present in the whole region and (+?) indicates a species that is not found on all parts of the region.

Species Richness

Number of species of mammals occurring in an area depends on the resources of that area, its productivity, diversity of its vegetation or other food resources, its temperature, latitude, rainfall, size, as well as factors (authority, year). To investigate species richness in the different geographical regions of Tunisia, I divided the country into quadrates that are 1° latitude X 1° longitude and counted the number of species occurring in each quadrate. Aulagnier (1992) used this method to study the zoogeography of Moroccan mammals. Figure 4.6-A shows the number of bat species occurring in different parts of Tunisia. High concentration of bat species is found in the northern parts in the montane habitats of Kroumerie and Mogod, and River Medjerda valley. The highest number is in Cap Bon peninsula and the area of Djebel Zaghouan. The availability of caves, mines and rocky shelters in that mountain and its proximity to the fertile agricultural fields of Medjerda valley and Cap Bon are probably among the most important reason why it harbors so many species of Mediterranean and Palaeartic bats. The area of the oases north of the Chotts, and Gabès-Médénine area also had high richness (8 and 5 species, respectively). The availability of water, insects and shelter in the oases near the Chotts probably accounts for this richness whereas adjacent areas are dry and devoid of roost sites. Date palm groves around Gabès also provides food and shelter for bats.

Figure 4.6. Species richness of mammalian fauna in Tunisia. (A) bats; (B) Gerbillids (upper numbers) and rodents; (C) Carnivores (upper numbers) and artiodactyles; (D) All land mammals (upper numbers) and all mammals.

Fig. 4.6-B shows the number of species of Gerbillidae and the total number of rodents (except for species of *Rattus* and *Mus*). The largest number of gerbillid rodent species is found in the area of the Chotts and Nefzaoua, the Upland steppe, the Djeffara on the Libyan border, and the Dahar mountains. A few gerbillid species penetrated to the north but they do not occur at high elevations. The number of non-gerbillid rodent species decreases as one progresses south into the Saharan habitats (Fig. 4.6-B).

Numbers of species of Carnivora and Artiodactyla occurring in the area are shown in Fig. 4.6-C. In general, more carnivore species occur in the north than in the south most likely because of the presence of Atlas mountains that extend into Algeria and Morocco. Artiodactyles do not show a certain pattern of richness most likely because of small number of specimens collected and areas surveyed. Five species of artiodactyles occur in the Upland steppe-Tell on the Algerian border and four species of desert artiodactyles occur in the Djeffara-Dahar area.

The highest number of species of mammals occurring in Tunisia is in the Dahar mountain series and east of it (Djefara plain). The next highest occurs in the oases and Upland steppe area north of the Chotts area. Those two areas contains a wide array of habitats (steppe, oases, marshes, montane, and Saharan) and approximately where the Mediterranean zone stops and the Saharan zone starts. The high species richness is most likely because of the overlap of species that occur in one area and extend into the other.

CHAPTER V

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study provided information on the systematics, distribution patterns, zoogeography, species richness and biology of Tunisian mammalian fauna. The main results, discussions, and recommendations can be summarized as follows.

1. My studies documented that seventy-nine species of mammals exist or have existed at some stage of Recent times in Tunisia and the associated islands. Fifteen species of marine mammals and eight species of domestic species also occur in Tunisia.

This diverse fauna exists in an area with a mosaic of physiographic zones. The majority of the surface area in Tunisia is desert and limited areas are mesic and forested. Some are fragile habitats and increased human activity is significantly impacting their distribution and abundance. The mammalian fauna in some regions deserves conservation. Areas that have high species richness are: Djebel Zaghouan, Tamerza-Kasserine area, Dahar-Djeffara mountains area, and the area of Ghardimaou. More sophisticated studies of the mammals of these areas are needed to determine the densities of some species and the viability of their populations.

To conserve the highest percentage of bat species occurring in Tunisia, I recommend the protection of the caves and mines of Djebel Zaghouan and Ghardimaou regions. Protection measures for certain parks in the area of the oases (Tamerza, Redeyef, Metlaoui, Tozeur and Nefta) are also recommended. The high species richness (especially for desert-adapted bats) is most likely the result of oases which provide roosts, fresh water, and food to sustain populations of bats.

In general, the establishment of a system of reserves in the area that extends from the north Chott el Djerid, east into Gafsa, north into Kasserine and west to the

Algerian border, will have the greatest positive benefits to the largest percentage of Tunisian indigenous bats, as well land mammals.

2. The biology of many Tunisian mammalian species is poorly known and little information is available on the reproductive biology, parasites, diseases, food and feeding habits, home range, sensitivity to pollution, physiology, etc. Further studies designed to provide more basic data are needed. Wise decisions concerning conservation of species, as suggested above, will require a better understanding of these biological data.

3. The systematics of species such as *Asellia tridens*, *Rhinopoma hardwickei*, *Jaculus jaculus*, *Gerbillus campestris*, and *Elephantulus rozeti* are in need of investigation to determine the subspecific relationships. *Eliomys melanurus* from North Africa is in need of revision with specimens from Tunisia compared to those from Algeria, Morocco, Egypt and east Mediterranean countries. Molecular and chromosomal data would be valuable in evaluating the relationships.

Some taxonomic decisions made in recent investigations of North African and Middle Eastern mammals were based on extremely small sample and in some cases North Africa was represented by samples from Morocco or Algeria only. This investigation showed the great diversity and complexity of the problems in one country (the smallest in the Maghreb region). Studies should include specimens from many parts of each country and all geographic regions should be represented if possible.

4. Zoogeography: The bat fauna in Tunisia dispersed into the country from two main faunas: Palearctic species and Mediterranean species invading from the north, and Saharo-Sindian species invading from the south. Land mammals are divided into four groups: strictly Mediterranean, more widely distributed Mediterranean, coastal, and southern species.

One endemic species, *Gerbillus zakariae*, is endemic to the Islands of Kerkenna and two hedgehog subspecies (*Atelerix algirus girbaensis* and *Paraechinus aethiopicus blancalis*) are found only on the Island of Djerba. Other species endemic to the north African region extend into Tunisia. The two Islands are good examples of areas that are in need of more detailed studies and conservation efforts.

5. Like other biological studies, this work raised more questions than answered. This study is not meant to be the final work on Tunisian mammals but is intended to be a foundation and a catalyst for further investigations.

LITERATURE CITED

- Abaigar, T., M. Cano, G. Espeso and J. Ortiz. 1997. Introduction of Mhorh gazelle, *Gazella dama mhorh* in Bou-Hedma National Park, Tunisia. Int. Zoo. Yb., 35: 311-316.
- Aellen, V. 1955. *Rhinolophus blasii* Peters (1866), Chauve-Souris Nouvelle pour l'Afrique du Nord. Mammalia, 19: 361-366.
- . 1966. Notes sur *Tadarida teniotis* (Raf.) (Mammalia, Chiroptera)--
Systématique, paléontologie et peuplement, répartition géographique. Revue Suisse de Zoologie, 73(6): 119-159.
- Aellen, V. and P. Strinati. 1969a. Chauves-souris cavernicoles de Tunisie. V International Kongress für Speläologie, 1969, Stuttgart, Bd. 4 (B.6): 1-5.
- . 1969b. Liste des chiroptères de la Tunisie. Revue Suisse de Zoologie, 76 (17): 421-431.
- . 1970. Chauves-souris cavernicoles de Tunisie. Mammalia, 34: 228-236.
- Al Saleh, A. A. and M. A. Khan. 1984. Cytological studies of certain desert mammals of Saudi Arabia. 1. The karyotype of *Jaculus jaculus*. J. Coll. Sci., King Saud Univ., 15(1): 163-168.
- Alados, C. L. 1987. A cladistic approach to the taxonomy of the dorcas gazelles. Israel J. Zoology, 34: 33-49.
- Allen, J. A. . 1939. A checklist of African Mammals. Bull. Museum Comp. Zool., Harvard, 83: 1-763.
- Anciaux de Faveaux, M. 1976. La léthargie chez les Chiroptères cavernicoles d'Afrique Centrale. International Journal of Speleology, 8: 291-303.
- . 1984. Les parasites des chiroptères du continent Africain. Zoologische Westenshappen-Ann., 244: 1-92.
- Andersen, K. 1918. Diagnoses of new bats of the families Rhinolophidae and Megadermatidae. Annals and Magazine of Natural History, 9(2): 374-384.
- Anderson, J. 1892. On a small collection of mammals, reptiles and batrachians from Barbary. Pro. Zool. Soc. London for 1892: 3-24.
- . 1895. On a new species of the genus *Erinaceus* from Somaliland. Proc. Zool. Soc. London for 1895, 2: 414-421.
- Angermann, R. 1983. The taxonomy of Old World *Lepus*. Acta Zoologica Fennica, 174: 17-21.

- Angermann, R., J. E. Flux, J. A. Chapman and A. T. Smith. 1990. Lagomorph classification. Pp. 7-13 in Rabbits, hares and pikas: status survey and conservation action plan (J. A. Chapman and J. E. Flux, eds.). IUCN, Gland, Switzerland, 168 pp.
- Anon. 1955. Presentation d'Echantillons. Société des Sciences Naturelles de Tunisie, pp. 26, 32, 50.
- . 1956. Presentation d'Echantillons. Société des Sciences Naturelles de Tunisie, pp. 12, 13, 33.
- . 1995. Arete du Ministre de l'Agriculture du 17 Aout 1995: Relatif a l'organisation de la chasse pendant la saison 1995-1996. Ministre de l'Agriculture, Direction Générale des Forêts, 20 pp.
- Ansell, W. F. 1971. Order Artiodactyla. Part 15. Pp. 1-84 in The mammals of Africa: An identification manual. (J. Meester and H. W. Setzer, eds.). [issued 1974]. Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington, D.C. not continuously paginated.
- Arnould, M. 1956. Correspondance échangée avec M. le Professeur Heim de Balsac. Communications orales. Procès-Verbaux des Séances Mensuelles de la Société des Sciences Naturelles de Tunisie, pp. 32, 33.
- Armstrong, D. M., J. R. Choate, and J. Knox Jones, Jr. 1986. Distributional patterns of mammals in the Plains States. Occasional Papers The Museum Texas Tech University, 105: 1-27.
- Auffray, J.-C. and D. Darviche. 1991. Morphometrical determination of the specific status of *Mus* fossils-- application to the Doukkala II Site (Late Pleistocene, Morocco). Manuscript, 1-7 + 7 pp. (manuscript in litt.).
- Aulagnier, S. 1992. Zoogeographie des Mammifères du Maroc: de l'analyse spécifique a la typologie de peuplement a l'échelle régionale. Ph.D. dissertation, Academie de Montpellier, France.
- Aulagnier, S. and M. Thevenot. 1986. Catalogue des mammifères sauvage du Maroc. Univ. Mohammed V, Institut Scientifique: Trav. Inst. Sci. Serie Zool., 41: 61-94.
- Baker, R. J. 1970. Karyotypic trends in bats. Pp. 65-96. in Biology of bats (W. A. Wimsatt, ed.). Academic Press, New York. 406 pp.
- Baker, R. J. and H. H. Genoways. 1978. Zoogeography of Antillean bats. Academy of natural Sciences of Philadelphia, Special Publication, 13: 53-97.
- Baker, R. J. and J. T. Mascarello. 1969. Chromosomes of some vespertilionid bats of the genera *Lasiurus* and *Plecotus*. Southwestern Naturalist, 14(2): 249-259.

- Baker, R. J., B. L. Davis, R. G. Jordan and A. Binous. 1974. Karyotypic and morphometric studies of Tunisian Mammals: Bats. *Mammalia*, 38: 695-710.
- Baker, R. J. and M. B. Qumsiyeh. 1988. Methods in chiropteran mitotic chromosomal studies. Pp. 425-435 in *Ecological and behavioral methods for the study of bats* (Kunz, T. H., eds.). Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington, D. C. 532 pp.
- Barrett-Hamilton, G. E. H. 1898. Description of a new species of hare from Algeria. *Annals and Magazine of Natural History*, 7(2): 422-423.
- Beaucournu, J. C., D. Bach-Hamba, H. Launay, H. Hellal and C. Chastel. 1983. Deux chiroptères peu connus de Tunisie. *Mammalia*, 47(1): 127-128.
- Bernard, J. 1963. Etudes sur la faune parasitaire de Tunisie: Nématodes parasites de Muridae. *Archives de l'Institut Pasteur de Tunis*, 40(1): 5-64.
- . 1969. Les mammifères de Tunisie et des régions voisines. *Bulletin de Faculté d'Agronomie*, 24-25: 41-172.
- . 1970. Clef de détermination des rongeurs de Tunisie. *Arch. Inst. Pasteur de Tunis*, 47: 265-368.
- Bernard, J. and M. S. Ben Rachid. 1969. Nématodes parasites du goundi *Ctenodactylus gundi* Rothman. *Arch. Inst. Pasteur de Tunis*, 46: 411-422.
- Bernard, J. and A. Gannoun. 1965. Etude de populations de rongeurs dans les cultures de la vallée de la Medjerda. *Bulletin de l' Ecole Nationale Supérieure d'Agriculture de Tunisie*, 6: 41-87.
- Blanc, M. 1935. Faune Tunisienne: Dactylographiée en trois parties, 1. Mammifères. Mimeographed. 53 pp.
- Blanford, W. T. 1875. Description of new Mammalia from Persia and Baluchistan. *Annals and Magazine of Natural History*, 4(16): 309-313.
- Bodemeyer, B. von. 1933. Über meine entomologischen Reisen nach Kleinasien. Bd. III, Tunis, Oasis Gafsa und die Khroumerie. Stuttgart. 79 pp.
- Bonhomme, F. 1986. Evolutionary relationships in the genus *Mus*. Pp. 19-34 in *Current Topics in Microbiology and Immunology: the wild mouse in immunology* (M. Petter, J. H. Naeau, and M. P. Cancro, eds.). Springer Verlag, Berlin 395 pp.
- Britton, J. and J. J. Thaler. 1978. Evidence for the presence of two sympatric species of mice (genus *Mus* L.) in southern France based on the biochemical genetics. *Biochem. Genet.*, 16: 213.
- Brosset, A. 1958. Note sur *Myotis capaccinii* et sur *Myotis emarginatus*. Chiroptère nouveau pour le Maroc. *Bull. Soc. Sci. Nat. Phys. Maroc*, 38: 85-89.

- Burton, M . 1969. The hedgehog. Andre Deutsch, London. 81 pp.
- Cabrera, A. 1914. The Barbarian forms of the genus "*Lepus*". C. R. Congrès International de Zoologie, Monaco, 9: 522-527.
- . 1932. Los mamíferos de marruecos. Trabajos del Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales. Serie Zoológica, 57: 1-361.
- Chaignon, V. H. de. 1904. Contributions a l'histoire naturelle de la Tunisie. Mammifères. Pp. 37-51 in Société d'Histoire Naturelle d'Autun. Bulletin, 17: 1-115.
- Chaworth-Musters, J. L. and J. R. Ellerman. 1947. A revision of the genus *Meriones*. Proc. Zool. Soc. London, 117(2-3): 478-504.
- Choumowitch, W. 1954. Observations sur les moeurs et l'éthologie de quelques petits mammifères du Sud tunisien. Bull. Soc. Sci. Nat. Tunisie, 1: 81-88.
- Cockrum, E. L. 1976a. On the status of the hairy-footed gerbil, *Gerbillus hirtipes* Lataste, 1881. Mammalia, 40(3): 523-526.
- . 1976b. Status of the name of a rhinolophid bat, *Rhinolophus euryale tuneti* Deleuil and Labbe, 1955. Mammalia, 40(4): 685-686.
- . 1977. Status of the hairy footed gerbil, *Gerbillus latastei* Thomas and Trouessart. Mammalia, 41(1): 75-80.
- Cockrum, E. L. and H. W. Setzer. 1976. Types and type localities of North African rodents. Mammalia, 40(4): 633-670.
- Cockrum, E. L., T. C. Vaughan and P. J. Vaughan. 1976a. A review of North African short-tailed gerbils (*Dipodillus*) with description of a new taxon from Tunisia. Mammalia, 40 (2): 313-326.
- . 1976b. *Gerbillus andersoni* De Winton, a species new to Tunisia. Mammalia 40(30): 467-473.
- . 1977. Status of the pale sand rat, *Psammomys vexillaris* Thomas, 1925. Mammalia, 41(30): 321-326.
- Coetzee, C. G. 1971. Order Carnivora. Pp. 1-42 in The mammals of Africa (J. Meester, and H. W. Setzer, eds.). Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington, D. C., not continuously paginated.
- Colas-Belcour, J. and J. Rageau. 1951. Tiques de Tunisie. Ixodines. Arch. Inst. Pasteur Maroc, 4: 354-359 (not seen).
- Conseil, E. 1909. Recherche sur la peste en Tunisie pendant l'anne 1908. Archives de l'Institute Pasteur, Tunis, 2: 59.

- Conseil, E. 1928. Répartition des différentes espèces de rongeurs en Tunisie. Pp. 128-134, *in* Rongeurs et Puces et la conservation et la transmission de la peste. (E. Roubaud, ed.), Enquête de l'Office International d'Hygiène Publique 1924-1927, pp.
- Corbet, G. B. 1971. Family Erinaceidae. Pp. 1-3, *in* The Mammals of Africa: an identification manual (J. Meester and H. W. Setzer, eds.), Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington, D. C., not continuously paginated.
- . 1978. The mammal of the Palaearctic Region: a taxonomic review. London: British Museum (Natural History), 314 pp.
- . 1983. A review of classification in the family Leporidae. *Acta Zoologica Fennica*, 174: 11-15.
- . 1988. The family Erinaceidae: a synthesis of its taxonomy, phylogeny, ecology and zoogeography. *Mamm. Rev.*, 18(3): 117-172.
- Corbet, G. B. and J. E. Hill. 1980. A world list of mammalian species. London: British Museum (Natural History), 226 pp.
- Crawford-Cabral, J. 1981. A new classification of the genets. *African Small Mamm. Newsletter*, 1981(6): 8-10.
- Daly, M. 1975. Early use of solid food by a leaf-eating gerbil (*Psammomys obesus*). *J. Mammalogy*, 56: 509-511.
- Daly, M. and S. Daly. 1973. On the feeding ecology of *Psammomys obesus* (Rodentia, Gerbillidae) in the Wadi Saouria, Algeria. *Mammalia*, 37(4): 54.
- . 1974. Spacial distribution of a leaf-eating Saharan gerbil (*Psammomys obesus*) in relation to its food. *Mammalia*, 38(4): 591-603.
- . 1975. Behavior of *Psammomys obesus* (Rodentia: Gerbillinae): in the Algerian Sahara. *Z. Tierpsychol.*, 37: 298-321.
- Darviche, D. and P. Orsini. 1982. Critères de différenciation morphologique et biométrique de deux espèces de souris sympatriques: *Mus spretus* et *Mus musculus*. *Mammalia*, 46(2): 205-217.
- De Winton, W. E. 1898. On the hares of western Europe and North Africa. *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.*, 7(1): 149-158.
- . 1902. Description of two new gerbils from Egypt. *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.*, 7(9): 46-47.
- . 1903. List of mammals obtained by the Hon. N. Charles Rothschild and the Hon. Francis R. Henley in the Natron Valley, Egypt. *Novitates Zoologicae*, Tring Museum, 10: 279-285.

- Deleuil, R. 1954. Prospection ornithologique des îles de Zembretta et Zembra. *Memoires de la Société des Sciences Naturelles de Tunisie*. 1956: 7-9.
- . 1956. Sur *Paraechinus ethiopicus* Hemp. et Ehr. de Djerba = *Paraechinus deserti blancalis* Thomas. *Communications Orales, Procès-verbaux des Soc. des Sci. Naturwelles de Tunisie*, 1956: 7-9.
- . 1957. Une nouvelle chauve-souris pour la Tunisie: *Otonycteris hemprichi* Peters, 1860. *Mammalia*, 21(2): 190.
- Deleuil, R. and A. Labbe. 1955a. Sur la variabilité de la pipistrelle de Kuhl (*Pipistrellus Kuhli*). *Bull. Soc. Sci. Nat. de Tunisie*, 8: 237-242.
- . 1955b. Contribution à l'étude des chauves-souris de Tunisie. *Bull. Soc. Sci. Nat. Tunisie*, 8: 39-55.
- Desmarest, A. 1804. Mammifères, Rongeurs. *Nouv. Dictionnaire d'Nat. Hist.*, 1st ed.: 24-30, 51-58.
- Dobson, G. E. 1878. *Catalogue of the Chiroptera in the collection of the British Museum*. British Museum (Natural History), London. 567 pp.
- . 1882. *A monograph of the Insectivora, Systematic and Anatomical*. Part 1: including the families Erinaceidae, Centetidae, and Solenodontidae. John Van Voorst, London. 96 pp.
- Dollfus, R. P. 1951. *Miscellanea helminthologique marocana*. I. Quelques Trématodes, cestodes et Acantocephales. *Arch. Inst. Pasteur Maroc*, 4: 103-229 (not seen).
- Duvernoy, G. L. 1830. Description d'un Macrocélide d'Alger. *Mém. Soc. Hist. Nat. Strasbourg*, 1+2: 1-24.
- Duvernoy, G. L. and A. Lereboullet. 1842. Notes et renseignements sur les animaux vertébrés de l'Algérie qui font partie du Musée de Strasbourg. *Memoires de la Société du Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle de Strasbourg*, 3: 1-75.
- Eisenberg, J. F. 1981. *The mammalian radiations: an analysis of trends in evolution, adaptation, and behavior*. The University of Chicago Press, Chicago. 610 pp.
- Ellerman, J. R. 1940. *The families and genera of living rodents, Vol. 1*. British Museum (Natural History), London. 689 pp.
- . 1941. *The families and genera of living rodents, Vol. 2*. British Museum (Natural History), London. 690 pp.
- Ellerman, J. R. and T. C. Morrison-Scott. 1951. *Checklist of Palearctic and Indian mammals 1758 to 1946*. British Museum (Natural History), London. 810 pp.

- Fain, A. 1959. La famille Gastronyssidae Fain, 1956. Bull. Inst. Royal Sci. Nat. Biol., 35(12): 1-22.
- Filippi, F. d. 1853. Notizia sopra uina nuova species di iena. Mem. Rea. Accad. Sci. Torino, 2: 127-132.
- Filippucci, M. G., M. V. Civitelli and E. Capanna. 1986. The chromosomes of *Lemniscomys barbarus* (Rodentia, Muridae). Boll. Zool., 53: 355-358.
- Filippucci, M. G., E. Rodino, E. Nevo and E. Capanna. 1988a. Evolutionary genetics and systematics of the garden dormouse, *Eliomys* Wagner, 1840. 2- Allozyme diversity and differentiation of chromosomal races. Boll. Zool., 55: 47-54.
- Filippucci, M. G., M. V. Civitelli and E. Capanna. 1988b. Evolutionary genetics and systematics of the garden dormouse, *Eliomys* Wagner 1840. 1- Karyotype divergence. Boll. Zool., 55: 35-45.
- Filippucci, M. G. 1992. Allozyme variation and divergence among European, Middle Eastern, and North African species of the genus *Apodemus* (Rodentia, Muridae). Israel J. of Zoology, 38: 193-218.
- Fitzinger, L. J. 1870. Systematische bersicht der Saugethiere. Sitzber. Akad. Wiss. Wien, Math. Nat., 62: 290.
- Gadeau de Kerville, H. 1906. Voyage zoologique in Khroumirie (Tunisie), Mai-Juin 1906. Mimeographed copy. 3 pp.
- Gaisler, J. 1983. Nouvelles données sur les chiroptères du bird Algérien. Mammalia, 47(3): 359-369.
- Galli Valerio, B. 1911. Notes de parasitologie et de technique parasitologique. Central-Bl. Bakt., Abt. 1, 60(5): 358-363 (not seen).
- Gentry, A. W. 1971. Genus *Gazella*. Part 15.1. Pp. 85-93 in The mammals of Africa: An identification manual. (J. Meester and H. W. Setzer, eds.). Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington, D.C. not continuously paginated.
- George, W . 1978. Reproduction in female gundis (Rodentia: Ctenodactylidae). J. Zool. London, 185: 57-71.
- . 1982. *Ctenodactylus* (Ctenodactylidae, Rodentia): one species or two? Mammalia, 46: 375-380.
- Gharaibeh, B. M. and M. B. Qumsiyeh. 1995. *Otonycteris hemprichii*. Mammalian Species, 514: 1-4.
- Gray, G. G. and C. D. Simpson. 1980. *Ammotragus lervia*. Mammalian Species, 144: 1-7.

- Grenot, C. 1973. Sur la biologie d'un rongeur héliophile du Sahara, le "Goundi" (Ctenodactylidae). *Acta Tropica*, 30(3): 237-250.
- Groves, C. P. 1969. On the smaller gazelles of the Genus *Gazella* de Blainville, 1916. *Z. Säugetierkunde*, 34: 38-60.
- . 1981. Notes on the gazelles: 3. The Dorcas gazelle of North Africa. *Annali del Museo Civico*, 83: 455-471.
- Grubb, P. 1993. Order Artiodactyla. Pp. 377-414 in *Mammal species of the world: a taxonomic and geographic reference* (D. E. Wilson and D. M. Reeder, eds.). Smithsonian Institution, Washington, D.C. 1206 pp.
- Haltenworth, T. and H. Diller. 1980. A field guide to the mammals of Africa, including Madagascar. Collins, London. 390 pp.
- Happold, D. C. D. 1973. The distribution of large mammals in West Africa. *Mammalia*, 37: 88-93.
- Harrison, D. L. 1964- 1972. *The Mammals of Arabia*. Ernest Benn Ltd., London. 1: 1-192 [1964]; 2: 193-381[1968]; 3: 383-670[1972].
- . 1967. Observations on some rodents from Tunisia, with the description of a new gerbil (Gerbillinae: Rodentia). *Mammalia*, 31: 381-389.
- . 1978. A critical examination of alleged sibling species in the lesser three-toed jerboas (subgenus *Jaculus*) of the North African and Arabian deserts. *Bull. Carnegie Mus. Nat. Hist.*, 6: 77-80.
- Hartert, E. 1913. Notes on ruminants and other large mammals. *Novitates Zoologicae*, 20: 33-37 (not seen).
- Hartmann, R. 1868. Geographische verbreitung der im nordöstlichen Afrika wildlebenden Säugethiere. *Zeitschri. Ges. Erdkunde*, Berlin, 3: 28-69, 232-271, 344-369, 406-421.
- Hayman, R. W. and J. E. Hill. 1971. Chiroptera. Part 2. Pp. 1-73 in *The mammals of Africa: An identification manual*. (J. Meester and H. W. Setzer, eds.). [issued August, 1977]. Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington, D.C. not continuously paginated.
- Heim de Balsac, H. 1923. Contribution à l'ornithologie dans le Sahara septentrional en Algérie et en Tunisie avec notes sur la flore et la faune des régions parcourues. *Rev. Franç. Ornithol.*, 8: 1-112 (not seen).
- . 1936. Biogeographie des Mammifères et des Oiseaux de l'Afrique du Nord. *Bull. Biologique de France et de Belgique*, Supplement, 21: 1-7, 42-65, 82-105, 170-185, 370-425 + 12 maps & plates.
- . 1940. Une musaraigne nouvelle de Tunisie. *Bull. Mus. Hist. Nat. Paris*, 12: 382-384.

- Heim de Balsac. 1968. Les Soricidae dans le milieu désertique saharien. Bonn. Zool. Beitr. 19(3-4): 181-188.
- Heim de Balsac, H. and M. Lamotte. 1957. Evolution et phylogénie des Soricidae Africains. Mammalia 21(1): 15-49.
- Heim de Balsac, H. and J. Meester. 1977. Order Insectivora. Part 1. Pp. 1-29 in The mammals of Africa: An identification manual. (J. Meester and H. W. Setzer, eds.). [issued August, 1977]. Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington, D.C. not continuously paginated.
- Heim de Balsac, H., M. Arnould, J. Cantoni, and R. Deleuil. 1954. Notes sur les regurgitations de la chouette effraye (*Tyto alba* Scop.). Bull. Soc. Sci. Nat. Tunisie, 7: 139-140.
- Hill, J. E. 1964. Notes on a collection of bats from Figuig, Morocco. Mammalia, 28: 83-87.
- . 1977. A review of Rhinopomatidae (Mammalia: Chiroptera). Bull. Br. Mus. Nat. Hist. (Zool.), 32(2): 29-43.
- Holden, M. E. 1993. Family Myoxidae. Pp. 763-770 in Mammal species of the world: a taxonomic and geographic reference (D. M. Wilson and D. M. Reeder, eds.). Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington, D.C. 1206 pp.
- Honacki, J. H., K. E. Kinman and J. W. Koepple (eds.). 1982. Mammal species of the world; a taxonomic and geographic reference. Allen Press, Inc. and the Association of Systematics Collections, Lawrence, Kansas. 694 pp.
- Hoogstraal, H. 1955. Notes on African *Haemaphysalis* ticks. I. The Mediterranean littoral hedgehog parasite *H. erinacei* Pavesi 1884 (Ixodoidea, Ixodidae). J. Parasitol., 41: 221-233.
- Hufnagl, E. 1972. Libyan mammals. Cambridge: The Oleander Press, 85 pp.
- Hutterer, R. 1986. The species of *Crocidura* (Soricidae) in Morocco. Mammalia, 50(4): 521-534.
- . 1996. Book Review (Proceedings of the II Conference on Dormice (Rodentia, Myoxidae). Editor: Filippucci, M. G. (1995): *Hystrix* N.S., Vol. 6 (1994), 340 pp.). Bonn. Zool. Beitr., 46: S. 132.
- Jefferson, T. A., S. Leatherwood and M. A. Webber. 1993. Marine mammals of the world. UNEP/FAO, Rome. 320 pp.
- Johnston, H. 1898. On the larger mammals of Tunisia. Proc. Zool. Soc. London for 1898: 351-353.
- Joleaud, L . 1927. Etudes de géographie zoologique sur la Bérberie. C. R. Ass. Franç. Avancem. Sci., 51: 523-526 (not seen).

- Jordan, R. G., B. L. Davis and H. Baccar. 1974. Karyotypic and morphometric studies of Tunisian *Gerbillus*. *Mammalia*, 38 (4): 667-680.
- Joyeux, C. 1921. Développement direct d'un *Hymenolepis* (Téniadés) dans les villosités intestinales du hérisson. *Bull. Soc. Pathol. Exot.*, 14: 386-390 (not seen).
- Joyeux, C. 1923. Recherches sur la faune helminthologique africaine. *Arch. Inst. Pasteur Tunis*, 12: 119-167 (not seen).
- Joyeux, C. and J. G. Baer. 1928. Cestodes. Pp. in *Recherches sur les helminthes de l'Afrique occidentale française*. Collection de la Société de Pathologie exotique, Monographie II: 17-54.
- Kacem, S. H., H. P., Müller, H. Wiesner. 1994. Gestion de la faune sauvage et des parcs nationaux en Tunisie: réintroduction, gestion et aménagement. Direction Générale des Forêts (DGF), Ministère de l'Agriculture, Tunis. 315 pp.
- Kahmann, H. 1958. Die Fledermaus *Rhinolophus mehelyi* Matschie, 1901 als Glied der Säugtierfauna in Tunesien. *Zool. Anz.*, 161: 227-237.
- Kahmann, H. and H. Altner. 1956. Die Wimperspitzmaus *Suncus etruscus* (Savi, 1822) auf der Insel Korsika und ihre circummediterrane Verbreitung. Ergebnisse der Lehrwanderungen des Zoologischen Instituts der Universität München 1952 bis 1955. *Säugetierkd. Mitt.*, 4: 72-81.
- Kahmann, H. and G. Thomes. 1987. Zur biometrie und bionomie des tunesischen Gartenschläfers *Eliomys quercinus tunetae* Thomas, 1903 (Mammalia, Rodentia, Gliridae). *Spixiana*, 10: 97-114.
- Kahmann, H. and I. Vesmanis. 1977. Zur Kenntnis des Wanderigels (*Erinaceus algirus* Lereboullet, 1842) auf der Insel Formentera (Pityusen) und im nordafrikanischen Verbreitungsgebiet. *Spixiana*, 1: 105-136.
- Koch-Weser, S. 1984. Fledermäuse aus Obervolta, W-Afrika (Mammalia: Chiroptera). *Senckenbergiana biol.*, 64: 255-311.
- Kock, D. 1969. Die Fledermaus-Fauna des Sudan (Mammalia, Chiroptera). *Abh. Senckenberg. Naturforsch. Ges.* 521: 1-328.
- . 1980. Distribution of hedgehogs in Tunisia corrected. *African Small Mammal Newsletter*, 5: 1-6.
- Kock, D. and H. Felten. 1980. Typen und Typus-Lokalität von *Apodemus sylvaticus rufescens* Saint Girons & Bree 1963. *Senckenbergiana Biologica*, 60: 277-283.
- Kock, D. and I. A. Nader. 1984. *Tadarida teniotis* (Rafinesque, 1814) in the W-Palaeartic and a lectotype for *Dysops rupelii* Temminck, 1826 (Chiroptera: Molossidae). *Z. Säugetierkunde*, 49: 129-135.

- Koffler, B. R. 1972. *Meriones crassus*. *Mammalian Species*, 9: 1-4.
- Kollmann, M. 1911. Remarques sur les hérissons de l'île de Djerba (Tunisie). *Bull. Mus. Hist. Nat. Paris*, 15: 400-401.
- Koopman, K. 1993. Order Chiroptera. Pp. 137-241 in *Mammal species of the world: a taxonomic and geographic reference* (D. E. Wilson and D. M. Reeder, eds.). Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington, D. C. 1206 pp.
- Kowalski, K. and B. Rzebik-Kowalska. 1991. *Mammals of Algeria*. Ossolineum Publishing House, Wroclaw, Poland. 370 pp.
- Lataste, F. 1881a. Note sur le genre *Pachyuromys*. *Le Naturaliste*, 43: 339.
- . 1883a. Les gerboises d'Algérie. Description d'une espèce nouvelle (*Dipus darricarrerei*). *Ann. Mus. Civ. Stor. Nat. Genova*, 18: 661-682.
- . 1885. Étude de la faune vertébrés de Barbarie (Algérie, Tunisie et Maroc). *Act. Soc. Linn. Bordeaux*, [19] 39(9): 1-299.
- . 1887. *Catalogue critique des mammifères appélagiques sauvages de la Tunisie*. Imprimerie Natinonle, Paris. 42 pp.
- Laurent, P. 1937. Essai d'une clef dichotomique des chéiroptères de la Barbarie. *Mammalia*, 1: 133-159.
- . 1939. Présence de l'Oreillard d'Europe *Plecotus auritus auritus* Linné dans le sud Tunisien. *Bull. Mus. Nat. Hist. Natu.*, 3: 279-282.
- Lavauden, L. 1924. *La chasse et la faune cynégétique en Tunisie*. Imprimerie Centrale, Tunisie (not seen).
- . 1926. Les gazelles du Sahara central. *Bull. Soc. d'histoire Nat. de l'Afrique du Nord*, 17: 11-27.
- Lay, D. M. 1983. Taxonomy of the genus *Gerbillus* (Rodentia: Gerbillinae) with comments on the applications of generic and subgeneric names and an annotated list of species. *Z. Säugetierkunde*, 48: 329-354.
- Lay, D. M. and C. F. Nadler. 1969. Hybridization in the rodent genus *Meriones*. I. Breeding and cytological analyses of *Meriones shawi* X *Meriones libycus*. *Cytogenetics*, 8: 35-50.
- Lay, D. M., K. Agerson and C. F. Nadler. 1975. Chromosomes of some species of *Gerbillus* (Mammalia Rodentia). *Z. Säugetierkunde*, 40: 141-150.
- Lehmann, E. von. 1972. Eine zoologische exkursion nach Tunesien. *Zool. Beitr.* 18: 203-225.
- Lever, C. 1985. *Naturalized mammals of the world*. Longman, London. 487 pp.

- Loche, V. 1858. Catalogue des Mammifères et des Oiseaux observés en Algérie. Librairie d'Arthus Bertrand, Paris. 32 pp.
- . 1867. Histoire Naturelle des Mammifères. Pp. 1-23 in Exploration scientifique de l'Algérie pendant les années 1840, 1841, 1842. Librairie Maritime et Scientifique, Paris. 123 pp.
- Macdonald, S. M. and C. F. Mason. 1986. Otters ecology and conservation. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, London. 236 pp.
- Malec, F. and G. Storch. 1972. Der Wanderigel, *Erinaceus algirus* Duvernoy und Lereboullet, 1842, von Malta und seine Beziehung zum nordafrikanischen Herkunftsgebiet. *Saugetierkd. Mitt.*, 20: 146-151.(not seen).
- Marshall, J. 1981. Taxonomy. Pp. 17-26 in The mouse in Biomedical Research. Vol. 1. History, Genetics, and Wild mice (H. L. Foster, J. D. Small and J. G. Fox, eds.), Academic Press, New York. 306 pp.
- . 1986. Systematics of the genus *Mus*. Pp. 12-18 in Current Topics in Microbiology and Immunology: the wild mouse in immunology (M. Petter, J. H. Nadeau, and M. P. Cancro, eds.). Springer Verlag, Berlin. 395 pp.
- Mason, C. F. and S. M. Macdonald. 1983. The otter (*Lutra lutra*) in Tunisia. *Mammal. Rev.*, 13: 35-37.
- Mathias, M. L. and A. Mira. 1992. On the origin and colonization of house mice in the Madeira Islands. *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 46: 13-24.
- Matschie, P. 1889. Liste der während de expedition im den Jahren 1896/97 von Carlo Freiherr von Erlanger in Tunesien gesammelten Säugetiere. Pp. 62-63 in Beiträge zur avifauna Tunesien, II (C. Von Erlanger, ed.). Kurzer Reisebericht. *J. Ornithol.*, 1899 (Beiheft): 1-65.
- Mead, J. G. and R. L. Brownell, Jr. 1993. Order Cetacea. Pp. 349-364 in Mammal species of the world: a taxonomic and geographic reference (D. E. Wilson and D. M. Reeder, eds.). Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington, D.C. 1206 pp.
- Mermod, C. 1970. Le retour au gîte chez six gerbillides Sahariens. *Mammalia*, 34(1): 1-17.
- Michaux, J., G. Cheylan and H. Croset. 1990. Of mice and men. Pp. 263-284 in Biological Invasions in Europe and the Mediterranean Basin (F. di Casteri, A. J. Hansen, and M. Debussche, eds.). Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht. 463 pp.
- Miller, G. S. 1912. Catalogue of the mammals of Western Europe (Europe exclusive of Russia) in the collection of the Museum. British Museum (Natural History), 1019 pp.

- Missone, X. 1971. Order Rodentia. Pat 6. Pp. 1-39. in The mammals of Africa: An identification manual. (J. Meester and H. W. Setzer, eds.). Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington, D.C. not continuously paginated.
- Müller, H. P. 1956. Observations faites sur une Musaraigne étrusque *Suncus etruscus*, capturée le Octobre 1956 à l'oued Chaffrou, près d'El Bathan. Communications orales. Procès-Verbaux des Séance Mensuelles de la Société des Science Naturelles de Tunisie. Pages 51-52.
- . 1970. Die Wasserbüffel Tunesiens. Säugetierkunde Mitt., 18: 215-224.
- Musser, G. and M. D. Carleton. 1993. Family Muridae. Pp. 501-755 in Mammal species of the world: a taxonomic and geographic reference (D. E. Wilson and D. M. Reeder, eds.). Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington, D.C. 1206 pp.
- Niethammer, J. 1959. Die nordafrikanischen unterarten des Gartenschfers (*Eliomys quercinus*). Zeitschrift für Säugetierkunde, 24: 35-45.
- Nombela, J. J., C. R. Murcia, T. Abaigar, and J. R. Vericad. 1990. GTG-banded karyotype of *Gazella dama mhorr* Bennett, 1833: Cytogenetic relationship with other members of the subgenus *Nanger*. Z. Säugetierkunde, 55: 194-201.
- Norman, H. L. 1977. Non-geographic variation in *Apodemus sylvaticus* (Linnaeus) (Rodentia: Muridae). M. S. Thesis, The University of Arizona.
- Nowak, R. M. 1991. Walker's mammals of the world. Fifth ed. The Johns Hopkins University Press, Baltimore, 1: 1-642, 2: 643-1629.
- Oliver, E. 1896. Matériaux pour la fauna de la Tunisie. Revue Scientifique du Bourbonnais et du Centre de la France, 12: 118-133.
- . 1909. *Rhinopoma microphylum* in Tunisia. Soc. Zoologique de France, Paris, Bull, 34: 118.
- Orsini, P., F. Bonhomme, J. Britton-Davidian, H. Croset, S. Gerasimov, and L. Thaler. 1983. Le complexe d'espèces du genre *Mus* en Europe Centrale et Orientale. II. Critères d'identification, répartition et caractéristiques écologique. Z. Säugetierkunde, 48: 86-95.
- Osborn, D. J. and I. Helmy. 1980. The land mammals of Egypt (including Sinai). Fieldiana Zoology, New Series, No. 5: 1-579.
- Owen, R. D. and M. B. Qumsiyeh. 1987. The subspecies problem in the Trident leaf-nosed bat, *Asellia tridens* : homomorphism in widely separated populations. Z. Säugetierkunde, 52: 329-337.
- Panouse, J. B. 1951. Les chauves-souris du Maroc. Travaux de l'Institut Scientifique Chérifien, Série Zoologie No. 1: 1-120.

- Pavesi, P. 1884. Materiali per lo studio della fauna Tunisina. II. Aracnidi. Ann. Mus. Civ. Stor. Nat. Genov., 20: 446-447 (not seen).
- Petter, F. 1957. La reproduction du Fennec. *Mammalia*, 21: 307-309.
- . 1961. Répartition géographique et écologique des rongeur désertiques. *Mammalia*, 25 (Supplement): 222 pp.
- . 1975. Subfamily Gerbillinae. Part 6.3. Pp. 1-14 in The mammals of Africa: An identification manual. (J. Meester and H. W. Setzer, eds.). Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington, D.C. not continuously paginated.
- . 1971. Order Lagomorpha. Pp. 1-7 in The mammals of Africa: An identification manual. (J. Meester and H. W. Setzer, eds.). Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington, D.C. not continuously paginated.
- Qumsiyeh, M. B. 1983. Occurrence and zoogeographical implications of *Myotis blythii* (Tomes, 1847) in Libya. *Mammalia*, 47: 429.
- . 1985. The bats of Egypt. Special Publications, The Museum, Texas Tech University, 102 pp.
- . 1986. Chromosomal evolution in the rodent family Gerbillidae. Ph.D. dissertation, Texas Tech University.
- . 1996. Mammals of the Holy Land. Texas Tech University Press, Lubbock. 389 pp.
- Qumsiyeh, M. B. and R. J. Baker. 1988. Comparative cytogenetics and the determination of primitive karyotypes. *Cytogenet. Cell. Genet.*, 47: 100-103.
- Qumsiyeh, M. B. and R. K. Chesser. 1988. Rates of protein, chromosome, and morphologic evolution in four genera of Rhombomyine gerbils. *Biochem. Syst. Ecol.*, 16: 89-103.
- Qumsiyeh, M. B. and J. W. Bickham. 1993. Chromosomes and relationships of long-eared bats of the genera *Plecotus* and *Otonycteris*. *J. Mammal*, 74: 376-382.
- Qumsiyeh, M. B., M. J. Hamilton, E. R. Dempster, and R. J. Baker. 1991. Cytogenetics and systematics of the rodent genus *Gerbillurus*. *J. Mamm.*, 72: 89-96.
- Qumsiyeh, M. B., M. J. Hamilton, E. R. Dempster, and D. A. Schlitter. 1987. Problems of using Robertsonian rearrangements in determining monophyly: examples from the genera *Tatera* and *Gerbillurus*. *Cytogenet. Cell. Genet.*, 44: 198-208.
- Ranck, G. L. 1968. The rodents of Libya: taxonomy, ecology, and zoogeographical relationships. *U. S. Nat. Mus. Bull.*, 275: 1-264.

- Rohlf, F. J., J. Kishpaugh, and D. Kirk. 1974. NT-SYS: Numerical taxonomy system of multivariate statistical programs. The State University of New York at Stony Brook, New York. 74 pp.
- Rosevear, D. R. 1974. The carnivores of West Africa. British Museum (Natural History). 548 pp.
- Said, K. and J. Britton-Davidian. 1991. Genetic differentiation and habitat partition of Robertsonian house mouse populations (*Mus musculus domesticus*) of Tunisia. *J. Evol. Biol.*, 3: 409-427.
- Saint-Girons, M. C. 1962. Notes sur les dates de reproduction en captivité du fennec, *Fennecus zerda* (Zimmermann, 1780). *Z. Säugetierkunde*, 27: 181-184.
- Saint-Girons, M. C. and P. J. Van Bree. 1962. Recherches sur la repartition et la systematique de *Apodemus sylvaticus* (Linnaeus, 1758) en Afrique du Nord. *Mammalia*, 26(4): 478-488.
- Sans-Coma, V., R. Fons, and I. Vesmanis. 1981. Ein morphometrische untersuchung am Schädel der Etruskerpitzmäusen, *Suncus etruscus* aus Süd-Frankreich. *Zool. Abhand. Dresden*, 37: 1-31.
- Schlitter, D. A. 1976. Taxonomy, zoogeography and evolutionary relationships of hairy-footed gerbils, *Gerbillus (Gerbillus)*, of Africa and Asia (Mammalia: Rodentia). Ph.D. dissertation, University of Maryland.
- Schomber, H. W. and D. Kock. 1960. The wild life of Tunisia. *African Wildlife*, 15: 137-150.
- Schwarz, E. 1930. Die Sammlung afrikanischer Säugetiere im Congo-Museum. Ginsterkatzen (Gattung *Genetta* Oken). *Rev. Zool. Bot. Africaines*, 19: 279-286.
- Seguignes, M. 1983. Approche des facteurs bioclimatiques qui régissent la distribution de *Ctenodactylus gundi* (Rodentia, Ctenodactylus) en Tunisie. *Mammalia*, 47(4): 493-506.
- Seguignes, M. and R. Vernet. 1996. Présence de *Ctenodactylus gundi* (Rodentia, Ctenodactylidae) dans deux sites isolés du sud tunisien. *Mammalia*, 60(1): 151-153.
- Setzer, H. 1956. Two new gerbils from Libya. *Proc. Biol. Soc. Washington*, 69: 179-182.
- . 1957. A review of Libyan mammals. *J. Egyptian Public Health Assoc.*, 32: 41-82.
- Seurat, L. G. 1911. Sur la présence en Tunisie de l'échinorhynque monoliforme chez le hérisson. *Bull. Soc. Hist. Nat. Afr. Nord*, 3: 14-16 (not seen).

- Seurat, L. G. 1917. Physaloptères des mammifères du Nord-Africain. C. R. hebdomadaire des séances de la Société de Biologie, 80: 210-218 (not seen).
- Smithers, R. H. 1975. Family Felidae. Part 8.1. Pp. 1-10 in *The mammals of Africa: An identification manual*. (J. Meester and H. W. Setzer, eds.). Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington, D.C. not continuously paginated.
- Stains, H. J. 1975. Distribution and taxonomy of the Canidae. Pp. 3-26 in *The wild canids: their systematics, behavioral ecology and evolution* (M.W. Fox, ed.). Van Nostrand Reinhold Company, New York. 508 pp.
- Thomas, O. 1902a. On the mammals collected during the Whitaker expedition to Tripoli. *Proc Zoological Soc London for 1902*, 2: 2-13.
- . 1902b. New species of *Dipodillus* and *Psammomys* . *Ann Mag Nat Hist*, 7(9): 362-265.
- . 1906. The history of the collections contained in the Natural History Department of the British Museum. *British Museum (Natural History) Publication*, 2: 3-66.
- . 1919a. The types of the mammals described by M. Fernand Lataste. *Ann. Mag. Nat. His.*, 9(4): 350-354.
- . 1925a. On some of the species of *Psammomys* found in Algeria, Tunis and Tripoli. *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.*, 9: 197-199.
- Thomas, O. and E. Trouessart. 1903. Note sur les rongeurs de Tunisie recueillis par M. Marius Blanc. *Bull. Soc. Zoologique de France*, 28: 171-174.
- Tranier, M. and F. Petter. 1978. Les relations d'*Eliomys tunetae* et de quelques autres formes de Lérots de la région méditerranéenne (Rongeurs, Muscardinidés). *Mammalia*, 42(3): 349-353.
- Trouessart, E. L. 1905. La faune des mammifères de l'Algérie, du Maroc et de la Tunisie. *Soc. Zool. France*, 1905: 354-409.
- . 1906. Liste des mammifères par M. H. Gadeau de Kerville de Khroumirie (Tunisie occidentale). *Bull. Mus. Hist. Nat. Paris*, 7: 447-448.
- Van Bree, P. J. H. 1968. Deux exemples d'application des critères d'âge chez la Loutre, *Lutra lutra* (Linnaeus, 1758). *Beaufortia*, 15(183): 27-32.
- Van Bree, P. J. H. and B. Dulic. 1963. Notes on some specimens of the genus *Plecotus* Geoffroy, 1818 (Mammalia, Chiroptera) from the Netherlands. *Beaufortia, Misc. Pub. Zool. Mus. Amsterdam*, 1: 7-18.
- Van Cakenberghe, V. and F. De Vree. 1994. A revision of the Rhinopomatidae Dobson 1872, with the description of a new subspecies (Mammalia: Chiroptera). *Senckenbergiana biologica*, 73: 1-24.

- Vaughan, T. C., E. L. Cockrum and P. J. Vaughan. 1977. Four vespertilionid bats new to the fauna of Tunisia. *Mammalia* 41(4): 517-522.
- Vesmanis, I. 1972. Einige Kleinsäuger von Galita-Archipel, Tunesien. *Senckenberg. Biol.*, 53(3/4): 189-195.
- . 1976a. Zur weiteren Kenninis von *Crocidura whitakeri* De Winton 1897. *Bonn. zool. beitr.*, 27: 1-6.
- . 1976b. Morphometrische untersuchungen an angerischen Wimperspitzmäusen. 2. Die *Crocidura suaveolens*- Gruppe. *Z. Säugetierkunde*, 41: 216-225.
- . 1977. Zur identität einer Wimperpitzmaus (Mammalia: Insectivora: *Crocidura*) der Sammlung Lataste aus Tunesien. *Zool. Beitrage*, 45: 50 ? 6 pages.
- . 1978. Ein beitrage zum bausystem von *Psammomys obesus* (Cretschmar, 1826) in Kebili, Süd-Tunesien. *African Small Mammal Newsletter*, 2: 3-6
- . 1979a. Bemerkungen zur verbreitung und taxonomie von *Erinaceus a. algiurs* Lereboullet 1842 und *Paraechinus aethiopicus deserti* (Loche, 1858). *African Small Mammal Newsletter*, 1: 1-14.
- . 1979b. Ein sehr merkwürdig stark abgekautes gebiss einer jungen waldmaus aus N-Tunesien. *African Small Mammal Newsletter*, 3: 8-11.
- . 1980. Über den Wanderigel, *Erinaceus algirues* Lereboullet 1842, von Djerba (Tunesien)(Mammalia: Insectivora: Erinaceidae). *Bonn. Zool. Beitr.*, 31: 207-215.
- . 1984b. Zur verbreitung von *Jaculus orientalis* Erxleben, 1777 and *Jaculus jaculus* (Linnaeus, 1758) in Tunesien. *Zoologische Abhandlungen*, 49: 59-65.
- Vesmanis, I. E. and A. Vesmanis. 1980. Beitrag zur Kenntnis der Crociduren-Fauna Marokkos 1. Die Wimperspitzmäuse aus den Sammlungen des Smithsonian Institution. *Zool. Abhand. Dresden*, 36(2): 11-80.
- Vesmanis, I. E., V. Sans-Coma and R. Fons. 1980. Die Etruskerspitzmaus, *Suncus etruscus* (Savi, 1822) (Mammalia: Insectivora) in Tunesien. *Afr. Small Mamm. Newsl.*, 3: 1-46.
- Wahrman, J. and A. Zahavi. 1955. Cytological contributions to the phylogeny and classification of the rodent genus *Gerbillus*. *Nature*, 175: 600-603.
- Wandeler, A. I. 1965. Die Wirbeltiere von Nefta-- beitrage zur Ökologie einer Oase. *Naturhistorisches Museum der Stadt NBern. Jahrbuch*, 1963-1965: 229-278.
- Wassif, K., R. G. Lutfy and S. Wassif. 1969. Morphological, cytological and taxonomical studies of the rodent genera *Gerbillus* and *Dipodillus* from Egypt. *Proceedings of the Egyptian Academy of Sciences*, 22: 77-96.

- Wassilief, A . 1932. Les rongeurs et les puces de la Tuniisie et leur role dans la propagation de la peste. Arch. Inst. Pasteur Tunis, 21(2): 298-340.
- Wayne, R. K. and S. J. O'Brien. 1987. Allozyme divergence within the Canidae. Systematics Zoology, 36: 339-355.
- Weiss, A. 1911. Catalogue et distribution des arthropodes piqueurs de l'ile de Djerba. Arch. Inst. Pasteur Tunis, 1911: 268-274 (not seen).
- Wickens, G. E. 1984. Flora. Pp. 67-75 in Sahara Desert (J. L. Cloudsley-Thompson), Pergamon Press, Oxford, 348 pp.
- Wilson, D. E. and D. M. Reeder. (eds). 1993. Mammal species of the World: a taxonomic and geographic reference. Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington, D. C. 1206 pp.
- Wozencraft, W. C. 1993. Order Carnivora. Pp. 279-348 in Mammal species of the world: a taxonomic and geographic reference (D. E. Wilson and D. M. Reeder, eds.). Smithsonian Institution Press, Washington, D.C. 1206 pp.
- Yom-Tov, Y., H. Mendelsohn, and C. P. Groves. 1995. Gazella dorcas. Mammalian Species, 491: 1-6.
- Zeuner, F. E. 1963. A history of domesticated animals. Hutchinson, London. 216 pp.